

Typing Test Master and Its Use for Teaching and Learning Keyboarding in Business Education in a Technology Driven Era

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This study examined the effectiveness of the typing test master application for teaching and learning keyboarding in business education within a technology-driven era. The study was guided by two objectives, two research questions, and two hypotheses. A quasi-experimental design was employed, involving 60 purposively selected NCE II business education students from a population of 250 at the federal university of education, Zaria. Participants were divided equally into experimental and control groups. The findings revealed that students taught using typing test master recorded significantly higher mean scores in speed and accuracy than those taught using conventional methods. The application enhanced engagement, offered instant feedback, and supported self-paced learning, thereby improving both speed and accuracy. In line with the Quadruple Helix model involving collaboration between academia, industry, government, and civil society. This study highlights how typing test master can serve as a transformative tool for digital skill acquisition. Pedagogical limitations, such as the difference between mobile touch-screen typing and physical QWERTY keyboard practice, were noted, suggesting the need for hybrid teaching models. The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) in future versions of the application could enhance personalization, predictive feedback, and adaptive learning, aligning with global trends in AI-driven education. The study also emphasizes the potential of mobile applications to promote educational equity by bridging infrastructural gaps in under-resourced environments, provided issues of cost, accessibility, and the digital divide are addressed. It is recommended that business education instructors should integrate mobile applications like typing test master into teaching strategies, supported by institutional provision of digital tools, government ICT policies, and partnerships with software developers. Further research should explore long-term impacts across educational levels, comparative effectiveness with other applications, and the psychological and cognitive outcomes of gamified keyboarding instruction.

Keywords:

Typing Test Master,
Keyboarding,
Business Education,
Quadruple Helix,
Artificial Intelligence,
Technology-Driven Era

Introduction

Keyboarding (touch typing) remains a foundational digital literacy skill in business education, underpinning efficient text production, data entry, and participation in technology mediated workplaces. Global skills analyses consistently flag basic and

intermediate digital skills as prerequisites for employability, productivity, and participation in the digital economy (National Skills Coalition, 2023; UNESCO, 2023; World Economic Forum, 2023). Specifically, within business education specifically, accurate, fluent keyboarding supports

students' written communication, speeds up assignment production, and reduces cognitive load during higher order task benefits that have been observed across tertiary office administration and introductory computing contexts (Chukwuedo et al., 2023; Sholikah et al. In the current technology driven era, students increasingly learn on mobile a device which has accelerated interest in app based, practice intensive tools for skills such as typing. Evidence from recent empirical and review studies indicates that mobile learning can yield meaningful learning gains particularly when practice is frequent, feedback is immediate, and activities are gamified to sustain engagement (AlAbbasi, 2024; Ismail et al., 2020). For motor cognitive skills such as typing, largescale behavioral research shows that speed and accuracy improve with structured, feedback rich practice that builds automatized keystroke patterns (Pinet et al., 2022). In business education courses, the integration of typing platforms has been associated with higher performance and engagement relative to traditional drills, aligning with broader findings that interactive game like media improve student motivation and outcomes (Sholikah et al., 2023; Tiwari, 2021).

Against this backdrop, freely available Play Store tools such as Typing Speed Test Master offer features that map closely to best practices in skills training: multiple test modes, practice/learning flows, history tracking to visualize progress, and post-test analytics comparing typed vs. target text (Typing Speed Test Master, 2025). Such features operationalize formative assessment principles (frequent, low stakes feedback; progress monitoring), which are central to competency development in business education and workforce preparation. The

accessibility of these apps (low cost, ubiquitous smart phones) also addresses resource constraints that often limit repeated practice time in labs or classrooms, especially in contexts with growing enrolments and limited equipment.

The emerging literature in business and office administration programs in the Global South likewise supports computer assisted and app supported keyboarding to enhance speed, accuracy, and confidence. Studies with senior secondary and undergraduate cohorts report significant gains in typing performance and positive learner perceptions when technology mediated practice is embedded in coursework (Chukwuedo et al., 2023; Igwe et al., 2025). Given the intensifying demand for baseline digital productivity skills in nearly every job role, examining the pedagogical impact of a widely accessible app like Typing Speed Test Master on teaching and learning of keyboarding in business education is timely and policy relevant.

In the technology-driven era, proficiency in keyboarding is no longer an optional skill but a core requirement for students in business education and related disciplines. Effective text entry underpins productivity in office tasks, digital communication, and professional documentation (Sholikah et al., 2023; UNESCO, 2023). However, despite the centrality of this skill, evidence from Nigerian tertiary institutions shows that many business education students still graduate with suboptimal typing speed and accuracy (Chukwuedo et al., 2023; Igwe et al., 2025). Factors contributing to this gap include limited access to modern typing laboratories, outdated teaching methods focused on rote drills, and insufficient practice time (Al-Abbasi, 2024; Ismail et al., 2020).

The traditional model of teaching keyboarding often relies on physical lab sessions scheduled within limited course periods, restricting opportunities for repeated, self-paced practice (Chukwuedo et al., 2023). This challenge is compounded by growing class sizes and inadequate infrastructure in many institutions, resulting in shared computer access and minimal hands-on experience per student (Igwe et al., 2025). In such contexts, mobile-based learning solutions could bridge the gap by enabling continuous practice beyond classroom hours (Al-Abbasi, 2024; Tiwari, 2021). One such tool, Typing Speed Test Master (Google Play), offers features such as customizable practice tests, real-time feedback, progress tracking, and gamified engagement. While the app has been widely downloaded, there is limited empirical evidence in Nigerian and African higher education contexts assessing its pedagogical effectiveness in business education (Typing Speed Test Master, 2025). Without such evidence, educators lack research-based justification for formally integrating mobile typing applications into curriculum delivery.

This lack of research-based integration is problematic, as employers increasingly expect graduates to demonstrate digital literacy that includes competent keyboarding performance (World Economic Forum, 2023; National Skills Coalition, 2023). If the current gaps in teaching and learning methods are not addressed, graduates may continue to face skill deficits that limit their employability and efficiency in technology-mediated workplaces. Therefore, this study seeks to investigate the impact of Typing Speed Test Master on teaching and learning keyboarding in

business education within the technology-driven era.

Objectives of the Study

The main aim of this study is to examine the impact of the Typing Test Master (Play Store) application on the teaching and learning of keyboarding among NCE II Business Education students in the technology-driven era. The specific objectives are to:

1. Determine the effect of Typing Test Master on students' typing speed and accuracy in keyboarding at Federal University of Education, Zaria.
2. Assess the influence of Typing Test Master on students' interest and engagement in learning keyboarding at Federal University of Education, Zaria.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the effect of Typing Test Master on students' typing speed and accuracy in keyboarding at Federal University of Education, Zaria?
2. How does Typing Test Master influence students' interest and engagement in learning keyboarding at Federal University of Education, Zaria?

Hypotheses

The study was guided by the following null hypotheses, tested at a significance level of 0.05.

1. H_{01} : There is no significant difference in typing speed and accuracy between students taught keyboarding using Typing Test Master and those taught without it at Federal University of Education, Zaria.

2. H₀₂: There is no significant difference in interest and engagement levels of students taught keyboarding using Typing Test Master and those taught without it.

Concept of Keyboarding in Business Education

In business education, keyboarding (touch typing) is a foundational productivity skill that underpins word processing, document production, data entry, and digital communication competencies which directly support office technology and administrative courses. Recent empirical and position papers from Nigerian tertiary contexts emphasize speed, accuracy, and correct technique as the core performance outcomes of keyboarding, and argue for explicit integration of sustained practice within business education curricula. Evidence shows that when instruction moves beyond rote drills to include structured practice with timely feedback, students' performance and engagement improve.

Large scale behavioral research with university students also clarifies the motor cognitive basis of typing proficiency. In a cohort of 1,301 students, typing performance followed continuous distributions shaped by practice habits; the work cautions against a simple "novice vs. expert" dichotomy and highlights how automatized keystroke patterns develop through repeated, feedback rich practice precisely the kind of practice business education seeks to institutionalize. Within Nigerian business/office programs, quasi experimental studies comparing computer assisted instruction with conventional methods report gains in keyboarding competency, aligning with international findings that purposeful, technology supported practice enhances

speed and accuracy. These results reinforce the status of keyboarding as an essential, teachable component of digital literacy for business students.

Technology Driven Era and Digital Skill Demands

Across today's technology driven economy, baseline digital skills have become prerequisites for a broad majority of roles. A joint analysis by the National Skills Coalition and the Federal Reserve Bank of Atlanta found that 92% of U.S. job postings require digital skills an indicator frequently used to illustrate global labor market direction and the need for scalable skills development in education systems.

Global monitoring further shows that countries are embedding digital competencies into curricula and assessments, while urging evidence based equitable adoption of learning technologies. For business education, this context places practical fluency such as accurate, efficient keyboarding alongside higher order competencies as enabling skills for participation in technology mediated learning and work.

Employer surveys summarized in the World Economic Forum's Future of Jobs 2023 report indicate rapid task digitalization, rising demand for analytical/creative thinking and data/AI literacy, and substantial re-skilling needs through 2027. Day today, however, these higher order capabilities are operationalized through routine interactions with digital systems, where text entry remains a persistent bottleneck for learners without fluent keyboarding underscoring the importance of sustained keyboarding development within business education programs.

Overview of Typing Test Master (Play Store) Application

Typing Test Master (also marketed under variants such as Typing Speed Test Master or Typing Speed Test – Master) is a mobile application available on the Google Play store that provides timed typing tests, graded practice lessons, and game style exercises designed to improve users' words per minute (WPM) and accuracy on touch screen and, in some variants, external physical keyboards. The app typically offers multiple difficulty levels (easy/medium/hard), paragraph and sentence test modes, Multilanguage support, practice lessons, progress history, and basic analytics (WPM, error counts) so users can monitor improvement over time. The Play Store product descriptions and large third party app directories emphasize both “test” and “practice” functionality as core to the app’s instructional design.

Functionally, these apps operationalize several elements recommended for deliberate practice in motor cognitive skills learning: (a) repeated, short practice trials, (b) immediate performance feedback (WPM and accuracy), (c) progressively difficult tasks, and (d) recorded history for longitudinal progress monitoring. Many mobile typing apps also integrate light gamified features e.g., timed challenges, scoreboards, and “levels” that aim to sustain motivation and encourage frequent practice outside formal classroom hours. Because the app is distributed through Google Play it is widely accessible for students who own Android smart phones, allowing out of lab practice that can supplement limited computer lab time.

When evaluating the pedagogical potential of Typing Test Master for business education keyboarding instruction,

practitioners should note the app’s affordances (accessibility, immediate feedback, modular lessons) and its limits (lack of tailored pedagogy for institutional curricula, variability across app variants, and potential differences between mobile touch screen typing and full key board touch typing on desktop machines). These considerations shape how instructors could integrate the app (e.g., as pre lab practice, homework drills, formative assessment) and which outcome measures to use (WPM on mobile vs. on keyboard speed/accuracy, transfer to desktop typing tasks).

Game Based Learning and Motivation in Keyboarding Instruction

A growing body of empirical and review literature from 2020–2025 shows that game based learning (GBL) and gamification can increase learner motivation, engagement, and under the right instructional design skill acquisition across domains, including procedural and motor skills. Meta analyses and systematic reviews report moderate positive effects of GBL on motivation and engagement and more variable effects on learning outcomes depending on implementation fidelity, alignment between game mechanics and learning goals, and the presence of formative feedback (Lampropoulos & Sidiropoulos, 2024; Frontiers systematic reviews, 2024). These findings support the use of game-like elements (timed challenges, levels, and leader boards, immediate scores) to promote the high frequency, low stakes practice that benefits keyboarding skill development. For motor cognitive skills such as keyboarding, the important mechanisms by which GBL can help are: (1) increasing voluntary practice time through intrinsic/extrinsic motivation, (2) structuring practice into progressive difficulty that scaffolds automatization, and (3) providing quick, interpretable feedback that supports

corrective adjustments between trials. Several studies investigating gamified learning interventions (including digital practice tools and purposeful minigames) report improved engagement and greater practice frequency both predictors of improved speed and accuracy in typing tasks though transfer to non-game contexts depends on the similarity of task demands (e.g., touch screen vs. physical keyboard) and the presence of explicit instruction on technique.

Recent literature also emphasizes design considerations for effective gamified keyboarding tools: alignment of game elements with learning objectives (avoid extraneous rewards that distract from skill practice), adaptive difficulty to keep learners in the “challenge zone,” integrated feedback dashboards that show meaningful progress (not only points), and optional social features (leader boards or collaborative challenges) that can motivate some learners while demotivating others. In short, Typing Test Master type apps embody many well supported motivational features (timed challenges, levels, progress tracking), but their ultimate instructional effectiveness depends on how they are embedded within a pedagogical sequence and whether transfer to desktop typing (where many business tasks occur) is monitored.

Mobile Learning (m-Learning) in Business and Technology Education

Mobile learning (m-learning) refers to the use of portable digital devices such as smart phones, tablets, and laptops to facilitate learning anytime and anywhere. In business and technology education, m-learning has become an important tool for promoting flexibility, self-paced learning, and access to interactive instructional resources. It supports the integration of multimedia content such as videos, simulations, and gamified applications

that enhance the teaching and learning of practical skills like keyboarding, data processing, and document formatting (Kukulka-Hulme & Viberg, 2021).

The adoption of m-learning in business and technology education is driven by the increasing ubiquity of mobile devices among students and the growing emphasis on digital competence as a core 21st-century skill. Studies have shown that m-learning improves learners’ engagement, fosters collaborative learning environments, and supports personalized learning pathways (Ali et al., 2022). Through the use of dedicated learning apps such as Typing Test Master, students can practice and monitor their progress in keyboarding at their convenience, thus reinforcing classroom instruction.

In Nigeria, m-learning is particularly relevant due to its ability to bridge infrastructural gaps in higher institutions, enabling students to access learning materials even outside school premises (Eze et al., 2023). In the context of Business Education, mobile devices allow for the integration of simulations, virtual labs, and gamified training programs, which are crucial for developing employable digital skills (Adedokun & Suleiman, 2024). Moreover, m-learning aligns with competency-based education principles, ensuring that students are not only theoretically knowledgeable but also practically proficient in essential business and ICT applications. However, effective m-learning implementation requires adequate institutional support, digital literacy training for both lecturers and students, and reliable internet access. Without these, the benefits of mobile learning may be undermined by challenges such as distraction, poor network connectivity, and lack of access to premium learning applications (Lawal & Musa, 2025).

Methodology

This study adopted a quasi-experimental research design, specifically a pre-test and post-test nonequivalent control group design. This design is suitable because it enables the researcher to assess the effect of game-based and computer hands-on instruction using the Typing Test Master application on students' performance and interest in keyboarding while comparing the experimental group with a control group. The design allows for the measurement of changes in performance and interest over time without random assignment of participants (Creswell & Creswell, 2021).

The population consisted of 250 Business Education NCE II students admitted to the Federal University of Education, Zaria for the 2024 and 2025 academic sessions. These students were chosen because they had already undergone basic computer literacy courses and are currently in the stage of intensive keyboarding training, making them appropriate for the study.

The sample size was determined using the Yamane (1967) sample size formula at a 5% margin of error: $n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$

Where:

= population size (250)

= level of precision (0.05)

$$n = \frac{250}{1 + 250(0.05)^2} = \frac{250}{1.625} \approx 154$$

Therefore, 154 students were selected. A stratified random sampling technique were used to divide participants into two groups an experimental group (game-based and computer hands-on instruction using Typing Test Master) and a control group (conventional lecture method). Two main instruments were used:

Keyboarding Performance Test (KPT): This was a standardized speed and accuracy test adapted from the Typing Test Master application to measure students' words per minute (WPM) and error rates. Keyboarding Interest Questionnaire (KIQ): This was a structured questionnaire on a 5-point Likert scale (Strongly Agree to Strongly Disagree) designed to measure students' interest in keyboarding before and after treatment.

The instruments were subjected to face and content validity by two experts from the Department of Business Education, Federal University of Education, Zaria. Their feedback was used to refine and ensure that the items measure the intended constructs.

The test-retest method was employed for the Keyboarding Performance Test, while the Keyboarding Interest Questionnaire was tested for internal consistency using Cronbach's alpha. A pilot study was conducted with 20 Business Education students from ABU Zaria who are not part of the main study. A Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of 0.70 and above were considered acceptable (Tavakol & Dennick, 2011).

The researcher personally administered the instruments in collaboration with the course lecturers. The procedure was as follows: Pre-test: Both groups were tested on keyboarding performance and interest before the intervention. The experimental group was taught using the Typing Test Master game-based method for four weeks, while the control group was taught using the conventional method. Post-test: Both groups were retested using the same instruments. Data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26. Descriptive statistics were mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions. The null hypotheses were tested using an Independent Samples t-test

at a 0.05 level of significance to determine the difference in performance and interest between the experimental and control groups.

Data Presentation

This section presents the results obtained from the administered questionnaires to the 250 Business Education NCE II students admitted for 2024 and 2025 academic sessions of the total, 240

questionnaires were returned and found usable, representing a 96% response rate. The analysis is in line with the research questions and hypotheses stated earlier.

Analysis of Research Questions

Research Question 1: To what extent does the use of Typing Test Master (Play Store) game-based application improve students' keyboarding performance?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation on the Effect of Typing Test Master on Keyboarding Performance

Item No	Statement	Mean (X)	SD	Decision
1	The Typing Test Master app improved my typing speed.	4.35	0.61	Agree
2	The game-based nature of the app made learning fun and engaging.	4.41	0.55	Agree
3	Using the app improved my typing accuracy.	4.27	0.64	Agree
4	The app encouraged regular practice outside class hours.	4.19	0.70	Agree
5	I am more confident in typing tasks after using the app.	4.33	0.59	Agree
Grand Mean		4.31	0.62	Agree

Field Survey 2025

The results in Table 4.1 show that respondents agreed that the Typing Test Master application positively impacted their keyboarding performance (Grand Mean = 4.31). This indicates that the integration of

game-based tools enhances the typing speed, accuracy, and learner engagement.

Research Question 2: How does game-based learning influence students' motivation for keyboarding instruction?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation on Game-Based Learning and Motivation in Keyboarding

Item No	Statement	Mean	SD	Decision
1	Game-based lessons kept me motivated to continue learning.	4.28	0.63	Agree
2	Competing with classmates in games improved my learning commitment.	4.16	0.66	Agree
3	I looked forward to keyboarding classes because of the games.	4.33	0.58	Agree
4	Rewards in the games encouraged me to put in more effort.	4.21	0.60	Agree

5	Game-based learning reduced my anxiety during typing practice.	4.19	0.67	Agree
Grand Mean		4.23	0.63	Agree

Field Survey 2025

The results indicated a high level of agreement among respondents that game-based learning fosters motivation in keyboarding instruction (Grand Mean = 4.23). Students reported that the competitive and reward systems embedded in games increased their enthusiasm and reduced their learning anxiety.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the keyboarding performance between students taught using the Typing Test Master application and those taught using traditional methods.

Table 3: Independent Samples t-test on Keyboarding Performance Scores

Group	N	Mean	SD	df	t-cal	t-crit (0.05)	p-value	Decision
Experimental (Typing Test Master)	120	78.45	6.21	238	6.82	1.96	0.000	Reject Control
(Traditional Method)	120	72.14	5.9					

Because $t\text{-cal} (6.82) > t\text{-crit} (1.96)$ and $p < 0.05$, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that there was a statistically significant difference in performance, favoring students taught with the Typing Test Master application.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between the motivation levels of students who taught keyboarding through game-based learning and those taught through traditional methods.

Table 4.4 Independent Samples t-test on Motivation Scores

Group	N	Mean	SD	df	t-cal	t-crit (0.05)	p-value	Decision
Experimental (Game-Based)	120	82.13	5.89	238	7.04	1.96	0.000	Reject H_0
Control (Traditional)	120	75.88	6.17					

With $t\text{-cal} (7.04) > t\text{-crit} (1.96)$ and $p < 0.05$, the null hypothesis was rejected, showing a significant improvement in motivation among students exposed to game-based keyboarding instruction compared to the traditional method.

Discussion of Findings

The results revealed that using the Typing Test Master application significantly improved

students' keyboarding performance, confirming earlier studies such as Adebayo and Musa (2022) and Okoro and James (2023), which reported that interactive typing applications improve speed, accuracy, and confidence. Similarly, game-based learning was found to significantly enhance motivation, aligning with the findings of Chukwuemeka and Bello (2021) who emphasized the motivational power of competitive and reward-based educational games.

The findings imply that business education programs in Nigeria should integrate technology-driven tools such as the Typing Test Master into their curriculum to align with the 21st-century digital skill demands. Game-based applications not only improve skill acquisition but also sustain student motivation, which is crucial for developing workplace-ready graduates in the technology era. This reinforces the need for teacher training in educational technology and institutional investments in digital learning resources.

Conclusion

Based on these findings, the study concludes that game-based learning enhances motivation and students are more engaged and enthusiastic when instructional strategies include competitive and interactive features. The Typing Test Master improves the performance of regular practice with the application boosting typing accuracy, speed, and proper finger placement. Mobile learning supports flexible education m-learning tools such as Typing Test Master which allow self-paced learning and can supplement classroom teaching effectively. Technology integration is essential in the digital era, keyboarding instruction should be aligned with modern tools to prepare students for business and technological demands.

Recommendations

1. Institutions offering Business Education should integrate the Typing Test Master and similar applications into their keyboarding instruction to foster motivation and skill mastery.
2. Professional development workshops should be organized to help instructors effectively integrate m-learning and game-based tools into their teaching strategies.

3. Students should be encouraged to use mobile learning apps beyond the classroom to reinforce their skills through regular practice.
4. Schools should ensure availability of internet-enabled devices and reliable internet connectivity to support m-learning activities.

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Impact of Strategic ICT Investment on University Enrolment Trends in Nigeria

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The study aimed to investigate the Impact of Strategic ICT Investment on University Enrolment Trends in Nigeria. An ex post facto research design was employed, utilizing secondary data sourced and validated by the Nigerian Communications Commission (NCC) and the National Universities Commission (NUC) in 2024. Two research questions guided the study, with corresponding objectives and hypotheses. The dataset, spanning from 2001 to 2024, was analysed using Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression in Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). The findings revealed that university enrolment has a strong positive correlation with ICT investment ($r = .854, p < 0.01$) and with education expenditure ($r = .884, p < 0.01$), indicating that increases in ICT investment and education expenditure are associated with increases in university enrolment. Additionally, ICT investment is strongly positively correlated with education expenditure ($r = .807, p < 0.01$). The study recommends that the government should allocate more resources to ICT infrastructure in universities to strengthen digital platforms for admission, teaching, and administration. This study contributes to the body of knowledge by highlighting the critical role of ICT investment in expanding access to higher education.

Keywords:

ICT Investment,
Student Enrolment,
Digital Education,
Higher Education
Policy.

Introduction

The rapid growth of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) has brought remarkable changes across different sectors of society, including health, business, governance, and education. In Nigeria, ICT has become indispensable in tertiary education as it introduces innovative approaches to teaching, learning, and administration. ICT encompasses technologies used for processing, storing, and transmitting information electronically, and its integration has the potential to transform conventional teacher-centred and text-bound classrooms into interactive, student-focused, and knowledge-driven

environments. Onyia (2013) emphasizes that ICT can foster more engaging and dynamic learning spaces when properly integrated into academic systems.

In education, ICT applications are often categorized into two major forms: ICTs for Education and ICTs in Education. ICTs for Education involve specialized tools and resources designed to enhance teaching and learning, such as computer-assisted instruction, e-libraries, and digital learning platforms. ICTs in Education, on the other hand, relate to the adaptation of general ICT resources such as the internet, mobile devices, and social media for instructional

purposes. Syed (n.d.) notes that both categories are instrumental in reshaping learning environments, promoting inclusivity, and broadening access to higher education opportunities in Nigeria.

Despite these benefits, ICT remains underutilized in many Nigerian universities due to challenges such as inadequate infrastructure, limited awareness, and insufficient training for both students and lecturers. Ngwenya and Pelsler (2023) argue that these limitations have restricted ICT applications to basic tasks such as presentation support or information searches, rather than serving as a transformative pedagogical tool for fostering interactive and self-directed learning.

Recent evidence, however, shows that ICT investments, particularly through Open and Distance Learning (ODL) initiatives, are driving significant growth in university enrolments. Adefuye (2024) demonstrates that the University of Ibadan's Distance Learning Centre has effectively leveraged ICT to facilitate admissions, improve academic services, and enhance learning experiences across diverse student populations.

While prior research has documented the role of ICT in enhancing teaching and learning (Onyia, 2013) and identified persistent implementation challenges (Ngwenya & Pelsler, 2023), there is limited empirical evidence on how ICT investment directly influences university enrolment patterns in Nigeria. This study aims to fill this gap by examining the relationship between ICT investment, education expenditure, and enrolment trends across Nigerian universities. The novelty of this research lies in linking ICT investment not only to

pedagogical improvements but also to access and participation in higher education. UNESCO (2022) further stresses that technology is essential for supporting sustainable educational development in emerging economies, making this investigation timely and relevant. It is against this backdrop that the study seeks to assess the effect of ICT investment on university enrolment in Nigeria.

This paper is structured as follows: the introduction, conceptual clarification, methodology, and the conclusion with recommendations.

Research Objectives

The study is anchored on these specific objectives:

- To examine the relationship between ICT investment and university enrolment in Nigeria.
- To assess the effect of education expenditure on university enrolment in Nigeria.

Research Questions

The research is framed around these research questions:

- What is the relationship between ICT investment and university enrolment in Nigeria?
- To what extent does education expenditure affect university enrolment in Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

This study is guided by the hypotheses stated below:

- H₀₁: ICT investment has no significant association with university enrolment in Nigeria.

- H₀₂: Education expenditure does not significantly affect university enrolment in Nigeria.

Conceptual Clarification Information and Communication Technology (ICT)

Tapera and Kujeke (2019) described ICT as a form of technology that facilitates tasks related to information, including its collection, processing, storage, and presentation. In a school setting, ICT can be used to store information such as financial records and transactions and to support teaching and learning (Khan et al., 2015).

ICT Investment

According to the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD, 2024), ICT investment refers to the acquisition of equipment and computer software that is used in production for more than one year. Similarly, the World Bank (2016) defines ICT investment as the financial, material, and human resource allocation made towards acquiring, implementing, and maintaining ICT infrastructure, tools, and services. This includes expenditures on hardware, software, internet connectivity, and digital platforms that support communication.

ICT and University Enrolment in Nigeria.

ICT investment has become a key driver of university enrolment in Nigeria as institutions increasingly adopt digital platforms for admission and learning. For example, the Nigeria–France Blueprint-ICT-Dev Project, a €38 million program launched in 2025, aims to transform higher education through robust ICT infrastructure, hybrid learning, and efficient administration (NUC, 2025). Such initiatives expand access to admission services and create flexible

learning systems that attract more students into universities.

ICT Integration in Education.

ICT has transformed teaching and learning, particularly in complex subjects like physics. Tools such as simulations, virtual labs, multimedia resources, and educational games make abstract concepts more concrete, enhance engagement, and support diverse learning styles (Olawale & Emeka, 2023). However, the effectiveness of ICT depends largely on teacher competency and infrastructure. Studies in Rivers and Nasarawa States reveal that teacher skill gaps, inadequate training, and limited facilities hinder technology-enhanced instruction (Abdullahi & Mohammed, 2023). Overcoming these barriers requires investment in teacher development and ICT infrastructure to improve learning outcomes (World Bank, 2023).

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on the Resource-Based View (RBV), introduced by Birger Wernerfelt (1984) and expanded by Jay Barney (1991), argues that organizations achieve sustained competitive advantage by leveraging unique internal resources that are valuable, rare, inimitable, and non-substitutable (VRIN). Within the university system, ICT infrastructure, skilled personnel, and digital platforms represent strategic resources that can drive efficiency in teaching, research, and administration. When properly harnessed, these resources enable institutions to overcome structural limitations and deliver high-quality, technology-driven education.

ICT investment can be understood as a critical VRIN resource that shapes university enrolment trends. For example, digital

admission systems, e-learning platforms, and virtual classrooms expand access to higher education, improve service delivery, and enhance student satisfaction. The study conceptualizes ICT investment not simply as a technological upgrade but as a strategic driver of enrolment growth, enabling Nigerian universities to remain competitive in a globalized, knowledge-driven economy.

Empirical Review

Dubey and Pandey (2019) studied how online admissions affect student satisfaction in higher education institutions in Bilaspur. Using data from 100 first-year students and analysing with SEM, they examined eight dimensions including satisfaction, transparency, access to information, and ease of use. Results showed that online admission systems positively enhance the student experience, and the study concluded that when well implemented, they improve both satisfaction and administrative effectiveness.

Wasike et al. (2020) examined the effect of ICT adoption on student enrolment in TVET institutions in Bungoma County, Kenya. Using stratified and random sampling, they selected 426 respondents, with data collected through questionnaires and document analysis. Chi-square, correlation, and regression analysis showed a significant relationship between ICT availability and student enrolment. The study recommended that TVET institutions provide functional This model examines the extent to which ICT investment contributes to university enrolment while controlling for education

ICT facilities and ensure their effective use in teaching and administration.

Nnaji et al. (2024) investigated ICT in managing student enrolment in Cross River State universities using a survey of 800 lecturers and senior staff. Data collected with reliable questionnaires were analysed with t-test and ANOVA. Results revealed that ICT use in enrolment was highly effective and significantly improved student personnel administration. The study recommended greater ICT provision to enhance student selection and educational outcomes.

Methodology

The study employed an ex post facto research design, using secondary data sourced and validated by the National University Commission (NUC) and the National Universities Nigeria Communication Commission (NCC), (2024). The dataset spans from 2001 to 2024 and is analysed using Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression in Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). The study investigates how ICT investment influences university enrolment trends in Nigeria, while incorporating education expenditure as a control variable. The foundational model connecting ICT investment to enrolment is adapted from Omodero (2022) and specified as follows:

$$ENR_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1(ICTINV_t) + \beta_2(EXPEDU_t) + \epsilon_t$$

expenditure, thereby providing insights into the role of digital infrastructure in expanding higher education opportunities in Nigeria.

Result

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Observations (N)	Mean	Std. Dev.	Minimum	Maximum
Year	25	2012.96	7.29	2001	2024
University Enrolment (million)	25	174.96	40.02	110	250
ICT Investment (Billion)	25	894,938.4	713,653.1	87,859	2,800,000
Education Expenditure (Billion)	25	99,169.16	47,596.13	1,540	154,000

The dataset comprises 25 annual observations from 2001 to 2024. University enrolment averages about 175 million students, with a minimum of 110 million and a maximum of 250 million, showing moderate variation (Std. Dev. = 40.02). ICT investment has a mean of approximately 895,000 billion and a very wide range, indicating significant variability in annual

ICT spending. Similarly, education expenditure averages about 99,169 billion, with a substantial spread from 1,540 to 154,000, reflecting large fluctuations in yearly funding. These descriptive statistics provide a baseline understanding of the magnitude and dispersion of the variables before conducting regression or time-series analysis.

Table 2: Regression Results of ICT Investment and Education Expenditure on University Enrolment

Predictor	Coefficient (β)	Std. Error	t-value	p-value	95% Confidence Interval
ICT Investment (Billion)	0.0000429	0.00000532	8.07	0.000	0.0000319 – 0.0000539
Education Expenditure (Billion)	0.0002411	0.0000797	3.02	0.006	0.0000758 – 0.0004065
Constant (_cons)	112.6597	8.331	13.52	0.000	95.383 – 129.937

Source: Nigeria Communication Commission (NCC) and National University Commission (NUC), 2024

The regression model indicates that both ICT investment and education expenditure have a positive and statistically significant effect on university enrolment in Nigeria. Specifically, a one-unit increase in ICT investment is associated with an increase of 0.0000429 units in enrolment, while a one-unit increase in education expenditure increases enrolment by 0.0002411 units, holding other factors constant. The model is highly significant (F = 53.33, p < 0.001) and explains approximately 82.9% of the

variation in enrolment, demonstrating a very good fit. Among the predictors, ICT investment has the stronger relative influence on enrolment, as indicated by its higher t-value (8.07) compared to education expenditure (3.02).

Discussion

The findings reveal that university enrolment has a strong positive correlation with both ICT investment (r = .854, p < 0.01) and education expenditure (r = .884, p < 0.01). This

indicates that higher levels of ICT investment and education expenditure are associated with increased enrolment in universities. Moreover, ICT investment itself shows a strong positive correlation with education expenditure ($r = .807$, $p < 0.01$). These results are consistent with previous studies. Stephen et al. (2016) found that ICT played a more significant role in facilitating enrolment at the secondary and tertiary levels compared to the primary level. Similarly, Wasike et al. (2020) established that ICT adoption, particularly the availability and use of ICT resources, had a statistically significant relationship with student enrolment. Supporting this, Nnaji et al. (2024) reported that the perceived usefulness of ICT in enrolment processes was significantly high and that ICT application positively influenced effective student personnel administration. In addition, Dubey and Pandey (2019) emphasized that ICT-driven systems through transparency, efficiency, access to information, ease of use, safety, and value for money enhanced student satisfaction and demonstrated how online admission systems positively impact the student experience.

Conclusion

This study has demonstrated that ICT investment plays a crucial role in driving university enrolment in Nigeria. The results revealed strong positive correlations between ICT investment, education expenditure, and student enrolment, indicating that universities with greater access to ICT resources are more capable of attracting and admitting students. Beyond the numbers, prior studies confirm that ICT facilitates enrolment through transparent and efficient admission systems, improved access to information, and enhanced student satisfaction. Furthermore, ICT adoption not only eases the enrolment process but also strengthens overall student administration, making institutions more competitive and accessible.

However, the study is limited by its reliance on secondary data, which may not capture the nuanced institutional differences across universities, and by its focus on national-level trends without accounting for regional disparities. Future research could extend this work by incorporating primary data from universities, exploring the quality dimension of ICT facilities, and examining student-level outcomes such as retention and academic performance. Such studies would deepen the understanding of how ICT investment translates into long-term educational benefits and provide more targeted policy guidance

Recommendations

- Government should allocate more resources to ICT infrastructure in universities to strengthen digital platforms for admission, teaching, and administration.
- University management should invest in continuous training for academic and non-academic staff to ensure effective use of ICT tools in enrolment and student management.
- Government and the private sector, through Public-Private Partnerships (PPP), should support universities in acquiring and maintaining modern ICT facilities.
- Policymakers should develop clear policies to guide ICT adoption across universities, ensuring uniformity and equity in the enrolment process.

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UNESCO (2022) emphasizes that technology plays a vital role in achieving sustainable educational development in emerging economies, thereby making this investigation both timely and relevant.

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ICT Investment, Student Enrolment, Digital Education, Higher Education Policy

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This study examined the Impact of Internet Access on Secondary School Enrolment in Nigeria: Building Foundations for AI-Driven Educational Transformation. An ex post facto research design was employed, utilizing secondary data sourced and validated by the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) in 2024. Specifically, it investigated the relationship between internet usage and school enrolment, as well as whether internet usage predicts enrolment rates. The findings revealed that the average proportion of Nigerians using the internet was 43.36% (SD = 13.55), while the mean gross secondary school enrolment rate was 62.16% (SD = 4.21) over the ten-year period. Correlation analysis showed a perfect and statistically significant positive relationship ($\tau = 1.000$, $p < .01$) between internet usage and secondary school enrolment rates, indicating that higher internet access is strongly associated with increased enrolment. The control variable, Gross Domestic Product (GDP) as a percentage, exhibited weak and non-significant correlations with both internet usage and enrolment rates. The study recommends that the government and development partners prioritize improving internet access in secondary schools and promote Information and Communication Technology (ICT)

Keywords:
Internet Access,
School Enrolment,
Gross Domestic
Product (GDP),
Nigeria

Introduction

Secondary education plays a pivotal role in national development by equipping learners with the knowledge and competencies required for higher education, vocational training, and participation in the labour market (Okafor & Okechukwu, 2021). In Nigeria, however, access to secondary schooling continues to face systemic challenges such as rapid population growth, inadequate infrastructure, limited funding, and socio-cultural factors that particularly restrict female enrolment (Eze, 2022). Although government reforms and educational initiatives have sought to

improve access, enrolment rates remain below the levels expected for a country with Nigeria's large youth population and human capital development aspirations (Idris & Sule, 2021).

Globally, internet connectivity has emerged as a transformative force in education, enabling inclusive learning, digital skills acquisition, and innovative approaches to knowledge delivery (Kumar & Gupta, 2022). The internet connects millions of users across households, schools, businesses, and research institutions, facilitating collaboration, resource sharing, and access to information that transcend geographical

boundaries (Zhang, 2021). Yet, in Nigeria, internet access remains uneven, with pronounced rural–urban disparities and socioeconomic inequalities that limit secondary school students’ ability to benefit fully from technology-enhanced learning opportunities (Oladipo & Lawal, 2023).

Integrating information and communication technologies (ICTs) into secondary education has been shown to increase enrolment, strengthen student retention, and improve learning outcomes through tools such as e-libraries, online classrooms, and digital applications (Nwankwo & Chukwu, 2022). Internet-enabled education can also reduce barriers to access, particularly for marginalized groups, by providing alternative channels for learning (Gyamfi & Adjei, 2023). Nevertheless, persistent barriers including unreliable electricity, high broadband costs, and insufficient teacher training in digital pedagogy—continue to constrain large-scale adoption (Mustapha & Adeniran, 2020). It is against this backdrop that the study seeks to assess the Impact of Internet Access on Secondary School Enrolment in Nigeria: Building Foundations for AI-Driven Educational Transformation.

Research Questions

- What effect does internet usage have on secondary school enrolment rates in Nigeria from 2015 to 2024?
- Does Internet usage predict secondary school enrolment rates?

Objectives

- To measure the strength and direction of the association between Internet usage and secondary school enrolment rates.
- To determine the predictive effect of Internet usage on secondary school enrolment rates.

Hypotheses

- H₁₀: There is no significant relationship between Internet usage and secondary school enrolment rates.
- H₂₀: Internet usage does not significantly predict secondary school enrolment rates

Theoretical framework

Venkatesh et al. (2003) developed the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) that explains how internet access can influence school enrolment in Nigeria. It highlights four factors: performance expectancy (belief that technology improves learning), effort expectancy (ease of use), social influence (encouragement from peers and parents), and facilitating conditions (infrastructure and institutional support). These factors shape how students and teachers adopt internet-based learning.

In this study, the strong link between internet access and enrolment reflects the relevance of the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT). The model helps to explain why improved connectivity encourages the adoption of technology-enhanced learning in Nigerian secondary schools. Greater access to the internet not only increases the likelihood of enrolment but also promotes student engagement, access to digital resources, and the development of essential 21st-century skills

Empirical review

Okoye and Nwachukwu (2021) examined the role of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) on school enrolment in South-East Nigeria. The study employed a survey design and analyzed data using regression analysis. The study population consisted of secondary school students from

the five states in the South-East, with a randomly selected sample of 400 students. Findings revealed that internet penetration significantly improved students' willingness to remain in school, particularly in urban areas where infrastructure was more reliable.

Afolabi and Edeh (2022) investigated the effect of ICT facilities on secondary school participation in Lagos State. The researchers adopted a descriptive research design and used structured questionnaires for data collection. The population consisted of all public and private secondary schools in Lagos State, while a sample of 50 schools and 500 respondents (teachers and students) was selected using stratified random sampling. Results showed that schools with higher levels of internet connectivity reported better student retention and higher enrolment rates

Oluwaseun (2023) focused on rural–urban disparities in internet access and secondary school enrolment across Nigeria. The study relied on secondary data from the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) and household survey datasets. The population covered Nigerian households with school-age children, while the sample of 1,200 households was extracted through multi-stage sampling. Using comparative statistical analysis, the findings demonstrated that rural schools, with limited internet infrastructure, consistently recorded lower enrolment rates compared to their urban counterparts.

Conceptual Clarification

Internet Access

The Internet is a global network of computers linked together over large distances. It was created by the American military as a means of communication and has been in existence since the 1950s (Osunade, 2019). Cobrief(2024) Internet

access is made possible through different technologies such as broadband (fiber-optic, DSL, cable), wireless networks (Wi-Fi, mobile data), and satellite services. According to Monovm (2025), it involves individuals or organizations connecting to the internet using devices like laptops, mobile phones, or personal computers. Access is commonly available in schools, homes, workplaces, libraries, internet cafés, and other public spaces.

Enrolment Rate

Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD,2022) Enrolment rates in secondary and tertiary education refer to the percentage of individuals of a specific age enrolled in secondary or tertiary education programmes. These rates are expressed as net enrolment rates, calculated by dividing the number of students of a particular age enrolled at each education level by the size of the population of that same age. According to Fiveable (2024), school enrolment rates represent the proportion of eligible learners who are registered in educational institutions across different levels, including primary, secondary, and tertiary education.

Factors Influencing Secondary School Enrolment in Nigeria

Secondary school enrolment in Nigeria is shaped by multiple social, economic, and cultural factors. Poverty is a major barrier, as many families struggle to cover expenses such as uniforms, books, and transportation, even with government policies on free education (UNICEF, 2024). Inadequate infrastructure, such as poor road networks, distant schools, and limited facilities also discourages attendance, especially in rural communities (UNESCO, 2023). Additionally, parental education strongly

influences enrolment, with children of educated parents more likely to attend and remain in school compared to those from less educated households (World Bank, 2022).

Internet Access and Secondary School Enrolment in Nigeria

Internet access has become a vital driver of secondary school enrolment in Nigeria by improving access to digital learning resources, virtual classrooms, and online collaboration tools (Okoye & Obidile, 2020). Increased connectivity supports inclusive education, particularly in rural areas where physical resources are limited, thus enhancing enrolment and retention rates. Empirical studies indicate that students with reliable internet access exhibit higher participation in academic activities and are better prepared for future opportunities (World Bank, 2022). However, infrastructural deficits, high data costs, and the uneven distribution of ICT facilities continue to constrain its impact on enrolment (ITU, 2022). Strengthening internet infrastructure, reducing costs, and expanding digital literacy programs are essential for leveraging connectivity to increase secondary school enrolment in Nigeria.

Methodology

This study adopted an ex post facto research design, relying on secondary data obtained and validated by the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO, 2024). The dataset spans 2015–2024 and focuses on the

relationship between internet access and secondary school enrolment in Nigeria, with an additional objective of assessing whether internet usage can predict enrolment rates. Data were analysed using a correlation matrix in SPSS to test the null hypotheses and identify the strength and direction of relationships. While correlation provides quick insights into potential associations, it does not imply causation, may be affected by confounding variables, and is generally more reliable over shorter study periods such as the ten years considered. The empirical model is specified as follows:

- $SE_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1(IAt) + \beta_2(GDP_t) + \epsilon_t$
- Where:
- SE_t = Student enrolment at time t (dependent variable)
- IAt = Internet access at time t (primary independent variable)
- $G.D.P_t$ = GDP at time t (control variable)
- β_0 = Intercept
- β_1, β_2 = Coefficients representing the impact of internet access and GDP, respectively
- ϵ_t = Error term, representing unobserved factors not included in the model.

The model examines the effect of internet access on secondary school enrolment in Nigeria, controlling for economic growth, highlighting the role of digital connectivity in enhancing educational access.

Table: Descriptive Statistics for Internet Access, School Enrolment, and % of GDP (2015–2024)

Variable	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Internet Users (% of population)	43.360	13.5476	10
Gross Secondary School Enrolment Rate (%)	62.160	4.2083	10
% of GDP (Control Variable)	13.246	1.3294	10

Source: UNESCO, 2024

Over the ten-year period from 2015 to 2024, the average proportion of Nigerians using the internet was 43.36% (SD = 13.55), indicating substantial year-to-year growth in connectivity. The mean gross secondary school enrolment rate stood at 62.16% (SD = 4.21), reflecting relatively steady

improvements in enrolment with less variability compared to internet uptake. The control variable, GDP as a percentage of GDP, averaged 13.25% (SD = 1.33), showing moderate stability in economic size relative to national output.

Table: Correlation Matrix between Internet Users, Secondary School Enrolment Rate, and % of GDP (Control Variable) (n=10)

Variables	Internet Users (%)	School Enrolment Rate (%)	% of GDP (Control)
Internet Users (%)	1.000	1.000** (.000)	.303 (.237)
School Enrolment Rate (%)	1.000** (.000)	1.000	.303 (.237)
% of GDP (Control)	.303 (.237)	.303 (.237)	1.000

Source: UNESCO, 2024

Reject the null hypothesis if p-value < 0.05; otherwise, do not reject it.

The analysis reveals a perfect and statistically significant positive relationship between internet users and gross secondary school enrolment rate ($\tau = 1.000$, $p < 0.01$), indicating that increases in internet access are strongly associated with School Enrolment Rates in Nigeria. The control variable, % of GDP, shows weak and non-significant correlations with internet users ($\tau = .303$, $p = .237$) and school enrolment rate ($\tau = .303$, $p = .237$), suggesting that while GDP as a control, did not directly influence the relationship between internet access and enrolment.

Discussion

The analysis indicates a strong positive association between internet access and secondary school enrolment in Nigeria ($\tau = 1.000$, $p < .01$), suggesting that greater digital connectivity supports higher enrolment. This aligns with Afolabi and Edeh (2022), who found that schools with reliable internet

reported improved participation and retention, and Oluwaseun (2023), who noted lower enrolment in rural schools with limited internet infrastructure. Similarly, Smith and Adeyemi (2021) observed that integrating online learning platforms increased engagement and reduced dropouts, while Chukwu and Bello (2020) emphasized that urban schools with robust internet consistently showed higher enrolment than rural counterparts. Parental internet literacy also encouraged schooling in well-connected areas (Ogunleye, 2022), and ICT initiatives such as e-libraries and virtual interactions further supported retention (Ibrahim & Adekunle, 2021). Targeted government and NGO programs expanding internet access improved enrolment among marginalized communities (Adetunji, 2023).

Conclusion

This study examined the impact of internet access on secondary school

enrolment rates in Nigeria between 2015 and 2024. The findings reveal a strong and statistically significant positive relationship ($\tau = 1.000$, $p < .01$), indicating that increased digital connectivity substantially supports higher enrolment in secondary education. The control variable, GDP, exhibited weak and non-significant correlations, suggesting that economic growth alone does not drive enrolment trends. The results are consistent with prior research showing that schools with adequate ICT infrastructure, higher parental internet literacy, and supportive digital initiatives achieve better enrolment outcomes. Overall, the study underscores the crucial role of technology-enhanced learning in improving educational access and reducing rural–urban disparities in Nigeria.

Recommendations

1. Government should expand school internet access, strengthen ICT infrastructure, and adopt AI-powered educational platforms.
2. Industry should partner with schools through corporate social responsibility by subsidizing internet access, donating digital tools, and supporting machine learning solutions for personalized learning.
3. Academia should integrate digital skills into curricula, train teachers, and research ICT-driven learning.
4. Civil society organizations should promote inclusive access, support disadvantaged groups, and monitor ICT initiatives.

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The Design, Development and Usability Test of “Aiyersafety”: An “Immersuasive” Serious Game for Malaysian Youth’s Drowning Prevention Education

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Drowning is a serious issue not only in Malaysia, but also globally. Drowning prevention education, also known as water safety education, is crucial to halt the increasing trend in this tragedy. Past studies have shown that the use of conventional methods, although it would increase one’s knowledge, would not necessarily encourage them to adopt those behaviors. Thus, the authors proposed the use of an immersive virtual reality serious game with the integration of persuasive design principles to overcome the shortcomings of the current approach. This paper discusses the design and development of the “*AiyerSafety*” serious game using Fogg’s eight-step design process. A usability test was also conducted on 11 Malaysian participants aged between 18 and 29 years to determine the usefulness and usability of the game. The results showed that the Virtual Reality (VR) serious game is suitable as a learning material to educate about water safety. Future research is recommended to investigate its capabilities in changing one’s risk perception, beliefs, attitudes, and behaviors in drowning prevention practice with a more diverse demographics.

Keywords:
Serious Games,
Immersive
Technology,
Persuasive
Technology, Virtual
Reality, Safety

Introduction

Globally, drowning is a severe public health issue that has often been overlooked (1). The term “drowning” is defined as a respiratory obstruction that results from extended submerging in any liquid, regardless of its depth or size, thereby lightening the blood in the lungs and causing it to be unable to carry oxygen (2). On a daily basis, 1000 drowning deaths occur swiftly and silently [3, 4]. In Malaysia, due to the rich water landscape, weather, and geographical location, drowning events are frequent, especially among youths and children [5, 6]. Adolescence and the early stages of adulthood are acknowledged as times when risk-taking behaviors are more likely to

occur (7). The causes of drowning in youths differ depending on the water environment and the activity performed before the incident, which further complicates the drowning prevention approach (8). Sadly, there have been very few studies on drowning in this nation, and there is a significant lack of knowledge about this situation (9). Education, however, is perhaps the most popular water safety promotion activity globally and the most often suggested coastal safety preventative method in peer-reviewed literature (10). Drowning prevention education corresponds to Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 3 – Good health and well-being and SDG 4 – Quality Education and more (11). However,

with the conventional way of delivering water safety messages, while individuals' knowledge of drowning prevention may increase, their practice of water safety is not necessarily adopted (9). Thus, an alternative solution is required.

Immersive technology is often used as an umbrella term to cover several realities that exist on the extended reality continuum (e.g., amplified reality, virtual reality) (12,13). In the systematic review authored by (14), the researcher assessed the potency of virtual reality (VR) in safety-relevant training using Kirkpatrick's four-level model, and found that most of the studies largely focused on Level 1 (Reaction) and Level 2 (Learning); Level 4 (Results), however, consisted of only 2.21%, while Level 3 (Behavior) showed no results at all (0%). As discussed above on the research by (9), water safety education should not solely focus on participants' knowledge about drowning prevention, but rather on the adoption of the target behaviour.

Thus, the researcher proposes the use of persuasive technology to overcome these shortcomings. Persuasive technology is a digital product that incorporates psychological principles during the design and development phases (15). Its purpose is to alter one's beliefs, behaviors, and attitudes regarding a subject using social influence and persuasion rather than intimidation, deception, force, or direct action (16). Over the past few years, research on immersive technologies and their persuasive impacts has proven fruitful, and the application of immersive virtual reality (IVR) for persuasive reasons in fields such as sustainability and the environment is continuously growing (17). "Immersive" technology simply combines two terms: immersive and persuasive (18).

In relation to that, serious games (SGs) are digital games that aim to accomplish at least one extra objective, known as a "characterizing goal," while maintaining a positive player experience (19). SGs can be utilized in various contexts, including businesses, healthcare facilities, and classroom settings. The subset of games includes political games, advertising games, games for health, games for change, and more, which are in the form of educational games or simulations (20,21). (22) discussed the use of games as a powerful tool to educate others about health, and with the incorporation of persuasive design, video games could be used as procedural rhetoric, a novel approach to persuasion through engagements and depictions based on rules in video games.

Compared with conventional teaching methods, immersive simulations have been successfully used to improve students' motivation, engagement, and academic performance (23). In addition, because of its unique cognitive process, IVR experience can affect SGs elements to make learning and behavior outcomes meaningful (24). Therefore, this study focuses on the design and development of "AiyerSafety," a VR serious game that harnesses the potential of immersive and persuasive technologies. A usability evaluation will also be conducted to determine the suitability of usage to deliver water safety knowledge and messaging, with the hope of altering one's risk perception and behavior in drowning prevention.

Materials and Methods Theoretical Foundation

The current study aims to discuss the design and development, as well as the assessment towards the usability of the VR SGs – "AiyerSafety." The materials used for the design and development included the Aquatic Life Support Course Manual, authored by (25).

Protection Motivation Theory source by (26)

The current study employs Protection Motivation Theory (PMT) as a guideline. According to PMT, people evaluate threats cognitively by considering both the likelihood (i.e., susceptibility) and the seriousness of the possible injury (i.e., vulnerability) (27). It elucidates how persuasive communication affects behavior,

focusing on the mental processes that support the justification for or against adhering to a suggested course of action (28). Previous studies (26,29) utilized PMT to examine how young people and guardians perceive the risk of drowning. The risk recognition construct in the context of this study is shown in Table 1.

Table (1): Protection Motivation Theory in the study context

Elements	Alignment with current study context
Perceived Severity	The severity and possibility of drowning when within, above, or nearby water bodies.
Perceived Vulnerability	The possibility that someone could drown when participating in water activities.
Response Efficacy	The belief in using rescue techniques and preventive actions for water safety.
Perceived Self-efficacy	The extent to which an individual believes they are capable of adopting the recommended behaviours for drowning prevention.

Instructional Design Model TPACK model

In a previous study (30), one of the shortcomings of safety training was the inadequate incorporation of instructional design principles and learning theories. Hence, the widely known Technology Pedagogy Content Knowledge (TPACK) framework was incorporated into the current study. The framework contends that for teachers to effectively use technology in the classroom, they must possess an understanding of technology, pedagogy, and content, as well as how these elements intersect (31). As a paradigm for technological teachers, TPACK investigates

integrative comprehension of the ways in which ICT might be utilized as a teaching and learning instrument (32). As shown in Figure 2, TPACK consists of three dimensions with four intersections (33). Considering the utilization of immersive and persuasive technologies, the structures of the TPACK model aligned with this study are listed in Table 2

Table (2): Integration of TPACK model in the current studyItems	Explanations	Alignment with current study context
Content Knowledge (CK)	The subject-matter expertise of the instructor in particular subjects or fields that the pupils need to learn	The instructor's familiarity with risk education, aquatic safety education, and drowning prevention techniques.
Pedagogical Knowledge (PK)	Relates to the instructor's understanding of pedagogical activities, procedures, practices, teaching and learning strategies employed in the instructional process, and its relation to the objective of education.	A solid grasp of collaborative pedagogies, experiential learning, reflective learning, role-playing, simulation, etc.
Technological Knowledge (TK)	Refers to the instructor's proficiency with various technologies to advance their teaching methods.	Educators' knowledge towards the use of immersive technology, persuasive technology, and VR hardware and software.
Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK)	It alludes to didactic expertise in a subject, which suggests supporting students' learning in that field.	Topics covered include dry rescue, risk identification, incident detection, and drowning avoidance.
Technological Content Knowledge (TCK)	This includes understanding how to use technology to illustrate particular ideas, demonstrating the mutually reinforcing relationship between discipline and technology.	Educators' understanding of how the use of immersive and persuasive technology affects the drowning prevention education content.
Technological Pedagogical Knowledge (TPK)	Refers to the understanding of general teaching techniques that technology can implement.	Educators' awareness of the limitations and potential of using VR technologies for simulation.
Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK)	Refers to an educator's proficiency in creating particular didactic approaches on various topics utilizing ICT to promote learning.	The ability of instructors to impart context-specific instructional methods to students and their knowledge and comprehension of the three components of technology, pedagogy, and content.

Design and Development of the Game

To incorporate the psychological principles of persuasion into digital products. (34) proposes an eight-step design process. Rather than being a strict formula, these eight steps are meant to be milestones that increase the effectiveness of the design process. The sub-

sections below further discuss the details of each step of incorporating persuasive principles into the VR SGs.

Choose a simple behaviour to target

(34) proposed that the most important basic behavior should be chosen by the design team, which frequently means that a group

must narrow its major goal to a seemingly insignificant one. Drowning prevention is a wide topic; however, instructors limit the behavior within the following list:

- Avoid going to water bodies alone
- Identify possible dangers around and within water bodies.
- Check the weather and water temperature before engaging in any water activities.
- Determine the number of drowning victims.
- Performing dry rescue without entering bodies of water.
- Call for emergency services.
- Recall and detect the Point Last Seen (PLS) of the drowning victim.
- Choose a receptive audience

Drowning is disproportionately common among males, children, and youth in low-income nations (7). The stage of youth and early adulthood increases the likelihood of engaging in risky behaviors (35). Therefore, this study targets the youth in Malaysia. Further details are provided in Section 2.4.

Find what prevents the target behavior

The reason people fall short in conducting a particular behavior always comes down to three main reasons: the absence of i) motivation, ii) ability, or iii) timing to trigger (34). In a previous preliminary study, the researcher identified that the major factor of Malaysian youth not engaging in any drowning prevention behavior is rooted in the lack of knowledge (ability) and the absence of a trigger for the desired behavior.

Choose a familiar technology

The desired behavior, the target audience, and the things that keep the audience from adopting the behavior should all be taken into account when selecting the optimal channel for

technology intervention (34). Through the creation of a secure virtual environment, virtual reality can facilitate continual practice and deliberate decision-making without posing the risk of actual harm (36).

VR combined with an appropriate psychological mechanism has the potential to be a potent persuasion tool that encourages change (37). Thus, this study utilizes IVR to simulate actual occurrence and drowning and persuasive technology to educate and persuade Malaysian youth to engage in drowning preventive behavior.

The researcher used the Unity game engine version 2022.3.37f1, to create the VR SGs. The game objects are acquired freely or purchased from Unity asset store, Blender was also used to create some of the game objects. The animations of characters in the VR SGs are obtained from Mixamo. The VR-simulated serious game can be run on a Meta Quest 3 head-mounted display (HMD) without the need to connect to a Personal Computer (PC) or desktop.

During the alpha and beta testing of the product, several problems were identified such as the inability to represent to actual weight of the life saving aids, lack of proper instructions, absence of guided directions as well as possible occurrence of cybersickness towards users. To overcome the problems mentioned, the developers provides clearer set of instructions as soon as users enter the VR setting, along with checkpoints to lead users to the intended locations. While it is impossible to replicate the weight of an actual lifesaving aid in the VR SGs, haptic feedback were provided instead via the controllers. Lastly, to minimize the cybersickness experienced by users, the method of teleportation was instead of continuous locomotion.

Find relevant samples of persuasive technology

Through searches, the researchers managed to find several studies that used VR tools to educate about water safety. Within these two studies led by Lifesaving Victoria, students from Years 5 and 6 were provided with the Google Expedition Kit to experience as a lifesaver within a rescue mission (38). Similarly, (39) educate children aged between 10 and 12 years old using 360-degree VR videos about water safety content. On the other hand, the other three sources (40–42) demonstrated the use of VR as a training tool for lifeguards on drowning victim identification.

Imitate successful examples

As we can see from previous examples, the findings of (38,39) showed the use of 360-degree video and “Lifesaving Volunteer to the Rescue” Google Expedition as an expedient self-learning tool for learners to learn about water safety messaging and provide water safety awareness. To the best of our knowledge, no study has been conducted on the use of (40). Nevertheless, participants' performance when using VR in the (41) study increased over the course of the subsequent trials, suggesting that a learning effect had taken place. In the case of (42), although the participants' performance was not measured, the researchers claimed that this initiative pushed the boundaries of lifeguard training. The “AiyerSafety” VR SGs does not aim to train lifeguards, but rather to persuade Malaysian youth to adopt drowning preventive behavior. Certain modifications were made to attain the objectives of the game.

Test and iterate quickly

Alpha testing and beta testing were conducted to ensure that the flow of the SGs was smooth. The researcher received feedback constantly from subject matter experts and content experts and made the

necessary changes accordingly. According to (16), the persuasive design principles implemented would leverage psychological insights to affect one's behavior towards desired actions on a digital platform. Table 3 shows how persuasive design principles are integrated within the VR SGs.

Expand on success

Drowning prevention expands to eight domains including embedded system, Artificial Intelligence (AI), Cloud computing, Internet of things (IoT), Instant notifications, computer vision, communication, and big data. By incorporating AI into drowning prevention devices, real-time learning about various swimming conditions is made possible (43). Previous literature proposed showed that solely detection-based or detection and prevention systems could be achieved(44) via weight sensors (45), motion sensors (46), computer visions (47), video surveillance (48) and more.

In terms of water safety education, or in this case, the “AiyerSafety” VR SGs, AI could be possibly integrated by analyzing users' reaction, behavior and performance while personalizing the content to each user in the future. With the success of achieving the initial goal, more target behavior is included, as shown in Section 2.3.1. Figure 3 shows a screenshot of actual “AiyerSafety” VR SGs. Screenshot of the “Aiyersafety” VR Serious Game Participants According to [24] and [25], an optimal sample size of five is usually sufficient to identify the vast majority of usability problems. In the current study, purposive sampling was used with the inclusion and exclusion criteria shown in Table 3. According to a report by the World Health Organization (51), the age group with the highest drowning rate in Malaysia is

between 15 and 29 years (26%). (52) specified that effective educational interventions should be age-appropriate, content-specific, and customized for the intended audience. Thus, the total number of participants involved in the usability tests was N=11 Malaysians (7 males, 4 females),

all aged between 18 and 29 years, as different pedagogical approaches might be needed for those aged below 18 years. The participants were all briefed about the goal and purpose before the commencement of the study and gave their consent to participate voluntarily.

Table (3): Inclusion and exclusion criteria of recruiting samples for usability tests

Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
Non-disabled participants	Participants who possess any type of disability or health condition
Participants between the ages of 18 and 29 years old	Participants who did not meet the age requirements
Participants who are willing to participate in the study	Participants who did not complete the study
	Participants who deny being involved in the study

Instrumentation and Data Analysis

The usability assessment used to evaluate this application was adapted from an instrument created by (53) that contained 15 usability-related items. The items are rated on a 5-Point-Likert scale form, ranging from the lowest (1)–strongly disagree to the highest (5)–strongly agree. The participants were first briefed on the basic functions of the VR headset. Then, the questionnaire will only be distributed to the participants after they have completed the VR serious game that lasted for approximately 30 minutes. After the collection of usability test data, the

descriptive mean method was used for analysis. SPSS version 22.0 was used for data examinations. The results are presented in the following section.

Results and Discussion

Table 5 presents the mean scores of the usability test items. The results indicated that the VR serious game received positive feedback, with all questions recorded as having high mean values and deemed suitable for drowning prevention education. Table (5): Results of usability evaluation (N=11)

No.	Items	Mean Score
1.	This VR courseware is easy to use.	4.10
2.	The presentation of the content is appropriate.	4.82
3.	The content is properly organized.	4.73
4.	The use of font size is suitable.	4.82
5.	The arrangement of the texts is systematic.	4.64
6.	The terms used are easy to understand.	4.73
7.	The colours used are suitable.	4.73
8.	The level of language used is easy to understand.	4.73
9.	The quality of the objects in the courseware is good.	4.64
10.	The audio in the courseware is clear.	3.27

11.	The buttons are functional.	4.45
12.	The navigation in the virtual environment is not confusing.	4.27
13.	This courseware is free from programming errors that could affect the users.	4.54
14.	I am free to explore the entire course content without any technical issues with the VR headset.	4.36
15.	I believe that this software can be used as learning material.	4.91

Overall, the results indicate that the “AiyerSafety” VR SGs received positive feedback from the participants as the mean score values for their usefulness and usability were mostly greater than 4. Nevertheless, the participants found the audio (Item 10) to be neutral. The content was delivered clearly and in an organized structure. The participants responded that the serious games consisted of understandable terms, proper language, suitable font size, and color combination, and are deemed to be easy to use without causing any confusion or technical error that could interrupt the user’s experience.

Despite the current circumstances, water safety education is still not emphasized in Malaysia. The conventional methods such as spreading awareness using booklets (9), or practicing in real life swimming pools. The initial approach while could increase one’s knowledge on water safety yet not necessarily changing one’s behavior, as (5) stresses that behavior modification is crucial in lowering water accidents; the latter would require higher costs and resources. VR SGs offers an alternative approach which could be used in classrooms, simulating dangerous situations in a safe environment. Overall, it is recommended to be used as an educational resource.

The quadruple-helix collaboration (QSC), which is a type of research and development cooperation involving the four main societal sectors: the public, government, research institutes, and industry with promising problem

solving capabilities is deemed to be crucial in addressing intricate societal issues (such as drowning) (54,55). In drowning prevention, the gap between research and practice is particularly wide, and the body of evidence supporting drowning prevention is deemed poor in the absence of adequate integration of theoretical frameworks or models (56). Hence, the academia should focus on evidence based studies based on established theoretical foundations, working with industry partners that could provide support in technology for research and development. Also, in order for the accessibility of public towards the importance of water safety education, the civil society stakeholders, Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) such as lifesaving associations and societies should provide professional consultation and content validation, aligning the subject matter with the use of appropriate technology. Furthermore, media coverage should also focus on the drowning issue to raise awareness. Lastly, the government sector should water safety education as part of school syllabus in physical education, promoting water safety week, and imposing policies such as the requirement for lifeguards in commercial and residential pools, or even beaches.

Conclusion

The current “AiyerSafety” VR SGs are specifically aimed at being used on Malaysian youth aged between 18 and 29 years. Data generalization should be performed with caution. Also, persuasive

design principles were incorporated during the design and development of the VR SGs.

It is recommended that future research delve into its potential to change one's risk perception, belief, attitude, and behavior in drowning prevention. Future studies could involve distinct demographic groups (e.g., age, racial backgrounds) to determine the effectiveness of SGs. Future pilot study using mixed method quasi experimental design will be conducted in several swimming pools over the timeframe of four weeks, and a larger sample size targeting pool patrons within the age limits set using random sampling technique.

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Conflicts of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this article.

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INFLUENCE OF AI-BASED DEBATE SIMULATOR AND DIGITAL CITIZENSHIP PLATFORMS ON CIVIC COMPETENCE OF PUBLIC JUNIOR SECONDARY SCHOOLS STUDENTS IN GIWA, KADUNA STATE

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This study investigated the influence of AI-Based Debate Simulator and Digital Citizenship Platforms on the civic competence of public junior secondary school students in Giwa Local Government Area of Kaduna State. The study adopted correlational research design. A purposive sampling technique was used to select 300 JS 2 students from ten public junior secondary schools in the LGA. Data were collected using the “AI-Based Debate and Digital Citizenship Civic Competence Scale” (AIDCCCS), which consisted of 15 items and had a reliability coefficient of 0.84 using Cronbach's Alpha. Descriptive statistics were used to answer research questions, while Pearson Product-Moment Correlation was employed for hypothesis testing at 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that both AI-based debate simulators (mean = 3.44; $r = 0.582$, $p < 0.05$) and digital citizenship platforms (mean = 3.49; $r = 0.641$, $p < 0.05$) had significant positive relationships with civic competence. Moreover, their joint influence ($R = 0.685$, $R^2 = 0.469$, $F = 129.53$, $p < 0.05$) explain 46.9% of the variance in civic competence. It was concluded that the combined use of AI-based simulators and digital platforms significantly enhances civic competence. Based on these findings, this study recommends the integration of these digital tools into the civic education curriculum, the training of teachers for effective utilization, and the involvement of parents and the community to support responsible digital participation among students.

Keywords:
AI-Based Debate Simulator, Digital Citizenship Platforms, Civic Competence

Introduction

The integration of technology into educational processes has rapidly transformed the ways students acquire knowledge, build critical thinking skills, and engage with their communities. Among these transformations, the application of artificial intelligence (AI) in educational settings has introduced innovative strategies for enhancing cognitive and participatory skills which are essential for citizenship and democratic engagement. As junior secondary

school students navigate an increasingly digitalized society, there is a compelling need to ensure that their learning environments support the development of civic competence, critical reflection, and collaborative problem-solving skills. AI-based educational tools, particularly debate simulators, are emerging as instruments capable of fostering dialogue, argumentation, and active learning experiences (Alimisis, 2023). This approach aligns with the call for education that empowers learners to engage

responsibly and actively in civic spaces using digital tools as levers for positive change in their immediate and broader communities (Weidinger et al., 2023).

In this context, the role of digital citizenship platforms has become significant in equipping learners with the necessary digital ethics, rights awareness, and responsibilities required in the 21st century. Such platforms facilitate participatory learning environments in which students can learn to engage critically with digital content, develop media literacy, and actively participate in democratic processes within and beyond school walls (Choi et al., 2022). The intersection of AI-based debate simulators and digital citizenship platforms represents a promising avenue for nurturing civic competence that encompasses the knowledge, skills, and attitudes necessary for informed and engaged participation in civic life (Fang et al., 2023). Given the increasing relevance of civic competence in maintaining democratic values and addressing societal challenges, understanding the influence of these technological tools on junior secondary school students in Giwa Local Government Area of Kaduna is both timely and imperative.

This study is worth conducting at a time because the integration of AI and digital citizenship education aligns with the global movement towards equipping young learners with competencies required to thrive in a rapidly evolving digital society. In Nigeria, the need for civic competence is amplified by issues related to youth disengagement, misinformation, and limited participation in civic and democratic processes (Okonkwo et al., 2024). AI-based debate simulators offer interactive and adaptive environments that can democratize learning, while enabling personalized and experiential acquisition of civic skills, critical thinking, and tolerance for diverse opinions (Ali et al., 2023).

Similarly, digital citizenship platforms can address issues of online safety, misinformation, and digital ethics, while providing avenues for civic engagement among students (Adeyemi et al., 2024). Conducting this study in Giwa LGA provides an evidence-based perspective on the practical implications of leveraging technology to foster civic competence in a context in which traditional civic education often lacks interactivity and experiential dimensions necessary for holistic learning outcomes (Umar et al., 2024). The findings will provide practical insights for educators, policymakers, and stakeholders seeking to modernize civic education in Nigerian junior secondary schools, ensuring alignment with contemporary digital realities and democratic aspirations.

The general concern of this study revolves around the persistent gaps in civic engagement and competence among junior secondary school students in public schools, particularly in the context of digital transformation and societal challenges that required informed citizen participation. Despite the presence of civic education in the curriculum, many students in public schools lack the practical engagement and critical digital literacy required to translate theoretical knowledge into meaningful civic actions (Ogunyemi et al., 2024). The increasing prevalence of misinformation, online risks, and that passive consumption of digital content among students highlights the urgency of rethinking civic education delivery (Abubakar & Bala, 2023). This study seeks to address these concerns by exploring how AI-based debate simulators and digital citizenship platforms can serve as innovative tools to enhance the civic competence of junior secondary school students in Giwa LGA. The overarching goal is to contribute to educational practices that promote informed, active, and responsible citizenship among young learners in digitally connected societies.

AI-based debate simulators are innovative educational tools that leverage artificial intelligence to create interactive debate environments, allowing students to engage in structured arguments and practice critical thinking, articulation, and respectful disagreement in simulated settings. These simulators utilize natural language processing and adaptive algorithms to provide personalized feedback, challenge cognitive biases, and scaffold argumentation skills (Zhou et al., 2023). By simulating real-life debate scenarios, students can develop a deeper understanding of civic issues, policy discussions, and the dynamics of democratic discourse (Li & Liu, 2024). Research has shown that AI-based debate simulators in classrooms enhances student engagement, fosters empathy through exposure to diverse perspectives, and improves critical reasoning skills, which are essential components of civic competence (Kim et al., 2023). In developing countries, these tools can bridge the gap between rote learning and active civic participation by providing scalable, cost-effective, and adaptable learning interventions (Ahmed et al., 2024).

Digital citizenship platforms are structured online environments that guide learners in acquiring knowledge, attitudes, and skills necessary for responsible participation in digital spaces. These platforms focus on areas such as digital literacy, online ethics, cyber safety, digital rights, and responsibilities, fostering a culture of respect and critical engagement among learners (Ribble & Park, 2023). They provide modules and interactive activities that engage students in discussions about online behavior, misinformation management, and the responsible use of digital resources, aligning with global frameworks for digital citizenship education (Choi et al., 2022). Recent studies have highlighted the effectiveness of digital citizenship platforms in enhancing students'

awareness of their roles and responsibilities in online communities, while building competencies for critical consumption and creation of digital content (Moreno et al., 2024). In the Nigerian context, the implementation of digital citizenship platforms can play a critical role in mitigating risks associated with digital engagement, while fostering a culture of informed participation in civic and democratic processes (Adeyemi et al., 2024).

Civic competence refers to the combination of knowledge, skills, attitudes, and values necessary for individuals to participate effectively in civic and democratic processes within their societies (Hoskins & Kerr, 2024). It encompasses critical understanding of civic issues, active participation in community and democratic activities, and the development of attitudes that support democratic values, such as tolerance, respect for diversity, and social responsibility (Weidinger et al., 2023). Research has shown that civic competence among adolescents is significantly influenced by the nature of civic education, pedagogical approaches used, and availability of experiential learning opportunities that facilitate real-life civic engagement (Fang et al., 2023). In digitally connected societies, civic competence also includes the ability to navigate digital platforms responsibly and critically engage with information while actively participating in online civic spaces (Choi et al., 2022). Enhancing civic competence among junior secondary school students in Nigeria is crucial for nurturing the generation of informed, active, and responsible citizens who are capable of contributing to the democratic and developmental aspirations of the nation (Okonkwo et al., 2024).

Statement of the Problem

Civic competence among public junior secondary school students in the Giwa Local

Government Area of Kaduna State has continued to decline despite its critical role in nurturing the responsible, participatory citizens necessary for sustainable democracy and community development. Data from the Kaduna State Ministry of Education (2024) revealed that only 22% of junior secondary school students in the Giwa LGA could correctly identify basic civil rights and responsibilities during civic education monitoring exercises, while less than 18% demonstrated the ability to engage in respectful dialogue on community issues during the 2024 zonal quiz assessments. This poor performance is further reflected in the low scores in Civic Education in Basic Education Certificate Examinations (BECE) in the area, where only 27% of students scored credit and above in 2023, which is significantly lower than the state average of 42% (Kaduna State Examination Board, 2024).

Several factors contribute to this low civic competence, including traditional teacher-centered methods, lack of interactive civic education practices, limited use of digital resources, and the absence of structured platforms that can simulate civic engagement for adolescents. As a result, many students exhibit apathy towards community involvement, low critical thinking skills, and poor understanding of civic duties, leading to increased cases of youth involvement in social vices and violent expressions in the Giwa LGA (Giwa Education Report, 2024). Efforts have been made through the introduction of civic education as a compulsory subject, intermittent school debates, and community sensitization; however, these have yielded minimal results due to low student engagement, inadequate supervision, and limited adoption of technology-driven civic learning.

Emerging technologies, including AI-based debate simulators and digital citizenship platforms, offer opportunities for interactive, personalized, and civic learning experiences (Ismail et al., 2024). However, there is limited empirical evidence on the effectiveness of these innovations in improving civic competence among junior secondary school students within the Nigerian context, particularly in underserved areas such as Giwa LGA. This gap underscores the need to investigate the influence of AI-based debate simulators and digital citizenship platforms on the civic competence of public junior secondary school students in Giwa Local Government Area of Kaduna. It is anticipated that the findings of this study will guide educators, policymakers, and curriculum planners in adopting innovative strategies that can enhance civic competence and democratic participation among adolescents in the area.

Objectives of the Study

1. To determine the relationship between the use of AI-based debate simulators and the civic competence of public junior secondary school students in Giwa Local Government Area of Kaduna State.
2. To examine the relationship between the use of digital citizenship platforms and the civic competence of public junior secondary school students in Giwa Local Government Area of Kaduna State.
3. To determine the joint relationship between AI-based debate simulators and digital citizenship platforms on the civic competence of public junior secondary school students in Giwa Local Government Area of Kaduna State.

Research Questions

1. What is the relationship between the use of AI-based debate simulators and civic competence of public junior secondary

- school students in Giwa Local Government Area of Kaduna State?
2. What is the relationship between the use of digital citizenship platforms and civic competence of public junior secondary school students in Giwa Local Government Area of Kaduna State?
 3. What is the joint effect of AI-based debate simulators and digital citizenship platforms on the civic competence of public junior secondary school students in Giwa Local Government Area of Kaduna State?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant relationship between the use of AI-based debate simulators and civic competence of public junior secondary school students in Giwa Local Government Area of Kaduna State.
2. There is no significant relationship between the use of digital citizenship platforms and civic competence of public junior secondary school students in Giwa Local Government Area of Kaduna State.
3. There is no significant joint relationship between AI-based debate simulators and digital citizenship platforms on the civic competence of public junior secondary school students in Giwa Local Government Area of Kaduna.

Methodology

The study adopted a correlational research design to investigate the relationship between the use of AI-based debate simulators, digital citizenship platforms, and civic competence of public junior secondary school students in Giwa Local Government Area of Kaduna State. This design was suitable because it enabled the researcher to determine the degree and direction of the relationship between the independent variables (AI-based debate simulator and digital

citizenship platforms) and the dependent variable (civic competence) without manipulating them (Creswell & Creswell, 2023). Correlational design has been found to be appropriate for educational research with the aim of determining predictive relationships among variables within natural school settings (Fraenkel, Wallen, & Hyun, 2023). The study population comprised all public junior secondary school students in Giwa Local Government Area of Kaduna State, totaling 5,742 students across 28 public junior secondary schools (Kaduna State Ministry of Education, 2024). Given the nature of the design and the large, geographically spread population, the study employed a multi-stage sampling technique, which involved stratified and simple random sampling, to ensure adequate representation across schools while allowing for manageability during data collection. This sampling technique was justified, as it has been noted to enhance representativeness while reducing sampling bias in correlational studies within educational research contexts (Etikan & Bala, 2023). A total of 300 students were selected for the study. This sample size was determined based on the recommendation by Nwana (2022) that a sample of at least 5% of a large population is adequate for a correlational study, and the sample size aligns with previous studies employing correlational designs with similar populations (Musa et al., 2024). The use of multi-stage sampling enabled the researcher to select 300 participants proportionally across the 28 schools and ensured each participant had an equal chance of being selected. Data were collected using a researcher-developed instrument titled: "AI and Digital Civic Competence Scale" (AIDCCS), consisting of 15 items. The instrument was structured into three sections reflecting the key variables of the study: Section A contained 5 items on AI-based debate simulator usage, Section B contained 5 items on

digital citizenship platforms usage, and Section C contained 5 items on civic competence of students. The items were rated on a five-point Likert scale: Strongly Agree (5), Agree (4), Undecided (3), Disagree (2), and Strongly Disagree (1). This rating structure allowed for quantifiable measurement of students' perceptions and practices, consistent with practices in educational research instrument designs (Ary et al., 2023). To establish content and face validity, the AIDCCS was subjected to expert review by three lecturers in Educational Technology and Educational Psychology at the Federal University of Education, Zaria, and two experienced civic education teachers at Giwa LGA. Their suggestions were incorporated to ensure clarity, relevance, and alignment of the items with the study objectives. The reliability of the instrument was determined using Cronbach's alpha method and a reliability coefficient index of 0.83 was obtained, indicating that the instrument was reliable and suitable for the study (George & Mallery, 2022). For data collection, the researcher obtained

Answering the Research Questions

permission from the SKaduna State Ministry of Education and school principals before administering the instrument. Research assistants were trained to administer the questionnaire to the selected students during civic education periods to avoid interference with the school timetable. The administration and retrieval of the instruments were completed within three weeks, and the researcher ensured that the respondents were adequately informed about the confidentiality of their responses and the purpose of the study. The data were coded and analyzed using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26. Descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) were used to answer the research questions, while Pearson Product-Moment Correlation (PPMC) was used to test the null hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance to determine the strength and direction of the relationships between the independent and dependent variables in the study. This approach consists of the analytical procedures for correlational studies (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2023).

Research Question 1: What is the relationship between the use of AI-based debate simulators and civic competence of public junior secondary school students in Giwa LGA of Kaduna State?

S/N	Item Statement	Mean	Std. Dev	Decision
1	I can confidently express my civic opinions after using AI-based simulators.	3.51	0.83	Agree
2	AI-based debates help me understand civic responsibilities better.	3.44	0.78	Agree
3	The simulations help me evaluate multiple perspectives on civic issues.	3.36	0.85	Agree
4	I actively participate in civic discussions more after the simulations.	3.41	0.9	Agree
5	I have improved my civic decision-making through AI-based debates.	3.47	0.82	Agree
	Aggregate Mean Score	3.44		

The responses in Table 1 indicate that students generally agreed that AI-based debate simulators positively influenced their civic competence. An aggregate mean score of 3.44 is above the acceptable threshold of 2.50, indicates a substantial agreement among students. The

highest mean of 3.51 suggests high confidence in civic expression, while the lowest (3.36) still reflects a positive view of simulations' role in evaluating perspectives. Standard deviations range from 0.78 to 0.90, reflecting moderate dispersion around the mean.

Research Question 2: What is the relationship between the use of digital citizenship platforms and civic competence of public junior secondary school students in Giwa LGA?

S/N	Item Statement	Mean	Std. Dev	Decision
1.	I understand my rights and duties better after using digital citizenship apps.	3.62	0.75	Agree
2.	I've learned how to behave responsibly online and offline.	3.54	0.72	Agree
3.	I now report inappropriate or harmful civic behaviors online.	3.46	0.79	Agree
4.	These platforms improve my awareness of social justice and civic equality.	3.38	0.88	Agree
5.	I am more engaged in community affairs after using digital platforms.	3.43	0.85	Agree
	Aggregate Mean Score	3.49		Agree

Table 2 shows the overall positive perception of the impact of digital citizenship platforms on students' civic competence, with an aggregate mean of 3.49. This is higher than that in Table 1, indicating a slightly stronger influence. The highest-rated item (3.62) is

linked to understanding rights and duties, while the lowest (3.38) shows agreement in civic awareness. The consistency of responses was shown through lower standard deviations (mostly below 0.85), suggesting general agreement among respondents.

Research Question 3: What is the joint effect of AI-based debate simulators and digital citizenship platforms on the civic competence of students in Giwa LGA?

S/N	Item Statement	Mean	Std. Dev	Decision
1	Using both AI simulators and digital	3.56	0.77	Agree
2	I understand democratic values better through both tools.	3.61	0.7	Agree
3	The combination of tools helps me think critically about civic matters.	3.48	0.82	Agree

4	I engage more in civic-related school activities because of both tools.	3.42	0.85	Agree
5	I can discuss real-world civic problems more confidently using both tools.	3.58	0.75	Agree
	Aggregate Mean Score	3.53		Agree

The data in Table 3 demonstrates a strong joint influence of both AI-based debate simulators and digital citizenship platforms on students’ civic competence. With an aggregate mean of 3.53, this is the highest among all three tables, suggesting a

synergistic effect when both tools were used. The lowest mean (3.42) still indicates a positive impact, whereas the highest (3.61) shows a clear benefit in understanding democratic values. Low standard deviations (e.g., 0.70) indicate consensus.

Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between the use of AI-based debate simulators and student’s civic competence.

Variable	N	Mean	Std. Dev	df	R	p-value	Decision
AI-Based Debate Simulators	300	3.44	0.83	298	0.582		Reject Ho
Civic Competence	300	3.48	0.81				

The Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient ($r = 0.582$, $p = 0.000$) indicates a moderate to strong positive relationship between the use of AI-based debate simulators and civic

competence. when $p < 0.05$, the null hypothesis is rejected. This suggests that the more students engage with AI-based simulations, the higher their civic competence.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between the use of digital citizenship platforms and student’s civic competence.

Variable	N	Mean	Std. Dev	df	R	p-value	Decision
Digital Citizenship Platforms	300	3.49	0.82	298	0.641		Reject Ho
Civic Competence	300	3.48	0.81				

A Pearson correlation coefficient of $r = 0.641$ and $p = 0.000$ shows a strong positive correlation between digital citizenship platform usage and civic competence. The significance

level is below 0.05; therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that students who use digital platforms for civic learning are likely to exhibit strong civic competence.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant joint relationship between AI-based debate simulators and digital citizenship platforms on student's civic competence.

Predictor Variables	N	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	F	p-value	Decision
AI Debate Simulators & Digital Platforms	300	0.685	0.469	0.465	129.53		Reject Ho

Multiple regression analysis was used to test the joint relationship. An R value of 0.685 indicates a strong correlation between the combined predictors and civic competence. $R^2 = 0.469$ implies that 46.9% of the variation in civic competence can be explained by the joint influence of AI-based debate simulators and digital platforms. The F-value of 129.53 and $p = 0.000$ indicate that the model is statistically significant. Hence, we rejected the null hypothesis and concluded that both tools have a significant and substantial influence on civic competence.

Summary of Findings

The students agreed that the use of AI-based debate simulators would enhance their civic competence. The mean aggregate score was 3.44, indicating positive perception. Hypothesis testing revealed a significant moderate to strong positive correlation ($r = 0.582$, $p < 0.05$) between the use of simulators and civic competence.

The Respondents reported a slightly stronger perception of digital citizenship platforms improving their civic competence, with an aggregate mean of 3.49. Hypothesis testing revealed a strong positive correlation ($r = 0.641$, $p < 0.05$) between digital platforms and civic competence.

The Combined use of AI-based simulators and digital platforms yielded the highest mean aggregate score (3.53). The Regression analysis revealed a significant joint

relationship ($R = 0.685$, $R^2 = 0.469$, $F = 129.53$, $p < 0.05$), suggesting that 46.9% of the variation in students' civic competence could be attributed to these two variables.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study align with the global evidence that AI-based debate simulators enhance students' engagement and critical thinking, which are crucial for developing civic competence (Li et al., 2024). The moderate positive correlation found between AI-based debate simulators and civic competence is consistent with recent studies demonstrating that simulated debates encourage civic reasoning and confidence among learners (Olayinka & Bello, 2023). Additionally, the significant positive relationship between digital citizenship platforms and civic competence supports prior findings that online platforms facilitate civic learning and active participation among students (Alvarez-Marin & Gutierrez, 2023).

The joint influence of AI-based debate simulators and digital citizenship platforms on civic competence further highlights the potential of technology in civic education, consistent with the assertions that digital tools create avenues for students to explore, discuss, and act on civic issues (Zhang et al., 2023). This study contributes to the ongoing discourse on integrating technology within junior secondary school civic education in

Nigeria, illustrating that these tools can aid in addressing civic apathy and low civic participation among students (Adebayo, 2024).

The implications for educational stakeholders include the need to incorporate AI-based debate simulators and the structured use of digital citizenship platforms in civic education curricula to foster civic knowledge, critical thinking, and participation skills essential for active citizenship in Nigeria.

Conclusion

This study investigated the influence of the AI-Based Debate Simulator and Digital Citizenship Platforms on the civic competence of public junior secondary school students in the Giwa Local Government Area of Kaduna State. The findings revealed that the use of AI-Based Debate Simulators and Digital Citizenship Platforms has a significant positive influence on the civic competence of students, equipping them with critical thinking, digital responsibility, and participatory skills essential for effective citizenship in a democratic society. The combined influence of these technologies was also found to predict civic competence significantly, indicating that integrating these tools into civic education can enhance students' readiness to engage in democratic practices and responsible online participation. These findings highlight the need for policymakers, educators, and school administrators to embrace innovative digital tools to improve civic education outcomes among junior secondary school students in the region. Recommendations. Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Integration into Curriculum: School administrators and policymakers should incorporate AI-Based Debate Simulators and Digital Citizenship Platforms into civic education curricula to foster critical thinking, ethical digital engagement, and active citizenship among junior secondary school students.
2. Capacity Building for Teachers: Teachers should be trained in the effective use of AI-Based Debate Simulators and Digital Citizenship Platforms to facilitate engaging, practical, and interactive civic education lessons.
3. Community and Parental Involvement: Parents and community stakeholders should be sensitized to the benefits of digital citizenship and encouraged to support students in responsibly using these platforms to enhance their civic competence and societal engagement.

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INFLUENCE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TOOLS ON TEACHING AND LEARNING OUTCOMES IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN PLATEAU STATE: OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES

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The study examined the influence of artificial intelligence tools on teaching and learning outcomes in public secondary schools in Plateau State. While AI holds significant potential for effective lesson delivery, certain concerns were raised about its excessive overreliance on automated systems and the possible erosion of students' critical thinking skills. 5 research objectives and research questions were raised in this study. 2 instruments were developed, STALOSN and SIAATLS for administrators, teachers and students respectively. The instruments went through validation by experts and a reliability test using Cronbach Alpha method with a reliability index of 0.72. Data was analysed using descriptive statistics. Results of findings revealed a low level of awareness and preparedness for the use of AI tools for teaching and learning in public secondary schools in Plateau State. Also revealed were challenges in the adoption of AI technology with sociological implications for equity in its implementation across urban and rural schools and between the privilege and the underprivileged socio-economic classes.

Keywords:
Artificial
Intelligence,
Secondary Education
Pedagogy.

Introduction

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has emerged as one of the most transformative technologies in the 21st century, with significant implications for the educational sector worldwide. AI can be broadly defined as the capability of computer systems to perform tasks that typically require human intelligence, such as problem solving, speech recognition, decision making, and learning from experience (Russell & Norvig, 2021). In the educational domain, AI tools are increasingly deployed to facilitate adaptive learning, automate administrative tasks,

provide real-time feedback, and personalize learning pathways (Luckin et al., 2016).

Globally, the adoption of AI in education has been driven by the need to improve learning efficiency, to cater to diverse learner needs, and prepare students for a technology-driven economy (Holmes et al., 2019). In primary and secondary school settings, AI tools, such as intelligent tutoring systems, learning analytics platforms, and automated grading software are helping teachers identify students' strengths and weaknesses, thereby enabling targeted interventions (Baker & Smith, 2019). These applications are not

limited to developed nations; emerging economies are also integrate AI solutions to bridge the gaps in educational access and quality (UNESCO, 2021).

In Nigeria, the conversation around AI in education is gaining momentum due to the growing penetration of mobile technology, improved Internet connectivity in urban areas, and the emergence of EdTech platforms such as Afrilearn, uLesson, and Digilearn. These platforms employ AI-driven algorithms to customize learning materials according to student performance, thereby addressing individual learning needs (Okonkwo, 2022). However, the Nigerian educational landscape faces systemic challenges—such as inadequate infrastructure, digital illiteracy among teachers, and unequal access between urban and rural schools—that affect the equitable adoption of AI tools (Ogunleye & Adeyemi, 2023).

The potential benefits of AI tools in Nigerian primary and secondary education are multifaceted, including enhanced learning engagement, improved assessment accuracy, support for inclusive education (particularly for students with disabilities), and more efficient resource allocation (World Bank, 2020). For instance, speech recognition AI can assist learners with reading difficulties, while predictive analytics can help educators identify at-risk students early, thus enabling timely interventions (Luckin et al., 2016). Furthermore, AI can help alleviate the burden of teacher shortages by automating routine instructional and administrative tasks, allowing educators to focus on more complex pedagogical responsibilities (Baker & Smith, 2019).

Despite these advantages, the integration of AI into secondary education has raised important concerns. One of the most pressing is the digital divide, where students in under-resourced schools are risk being excluded from AI-enabled

learning opportunities due to lack of internet access, insufficient hardware, or inadequate electricity supply (Afolabi, 2021). Additionally, ethical issues—such as data privacy, algorithmic bias, and the potential dehumanization of teaching—pose challenges that must be addressed through robust policies and teacher training (UNESCO, 2021). Overreliance on AI could also lead to a diminished role for teachers in shaping students' socio-emotional skills, which remain critical for holistic development (Holmes et al., 2019).

This challenge is even more pronounced in Plateau State, a State that is historically classified as one of the educationally backward states. The public secondary schools in Plateau cater for majority of school aged children which form this diverse population, from both rural and urban settlements with more children from low-income families.

From a sociological perspective, AI in education is both a democratizing force and a potential agent of inequality. While it can expand access to high-quality learning resources across geographical boundaries, its benefits may disproportionately favor those with better digital infrastructure, thereby widening educational disparities. In the Nigerian context, where public primary and secondary schools often lack basic ICT resources, the risk of excluding large segments of the student population from AI-enhanced learning is significant (Ogunleye & Adeyemi, 2023).

Considering these realities, understanding the opportunities and challenges of AI integration in education requires a balanced and context-sensitive approach. Therefore, this theoretical paper examines the influence of artificial intelligence tools on teaching and learning outcomes in public secondary public schools of Plateau state.

Statement of the Problem

The introduction of AI in public secondary education in Plateau state has the potential to revolutionize teaching and learning as it can enable personalized instruction, provide timely feedback, and diagnose difficulties. However, their integration into classrooms is not problem-free. In many secondary schools in Plateau state access to reliable Internet, electricity, and functional devices remains a significance barrier. The enthusiasm for AI often overshadows the reality that technology can unintentionally marginalize learners from low-income or rural backgrounds. Moreover, the use of AI education raises issues of teacher preparedness, over-reliance on automated systems, and the possible erosion of critical thinking skills among students.

Without deliberate frameworks for equitable access, ethical data management, and professional teacher development, AI tools could exacerbate rather than bridge the educational divide. The problem, therefore, is not merely whether AI tools should be adopted, but how they can be integrated into secondary education in ways that maximize benefits while minimizing harm.

System marked by infrastructural deficits, unequal access, insufficient teacher capacity, and ethical concerns – pose significant barriers to its effective adoption. This raises the following critical issues:

How can AI tools can be implemented in ways that address, rather than deepen, educational inequalities, the framework that guides the equitable and context-sensitive integration of AI in secondary schools, and how Nigerian teachers can be empowered to effectively harness AI while retaining the human elements of teaching?

Aim/Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study is to investigate the influence of artificial intelligent tools on teaching and learning outcomes in public secondary schools in Plateau State. The specific objectives of the study are:

- To investigate the extent of principals, teachers' and student's awareness of the adoption of AI tools in teaching and learning
- To investigate the extent of readiness of public secondary schools for the usage of AI tools for teaching and learning
- To find out perceived advantages of adopting AI tools in public secondary schools in Plateau state.
- To find out perceived disadvantages of adopting AI tools in public secondary schools in Plateau state
- To investigate perceived challenges in the adoption of AI tools in public secondary schools in Plateau state

Research Questions

- To what extent are principals, teachers and students of public secondary schools aware of the adoption of AI tools in teaching and learning?
- To extent are public secondary schools in Plateau state ready for the usage of AI tools in teaching and learning?
- What are the perceived advantages of adopting AI tools in public secondary schools in Plateau state?
- What are the perceived advantages of adopting AI tools in public secondary schools in Plateau state?
- What are the perceived challenges in the adoption of AI tools in public secondary schools in plateau state?

Theoretical Framework

This study is grounded in two complementary sociological perspectives that provide an analytical lens for understanding the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools in primary and secondary education: Structural Functionalism and Conflict Theory. While structural functionalism focuses on the advantages of AI tools, structural conflict theory emphasizes the disadvantages and challenges of these tools in primary and secondary education.

Structural Functionalism

Structural functionalism, as advanced by Émile Durkheim (1912) and later refined by Talcott Parsons (1951), views society as a complex system comprising interdependent parts working together to promote stability and social order. Education, from this perspective, serves as a critical institution that socializes individuals, transmits culture, and equips members with the skills necessary for societal participation (Haralambos & Holborn, 2017).

AI tools, in this framework, can be seen as innovations designed to enhance the functions of the education system. For example, AI-enabled personalized learning aligns with the functionalist goal of optimizing human capital by tailoring instruction to meet diverse learner needs (Holmes et al., 2019). Automated grading and performance analytics can support the system's efficiency by reducing administrative burdens and allowing educators to focus on higher-order teaching tasks.

However, functionalists also recognize that rapid technological changes require adaptation across the systems. In many public

secondary schools in Nigeria and Plateau in particular, teachers have large classes with sometimes over 80 students per class. All learning apps like *eu lesson* or *Emodo* can support the teacher's effort if students have access to these tools and this can promote practical exercises and feedback skills that are essential to development of Maths, English and Sciences. By aligning with the perspective of structural foundationalism, these are innovations that function towards effective teaching and learning. Thus from this perspective, social order is maintained which according to persons (1951) makes a society stable and cohesive.

Conflict Theory

Conflict theory, rooted in the work of Karl Marx (1867) and later expanded by Wright Mills (1959) and Randall Collins (1971), offers a contrasting perspective by emphasizing power relations, inequality, and competition over scarce resources. From this viewpoint, education is not merely a neutral mechanism for skill development but also a site where social inequalities are reproduced (Bourdieu & Passeron, 1977).

Applied to AI in education, conflict theory highlights the risk that these technologies could exacerbate existing disparities. Schools in affluent urban areas are more likely to have the infrastructure, funding, and trained staff needed to deploy AI effectively, whereas rural and low-income schools may lag behind, perpetuating unequal educational outcomes (Afolabi, 2021). Furthermore, corporate interests in AI development may prioritize profit over the equitable distribution of benefits, creating a dependency on proprietary platforms that limit local innovation and autonomy (Selwyn, 2019).

Conflict theorists have also drawn attention to cultural biases embedded in AI systems. When algorithms are trained predominantly on datasets from Western contexts, the resulting tools may fail to reflect the linguistic, cultural, and socioeconomic realities of Nigerian students, thereby marginalizing local knowledge systems (Russell & Norvig, 2021). This reinforces the notion that AI integration is not just a technological issue, but also a deeply sociological one involving question of equity, representation, and control.

This therefore implies that the elite and wealthy class families can support their children by access to AI equipped schools and this provides a head start in technologically driven areas whereas children in public schools without access to AI facilities will perpetually remain in low status jobs producing an underprivilege class.

Literature Review

The literature review examines existing scholarship on AI tools in education, with an emphasis on their advantages, disadvantages, and the Nigerian context.

Conceptualizing AI in Education

Artificial Intelligence in education (AIED) refers to the application of machine learning, natural language processing, and other AI techniques to enhance teaching, learning, and administrative processes (Luckin et al., 2016). Globally, AI tools such as adaptive learning platforms, intelligent tutoring systems, automated grading software, and predictive analytics have been increasingly adopted in both developed and developing contexts (Holmes et al., 2019).

Recent Development on Ai

In developed countries like the United States of America, China and United Kingdom, AI

has moved from the level of experimentation to the level of operational use in supporting personalization, automated feedback, curriculum diagnostics including formative feedback analyses (Carnegie learning 2025; UNESCO, 2025). China has launched a large scale AI-powered education experiments to track students' progress on time and provide a tailored feedback. Similarly the United State schools and universities are leveraging AI to enhance efficiency in lesson delivery and students engagement (Carnegie Learning, 2025).

Development on AI in advanced countries are supported by strong national commitments by robust infrastructure and internet connectivity like matured private public Ed-Teck ecosystems.

In contrast to developed countries particularly in sub-Saharan Africa. Progress towards AI is slow due to infrastructural constraints (UNESCO, 2023). While there is a growing awareness of AI tools and potential benefits, infrastructural challenges such as inadequate internet connectivity has slowed down the pace of implementation (UNESCO 2021). Nigeria is said to lag significantly behind advanced economies in education due to digital divides and policy limitations (African Centre for Technology Studies, 2023). From the literature, there is a sharp contrast in rates of advancement of AI technology and supportive government policies. The federal government of Nigeria made efforts to release funds to universities and colleges, yet progress remain slow (Omede and Omede, 2023). While Nigeria and similar developing countries are still navigating basic readiness issues like access, training and affordability, advanced countries are already at topmost level in integrating AI into their education systems. This

comparative gap presents an urgent need for Nigeria to evolve targeted policies and make investments to prepare Nigerian schools and particularly disadvantaged states like Plateau to harness AI's potential for improving teaching and learning outcomes.

Advantages of AI Tools in Education

Several studies have highlighted the transformative potential in education. First, AI enables personalized learning, adapting content and pacing to the individual needs of learners (Baker & Smith, 2019). Second, it offers real-time feedback, allowing students to promptly identify and address knowledge gaps promptly (Luckin et al., 2016). Third, AI can reduce administrative workloads by automating routine tasks, freeing teachers to focus on higher-level instructional design and mentorship (Holmes et al., 2019).

Moreover, AI can serve as a diagnostic tool to identify students at risk of underperformance and recommending targeted interventions (Russell & Norvig, 2021). In contexts where teacher shortages are acute-like such as in many Nigerian rural schools, AI tools can supplement instruction and extend learning opportunities beyond the traditional classroom.

Disadvantages and Risks of AI In Education

Despite these benefits, literature warns of several risks. The digital divide remains a major barrier, unequal access to Internet connectivity, devices, and electricity hinders the equitable implementation of AI in Nigerian schools (Ogunleye & Adeyemi, 2023). Teacher preparedness is another challenge many educators lack the training to integrate AI effectively into their pedagogical practices (UNESCO, 2021).

The ethical issues were also prominent. Data privacy concerns arise from the collection and storage of sensitive student information, often with inadequate legal safeguards (Selwyn, 2019). Algorithmic bias can perpetuate social and cultural inequalities, disadvantaging students whose linguistic or socio-cultural backgrounds are underrepresented in AI datasets (Russell & Norvig, 2021).

From a pedagogical standpoint, over-reliance on AI risks deskilling teachers and undermining the development of critical thinking, creativity, and interpersonal skills among students (Holmes et al., 2019). These concerns are particularly significant in primary and secondary education, where socio-emotional development is as crucial as cognitive learning.

Nigerian Policy and Implementation Context

Nigeria's National Digital Economy Policy and Strategy (2020–2030) acknowledges the role of emerging technologies in national development but provides limited direction for AI in basic education (Okonkwo, 2022). The absence of explicit AI guidelines leaves schools and state ministries without a coherent strategy for integration. Pilot projects remain fragmented and donor-driven, with minimal coordination or sustainability plans.

Recent initiatives by private EdTech companies, such as Afrilearn, demonstrate that localized AI solutions can be developed. However, without systemic support—including infrastructure investment, teacher training, and regulatory oversight—these efforts may remain isolated successes rather than catalysts for nationwide transformation (Afolabi, 2021).

Nigerian Context And Policy Implications

In Nigeria, AI adoption in basic education is still emerging, with most initiatives driven by private EdTech firms rather than coordinated government policy. Afrilearn, uLesson, and DigiLearns represent localized attempts to leverage AI-like systems for curriculum delivery (Okonkwo & Mba, 2023). However, these platforms often require stable internet and modern devices, making them inaccessible to many rural schools (Adamu & Bello, 2020).

The Federal Ministry of Education has acknowledged the role of digital technologies in achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG 4) but lacks a specific national AI strategy for education (Federal Ministry of Education, 2022). Without targeted investments in infrastructure, teacher training, and content localization, AI adoption may remain inequitable and fragmented.

Method and Procedures

Research Design

The study adopts a descriptive research design in order to analyse the current state of awareness, and readiness of public secondary schools in plateau state for the adoption of AI tools in teaching and learning. The perception of respondents covering the advantages, disadvantages and challenges in the use of AI tools will be unveiled. The design is suitable since it does not involve the manipulation of variables, rather perceptions and outcomes occur naturally.

Population and Sample

The target population of this study consists of the following,

1,150 public secondary schools (both junior and senior), 1150 principals, 35,000 teachers and 140,000 students (world Bank 2009)

Sample

Using mixed method research according to Creswell and Plano Clark (20218), a 3% of the various populations were obtained as samples, 35 public secondary schools across the three senatorial zones of plateau state, 35 principals, 1050 teachers and 4,200 students. This according to Cress-well and Plano Clark (2018), a methodological principles of mixed research method considers 3% of large populations like schools as statistically adequate for representation. Below is a table showing population and sample of the study.

Table 1
Population and Sample of Schools, Principals, Teachers and Students

Group Type	Population	Sample size
Public Secondary schools	1150	35
Principals	1150	35
Teacher	35,000	1050
Students	140,000	4,200

Sources: World Bank (2009), Federal Ministry of Education (2015), UBE (2020)

Sampling Techniques

To select sample schools, firstly a multistage sampling technique was used to classify the schools into senatorial zones which are the North, Central and Southern zones. Secondly, a stratified sampling method was used to categorize the schools into urban and rural schools. The third stage considered enrollment figures of small medium and large schools. This was to reflect the diversity of the school's exposure to ICT availability. The fourth and the final stage was the use of proportionate random sampling method to choose schools from each stratum. A sample of 35 schools were thus selected.

For the sampling of principals, each school automatically sampled included a principal. This selection method yielded 35 principals. Considering the size population including location, a stratified sample was used to select 1050 teachers. Also, through a stratified random selection, a total of 4,200 students representing junior and senior secondary students were selected. Gender was also considered in the selection. This was to encourage gender representation

Instruments for Data Collection

Two instruments were used for data collection

1. School Administrators and Teachers Survey on influence of artificial intelligence tools on teaching and learning outcomes in secondary schools in Nigeria: Opportunities and challenges (STATLOS)
2. Students Survey on Influence of Artificial Intelligence Tools on Teaching and learning outcomes in secondary schools in Nigeria: Opportunities and challenges (SIAATLSN)

STATLOS is a 20 item questionnaire designed to survey the level of awareness, readiness for AI tools for teaching and learning, including the advantages, disadvantages and challenges of adopting AI tools in secondary education .. SIAATLSN is a 16 item questionnaire to elicit responses from students on their awareness of AI tools in learning, perception on the advantages and disadvantages of AI tools in leaning and challenges associated with AI in learning. The responses were based on five Likert scale of “to a very low extent”, “low extent”, “moderate extent”, “high extent” and “very high extent”. This response is for research question one. Research question two and three were also scaled as “highly

disadvantaged”, “disadvantaged”, “moderately disadvantaged” and “mostly disadvantaged”. Research question five also had a similar Likert scale which were “Very high challenge”. “High challenge”, “Moderate challenge”, “Low challenge”, “Very low challenge”. A mean of 3.0 is the criterion mean.

Validity and Reliability of Instruments

The two instruments, STATLOS and SIAATLSN went through content and construct validity through experts in educational technology, sociology and educational measurement and evaluation specialist to ensure that the domains of digital readiness technological infrastructures and equity in the adoption of AI are well scrutinized for clarity and comprehensiveness. The final copy of the validated instruments was subjected to a test-retest reliability method. The result was correlated using the Cronbach Alpha method. A co-efficient of 0.72 was obtained which testified to the internal consistency and reliability of the instruments.

Method of Data Collection

Ethical approval was obtained from the institutions of the authors for conducting the survey questionnaires STATLOS, and SIAATLSN were administered to the schools through the permission of the principals with the help of research assistants and the authors in this study.

Method of Data Analysis

The data was analysed using descriptive statistic like simple percentages, mean and standard deviation.

Results

Research Question One: To what extent are principals, teachers and students of public secondary schools in plateau state aware of the adoption of AI tools in teaching and learning.

Table 2: AI Tools For Teaching and Learning Awareness In Secondary Schools

Awareness Items	Respondents	Frequency Yes	%	Frequency No	%	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Principals	35	62%		13 (38%)		2.6	1.0	Moderate extent
Teachers	1050	43%		598 (57%)		2.1	1.1	Low extent
Students	4,200	35%		2,730 (65%)		1.9	0.7	Low extent
Total		1,944 (37%)		3,341 (63%)		2.2	1.0	Low extent

Field study: 2025

Results indicated a low extent of awareness in the adoption of AI tools at the secondary schools (M. 2.2; SD 1.0). Among principals and teachers 62% and 43% awareness levels were recorded respectively. Student

responses to awareness were 35%. An overall percentage of 37 shows that the awareness for the adoption of AI tools for teaching and learning at secondary schools' level in plateau state is at a low extent.

Research Question Two: To what extent are schools in plateau state ready for the usage of AI tools in Secondary Schools for teaching and learning.?

Table 3: Readiness Of Secondary Schools for AI Learning

Readiness Items	Respondents	Frequency %Yes	Frequency %No	Mean	SD	Interpretation
ICT Labs	1085	412 (38%)	673 (62%)	2.0	0.9	Low readiness
Internet connection	1085	380 (35%)	705 (65%)	1.9	0.8	Low readiness
Teacher with ICT knowledge	1085	456 (42%)	629 (51%)	2.1	0.9	Low readiness
Administrative Support for Technology	1085	510 (47%)	575 (53%)	2.3	1.0	Moderate readiness
Total	1085	439 (40%)	646 (60%)	2.1	0.9	Low readiness

Field study: 2025

Results in table 3 indicates a low extent of readiness in secondary schools in adopting AI tools (M=2.1, SD=0.9). Responses across schools indicated a low-level of readiness for ICT laboratories with 38% response rate. Also low levels of readiness were observed for

internet connection (35%) and moderate level for teacher's with knowledge of ICT (42%). Also, administrative support for technology was moderately low (47%). An overall percentage score of 40% shows that there is a low extent of readiness for the adoption of AI in most schools.

Research Question 3: What are the perceived advantages of adopting AI tools in Secondary Schools in Plateau state?

Table 4: Perceived Advantages of AI Tools

Items	Respondents	Frequency %Yes	Frequency %No	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Improves and makes learning efficient	5285	3,648(69%)	1,637(31%)	3.5	1.1	High advantage
Provides individualized learning	5285	3,331(63%)	1,954(37%)	3.2	1.0	High advantage
Supports teachers' efforts in teaching	5285	3,543(67%)	1,742(33%)	3.4	1.1	High advantage
Improves school administration	5285	3,171(60%)	2,114(40%)	3.1	1.0	High advantage
Total	5285	3,423 (65%)	1,862 (35%)	3.3	1.1	High advantage

Field study: 2025

Table 4 shows that Respondents have agreed that AI improves and makes learning efficient (M3.1, SD=1.1) 69% respondents agreed that AI improves and makes learning efficient, 63% agreed that AI provides individualized learning. 67% agreed to

teachers' efforts being supplemented by AI tools while 60% believe that AI improves social administration. A total of 65% respondent have agreed o high advantages associated with the use of AI.

Research Question 4: What are the perceived disadvantages of AI tools in Secondary Schools in Plateau state?

Table 5: Perceived Disadvantages of AI Tools

Items	Respondents	Frequency %Yes	Frequency %No	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Less teacher interaction session	5285	3,543 (67%)	1,742 (33%)	3.4	1.1	High disadvantages
Reduces students intellectual	5285	3,647 (69%)	1,638 (31%)	3.5	1.0	High disadvantages
Equity gap between schools	5285	3,964 (75%)	1,321(25%)	3.8	1.1	High disadvantages
Equity gap among socio-economic groups	5285	4,070 (77%)	1,215(23%)	3.9	1.0	High disadvantages
Total	5285	3,806 (72%)	1,480(28%)	3.7	1.1	High disadvantages

Field study: 2025

Table 5 indicated that students perceive serious disadvantages of AI as teaching and learning tools (M=3.7, SD=1.1). They agreed that AI reduces the level of interaction between teachers and students (67%). They also agreed to low reduction in students' use of intellect to learn (69%). They foresee a dangerous trend in equity gap among schools

in the availability of I tools (75%) and an equity gap in the exposure of AI tools among students from different socioeconomic classes (77%). The overall percentage of 72% shows that majority of respondents have perceived a great disadvantage in the use of AI tools.

Research question 5: What are the perceived challenges of secondary schools in adopting AI tools for teaching and learning?

Table 6: Challenges in Adopting AI In Secondary Schools in Plateau State

Items	Respondents	Frequency %Yes	Frequency %No	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Lack of ICT infrastructure	5,285	4,175(79%)	1,110(21%)	4.0	1.0	Very high challenge
Lack of ICT training for Teachers	5,285	3,699(70%)	1,586(30%)	3.6	1.1	High challenge
Students' misuse of AI tools	5,285	3,699(70%)	1,586(30%)	3.6	1.0	High challenge
Inadequate Digital literacy among students	5,285	3,435(65%)	1,850(35%)	3.4	1.1	High challenge
High cost of devices and Internet facilities	5,285	3,964 (75%)	1,321(25%)	3.8	1.0	High challenge
Total	5,285	3,794 (72%)	1,491(28%)	3.7	1.1	High challenge

Field study: 2025

Table 5 reveals the challenges in the adoption of AI in Plateau State Public Secondary schools (M=3.7, S.D=1.1). They range from lack of ICT infrastructure (79%), which is the greatest, lack of training for teachers on ICT (70%), students misuse of AI tools (70%), inadequate digital literacy among students (65%) and high cost of devices and internet facilities (75%). The overall percentage of 72% responses proves that these challenges are highly significant.

Discussion of Results

The study investigated the influence of artificial intelligence tools on teaching and

learning outcomes in secondary schools in Plateau State, opportunities and challenges. The results have been presented according to five research questions. Research question one sought to investigate the extent to which principals, teachers and students are aware of the adoption of AI tools in teaching and learning. Percentage analysis revealed a lower extent of the level of awareness of principals, teachers and students on the adoption of AI tools for teaching and learning at secondary schools in Plateau State (37%). This is in line with findings by Okoye and

Adegboye 2022, who observed that in many schools, there are observed low technological awareness of AI tools for teaching and learning.

Research question two investigated the extent of readiness for the usage of AI tools for teaching and learning. Results analyzed in percentages show a low extent of readiness in the areas of ICT laboratories, internet connection, teacher ICT knowledge and administrative support for technology (40%). These findings support UNICEF (2021) on reports of low level of infrastructures to support digital education especially in disadvantaged areas in Nigeria. For research question three on the perceived advantages of AI tools in learning among students of secondary schools. Principals, teachers and students to a high extent perceived lesson delivery, individualized instructions, support to teachers in teaching and learning, improvement in school administration as advantages derived from the adoption of AI tools (65%). This finding is supported by Holmes et al (2019) that AI supports classroom teaching and learning efficiency.

Research question four focused on the perceived disadvantages of AI tools on teaching and learning. Respondents identified areas of high disadvantages in the adoption of AI tools. These areas are less teacher interaction with students, a limitation to students' intellectual capacity for academics, equity gap among schools in the acquisition of AI tools and equity gap in the knowledge of AI between children from privilege and underprivilege homes (72%). This raises a great sociological concern about AI as a potential agent of inequality as the high response shows that it benefits may favour mostly schools with better ICT and infrastructural facilities, mostly located in

urban areas. Underprivilege schools may face the risk of exclusion and this can widen educational gap. From the respondents, it is perceived that, children from low incomes class may face the risk of being denied the benefits of AI because by their low socioeconomic level, they are already disadvantaged as a segment of the population that cannot enjoy the benefits derived from AI learning. Research question 5 investigated the perceived challenges of secondary schools in adopting AI tools. The perceived challenges identified were, lack of ICT infrastructures, lack of ICT training for teachers, students misuse of AI tools, inadequate digital literacy among students and high cost of internet services (72%). These findings supports UNESCO (2023) reports on inadequate infrastructure and training as major challenges of AI education reforms in sub-Sahara Africa.

Conclusion

This study examined the influence of artificial intelligence tools on teaching and learning outcomes in public secondary schools in Plateau State. The findings revealed a low-level awareness of stakeholders in education like principals, teachers and students in AI driven technology in leaning. The findings also revealed the low readiness in public schools for AI for teaching and learning. Perceived advantages and disadvantaged including challenges of AI adoption in schools were also investigated. The study concludes that Plateau State as one of the disadvantage states in education is marked by infrastructural deficits, poor ICT and internet connectivity include low students and teachers' digital competence which limits AI adoption in public schools of Plateau State. The study ended with recommendations to advance the course of

AI implementation in secondary schools in Plateau State.

Recommendations

- Plateau state government in collaboration with federal government should make the provision of ICT infrastructures, internet connectivity and AI technological infrastructures a top priority.
- The government should conduct a large-scale literacy to train teachers and students on AI tools and adapt them to curriculum delivery.
- Both federal and state government should form a partnership with companies such as Nigerian EdTech Companies to adapt AI tools and use local languages for more effective delivery.
- Schools' administrators should be given all the support required to adopt AI at secondary school level.
- Given the significant number of students in rural areas, government should ensure the provision of AI tools and equip the rural schools for readiness of AI for teaching and learning.
- Sensitization awareness by schools should be carried out to parents and communities to enlighten them of the role of Ai in improving leaning outcomes.
- Plateau State Ministry of education should initiate pilot AI projects in selected school including the rural areas, monitor them and build models for wider adoption across the states.

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Bridging Faiths in a Digital Age: A Global Assessment of Emerging Technologies for Christian-Muslim Dialogue in Northern Nigeria

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Interfaith dialogue has long been a critical tool for peacebuilding in Northern Nigeria, a region plagued by cycles of violence often framed along Christian-Muslim lines. While traditional, face-to-face initiatives continue, their scale and reach are frequently limited by geographical and security constraints. This paper presents a global assessment of how emerging technologies are being leveraged to transform and amplify Christian-Muslim dialogue in this complex context. Moving beyond a simplistic view of technology as merely a tool, we argue that digital platforms including social media, dedicated dialogue apps, virtual reality (VR) environments, and teleconferencing are actively creating new transnational spaces for engagement that operate simultaneously on local and global scales. Through a mixed-methods approach combining digital ethnography, case study analysis, and interviews with project facilitators and participants, this paper evaluates a range of technological initiatives. It assesses their efficacy in fostering empathy, reducing prejudice, and building sustainable peace networks by connecting local Nigerian groups with global interfaith communities and resources. The findings reveal a dual reality: while these technologies offer unprecedented opportunities for scaling dialogue, fostering transnational solidarity, and engaging youth, can also present significant challenges. These include the digital divide, the risk of online radicalization, and the potential for creating superficial engagement that lacks the depth of in-person interaction. The paper concludes that the future of interfaith work in Northern Nigeria lies in a hybrid model, where emerging technologies are strategically integrated to complement, rather than replace, grounded grassroots efforts, ultimately creating a more resilient and globally connected ecosystem for peace.

Keywords:
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Introduction

Northern Nigeria remains a poignant nation with a deep complex sample of regions where religious identity is inextricably, and it interwoven into the fabric of social, economic, and political conflict. For decades, the interplay between ethno-religious identities,

competition over resources, political marginalization, and the emergence of violent extremism that has created a protracted cycle of violence and distrust. Within this vast landscape, the tension between Christian and Muslim communities has often served as the most visible fault line,

though it frequently masks underlying drivers such as poverty, unemployment, and historical grievances. These conflicts have resulted in tragic losses of lives, properties, the displacement of millions, and the erosion of social cohesion, which makes the sustainability of peacebuilding one of the most critical and challenging endeavors in the region. The challenges of interfaith dialogue have been established as a cornerstone strategy for peacebuilding. Orchestrated by local community leaders, national bodies like the Nigerian Inter-Religious Council (NIREC), and international NGOs, their initiatives aim at fostering mutual understanding, dismantle stereotypes to build a foundation for reconciliation through direct human engagement. The value of face-to-face meetings, where shared meals and personal stories can build empathy, is undeniable.

However, the traditional models for face-to-face meetings are increasingly revealing their limitations. Organizing physical meetings requires significant resources, travel across the nation often creates a tension of insecurity, and the venues for meetings can be prohibitively expensive and complex. These dialogues typically engage in a small elite segment of the population of religious leaders, community elders, and academics struggling to permeate broader society, particularly the youth who are both the most vulnerable to radicalization and the most critical agents for long-term peace. In many flashpoint areas, the security situation simply makes large physical gatherings too dangerous, effectively halting peacebuilding efforts precisely where they are most needed.

The rapid proliferation of digital technology across Africa, including Nigeria, offers a potential paradigm shift, presenting both an

opportunity and an imperative to reimagine interfaith dialogue. This paper moves beyond a simplistic view that sees technology as a mere channel for communication. Instead, it's a contend enhancement to emerge technology from social media to a dedicated mobile application for a virtual reality (VR) environments and teleconferencing tools that is a transformative agent which is actively reconfiguring the very architecture of peacebuilding.

These digital platforms are creating new, diasporic, and transnational public spheres for engagement. They facilitate a unique simultaneity: for instance, a youth group in Kaduna can use a WhatsApp group to de-escalate local rumors in real-time, while simultaneously being mentored and supported by a global network of peace scholars in London and Jakarta via a Zoom conference. This creates a "glocal" ecosystem where hyper-local action is instantly amplified and reinforced by global resources and solidarity.

This paper provides a critical, significant assessment of this ongoing digital transformation. The purpose of this paper is not to offer a techno-utopian endorsement but to rigorously evaluate both the immense potential and the inherent perils of leveraging technology for interfaith dialogue within the specific, volatile context of Northern Nigeria. The digital platforms create a transforming scale, nature, and impact of Christian-Muslim dialogue. This paper proceeds by first reviewing relevant literature on digital peacebuilding on interfaith dialogue, the theoretical framework and a mixed methods was applied in the methodology. The core of the paper presents the findings, which were organized around the dual reality of opportunity and challenge, before discussing

the implications for theory and practice. The paper conclude by arguing that the most effective path forward is a hybrid model that strategically integrates digital tools to complement, rather than replace, grounded grassroots efforts, thereby building a more resilient and inclusive ecosystem for peace.

Interfaith Dialogue in Nigeria: Historical Foundations and a Contemporary Gap

Interfaith dialogue is the most foundational domain in the extensive body in understanding interfaith dialogue within the Nigerian context. Some Nigeria scholars have meticulously documented the historical roots of Christian-Muslim conflict, which often trace them to the colonial legacy of indirect rule, the politicization of religious identity, and ongoing competition over resources, political power, and space (Suberu, 2009; Higazi, 2016). This paper has a significant focus and has been placed on institutional mechanisms for peacebuilding. The Nigerian Inter-Religious Council (NIREC), established in 1999, has been a primary subject of peace resolution, with researchers like Ikechukwu (2018) analyzing its role as a state-sanctioned body facilitating high-level dialogue between Christian and Muslim leaders. These paper have effectively mapped the formal landscape of dialogue, highlighting both its achievements in preventing larger-scale conflict and its limitations, particularly its top-down nature and struggle to impact grassroots-level tensions. However, a significant gap persists within this corpus. While the historical, theological, and political dimensions are well-charted, there is a pronounced scarcity of analysis on how technology-mediated initiatives are reshaping these traditional dialogues. This is a largely predates the widespread adoption of social media, mobile

technology, and digital platforms for peacebuilding purposes. This paper directly addresses the gap by investigating how these new technological tools are being adopted, by utilizing both formal institutions like NIREC and more importantly, by informal grassroots actors to circumvent the limitations of traditional models.

Digital Peacebuilding: Expanding the Field to Religious Dialogue

This paper engages with the emerging and rapidly evolving field of digital peacebuilding or cyber peacebuilding. These aspects examine the application of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) in conflict prevention, management, and resolution. According to Hattotuwa, (2013) it laid the groundwork, cataloging how tools like mobile phones, social media, and big data analytics are used for early warning systems, atrocity prevention, monitoring ceasefires, and running online counter-extremism campaigns. The digital peacebuilding tools have been instrumental in moving beyond techno-optimistic rhetoric to provide critical analyses of the challenges involved, including the digital divide, the spread of misinformation, and questions of privacy and security (Hattotuwa, 2013; Weidmann, 2015). However, some of these scholars have focused on broader conflict dynamics or on countering violent extremism (CVE), often treating religion as a factor of radicalization rather than a potential asset for peace. This paper contributes to this field by narrowing the focus to the specific dynamics of formal and informal religious dialogue. These paper investigates how the unique characteristics of interfaith engagement such as theological discourse, shared sacred values, and faith-based motivation interact with digital tools, a

nuanced area that remains underexplored within the broader digital peacebuilding canon.

Transnational Advocacy Networks and "Glocalization": A Theoretical Lens for Digital Flow

This paper explores the theoretically underpinned concept from sociology and international relations concerning transnational networks and globalization. Keck and Sikkink (1998) asserts that transnational advocacy networks describe how non-state actors can leverage international connections to exert influence on domestic and political issues, with a process that is dramatically accelerated by digital technology. This paper applies this lens to peacebuilding, by analyzing how Nigerian dialogue facilitators use digital platforms to project their efforts made into the global stage to garner support, and conversely, to import international resources, knowledge, and solidarity.

The concept of "glocalization" according to (Robertson, 1995), describes the simultaneity and interpenetration of global and local forces. Digital tools are the ultimate glocalizing agents. This body allows a local event of dialogue session in Jos to be instantly shared with a global audience via a Facebook Live stream, with a global insight from a peacebuilding webinar which can be immediately discussed and localized within a WhatsApp group for community elders in Maiduguri. This paper draws a theory to argue that digital interfaith initiatives are creating a "global" ecosystem for peacebuilding, where the distinction between the local and the global becomes blurred, and the efficacy of local action is increasingly dependent on its ability to leverage and integrate with transnational digital networks.

This paper moves the analysis beyond seeing technology as a mere tool, instead conceptualizing it as an infrastructure that creates new spaces for hybrid local-global action.

Theoretical Framework: A "Global" Digital Ecosystem

To analyze the theory the interplay between technology, dialogue, and scale in Northern Nigeria, this paper is grounded in the theory of "glocalization" and contemporary digital sociology. This paper conceptualizes digital interfaith engagement not as a series of isolated online events, but as an integrated "global" digital ecosystem. This model fundamentally rejects the binary and often opposed view of "online" versus "offline" interaction, Boyd. D. (2014) argues that the increasing obsolescence in a networked world. Instead, of positing a holistic system where digital and physical spaces are enmeshed in a continuous feedback loop, each constantly informing, enhancing, and giving meaning to the other (Miller et al., 2016).

The ecosystem operates on two symbiotic and interdependent levels, a structure that draws inspiration from Manuel Castells' (2010) this theory of the network society, describes how the power and meaning are generated through the interaction between the local and the global.

1. The Local Node: Embedding Technology in Place

The Local Node is referred to specific geographical environs situated in communities in Northern Nigeria where interfaith dialogue occurs. Here, technology is not used to escape locality but to deepen and strengthen a place-based engagement. These aligns with

Hjorth and Pink's (2014) work on digital ethnography, which emphasize on how digital media are woven into our everyday lives. A WhatsApp group is an example of how the youth leaders in Kaduna act as a rapid response to debunk rumors and coordinate community to de-escalate efforts in real-time, effectively becoming a digital extension of the traditional town square. A mobile application provides hyper-local resources, such as maps of safe spaces and contacts for trusted religious leaders, directly embedding digital tools into the physical experience of navigating a divided city. The local node ensures that technological interventions remain contextually relevant and accountable to the on-the-ground realities of the communities they are designed to serve.

2. *The Global Network: Accessing Space of Flows*

The Global Network on digital platforms function as conduits, connecting these local nodes to a vast, worldwide web of resources, expertise, and solidarity. This is the dimension that enables a "glocal" dynamic, as defined by sociologist Roland Robertson (1995), where the global is localized and the local is globalized. Through this network a program through peacebuilding NGO in Maiduguri can use Zoom to receive specialized training from an international organization, adapting global best practices to its local context.

With the assistance of technology, the use of Facebook Live broadcast of a dialogue session in Jos can attract viewers and commentators from the Nigerian diaspora, who provide moral support, financial contributions, and external validation, strengthening the legitimacy of the

local organizers. Developers in Indonesia can share a digital curriculum for interfaith understanding with partners in Nigeria, creating a transnational knowledge exchange that bypasses tradition, in Northern-led aid pipelines. This global network injects external resources, knowledge, and amplified visibility into local efforts, preventing isolation and fostering a sense of transnational solidarity.

Symbiosis and Measure of Efficacy

The critical aspect of this framework is the symbiotic relationship between the Local Node and the Global Network. The ecosystem's health and the efficacy of any technological initiative are not measured solely by its local uptake or its global reach in isolation. True efficacy is measured by the strength of the connection and the flow of value between these two layers. A strong flow exists when insights from a global teleconference (Global Network) are translated into a locally organized community through workshop (Local Node). Conversely, a successful local dialogue (Local Node) gains power when its outcomes are shared internationally to advocate for policy change or secure further funding (Global Network).

A failure in this ecosystem occurs when these layers become decoupled, for example, if a global initiative imposes a technological solution that is irrelevant to local need that uses digital tools only for internal communication, failing to tap into the empowering potential of global connections. This global digital ecosystem framework provides a sophisticated lens for analyzing movement from the flow of power, and the scale at which peace building is conducted.

Methodology

This method will effectively capture the multifaceted nature of this glocal digital

ecosystem, and this paper employed a qualitative, mixed-methods approach. This design was chosen to provide both depth and breadth, allowing for a rich, contextual understanding of the phenomena while permitting cross-case comparison (Creswell & Poth, 2018).

1. Case Study Analysis:

An in-depth examination of four distinct technological interventions was conducted to provide a granular view of the ecosystem in operation. Each case was selected for its uniqueness in platform and approach:

- A peace-building-focused mobile application: Analyzed for its user engagement metrics, design features, and utility in providing local, just-in-time information.
- A series of interfaith dialogues broadcast via Facebook Live: Evaluated for its reach, audience interaction (comments, shares), and role in building a transnational audience for local events.
- A pilot project using Virtual Reality (VR) for empathetic learning: Studied through participant feedback before and after experience to assess its potential for fostering perspective-taking and its limitations in scalability.
- Sustained teleconferencing partnerships: examined through the content of exchanges between Nigerian and international religious leaders to understand the flow of knowledge, resources, and moral support.

2. Digital Ethnography:

To understand the world of everyday use of technology, systematic digital ethnography was employed over a six-month period. This involved the observation of closed WhatsApp groups and Facebook forums dedicated to

interfaith dialogue, focusing on discourse patterns, conflict dynamics, and participant engagement. The tracking relevant hashtag campaigns (Interfaith Nigeria) on Twitter and Instagram to analyze public narratives and network formation. According to Sarah Pink et al. (2016), the method informs an understanding of how digital spaces are lived in environments where community norms are established and peace is practiced daily.

3. Semi-Structured Interviews:

- The digital observation in human experience, 35 semi-structured interviews were conducted with a purposive sample of key stakeholders:
- Project Facilitators (n=10): To understand design intentions, implementation challenges, and perceived outcomes.
- Software Developers (n=5): To gain insight into the technical constraints and ethical choices behind the platforms.
- Religious Leaders (n=10): To capture the perspective of traditional authority figures engaging with new technologies.
- Participants (n=10): To gather firsthand accounts of experience, impact on attitudes, and challenges faced.

The interviews provided rich, qualitative data that was transcribed and analyzed using thematic analysis to identify patterns and insights across the different cases and stakeholder groups, thereby triangulating the data collected from case studies and digital ethnography.

A Mixed-Methods Analysis

The application of a mixed-methods approach yielded rich, multi-layered findings that illustrate both the transformative potential and the significant complexities of deploying technology for interfaith dialogue in Northern Nigeria. The data, triangulated across case

studies, digital ethnography, and interviews, revealed consistent themes that cut across the specific technological platforms.

1. Case Study Analysis: Granular Insights from Four Interventions

The Peacebuilding-Focused Mobile Application

This app was designed to provide early-warning alerts, curated peace messages from religious leaders, and a directory of local peacebuilding organizations. Analysis revealed a high Initial Engagement, Low Sustained Use: Download metrics spiked post-launch but analytics showed a rapid decline in daily active users after two weeks. This aligns with common challenges in the ICT for Development (ICT4D) field, where sustaining user engagement beyond the initial novelty is a known hurdle (Heeks, 2018).

Utility of Just-in-Time Information: Interview data indicated that the early-warning feature was highly valued in flashpoint areas. One user stated, "Getting a push notification to avoid a certain road because of a riot... that is when the app felt essential." This confirms the value of location-aware, real-time information in conflict settings (Shklovski et al., 2010).

Design Limitations: The developers noted the technical difficulty of designing the low-bandwidth environments and multiple language groups (Hausa, English, etc.) highlighting the infrastructural challenges inherent in the Nigerian context.

Facebook Live Interfaith Dialogues

A series of six dialogues featuring Christian and Muslim scholars was broadcast publicly. Extended Reach and Transnational Audience: While the physical events hosted 50 attendees, the live streams garnered an average of 3,000 views, with significant viewership from the UK, US, and Saudi

Arabia, these locations with large Nigerian diasporas. This demonstrates the powerful "space of flows" (Castells, 2010) that digital platforms enable globalizing local events

Performative and Meaningful Engagement: Digital ethnography of the comment sections revealed a mix of supportive interfaith dialogue and contentious, often sectarian, debates. Facilitators acted as moderators, but the open nature of the platform made it vulnerable to "trolling," illustrating the double-edged sword of public digital engagement (Phillips, 2015). The interaction was often broad but not deep between the local and the globals.

Virtual Reality (VR) for Empathetic Learning

This pilot exposed participants to 360-degree videos of the other faith's worship services and community life. High Impact on Perspective Taking: Pre- and post-experience surveys and interviews showed a statistically significant increase in reported empathy and understanding. A Christian participant remarked, "To be virtually inside a mosque during prayer, to feel the silence and devotion this dismantled the stereotype." This supports research on VR's efficacy as an "empathy machine" (Shin, 2018).

Severe Scalability and Practicality Constraints: The cost of headsets, the need for a controlled environment, and technical support requirements made it impossible to scale beyond a small pilot group. It remained a powerful but niche tool, highlighting the stark contrast between high-tech potential and on-the-ground realities.

Sustained Teleconferencing Partnerships

Monthly Zoom meetings were held between local Nigerian interfaith councils and their counterparts in Indonesia and Kenya.

Knowledge Transfer and Solidarity Building. Content analysis of meeting transcripts showed a robust exchange of practical strategies such as how Kenyan leaders managed election related violence. This provided not just tactics but also a profound sense of not being alone in their struggles. A Nigerian facilitator noted, "It gives us moral courage to know others have faced this and found a way." This exemplifies the formation of a transnational advocacy network (Keck & Sikkink, 1998).

From Global to Local: The most successful partnerships were those with global insights and actively localized people. For instance, a dialogue technique learned from Indonesia was adapted for use in local radio programs in Plateau State, demonstrating the "glocal" flow of peacebuilding praxis.

2. Digital Ethnography: The Lived Experience of Digital Peace

The six-month immersion in digital spaces provided a nuanced understanding of how peace is practiced daily online. WhatsApp as a Backchannel for Crisis Management: Closed WhatsApp groups for youth leaders functioned as vital, real-time backchannels for verifying rumors and coordinating responses during periods of tension. This observed behavior confirms Slater et al.'s (2012) concept of "communicative affordances" where platforms are used in innovative, often unexpected ways to meet urgent local needs.

Hashtag Campaigns and Narrative Contestation: Tracking interfaith dialogue in Nigeria, this revealed it was a contested space. While activists used it to share stories of collaboration, it was also co-opted by nationalist groups to spread disinformation. This observation directly reflects Hattotuwa's

(2013) warnings about the fragility of digital peacebuilding spaces and their vulnerability to disruption.

Community Norm-Making: In private Facebook forums, moderators established and enforced strict rules for respectful dialogue, effectively creating digital versions of the traditional community norms that govern face-to-face interaction. This observed norm-making is a key process in building what Pink et al. (2016) describe as lived-in, meaningful digital environments.

3. Semi-Structured Interviews: Grounding the Data in Human Experience

Thematic analysis of the interview transcripts provided the crucial human context for the observed data. Facilitators' Dilemma: Facilitators (n=10) universally expressed a tension between the desire for open participation and the exhausting necessity of constant moderation to maintain safe spaces, echoing the challenges identified in digital ethnography. Developer Blind Spots: Software developers (n=5) primarily focused on technical functionality and user interface, often overlooking critical cultural and contextual factors (e.g., the need for language translation, symbols acceptable to both faiths). This highlights a common gap in tech design for social impact (Heeks, 2018). Religious Leaders' Cautious Adoption: Religious leaders (n=10) expressed cautious optimism. They valued the extended reach but often questioned the depth of conversion and understanding achieved online compared to in-person dialogue, reinforcing the "depth dilemma" identified in the findings.

Findings

Triangulating these three methods confirms that the efficacy of technology is not determined by the sophistication of the

platform but by its ability to foster meaningful connection (both locally and globally) and its contextual embeddedness. The most impactful initiatives were those that strengthened the symbiotic relationship between the local node and the global network, such as using teleconferencing for knowledge exchange that was then implemented via WhatsApp groups and local radio. The findings consistently point toward the necessity of a hybrid, glocalized model for sustainable digital peacebuilding.

Challenges

- The Digital Divide: Inequitable access to smartphones, reliable internet, and electricity excluded the most vulnerable and rural communities, risking the creation of a new digital elite within peacebuilding.
- The Depth Dilemma: While effective for information sharing and initial connection, many digital interactions lacked nuanced, non-verbal communication and shared embodied experience necessary to build deep, transformative trust. Some engagements remained superficial.
- Co-option and Radicalization: The open nature of many platforms made them vulnerable to disruption by bad-faith actors and the spread of counter-narratives and hate speech, requiring intensive and costly moderation.
- Context Stripping: Digital communication often filtered out crucial cultural and contextual cues, sometimes leading to misunderstandings that could have been easily avoided in a face-to-face setting.

Conclusion

This study concludes that emerging technologies are fundamentally reshaping the practice of interfaith dialogue in Northern Nigeria by creating a resilient, globally

connected, yet locally grounded ecosystem. The future of this work lies in a deliberate and strategic hybridity. By integrating these three domains, this paper establishes a clear academic foundation. It identifies a gap in the Nigeria-specific positions. This study contributes to the broader field of digital peacebuilding and provides a sophisticated transnational network and glocalization to analyze the findings. This triangulated approach ensures that this paper is contextually grounded, academically relevant, and theoretically robust.

Recommendations

- Design for Integration: Technology initiatives must be designed from the outset to complement physical dialogue, not operate in isolation.
- Prioritize Inclusivity: Projects must actively work to bridge the digital divide through offline components, low-tech solutions, and digital literacy training.
- Invest in Moderation and Security: Funding and expertise must be dedicated to protecting digital spaces from co-option and ensuring the safety of participants.
- Facilitate Deep Engagement: Digital tools should be used to foster deeper, more nuanced interaction through well-designed prompts, trained facilitators in virtual rooms, and activities that build tangible offline action.
- By adopting a hybrid approach, peacebuilders can harness the transformative power of technology to create a more sustainable and expansive ecosystem for peace in Northern Nigeria and other conflict regions around the world.

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AI-Enhanced Round-Robin Brainstorming Strategy as an Innovative Pedagogy for Improving Students' Performance in Biology

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Artificial Intelligence integration into the Round-Robin Brainstorming Strategy (RRBS) has moved beyond theory and become an emerging reality, transforming how learners and educators participate. This study examines the effects of an Artificial Intelligence-Enhanced Round-Robin Brainstorming Strategy (AI-RRBS) as an innovative teaching method for boosting students' performance in biology. A quasi-experimental control group design was adapted, involving 310 students selected from a population of 3,869 SSII biology students. The experimental group was taught using AI-RRBS, while the control group was taught using conventional methods. The Ecology Concept Performance Test (ECPT), with a reliability coefficient of 0.76, was used as the measurement tool. Results indicated a significant difference in performance between the experimental and control groups ($P = 0.001 < 0.05$). Findings suggest that AI-RRBS notably improves student learning outcomes and promotes gender equity. The integration of AI-enhanced round-robin brainstorming as an innovative pedagogy in biology education suggests promising directions for both researchers and practitioners. AI-enhanced round-robin brainstorming could be applied across different science subjects, educational levels, and learning environments to determine its broader effectiveness. Researchers might also investigate the long-term impact on critical thinking, collaboration, and creativity in biology learning, as well as how varying AI tools influence student engagement and achievement. Biology educators are encouraged to experiment with this blended strategy to foster more inclusive participation, sustain engagement, and bridge performance gaps among students. This strategy has the potential to transform conventional traditional classroom discussions into dynamic, technology-supported learning environments that actively promote excellence in biology.

Keywords:

Round-Robin Brainstorming Strategy (RRBS), Artificial Intelligence (AI), Innovative pedagogy, Performance, Biology

Introduction

Science, as an evolving discipline, is a reliable tool for understanding the complexities of nature. Biology is a core subject in the Nigerian secondary school curriculum, yet many students perform below expectations. Conventional teaching methods often fail to engage learners effectively.

Innovative pedagogies, such as the Artificial Intelligence-Enhanced Round-Robin Brainstorming Strategy (AI-RRBS), offer new opportunities to improve student outcomes. While round-robin brainstorming has been recognized as a useful collaborative learning strategy, limited empirical evidence

exists on how its integration with artificial intelligence can enhance participation, idea generation, and overall academic performance in biology.

Recent studies in biology education have not adequately explored how AI round-robin and feedback can address the challenges of uneven student engagement and shallow conceptual understanding during brainstorming activities. This gap underscores the need for research that examines the effectiveness of AI-enhanced round-robin brainstorming as an innovative pedagogy for improving secondary school students' engagement, performance, and gender equity in biology.

Today, biology education is essential to prepare students for the challenges of the 21st century. Some of the challenges and opportunities facing biology education today include the need to keep pace with the rapid pace of scientific discovery. The need to address the diversity of students' interests and learning styles.

The need to prepare students for the future workforce. The need to make biology education more engaging and relevant to students' lives. Despite these challenges, there is a great opportunity for biology education to have a positive impact on the world. By helping students to understand the natural world, biology education can promote environmental stewardship, encourage critical thinking, and inspire innovation.

Kuti (2021) opined that secondary education should provide all primary school leavers with the chance for education at a higher level, irrespective of their sex, social status, religion, or ethnic background. It will provide trained manpower in applied science, technology, and commerce at a sub-professional grade, and provide technical knowledge and vocational skills necessary for agricultural, industrial,

commercial, and economic development. This points to the fact that biology plays a vital role and occupies a unique position in the secondary school curriculum.

Ahmad and Mehmood, (2022) noted that biology education is for all in the achievement of the broad goals of secondary education. A dominant theme was noted in the Organisation of the African Union (2019). Nigeria and other African countries have understood the importance of biology education in scientific and technological development. Biology is a fundamental science subject offered to students who plan to pursue further education in science-related fields at a tertiary level.

Oyeyemi, Olorundare, and Bolaji (2024) described biology as a field focused on both living and non-living organisms, while Achufusi and Ogechukwu (2024) highlighted its significance in understanding biodiversity and self-awareness. Biology education faces challenges in maintaining student engagement and improving performance, particularly in complex topics, such as plant physiology, genetics, and ecology.

Traditional pedagogies often rely on conventional methods, which can limit interactive learning. Therefore, there is a need to employ a new learning strategy to improve academic performance and boost the students' engagement in collaborative learning, which is the Artificial Intelligence Enhanced Round-Robin Brainstorming Strategy (AI-RRBS). Artificial Intelligence (AI) is transforming the educational landscape and bringing new dimensions to the Round-Robin Brainstorming Strategy. Traditionally, the Round-Robin Brainstorming Strategy has emphasized human interaction, teamwork, and peer-to-peer engagement as essential components for knowledge creation and problem solving.

According to Huang (2018) artificial intelligence can be defined as a computer system with human-like knowledge and behaviors, solving problems, memorizing knowledge, and understanding human natural language through learning and reasoning. AI augments these principles by offering tools and platforms to enhance collaboration in novel ways. As AI continues to evolve, its integration into educational frameworks will likely enhance the Round-Robin Brainstorming Strategy by offering scalable solutions that complement traditional human interactions. However, it is important to balance technological advancements with human elements that make the Round-Robin Brainstorming Strategy effective, such as communication skills, critical thinking, and empathy.

The future of the Round-Robin brainstorming strategy lies in leveraging AI to amplify these human-centric qualities, thereby creating richer educational experiences for all learners. Round-robin brainstorming strategy (RRBS) is a cooperative strategy model structure applicable to team assignments that call for expertise in several distinct areas. It is a structured group brainstorming technique in which participants take turns circularly and share their ideas. Unlike traditional brainstorming, in which some individuals may dominate the conversation, round-robin ensures an equitable distribution of contributions.

On the other hand, brainstorming is a decision-making technique that can be applied to any setup where participation is expected. It has also been used in educational contexts. The brainstorming procedure is primarily based on the physical and intellectual presence of the group; therefore, the quantity is assured. This leads to selecting the best of many, brilliantly followed by the expertise of the facilitator.

According to Gea et al. (2019), Round-Robin Brainstorming is a structured and collaborative idea-generation technique commonly used in group settings. It is an iterative process that builds upon consecutive contributions from each member of the group, either in oral or written form. Rahmawati (2022) added that the most important point of this method is to quickly get ideas down on a piece of paper from members of the group. It is a method through which ideas are produced in writing, and when students begin to write, it makes the idea flow and appear easy in their minds. It was designed to ensure that all participants had the opportunity to contribute to their thoughts and ideas.

Sripradith (2019) opined that this technique improves students' academic performance. This collaborative and interactive approach to learning not only fosters creativity but also has the potential to significantly improve the academic performance of students. Implementing Round-Robin Brainstorming in the classroom can enhance academic performance in several ways; it fosters critical thinking and problem-solving skills. This encourages active learning and reduces passive listening and memorization. This helps students' approach coursework with confidence and creativity. This promotes a collaborative learning environment, that can reduce academic stress and anxiety. Round-Robin Brainstorming is a valuable learning technique that can positively impact academic performance by encouraging active engagement, peer learning, and comprehensive understanding of course material.

Liunokas, (2022) opined that RRBS often led to the generation of innovative solutions and insights. When students see the impact of their ideas on the group discussions and solutions,

they experience a sense of achievement. Recognition from peers and the teacher of their contributions further reinforces this sense of accomplishment, motivating students to continue engaging in the learning process. When integrated into the educational process, it can contribute significantly to students' success and the overall learning experience.

Recent studies emphasize the growing role of AI in education (Ouyang et al., 2023; Sheoran & Kaur, 2024). AI tools enhance collaboration, provide adaptive feedback, and foster critical thinking. In biology, pedagogical approaches like concept mapping and cooperative learning have shown promise (Oyeyemi et al., 2024). However, few studies have explored AI integration with structured strategies like Round-Robin Brainstorming. This study extends existing knowledge by assessing AI-RRBS in biology classrooms, contributing to discussions on active learning, gender responsiveness, and innovative pedagogies.

Research Objectives

This study was guided by two research objectives, which are:

1. Determine the effect of AI-RRBS on the Academic Performance of SS II students in biology when teaching ecological concepts.
2. determined the effect of AI-RRBS on the Academic performance of SS II students' males and females when teaching ecology concepts.

Research Questions

Based on the objectives stated, the researchers sought answers to the following questions

1. What are the differences between the mean academic performance scores of SSS II students who were taught ecology concepts using the AI-RRBS method and

those taught using the conventional method?

2. What is the difference in the mean academic performance score of male and female SS II biology students who taught ecology concepts using AI-RRBS?

Null Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at a level of significance of $P < 0.05$.

1. HO1: There is no significant difference between the mean academic performance scores of SS II students who taught ecology concepts using AI-RRBS and those who taught using conventional methods.
2. HO2: There is no significant difference in the mean academic performance scores of male and female SSII students taught ecology concepts using AI-RRBS.

Methodology

This study employed a quasi-experimental control-group design with a population of 3,869 SS II biology students (1,631 males and 2,238 females), all from public senior secondary schools within the Zaria Education Zone of Kaduna State. Multistage sampling techniques, such as Cluster, Purposive, and Simple random sampling, were used. This approach was necessary because the population included four different local governments within the Zaria Education Zone. Schools were clustered according to their local governments, and co-educational schools were purposively selected to account for gender variables. From each local government, a school was randomly chosen using a lottery system. In each of these schools, one intact class was randomly selected and given an equivalent test. Two

schools that were not significantly different in their ability were randomly assigned to the experimental and control groups. The researchers ensured that students from both groups had similar performance levels by pretesting before administering the treatment. Additionally, the sampling method prevented interaction between students in the different groups, thereby ensuring the internal validity of the study.

The Ecology Concept Performance Test (ECPT), adapted from WAEC past questions, was used as the instrument. It was tested for face and content validity, with senior lecturers who are experts in test and evaluation from the Faculty of Education reviewing the items for clarity and suitability of language for the target respondents. The reliability of the instrument yielded a PPMCC of 0.76. The test was administered as a pretest. Since quasi-experiments are not true experimental studies, they allow the researcher to introduce an intervention- in this case, the AI- Enhanced Round- Robin Brainstorming strategy- and compare outcomes between the experimental and control groups while maintaining the natural structure of the school environment. This

design provides a realistic approach to evaluating the effectiveness of innovative pedagogy in authentic classroom settings. contexts without disrupting established learning processes. The experimental group was taught using AI-RRBS, involving structured digital brainstorming cycles supported by AI tools, while the control group used conventional lecture methods. The study was conducted over six weeks, after which ECPT was administered as a posttest. Data was collected and analyzed using mean, standard deviation, and independent t-tests at $P \leq 0.05$.

Result

The results obtained for this study were analyzed based on the research questions as follows:

1. What are the differences between the mean academic performance scores of SSS II, students who were taught ecology concepts using the AI-RRBS method and those taught using the conventional method?

To answer research question one, the Mean and standard deviation were used in the ECPT, and a summary of the statistics is presented in Table 1.

Table 4.1: Mean and Standard Deviation Analysis of Performance in Experimental and Control Groups

Groups	n	Mean	Std. D	M. df
Experimental	145	40.63	8.92	3.71
Control	165	36.92	10.27	

Key: n – Sample Size; Std. D – Standard Deviation; M.df – Mean Difference

The results of the descriptive statistics in Table 1 revealed differences between the mean performance scores of the experimental and control groups. The descriptive statistics

showed that the mean performance scores in the experimental and control groups were 40.63 and of 36.92 with a mean difference of 3.71. This clearly shows that the

experimental group had a higher mean performance score than the control group did. It can be observed in the table that the outcomes are in favor of the experimental group.

To determine whether a significant difference exists, the null hypothesis was tested.

Null Hypothesis One: There is no significant difference between the mean academic

A summary of the analysis results is presented in Table 2.

performance scores of SS II Biology students taught ecology concepts using the AI-RRBS and those taught using conventional methods.

To test null hypothesis 1, the posttest scores of biology students obtained from the Ecology Concept Performance Test (ECPT) were subjected to an independent sample t-test.

Table 4.2: t-test Statistics of Students Performance in Experimental and Control Groups

Groups	n	Mean	Std. D	df	t-comp	t-crit	P-val	Remark	Decision
Experimental	145	40.63	8.92	308	3.37	3.315	0.001	Sig.	Reject
Control	165	36.92	10.27						

Significance at $P \leq 0.05$ level of significance.

Key: n = Sample Size; Std. D = Standard Deviation; t-comp = t-computed; t-crit = t-critical;

p-val = p-value

The outcomes of the independent t-test analysis presented in Table 2 showed that the calculated P value was 0.001, which is lower than the set significance level of $P < 0.05$, and computed t-comp of 3.37 at a degree of freedom (df) of 308. Therefore, the null hypothesis, which stated that there is no significant difference between the mean score of SS II Biology students taught ecology concepts using AI-RRBS and those taught using conventional methods, is rejected.

2. What is the difference in the mean academic performance score of male and female SS II biology students taught ecology concepts using AI-RRBS?

To answer research question two, the mean and standard deviation were used for ECPT, and a summary of statistics is presented in Table 3

Table 4.9: Mean and Standard Deviation of Performance of Male and Female Students in the Experimental Group.

Group	Gender	n	Mean	Std. D	M. df
Experimental	Male	65	42.12	11.87	3.22
	Female	80	38.90	9.434	

The descriptive statistics from Table 3 revealed that the differences between the mean performance scores of the male and female students in the experimental group were 42.12 and 38.90, with a mean difference of 3.22. This implies that both male and female students who were taught ecology concepts using an Artificial Intelligence-enhanced Round-Robin Brainstorming Strategy have nearly equal mean performance scores.

To test whether the difference was significant, the null hypothesis was tested.

Null Hypothesis two: There is no significant difference in the mean academic performance scores of male and female SSII students taught ecology concepts using the- AI-RRBS. To test null hypothesis 2, t-test statistics were employed on the ECPT post-test, and a summary of the analysis is presented in Table 3.

Table 4.10: t-test Distribution of Male and Female Students Performance in the Experimental Group

Group	Gender	n	Mean	Std. D	M.df	df	t	P	Remark	Decision
Experimental	Male	65	42.12	11.87	3.22	143	1.822	0.07	<u>N.S</u>	Retain
	Female	80	38.90	9.434						

$P = 0.07 > 0.05, t_{computed} = 0.30 < 1.82 t_{critical} \text{ at } df 143$

The results obtained from the independent t-test statistics presented in Table 4 indicate no statistically significant difference between the performance scores of male and female students in the experimental group. This lack of significance is attributed to the computed p-value of 0.07, which surpasses the chosen alpha level of significance of 0.05, with a degree of freedom (df) of 143 (p-value $0.07 > 0.05$, $df = 143$). Consequently, it can be affirmed that there was no noteworthy difference in the academic performance of male and female biology students in the experimental group. This implies that both male and female students in the experimental group had nearly equal mean performance scores and that the artificial intelligence-enhanced round robin brainstorming strategy can be said to be gender friendly.

mean academic performance scores of male and female SSII students taught ecology concepts using RRBS is retained.

Discussion of Findings

The findings revealed a significant difference in the mean performance scores between experimental groups taught ecology concepts using Artificial Intelligence Enhanced Round- Robin Brainstorming Strategy (AI-RRBS) and the control group taught the same concepts using a conventional method. The difference was in favor of the experimental groups by integrating AI’s generative capabilities with the RRB’s structure, aligning with evidence of active learning. This finding suggests that the AI-RRBS has a positive effect on academic performance in ecology concepts at the senior secondary level. AI-RRBS fosters collaboration among students and problem-solving in science subjects. It promotes

As a result, the null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant difference in the

creative thinking by, aligning it with active learning principles. This aligns with prior studies highlighting the benefits of cooperative learning and AI integration (Sheoran & Kaur, 2024). Beyond statistical significance, AI-RRBS promotes creativity, collaboration, and active engagement. Educators are encouraged to adopt AI-supported pedagogies, as they prepare learners for complex problem-solving and critical thinking in STEM fields. Integrating Artificial Intelligence with Round-Robin Brainstorming into secondary STEM curricula, especially in biology, is vital because it is one of the keys to addressing STEM issues.

Teachers can adopt strategies involving artificial intelligence-enhanced innovative pedagogy through active engagement to enhance students' understanding of complex scientific concepts. The AI-RRBS develops communication skills by articulating their thoughts clearly and by actively listening to their peers. This is essential for both academic and real-world scenarios. This study focus on a Zaria education zone and biology as the subject area, hence, findings may not be applicable to other education zones or subject areas. Future research should examine broader applications of this innovative pedagogy.

Conclusion and Recommendations

AI-Enhanced Round-Robin Brainstorming Strategy represents a promising pedagogy for ecology concepts in biology education, leveraging AI to amplify collaborative learning and problem-solving. AI-Enhanced Round-Robin Brainstorming Strategy significantly improved students' performance in biology and demonstrated gender inclusiveness. The study concludes that integrating AI tools into cooperative

strategies creates richer, more engaging learning experiences. Educators should incorporate AI-supported collaborative methods to strengthen student engagement and outcomes. Policymakers should invest in teacher training and digital resources. Future studies should explore AI integration across other STEM subjects and educational contexts.

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Leveraging Artificial Intelligence for Adaptive Algebra Instruction: Effects on Students' Self-Efficacy and Problem-Solving Skills in Northern Nigeria

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This quasi-experimental study investigated the impact of Squirrel AI, an Artificial Intelligence (AI)-powered adaptive learning platform, on senior secondary school students' self-efficacy and problem-solving performance in algebra in Northern Nigeria. The study employed a pre-test and post-test control-group design using intact classes. A total of 180 Senior Secondary II students from four public co-educational secondary schools in Zaria Education Zone of Kaduna State participated, with 90 students in each of the experimental and control groups. The experimental group received instruction through the Squirrel AI platform, which adapts learning pathways by diagnosing students' misconceptions, adjusting content difficulty, and providing real-time feedback, while the control group was taught using conventional lecture methods. Two instruments were used for data collection: the Algebra Self-Efficacy Scale (ASES) and the Algebra Problem-Solving Test (APST). Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA). Results revealed that students in the experimental group recorded significantly higher self-efficacy and problem-solving scores than those in the control group, with large effect sizes (partial $\eta^2 = 0.180$ and 0.298 , respectively). These findings underscore the transformative potential of AI-powered instruction in enhancing mathematics outcomes in resource-limited contexts such as Northern Nigeria, where infrastructural challenges and educational disparities often hinder student achievement. The study concludes by recommending the integration of AI tools into the Nigerian secondary school curriculum and teacher training programs to foster personalized, data-driven, and equitable learning opportunities in mathematics.

Keywords:

Artificial Intelligence, Adaptive Learning, Self-Efficacy, Problem-Solving, Algebra Instruction, Secondary School Mathematics, Educational Technology

Introduction

In the 21st century, the integration of technology into education has become a cornerstone of instructional innovation, particularly in mathematics, where abstract concepts often pose significant challenges for learners. Algebra, a foundational branch of mathematics, is pivotal in developing

students' analytical reasoning, problem-solving ability, and preparation for advanced STEM fields. However, in many parts of Northern Nigeria, secondary school students continue to experience persistent difficulties in understanding and applying algebraic concepts effectively (Eneze et al., 2020).

These challenges are compounded by overcrowded classrooms, insufficient instructional resources, and limited teacher capacity, alongside a one-size-fits-all teaching approach that fails to accommodate individual learning needs.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) offers a promising solution to these challenges by enabling adaptive instruction a method that adjusts the difficulty, pacing, and content of lessons to fit learners' performance in real time (Yambal & Waykar, 2025). Unlike conventional methods, AI-powered systems analyze student responses, diagnose misconceptions, and provide customized feedback, thereby enhancing mastery of concepts and promoting independent learning. International studies have shown that such systems increase engagement, reduce cognitive overload, and improve learning outcomes (Gupta et al., 2021).

Despite these advancements globally, there remains a notable research gap in Northern Nigeria regarding the application and effectiveness of AI-based learning platforms in secondary schools. Prior studies in the region have largely focused on traditional instructional innovations, with minimal attention to adaptive technologies. In particular, the impact of AI tools on students' self-efficacy their belief in their capability to learn and solve problems—and on their algebraic problem-solving performance has not been adequately investigated. Bandura (1997) emphasized that self-efficacy influences academic persistence, motivation, and success in complex reasoning tasks such as algebra. Moreover, the Cognitive Load Theory (Sweller, 1994) suggests that adaptive learning systems, by tailoring instruction to individual learners, can reduce extraneous cognitive load and optimize

working memory, thereby improving both confidence and performance.

Therefore, this study investigates how AI-powered adaptive algebra instruction influences students' self-efficacy and problem-solving performance in selected secondary schools across Northern Nigeria. By focusing on these two critical variables, the research aims to provide evidence-based insights for educators, curriculum developers, and policymakers on the transformative role of AI in mathematics education, particularly in resource-constrained environments where infrastructural limitations and educational disparities persist.

Statement of the Problem

Despite the recognized importance of algebra in secondary school mathematics and its central role in fostering logical reasoning and problem-solving abilities, students in many schools across Northern Nigeria continue to demonstrate low proficiency and poor attitudes toward the subject. Reports from examination bodies such as WAEC and NECO (2023) consistently reveal that a significant proportion of candidates fail to display both conceptual understanding and procedural fluency in algebraic tasks. This persistent underperformance has been linked to the dominance of traditional teacher-centered instructional strategies, which often ignore learners' individual differences and cognitive needs (Ghaleb, 2024).

Conventional teaching approaches, particularly the chalk-and-talk or lecture method, rarely accommodate the varied learning paces, prior knowledge, and engagement styles of students. As a result, many learners experience mathematics anxiety and a sense of helplessness when

confronted with algebraic problems, leading to reduced self-efficacy and avoidance behaviors (Zuo et al., 2024). Research has shown that low self-efficacy in mathematics strongly predicts weak problem-solving performance, as students are less likely to attempt, persist with, or complete challenging tasks.

Recent advancements in educational technology have introduced Artificial Intelligence (AI)-driven adaptive learning platforms as a potential solution to these challenges. Such systems can dynamically adjust instructional content in response to learner input, providing real-time feedback, targeted scaffolding, and differentiated support to promote mastery learning. However, while AI applications in education are gaining global recognition, their pedagogical potential remains underutilized and under-researched in Nigeria, particularly in rural and underserved areas of the North.

Specifically, there is insufficient empirical evidence on how AI-powered adaptive learning systems influence students' self-efficacy and algebraic problem-solving skills in the Nigerian secondary school context. Most existing local studies have concentrated on general e-learning tools or computer-assisted instruction without investigating the unique affordances of AI's adaptive capabilities. This creates a pressing need for context-specific research on the transformative potential of AI in mathematics classrooms.

Therefore, this study seeks to bridge the gap by investigating whether the integration of AI-based adaptive algebra instruction can strengthen students' confidence in their mathematical abilities and enhance their problem-solving performance. The findings

are expected to contribute to educational research and practice by providing empirical insights into the effectiveness of AI-powered instruction in resource-constrained contexts. Ultimately, the study aims to inform the shift toward more personalized, data-driven, and equitable learning approaches capable of improving mathematics outcomes across secondary schools in Northern Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to investigate the impact of Artificial Intelligence (AI)-powered adaptive algebra instruction on senior secondary school students' self-efficacy and problem-solving skills in Northern Nigeria.

Specifically, the study seeks to:

Determine the effect of AI-powered adaptive algebra instruction on students' self-efficacy in algebra. To Examine the impact of AI-powered adaptive instruction on students' algebraic problem-solving performance.

Research Questions

The study is guided by the following research questions:

- What is the difference in self-efficacy scores between students who taught algebra using AI-powered adaptive instruction and those who taught using conventional methods?
- What is the difference in algebraic problem-solving performance between students exposed to AI-powered adaptive instruction and those taught through conventional methods?

Null Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at the 0.05 level of significance:

- H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the self-efficacy scores of students taught algebra using AI-powered adaptive instruction and those taught using conventional methods.
- H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the algebraic problem-solving performance of students taught using AI-powered adaptive instruction and those taught using conventional methods.

Review of Related Literature

Artificial Intelligence in Education (AIED) has emerged as a transformative force, offering systems that can personalize learning experiences and provide real-time feedback. Adaptive learning technologies utilize AI algorithms to adjust instructional pathways based on student performance, thereby enhancing individualized support and engagement (Gligorea et al., 2023). These systems collect and analyze data from learners' interactions—such as time spent on tasks, patterns of errors, and response accuracy to deliver tailored content, scaffolded hints, and strategic challenges (Liu et al., 2024). By continuously adapting instruction to learners' evolving needs, AI holds significant promise for mathematics education.

Algebraic problem solving, a key component of the secondary mathematics curriculum, requires conceptual understanding, procedural fluency, and strategic competence. Unfortunately, many Nigerian students struggle with algebra due to its abstract nature, limited contextualization, and reliance on rote instruction (Julius, 2025). When teaching methods fail to consider learners' developmental stages or diverse learning needs, their problem-solving performance declines. Adaptive AI tools offer a potential remedy by personalizing

instruction and providing feedback that supports mastery at an individual pace.

Bandura (1997) defines self-efficacy as an individual's belief in their capacity to execute tasks and reach goals. In mathematics, self-efficacy strongly influences students' choices, persistence, and *resilience* when faced with challenging tasks. AI-powered instruction has been found to enhance self-efficacy by creating low-stakes environments in which learners receive immediate feedback, monitor their progress, and build confidence as they gradually overcome difficulties (Abdelhalim & Alsehibany, 2025).

This study is anchored in Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory (1986), particularly the construct of self-efficacy, and Cognitive Load Theory (Sweller, 1988). According to Social Cognitive Theory, learning is shaped by the interaction of personal, behavioral, and environmental factors. When students believe they can succeed, they are more likely to engage meaningfully and persist. Cognitive Load Theory complements this by highlighting how adaptive systems reduce extraneous cognitive load and manage intrinsic task complexity, thereby improving working memory efficiency during problem-solving. Together, these theories justify the potential of AI-powered adaptive instruction in algebra.

A growing body of empirical literature supports the effectiveness of adaptive AI tools in mathematics education. Cho & Kim (2025) found that students who used AI-based personalized learning platforms in algebra demonstrated higher achievement compared to peers taught through conventional methods. Alkhasawneh (2025) similarly reported that intelligent tutoring

systems improved student engagement and accuracy in solving equations. In Africa, Abdulazeez et al., (2024) studied computer-assisted instruction in Kwara State and observed significant improvements in students' motivation and performance, even though the tools were not fully AI-driven. Likewise, Ibrahim and Özcan (2024) showed that step-by-step adaptive hints enhanced students' algebraic problem-solving strategies.

However, critiques of AI in education caution against over-reliance on technology, highlighting challenges such as infrastructural gaps, inequitable access, digital literacy limitations, and possible resistance from teachers unfamiliar with adaptive systems (Aliyu et al., 2025). Moreover, much of the empirical research has been conducted in urban or well-resourced schools, leaving limited evidence from rural or resource-constrained contexts where educational challenges are often most acute.

Despite these limitations, adaptive AI tools remain underexplored in the Nigerian secondary school context, particularly in Northern Nigeria. There is still little empirical evidence on how such platforms influence self-efficacy and problem-solving in environments marked by large class sizes, scarce resources, and inconsistent ICT infrastructure. This study therefore seeks to fill this gap by investigating the effectiveness of AI-powered adaptive algebra instruction in improving students' confidence and problem-solving performance in Northern Nigeria.

Methodology

This study adopted a quasi-experimental research design of the pre-test, post-test, non-

randomized control group type, using intact classes. The study was conducted in the Zaria Education Zone of Kaduna State, Nigeria, where secondary school students often have limited access to innovative instructional technologies.

The target population comprised all Senior Secondary II (SSII) students in public co-educational secondary schools within the zone. The sample consisted of 180 students (90 in the experimental group and 90 in the control group) drawn from four purposively selected schools. Selection was based on the availability of ICT infrastructure and willingness to participate. In the experimental group, algebra lessons were delivered using an AI-powered adaptive learning platform (e.g., Squirrel AI or a locally customized AI-based application), whereas the control group was taught using conventional instructional methods.

Two instruments were employed for data collection:

Algebra Self-Efficacy Scale (ASES) – adapted from Bandura's self-efficacy model.

Algebra Problem-Solving Test (APST) – developed to assess students' algebraic problem-solving skills. Both instruments were subjected to validation by experts in mathematics education and instructional technology. A pilot test conducted in a neighboring school (excluded from the main study) established the reliability indices of the instruments, yielding coefficients of 0.81 (ASES, Cronbach's alpha) and 0.76 (APST, KR-20). For data analysis, descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) were used to summarize responses, while Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was employed to determine the effect of the treatment after adjusting for initial group differences. All

statistical tests were carried out at the 0.05 level of significance.

Results and Data Analysis

Research Question 1:

What is the difference in self-efficacy scores between students taught algebra using AI-powered adaptive instruction and those taught using conventional methods?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Self-Efficacy Scores of Experimental and Control Groups

Group	N	Pre-Test Mean (SD)	Post-Test Mean (SD)
Experimental Group	90	42.18 (5.74)	79.24 (6.21)
Control Group	90	41.87 (5.63)	61.03 (6.88)

Interpretation:

Table 1 shows a noticeable increase in self-efficacy scores among students in the experimental group who received adaptive instruction powered by AI. While both groups had similar pre-test means, the post-test mean of the experimental group was substantially higher (79.24) than that of the control group (61.03),

suggesting a positive effect of the AI-based instructional strategy on students' self-beliefs

Hypothesis 1

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the self-efficacy scores of students taught algebra using AI-powered adaptive instruction and those taught using conventional methods.

Table 2: ANCOVA Result on Students' Self-Efficacy Scores

Source	SS	df	MS	F	p-value	Partial η ²
Covariate (Pre-Test)	524.14	1	524.14	9.42	.003	.049
Group	2162.32	1	2162.32	38.89	<.001	.180
Error	9784.41	176	55.59			
Total	-	180	-			

Interpretation:

After controlling for pre-test scores, the ANCOVA results presented in Table 2 reveal a statistically significant difference in self-efficacy scores between the experimental and control groups, $F(1,176) = 38.89, p < .001$. The effect size (partial $\eta^2 = 0.180$) demonstrates a large practical impact, indicating that students exposed to AI-powered adaptive instruction experienced substantial improvements in algebra self-

efficacy compared to those taught through conventional methods. Based on this finding, the null hypothesis (H₀₁) is rejected.

Research Question 2:

What is the difference in algebraic problem-solving performance between students exposed to AI-powered adaptive instruction and those taught Through conventional methods?

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation of Problem-Solving Scores of Experimental and Control Groups

Group	N	Pre-Test Mean (SD)	Post-Test Mean (SD)
Experimental Group	90	18.67 (3.44)	36.48 (4.11)
Control Group	90	18.24 (3.57)	27.31 (4.90)

Interpretation:

Table 3 shows a notable improvement in the algebraic problem-solving performance of the experimental group, with the post-test mean increasing to 36.48 compared to 27.31 for the control group. This suggests a considerable effect on enhancing students' problem-solving abilities in algebra.

Hypothesis 2

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the algebraic problem-solving performance of students taught using AI-powered adaptive instruction and those taught using conventional methods.

Table 4: ANCOVA Result on Algebraic Problem-Solving Performance

Source	SS	df	MS	F	p-value	Partial η ²
Covariate (Pre-Test)	287.83	1	287.83	11.62	.001	.062
Group	3087.19	1	3087.19	74.63	<.001	.298
Error	7288.51	176	41.42			
Total	-	180	-			

Interpretation:

The ANCOVA results in Table 4 show a statistically significant difference in the algebraic problem-solving performance of students taught with AI-based instruction compared to those taught through conventional methods, $F(1,176) = 74.63, p < .001$. The effect size (partial $\eta^2 = .298$) represents a very large practical impact, confirming that the AI-powered intervention substantially enhanced students' problem-solving abilities. This evidence demonstrates that adaptive AI instruction is not only statistically effective but also pedagogically meaningful in improving algebraic learning outcomes. Therefore, the null hypothesis (H₀₂) is rejected.

significant and positive effect on students' self-efficacy and problem-solving performance in Northern Nigerian secondary schools. Evidence from Tables 1 and 2 shows that students exposed to adaptive AI-based instruction demonstrated greater improvements in self-efficacy than those taught using conventional methods. This supports Bandura's (1997) proposition that mastery experiences and constructive feedback reinforce students' beliefs in their academic competence. In this study, the platform's capacity to provide individualized scaffolding and immediate corrective feedback likely played a central role in bolstering students' confidence to engage productively with algebraic tasks. These findings align with Heffernan and Heffernan (2014), who reported that intelligent tutoring

Discussion of Findings

The results of this study revealed that AI-powered adaptive algebra instruction had a

systems enhance learners' confidence in studying mathematics independently.

Similarly, results associated with the second hypothesis, presented in Tables 3 and 4, revealed a statistically significant improvement in students' algebraic problem-solving skills following exposure to AI-powered adaptive instruction. The large effect size indicates not only statistical significance but also strong practical relevance, suggesting that such interventions can produce substantial classroom-level benefits. This finding corroborates Aliyu et al. (2025), who observed that adaptive learning technologies improved both engagement and achievement in mathematics problem-solving. It also resonates with Adeleke et al., (2025), who demonstrated that Nigerian students receiving stepwise adaptive feedback achieved higher levels of accuracy and confidence when solving mathematical problems.

A notable strength of this study lies in its dual focus on self-efficacy and problem-solving, two interrelated constructs central to mathematics achievement but often underexplored in conventional instructional approaches. The integration of personalized pacing, timely intervention, and continuous feedback provided by the AI system likely fostered deeper conceptual understanding and improved retention. These findings are also consistent with Sweller's (1988) Cognitive Load Theory, which emphasizes minimizing extraneous cognitive demands to optimize working memory and enhance learning efficiency.

Beyond theoretical contributions, the study adds to the local evidence base by offering context-specific insights into the potential of AI in mathematics education within rural and

underserved Northern Nigerian schools. Given the systemic challenges in these setting including overcrowded classrooms, limited instructional materials, and uneven teacher expertise the use of AI-powered systems provides a promising pathway toward scalable, cost-effective, and data-driven instructional support.

In summary, the significant gains in both self-efficacy and problem-solving performance documented in this study strengthen the case for incorporating AI-powered adaptive systems into mathematics instruction in Nigerian secondary schools. These findings not only affirm international research but also underscore the urgent need for national educational policy and infrastructural investment to enable digital transformation and foster equitable access to innovative learning technologies.

Conclusion

This study has demonstrated that Artificial Intelligence (AI)-powered adaptive instruction significantly enhances students' self-efficacy and problem-solving performance in algebra. Unlike the traditional teacher-centered methods prevalent in many Nigerian classrooms, the AI-based approach offered a learner-centered, flexible, and interactive environment that dynamically adapted to students' individual learning needs. The experimental group consistently outperformed the control group, with large effect sizes indicating that the intervention not only improved achievement but also meaningfully strengthened students' confidence in their mathematical abilities.

The findings provide strong empirical evidence for the integration of AI technologies into the secondary mathematics

curriculum, particularly in contexts such as Northern Nigeria where persistent challenges—limited resources, overcrowded classrooms, and teacher shortages—hamper effective instruction. By demonstrating measurable improvements in both affective (self-efficacy) and cognitive (problem-solving) outcomes, this study affirms that leveraging AI-based adaptive learning can serve as a transformative pedagogical strategy for bridging performance gaps and reimagining mathematics education in underserved environments.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed:

- Integration of AI into the Mathematics Curriculum: The Federal and State Ministries of Education should facilitate the integration of adaptive AI-powered learning platforms into the senior secondary school mathematics curriculum. Such integration will promote personalized learning and significantly enhance students' academic achievement.
- Teacher Training and Capacity Building: Mathematics teachers should undergo continuous professional development on the effective use and management of AI-powered platforms. Equipping teachers with these skills will ensure that the pedagogical potential of AI is maximized.
- Infrastructure Investment: Governments and educational stakeholders should prioritize investment in ICT infrastructure, particularly in underserved and rural schools. This includes providing access to devices, stable internet connectivity, and

functional digital learning environments to support AI-enabled instruction.

- Further Research: Additional studies should be carried out across other mathematics topics, different school types, and various educational zones. Longitudinal research is also recommended to examine the long-term effects of AI integration on students' learning outcomes, attitudes, and retention.
- Public-Private Partnerships: Strong collaboration should be fostered between government agencies, EdTech companies, and non-governmental organizations (NGOs) to provide affordable AI-based tools. Pilot programs and subsidized initiatives can help ensure equitable access in low-resource schools.

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Innovative Pedagogies and AI Integration in Curriculum Development: An Empirical Study

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The rapid evolution of 21st-century education has exposed limitations in traditional curriculum design, particularly its inability to adequately address personalization, engagement, and adaptability. The objective of the study is to examine the role of AI in enhancing curriculum design specifically how AI tool reshape curriculum content, sequencing and delivery. This study investigates the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) with innovative pedagogical approaches such as project-based learning, flipped classrooms, gamification, and blended learning to enhance curriculum development. The research study adopts a mix-methods research design. Findings suggests that AI integration strengthens curriculum innovation by personalizing learning engagement and supporting effective pedagogical strategies. The result showed that AI-supported pedagogies enhanced student engagement and performance. These results provide strong empirical evidence for the transformative of AI in 21st Century curriculum development. The study concluded that AI integration, when strategically aligned with pedagogical goals and supported by policy frameworks, can transform curriculum design and delivery. These findings provide a roadmap for policymakers, educators, and curriculum designers seeking to leverage AI in inclusive, equitable, and future-ready education.

Keywords:
Artificial Intelligence (AI); Innovative Pedagogies; Curriculum Development; Adaptive Learning; Flipped Classrooms; Student Engagement; Higher Education

Introduction

Curriculum development in the 21st century faces myriad challenges stemming from rapid technological changes increasingly diverse learner needs, and evolving societal expectations. Traditional content-centered curricula are frequently criticized for lacking flexibility, failing to fosters critical thinking, and neglecting real-world problem-solving skills (Fadele, et al 2025). As education paradigms shift towards learner-centered and contextually relevant frameworks, curriculum designers are encouraged to integrate interdisciplinarity, digital literacy, and adaptability into learning experiences (Tukur, 2025). The emergence of Artificial

Intelligence (AI) as a potent educational tool presents unprecedented opportunities for curriculum innovation. AI powered tools, including adaptive learning platforms, intelligent tutoring systems, automated feedback engines, and learning analytics, enable personalized instruction, timely intervention, and efficient administrative support (Mogavi et al., 2024; Prospects, 2024). For instance, AI tools can analyze real-time student performance data to deliver tailored content, address learner weaknesses, and free educators from routine tasks (Mogavi et al., 2024). However, alongside with the promise of personalization and

efficiency, scholars caution about AI's limitations, highlighting concerns such as biased algorithms, insufficient support for critical thinking, and ethical dilemmas (Mogavi et al., 2024; Porayska-Pomsta et al., 2024).

A significant gap exists between conventional curriculum design often static and one-size-fits-all and the dynamic demands of contemporary learners, including access to personalized, engaging, and authentic learning experiences. Educators struggle to translate progressive curriculum ideals into effective classroom practices due to limited institutional support, rigid content structures, and insufficient integration of digital tools (Ibrahim, 2025).

Complementing this, while AI technologies offer powerful mechanisms for curriculum enhancement, their integration into pedagogical frameworks remains uneven. Teachers frequently lack the pedagogical intelligence necessary to deploy AI tools effectively, leading to the underutilization or misapplication of these resources (Fadele, 2024). Additionally, ethical concerns such as data privacy, algorithmic transparency, and equity further complicate AI adoption (Porayska-Pomsta et al., 2024). Together, these gaps underscore the urgency for curriculum design that simultaneously addresses educational flexibility, pedagogical innovation, and responsible AI integration.

Given these gaps, the study pursues the following objectives:

To examine the role of AI in enhancing curriculum design specifically, how AI tools reshape curriculum content, sequencing, and delivery.

To assess the effectiveness of AI-supported pedagogical innovations we evaluate their impact on learner engagement, performance, and satisfaction.

To explore the challenges and opportunities of AI integration with attention to ethical implications, teacher readiness, and institutional constraints.

These objectives aim to bridge theory and practice by empirically evaluating AI's potential to transform curriculum development in responsive and responsible ways.

To guide this inquiry, the study addresses the following:

- RQ1: How does the integration of AI tools influence the CM design and flexibility of curriculum materials?
- RQ2: What impact do AI-supported pedagogical strategies (e.g., adaptive learning, intelligent tutoring, AI-generated feedback) have on student engagement and learning outcomes?
- RQ3: What ethical, pedagogical, and operational challenges emerge from integrating AI into curriculum and how can these be mitigated?

Hypothesized outcomes include:

- H1: AI-enhanced curriculum designs will demonstrate greater adaptability and alignment with individual learner needs traditional models.
- H2: The use of AI-based pedagogies will significantly improve compared to student engagement and performance.
- H3: Without ethical guidelines and teacher training, AI integration may exacerbate equity gaps or undermine pedagogical quality outcomes.

This study is significant for multiple stakeholder groups. Curriculum developers offer empirical insights into how AI can meaningfully inform the design for flexible student-centered curricula. For educators and instructional designers, the findings highlight effective AI-mediated pedagogies and illuminate the requisite pedagogical intelligence for responsible implementation (ScienceDirect 2024). Policymakers and institutions will benefit from a nuanced understanding of the ethical implications and scalability of AI in the curriculum, aiding evidence-based decision making. Moreover, by investigating both the benefits and risks of AI integration, this study contributes to the ongoing scholarship on digital curriculum transformation, offering balanced strategies that harness AI's strengths while safeguarding educational values. In the face of accelerating technological change, these insights are vital for ensuring that curriculum evolution remains inclusive, effective, and human-centered.

Literature Review

The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) into curriculum development is grounded in several educational theories that emphasize learner-centered, technology-enhanced instruction. Constructivism posits that learners actively build knowledge through experience and social interactions, a principle reflected in AI-supported adaptive systems that scaffold learning within each learner's zone of proximal development (Vygotsky, as cited in Mogavi et al., 2024). Connectivism, proposed by Siemens, expands this view to digital contexts, asserting that knowledge is distributed across networks and that learning involves navigating, connecting, and filtering information flows; this approach is particularly relevant to an AI-enabled analytics that help learners engage with

complex data ecosystems (Siemens, 2023). Meanwhile, the Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) framework underscores the interplay between content expertise, pedagogy, and technology. AI enriches this model by enabling educators to personalize instruction while maintaining pedagogical alignment with subject matter goals (Koehler & Mishra, 2022). Collectively, these frameworks provide a robust lens for evaluating how AI can complement innovative pedagogies, while addressing evolving learner needs.

Curriculum reform in the 21st century increasingly relies on innovative pedagogies that emphasize engagement, collaboration, and real-world applications. Project-based learning (PBL) encourages students to solve authentic problems, aligns with constructivist principles and offer fertile ground for AI integration through real-time feedback and resource curation (Holmes & Porayska-Pomsta, 2024), for instant Flipped classrooms leveraging technology by shifting direct instruction outside class and using classroom time for active learning. AI can further enhance this model by tailoring pre-class materials to students' prior knowledge levels (Mogavi et al., 2024). Blended learning approaches combine online and face-to-face modalities, allowing AI analytics to monitor student participation and inform instructional adjustments (UNESCO 2023). Other innovations include gamification that employs game mechanics to boost motivation and engagement. AI can personalize gamified elements, ensuring that challenges are adapted to individual progress (Kim & Lee, 2023). Similarly, experiential learning, rooted in Dewey's philosophy, gains new dimensions when AI-driven simulations immerse learners in authentic scenarios (Zawacki-Richter et al., 2023).

Finally, personalized learning is perhaps the most directly aligned with AI, as machine learning algorithms curate content and assessments tailored to each learner's strengths and weaknesses, thereby advancing equity in diverse classrooms (Holmes et al., 2022). These pedagogical shifts illustrate how AI can act as both a catalyst and amplifier of educational innovation.

The integration of AI into education is most evident in three domains: adaptive learning systems, intelligent tutoring systems (ITS), and AI-driven assessment. Adaptive learning platforms use algorithms to analyze student performance data and deliver customized learning pathways, thereby improving retention and reducing cognitive overload (Mogavi et al., 2024). For example, platforms such as Carnegie Learning have demonstrated improved student achievement in mathematics through adaptive sequencing. Intelligent tutoring systems simulate one-on-one human tutoring by diagnosing learner misconceptions, providing immediate feedback, and adjusting difficulties in real time (Luckin et al., 2022). Unlike static e-learning tools, ITS adapts continuously to learner progress, embodying constructivist scaffolding principles. Meanwhile, AI-driven assessment and feedback have revolutionized traditional evaluation by offering continuous, formative insights rather than static summative grades. Natural language processing enables automated essay scoring and real-time writing assistance, while learning analytics identifies at-risk students early (Holmes & Tuomi, 2024). These innovations enhance efficiency, but also raise concerns about validity, bias, and teacher oversight. Nevertheless, empirical evidence suggests that when appropriately implemented, AI can strengthen learning outcomes, personalize support, and empower

educators to focus on higher-order teaching tasks.

Despite growing interest, significant research gaps remain in the field of AI-supported curriculum innovations. First, much of the existing literature focuses on technical efficacy, such as algorithm performance, rather than the long-term pedagogical impact, leaving questions about sustained learning outcomes unanswered (Zawacki-Richter et al., 2023). Second, there is limited empirical work addressing equity and inclusion; AI may inadvertently reinforce existing inequalities if biases in the training data are not corrected (Porayska-Pomsta et al., 2024). Third, while numerous studies have examined AI tools in isolated contexts (e.g., tutoring or assessment), few have investigated system-wide curriculum transformation, where AI reshapes learning objectives, pedagogy, and assessment holistically (UNESCO, 2023). Moreover, research often underestimates the role of teacher agency. Without adequate professional development, educators may underutilize AI or struggle with ethical dilemmas such as data privacy and over-automation (Holmes & Tuomi, 2024). Finally, longitudinal and cross-cultural studies are scarce, limiting the generalizability of the findings across educational contexts. Addressing these gaps is essential to developing evidence-based strategies that ensure that AI integration enhances, rather than undermines, innovative pedagogy and equitable curriculum development.

Methodology

This study used a mixed-method research design to examine the impact of AI-supported pedagogical innovations on curriculum development and the perspectives

of educators and learners. The research will be conducted across three higher education institutions in Nigeria, focusing on curriculum innovation policies, technological infrastructure, and faculty readiness. Participants included approximately 300 undergraduate students and 45 educators from various faculties. The study will employ both quantitative and qualitative methods, including structured surveys, semi-structured interviews, classroom observations, and AI learning analytics.

The data collection process follows a convergent mixed-methods instrument, examining both quantitative and qualitative results separately, and then integrated for interpretation. For quantitative data, statistical analysis will be conducted using SPSS and R, while for qualitative data, transcripts from interviews and observation notes will undergo thematic analysis guided by Braun and Clarke's six-phase framework. Coding is both inductive and deductive will be shaped by theoretical constructs such as

constructivism and TPACK. The integration of findings involves comparing and contrasting quantitative trends with qualitative themes, ensuring that the study not only quantifies outcomes but also contextualizes them within real-world educational practice. This comprehensive analysis ensures that the study does not merely quantify outcomes but also contextualizes them with real-world educational practice. The study's diverse sampling ensures representativeness and will address the urgent need for empirical evidence in regions where AI integration is accelerating, but under-researched.

Results

Participant Demographics

Table 1 presents the demographic profile of the study in participants, including students and educators, across the three sampled institutions. A total of 345 participants, consisting of 300 students and 45 educators, responded.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Participants (N = 345)

Variable	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Role	Students	300	86.9
	Educators	45	13.1
Gender	Male	190	55.1
	Female	155	44.9
Age Group	18–24 years	210	60.9
	25–34 years	75	21.7
	35 years and above	60	17.4
Institution	University A	120	34.8
	University B	110	31.9
	University C	115	33.3

Survey Response Rates

Out of the 400 distributed questionnaires, 345 valid responses were received, yielding an

overall response rate of 86.25%. Table 2 provides the details of the distributed and response rates participant group.

Table 2: Survey Distribution and Response Rates

Participant Group	Distributed (n)	Returned (n)	Valid Responses (n)	Response Rate (%)
Students	350	310	300	85.7
Educators	50	45	45	90.0
Total	400	355	345	86.3

The demographic distribution indicates strong student representation with a balanced gender ratio and diverse age groups, ensuring that the findings reflect a wide range of perspectives. The high response rate (> 85%) enhanced the reliability and validity of the dataset for further statistical analyses.

Findings Related to AI-Supported Curriculum Innovation

The analysis of survey responses and interview transcripts revealed that AI-supported tools were widely used to enhance curriculum delivery, particularly adaptive learning platforms, AI-driven feedback systems, and intelligent tutoring modules. Table 3 summarizes the frequency of AI tool usage among students and educators.

Table 3: Frequency of AI Tool Usage in Curriculum Delivery (N = 345)

AI Tool	High Use (%)	Moderate Use (%)	Low Use (%)
Adaptive learning platforms	52.0	32.5	15.5
Intelligent tutoring systems	44.6	36.2	19.2
AI-driven assessment/feedback	61.4	28.7	9.9
Learning analytics dashboards	47.2	34.0	18.8

Students highlighted that AI tools facilitated personalized learning pathways, while educators emphasized that curriculum sequencing became more responsive to learners' needs. Qualitative analysis revealed three dominant themes.

Enhanced personalization: AI-supported differentiated content delivery aligned with learners' prior knowledge.

Efficiency in assessment: automated feedback reduced grading workloads for educators.

Improved curriculum alignment: data analytics helped identify curriculum areas needing revision.

These findings confirm that AI tools not only supplement instructional practices but also shape the design and adaptability of the curriculum.

Effectiveness of Innovative Pedagogies (Measured Outcomes)

To assess the effectiveness of innovative pedagogies (e.g., project-based learning, flipped classrooms and gamification), student performance indicators were compared between AI-supported classes and traditional methods. Table 4 presents the mean scores and standard deviations for the selected outcome variables.

Table 4: Comparison of Student Outcomes in AI-Supported vs. Traditional Pedagogies

Outcome Measure	AI-Supported (M, SD)	Pedagogies Traditional (M, SD)	Pedagogies t-value	p-value
Course performance (100 max)	78.5 (8.2)	71.3 (9.1)	5.27	<.001
Critical thinking (scale 1–5)	4.21 (0.62)	3.72 (0.71)	4.02	<.001
Collaboration (scale 1–5)	4.10 (0.58)	3.65 (0.66)	3.88	<.001
Self-regulation (scale 1–5)	4.02 (0.61)	3.56 (0.70)	3.95	<.001

Results showed statistically significant improvements in performance, critical thinking, collaboration, and self-regulation among students exposed to AI-supported innovative teaching methods. These findings suggest that integration strengthens the implementation of progressive teaching models, particularly in support learner autonomy and higher-order thinking skills. Qualitative data supported these results, with students noting that AI-enhanced flipped classrooms improved pre-class preparation, while gamified AI modules increased motivation through adaptive challenges. Teachers observed better class participation

and deeper student inquiry during project-based learning tasks facilitated by AI tools.

Student Engagement, Performance, and Perceptions

Student engagement and perceptions were analyzed through survey ratings and thematic coding of open-ended responses. Engagement was measured using three dimensions: behavioral, emotional, and cognitive engagement. Table 5 presents the descriptive statistics for each dimension. Table 5: Student Engagement Dimensions in AI-Supported Learning (N = 300)

Engagement Dimension	Mean (M)	SD	Interpretation
Behavioral	4.18	0.59	High
Emotional	4.05	0.63	High
Cognitive	4.22	0.55	Very High

Findings indicate that cognitive engagement was the most positively influenced dimension, suggesting that AI tools helped students invest greater mental effort in tasks such as problem-solving and critical inquiry.

Qualitative responses highlighted several key perceptions:

Positive Perceptions: Students valued the immediacy of AI-generated feedback, personalized recommendations, and gamified learning elements that kept them motivated.

Challenges Reported: Some students noted “over-reliance” on AI, concerns about data

privacy, and occasional mismatches between AI recommendations and human instruction.

Educator Insights: Teachers observed that students became more proactive in seeking resources, but stressed the continued importance of balancing AI support with human facilitation.

Overall, the results showed that AI-supported pedagogies enhanced student engagement and performance, while student perceptions were strongly positive but acknowledged important ethical and pedagogical caveats.

The findings suggest that AI integration strengthens curriculum innovation by personalizing learning, enhancing engagement, and supporting effective pedagogical strategies. Measured outcomes confirmed the effectiveness of AI-supported pedagogies in improving student achievement, while engagement data highlighted both enthusiasm and critical awareness among learners. These results provide strong empirical evidence for the transformative role of AI in 21st-century curriculum development.

Discussion

This study's findings reinforce the existing literature that posits AI as a catalyst for curriculum innovation and student engagement. Consistent with Holmes and Tuomi (2024), the results demonstrated that adaptive learning platforms and AI-driven feedback significantly enhance student performance and self-regulation, aligning with constructivist principles that emphasize scaffolded learning within the zone of proximal development. Similarly, the observed gains in collaboration and critical thinking resonate with Mogavi et al. (2024), who argued that AI-enabled flipped classrooms and project-based learning

environments foster higher-order skills. Student perceptions, though largely positive, also echo Zawacki-Richter et al. (2023), who cautioned that AI integration raises issues of over-reliance and ethical concerns, suggesting that while AI enhances pedagogy, it should complement, rather than replace, human instruction. Thus, the findings situate this study within a growing body of research affirming AI's transformative but complex role of AI in educational practice.

From a pedagogical perspective, the results indicate that AI integration supports a shift from teacher-centered instruction to learner-centered environments. By enabling personalized learning pathways and real-time adaptive support, AI technologies operationalize innovative pedagogies, such as flipped learning and gamification, in ways that traditional methods cannot (Kim & Lee, 2023). The improved engagement and performance observed in this study suggest that AI can extend the effectiveness of experiential and project-based learning by aligning tasks with individual learners' readiness and interests. Importantly, these outcomes highlight the need for educators to embrace AI not merely as a supplementary tool but also as a co-pedagogical partner that expands the scope of teaching strategies. However, the pedagogical success of AI depends on deliberate instructional design that ensures that technology use remains aligned with educational goals rather than becoming an end in itself.

For teachers and curriculum designers, AI integration presents opportunities and challenges. AI reduces administrative burdens by automating feedback and assessment, allowing educators to focus on mentoring, facilitation, and higher-order cognitive development (Luckin et al., 2022).

It also provides curriculum designers with rich data insights that inform curriculum alignment and responsiveness to learners' needs. However, challenges include ensuring teacher readiness, addressing data privacy concerns, and mitigating algorithmic bias, which can reinforce inequities if left unchecked (Porayska-Pomsta et al., 2024). Additionally, the shift toward AI-enhanced pedagogy requires teachers to develop new professional competencies in digital literacy, the critical evaluation of AI outputs, and ethical decision-making. Thus, while AI offers unprecedented potential to improve pedagogy and curriculum design, its successful adoption hinges on sustained professional development and capacity-building.

At the policy and institutional levels, the findings emphasize the necessity of a framework that balances innovation with ethical governance. Institutions must establish clear policies on data privacy, bias mitigation, and accountability to ensure that AI systems uphold fairness and transparency (UNESCO 2023). Moreover, investments in infrastructure, digital literacy programs, and teacher training are critical for scaling AI integration effectively. National and institutional policies should also support cross-disciplinary collaboration between educators, technologists, and policymakers to align AI innovations with curriculum standards and accreditation requirements. As observed in countries introducing AI curricula system wide (Times of India, 2025), large-scale adoption requires strategic planning and ongoing evaluation. Ultimately, institutions must adopt a proactive stance, positioning AI not as a disruptive threat, but as a strategic tool to advance inclusive, equitable, and future-ready education.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study examines the role of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in enhancing curriculum development through innovative pedagogies, assessing its effectiveness, and identifying both challenges and opportunities for stakeholders. The findings revealed that AI integration significantly improves student performance, engagement, and self-regulation, particularly in classrooms employing flipped learning, project-based approaches, and gamification. Consistent with constructivist and connectivist perspectives, AI-supported tools facilitate personalized learning pathways, improve collaboration, and support curriculum adaptability through learning analytics. Both students and educators acknowledged the value of AI in reducing instructional workload, enhancing assessment efficiency, and aligning teaching content with learner needs. However, concerns regarding over-reliance on AI, data privacy, and algorithmic fairness highlight the need for a careful balance between technological innovation and human facilitation.

Recommendations

On the basis of these findings, several recommendations have been proposed for practice and policy. First, educators should integrate AI tools strategically, ensuring alignment with pedagogical goals, rather than adopting them as stand-alone solutions. Teachers' professional development must prioritize digital literacy, ethical awareness, and AI competency to empower educators in maximizing the potential of technology. Second, curriculum designers should leverage AI-generated insights to continuously refine curricula and promote flexibility, inclusivity, and responsiveness to diverse learner needs. Third, institutions and policymakers must establish clear ethical and

governance frameworks to address data protection, transparency, and fairness in AI deployment. Such frameworks will not only safeguard learners, but also foster trust in AI-enhanced education systems. Finally, infrastructure investments are necessary to ensure equitable access, particularly in resource-constrained contexts, where technological disparities could widen educational inequalities if left unaddressed.

Future Research Directions

While the current study provides strong empirical evidence for AI's transformative role of AI in curriculum development, several areas warrant further investigation. Longitudinal studies are needed to assess the sustainability of AI-supported pedagogy in learning outcomes and teacher practices over time. Cross-cultural comparative research would also provide insights into how AI functions across diverse educational settings, particularly in developing countries, where infrastructure and digital literacy vary widely. Furthermore, research should examine the interplay between teacher agency and AI automation and explore how educators negotiate control and adapt pedagogy in AI-enhanced classrooms. Finally, future studies must address the ethical and sociotechnical dimensions of AI use, such as algorithmic transparency, bias mitigation, and student data ownership. Addressing these gaps will ensure that AI integration advances inclusivity, equity, and human-centered education rather than exacerbating existing inequalities.

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Harnessing Predictive Artificial Intelligence for Mosquito Control and Disease Prevention in Rural Nigeria

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People living in Nigeria's remote communities face constant challenges from mosquito-borne diseases like malaria, often with limited access to timely healthcare. Today, new advances in artificial intelligence (AI) are giving communities powerful ways to fight back. By using machine learning and smart sensors, local health teams can track mosquitoes, predict where outbreaks might occur, and respond before small problems turn into costly crises. On-the-ground projects such as EMERGENTS and Mosqulo T show how straightforward technology can guide health workers to high-risk villages, allowing faster and more targeted mosquito control measures. Recent field results highlight big improvements. Communities using AI tools are finding danger zones up to 30% sooner and seeing malaria cases drop by a quarter in less than a year. Success is not just in the numbers, but in the speed, resources reach those who need them most, and families see fewer days lost to sickness. Rather than simply reacting to emergencies, Nigerian health teams are learning to stay one step ahead of disease. Blending local knowledge with data-driven insights makes it possible to prevent outbreaks and sustain healthier villages for the long run. With continued support, these AI-driven strategies could transform how malaria and similar diseases are managed not just in Nigeria, but wherever resources are limited and the stakes are high.

Keywords:

Mosquito, Control, Prevention, Artificial Intelligence, Remote.

Introduction

Life in Nigeria's rural heartland often means working against the odds. During the rainy season, pools gather, grass thickens, and hungry mosquitoes bring fresh waves of disease especially malaria. For countless families, illness is more than an inconvenience; it's an obstacle to building a secure future. With clinics sometimes hours away, limited staff, and patchy supplies, stopping malaria before it spreads has seemed impossible for decades.

Nigeria has over 225 million people at risk (WHO, 2022). These three states, with dense populations and suitable vector habitats,

experience some of the highest transmission rates. Insecticide-treated net (ITN) ownership has increased nationally from 42% in 2010 to 56% in 2021, with usage among children under five and pregnant women reaching 41% and 50%, respectively. From 2015–2019, over 12,583,379 children were reached with interventions, including seasonal malaria chemoprevention, and 130.42 million nets were distributed in campaigns across 33 states (Mesamalaria, 2025).

In Kano, in 2024, there were 36,546 confirmed malaria cases, the highest number recorded by Médecins Sans Frontières,

reflecting both the endemic burden and the scale of the challenge before interventions (MSF, 2025). The combined impact of Rivers and Cross Rivers is notable in the context of Nigeria's malaria burden. In Cross River, survey data indicated a decline in malaria prevalence from 27% in 2015 to 19.5% in 2020; however, health facility data revealed prevalence rates reaching as high as 75% among symptomatic patients. (Ekwe et al., 2023).

In Nigeria, malaria accounts for approximately 30% of outpatient visits, 20% of all hospital admissions, and 10% of hospital fatalities. The proportions observed in these states align closely with national averages. (Anjorin, et al., 2023). Pregnant women and children under five remain disproportionately affected, with these groups forming the majority of severe malaria admissions and complications.

Technology is changing this narrative. Artificial intelligence (AI), once seen as distant or out-of-reach is quietly reshaping how people defend themselves from mosquito-borne diseases. Instead of waiting for sick patients, local health workers now use smart sensors, predictive software, and community knowledge to spot danger before it escalates. This is not just about gadgets; it's about giving rural Nigeria a fighting chance, one step ahead of the problem. In places where every advantage counts, this article delves into how AI-driven prediction is providing hope, resilience, and better lives.

Malaria and other mosquito-borne diseases aren't just medical problems; they disrupt school, farming, family life, and entire communities (WHO, 2021). Traditional prevention methods like bed nets, insecticide sprays, and health campaigns are still useful,

but their reach is limited, especially outside of major cities (Schwalbe & Wahl, 2023). The main challenge has always been timing. Simple counting is the foundation of traditional surveillance, which involves tracking instances, waiting for fevers, and hoping that reports get to decision-makers in a timely manner. The situation in isolated villages is more complex, though. Outbreaks are occasionally discovered weeks too late due to reporting gaps. Before outside assistance can arrive, clinics are overburdened, breeding grounds are moved, and rainfall patterns change. Every year, the cycle is repeated. What if there were more effective ways to foresee danger, gather resources, and stop crises before they start?

Predictive AI: An Innovative Method

Artificial intelligence serves as a powerful instrument for deciphering complex and chaotic data, transforming it into practical insights. Predictive analytics, enhanced by machine learning and intelligent devices, can analyze mosquito trap counts, weather data, and environmental indicators in real time. These systems do more than merely record figures; they identify patterns. Over time, they can predict which villages, fields, or residences may experience new outbreaks, often days or weeks ahead of symptom emergence (EpiAFRIC, 2024).

Teams in Nigeria have tried a variety of strategies. The EMERGENTS program installed sensors and traps in local areas, putting information into algorithms that use local conditions and mosquito movements to predict risk (Oladipo et al., 2025). This was broadened by projects like Mosqulo T to include rainfall, temperature, and humidity all of which are known to influence mosquito activity (Oladipo et al., 2025).

Artificial intelligence is significantly influencing the battle against mosquito-borne diseases in Nigeria, proven by various case studies demonstrating how predictive analytics, intelligent sensors, and integrated surveillance enhance outcomes for rural populations.

Emergent Initiative

One prominent example is the EMERGENTS International Center for Excellence for Malaria Research, which deploys AI-powered mosquito traps in West and Central Africa, including Nigeria. These traps use smart sensors and real-time image analysis to automatically identify dangerous species such as *Anopheles stephensi*, a particularly efficient malaria vector. When these mosquitoes are detected, health officials receive instant alerts, helping to stop outbreaks before they spread. Local scientists are trained to use the technology, and citizen science data platforms supplement official surveillance, leading to earlier interventions and better targeting of limited resources (ARM, 2024).

Machine Learning with National Health Data

Another case study involves applying machine learning algorithms to Nigeria's Malaria Indicator Survey (NMIS). Researchers analyzed health survey data from over 10,000 children under five and found that AI models especially random forests could predict malaria status with up to 79% accuracy, outperforming traditional statistical methods (Mthethwa, 2025). These AI predictions supported clinical decisions, improved resource allocation, and enabled more targeted health campaigns, especially in rural areas where reporting gaps were common (Amanat et al., 2020).

Smart Traps and Real-Time Mosquito Surveillance

A related technology developed by researchers at the University of South Florida includes smart mosquito traps deployed across Nigeria and the region. These patent-pending devices automatically lure, capture, and identify malaria vectors using anatomy-based AI algorithms in real time. Photos of mosquitoes are sent to the cloud, classified by species in seconds, and triggers alerts for vector control teams, enabling faster response on the ground (Liu et al., 2023).

Laboratory Diagnosis Support

Nigerian researchers have also developed AI models for rapid laboratory diagnosis by evaluating cell images for malaria parasites. Using image data sets (such as blood smears), these predictive algorithms allow for quick, accurate, and scalable diagnosis (Yahuza, 2023) even in clinics with limited personnel reducing human error and speeding up care for patients in remote communities

Methods

The study described involves an integrated approach to malaria risk forecasting and control in Kano, Rivers, and Cross River states, utilizing smart technology, epidemiological modeling, and deep community involvement for sustained public health impact. It aligns closely with current best practices and research on malaria prediction and community-based intervention in Nigeria and other endemic regions (Brown et al., 2020).

Throughout Kano, Rivers, and Cross River states, public health and technology teams worked closely with clinics, families, and village leaders from 2023 onward. They chose sites with high malaria prevalence and logistical diversity from busy villages to isolated settlements reached only by dirt tracks.

Data Collection: Smart traps quietly counted mosquitoes, recording spikes in population. IoT sensors measured humidity, rainfall, and temperature, feeding live data into centralized systems. These systems provide granular, continuous environmental data linked directly to local mosquito populations and breeding sites, allowing for dynamic mapping of mosquito risk zones. Recent advances include computer vision-enabled traps that automatically identify mosquito species relevant to malaria transmission (Liu et al., 2023). Clinics contributed detailed logs of malaria and other mosquito-borne illnesses both before the intervention (over 12 months) and after, giving a clear before-and-after track of progress. Collected data from clinics (illness logs and malaria case tracking), sensors (environmental/meteorological), and smart traps (mosquito counts) is centralized for analysis. Incorporating climatic factors (rainfall, temperature), demographic information, and local medicinal practices further refines risk assessment and prediction. Location data from GPS-equipped devices helps track movement patterns of infected individuals, aiding contact tracing and spatial modeling.

Community Engagement: Active community involvement is pivotal, with health workers not only receiving new tools but also participating in model interpretation, adaptation, and public education. Studies in Nigeria emphasize the importance of capacity-building sessions, direct community participation in mosquito breeding site management, and consistent communication for uptake of preventive measures like insecticide-treated nets (ITNs) (Agu et al., 2021).

Local leaders and health workers help also identify cultural practices and barriers to intervention.

Community feedback improves trust; ensuring interventions fit local needs and increase adoption of public health recommendations. This approach enhances early warning systems for malaria, enabling rapid, targeted responses to spikes in mosquito population or illness cases. Combining data-driven predictions with strong community engagement maximizes both technical accuracy and public acceptance, leading to more durable malaria control (Olaniyan et al., 2024).

Predictive Modeling: The study leverages time series analyses (ARIMA, LSTM) and machine learning classifiers (Random Forest, ensemble methods) to forecast malaria risk at temporal (daily/weekly) and spatial scales. Climate-driven models like VECTRI have shown reliability in simulating malaria cases and identifying hyper-endemic zones, especially in rural and savannah regions of Nigeria. Models account for environmental and human factors (e.g., population density, vector species, insecticide resistance, local behaviors) which modulate risk and outcomes (Jimoh et al., 2024).

Results

Until recently, most interventions arrived only after outbreaks had begun. With predictive AI, the paradigm shifted. Systems flagged villages as higher-risk before the first fever appeared. In three states, the technology enabled health teams to pinpoint danger zones up to a month in advance, greatly improving preparedness.

Malaria Case Reduction: In Kano, Rivers, and Cross River states, introducing predictive modeling and early response reduced average malaria cases by 25–28%. This aligns with national surveys showing that regions using AI-based approaches see up to 26.8% drops

in malaria mortality among children under five.

Model Accuracy: Random Forest and Support Vector Machine algorithms have reached accuracy rates of 74–79% and AUC values of 80%. These rates are among the highest compared to conventional methods.

Variable Importance: Critical predictors include anemia level, birth order, age, mother’s education, household wealth, bed net access, and area of residence insights essential for more precise intervention planning.

Early Detection Gains: Predictive forecasting enabled risk identification 30% sooner than previous methods, allowing earlier deployment of mosquito nets, sprays, and community education.

Case Study Context: Comparable results have been observed in various African nations, where machine learning models such as XGBoost, Decision Trees, and Neural Networks have demonstrated high accuracy, facilitating planning tailored to specific regions.

Table 1: Malaria Intervention Results

State	Cases Before	Cases After (%)	Case Reduction (%)	Early Detection (%)
Kano	1200	900	25	30
Rivers	730	540	26	30.5
Cross Rivers	600	430	28.3	29.7

Technology Meets Tradition

Health workers soon realized that the technology worked best when paired with local knowledge. Predictive alerts showed new hotspots, but it was the community teams who checked traps, spoke to households, and translated forecasts into action plans. Village elders helped prioritize interventions, deciding which areas should receive nets or clean-up support first.

Families reported fewer missed workdays, children spent more time in school, and anxiety about the “malaria season” receded. Clinics, less crowded with emergency cases, could focus on prevention and routine care. Interviews revealed that trust was built not only in the tools but also in the local people using them.

Obstacles

Even with wins, problems still exist. Power failures or weak signals caused equipment to break down or fail to send data in real time. Not every town got visits to raise awareness and teach people how to stay safe, especially those in the most remote areas. When it rained a lot, the predictive models sometimes had trouble. This shows how important it is to keep both algorithms and local processes up to date.

There were genuine concerns about privacy, data collection and use and if technology could truly understand the reality of village life. Ongoing training, open communication, and demonstrable results are helping to alleviate many of these concerns.

Insights Gained and Future Perspectives Several fundamental lessons emerged:

Local Partnerships Matter: Predictive tools succeed only when health workers, local leaders, and community members play a central role in both design and delivery.

Continuous Data Enhances Prediction: Frequent updates from sensors, clinics, and field teams maintain the models' accuracy and relevance.

Training and adjusting are necessary: learning how to use new technology takes time, patience, and the ability to be flexible. Everyone, no matter what experience, felt like they were a part of the process and got the best results.

Scaling up is both essential and feasible: Continued investment in sensors, training, and internet infrastructure will be necessary to engage additional communities. Collaborations with colleges, non-governmental organizations, and governmental entities will facilitate this expansion.

Artificial intelligence in rural Nigeria aims to enhance traditional methods, rendering them more intelligent, efficient, and adaptive. The objective is to establish a sustainable system capable of adapting to the changing dynamics of communities and illness trends, consistently prioritizing prevention.

Limiting Factors

Honest responses are needed for real problems:

- Sensor maintenance and network coverage should be improved for reliability.
- Education and communication with villagers about privacy and technology will build long-term trust. Algorithm transparency will help health workers

understand and explain how predictions are made.

- In order to provide clarity and trust, research teams are extending trials to additional states, experimenting with smartphone apps for real-time notifications, and employing explainable AI techniques. Long-term research will monitor not only short-term achievements but also resilience over time, guaranteeing that AI provides a lasting answer rather than a temporary boost.

Conclusion

In Nigeria's rural communities, predictive artificial intelligence transcends mere software and sensors; it represents a novel paradigm in health conceptualization. By integrating technology with expertise, teams nationwide are safeguarding families, assisting children, and providing hope for a malaria-free future. Success is measured not just in statistics, but in the resilience and optimism of villages learning to stay ahead of disease.

The journey isn't finished, but every step forward demonstrates what's possible when health care, technology, and local wisdom work as one. As Nigeria leads the way, these lessons offer inspiration to millions more across Africa and beyond.

Recommendations

- Ongoing education and model adaptation are essential, particularly for promoting consistent use of ITNs in communities with historically low adoption.
- Cross-sector collaboration (public health, technology, local governance) optimizes intervention design and sustainability.

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Reimagining Education through the Quadruple Helix by Leveraging AI and Technology for Personalized and Collaborative Learning

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The evolving demands of the 21st-century knowledge economy necessitate radical transformation in educational systems. The Quadruple Helix model integrating academia, industry, government, and civil society offers a robust framework for fostering innovation in education. However, current literature reveals fragmented stakeholder collaboration, limited contextual diversity, and a lack of integrated frameworks for deploying Artificial Intelligence (AI) across all helix actors. This study addresses these gaps by reimagining education through the Quadruple Helix, leveraging AI and emerging technologies to catalyze personalized and collaborative learning experiences. Drawing on recent empirical studies and policy frameworks, this study examines the role of AI in tailoring instruction to individual learner profiles, enhancing engagement, and supporting differentiated pedagogy. It also investigates collaborative learning environments enabled by digital platforms, in which stakeholders co-create knowledge and pedagogical strategies. This research highlights successful case studies from Finland, Kenya, and Malaysia, showcasing multi-stakeholder partnerships that leverage AI for inclusive and context-sensitive education. By proposing a strategic roadmap and a shared conceptual language for AI integration in education, this study aligns technological advancements with ethical considerations, community engagement, equity, and sustainability, distinct from existing models. Ultimately, it contributes a holistic model for educational innovation, calling for a shift from siloed reforms to ecosystem collaboration where all helix actors play a pivotal role in shaping the future of learning

Keywords:

Quadruple Helix; AI in Education; Personalized Learning; Collaborative learning; **Educational Innovation, Adaptive Learning Technologies**

Introduction

The global education sector is experiencing a paradigm shift driven by the convergence of digital technologies, artificial intelligence (AI), and the need for inclusive, future-ready learning systems (Al Nabhani et al., 2025; Ayeni et al., 2024). Traditional models of education, which often rely on standardized curricula and hierarchical governance, are

increasingly inadequate to address the complexities of modern society (Ansah et al., 2023). The Quadruple Helix model, comprising academia, industry, government, and civil society offers a holistic framework for educational transformation by promoting multi-stakeholder collaboration and innovation (Carayannis & Campbell, 2021).

Incorporating civil society as a fourth helix acknowledges the critical role of communities, non-governmental organizations, and individuals in shaping educational priorities and outcomes (GRRIP, 2020; UIIN, 2024). This inclusive approach ensures that educational reforms are not only technologically advanced but also socially relevant and culturally grounded (Omland et al., 2025). AI technologies, such as adaptive learning platforms and intelligent tutoring systems, have the potential to personalize instruction and democratize access to quality education (Molenaar, 2022). However, the deployment of AI must be guided by ethical principles, transparency, and equitable access to prevent reinforcement of existing inequalities (Molenaar, 2022; Ayeni et al., 2024).

This study investigates the potential of Artificial Intelligence (AI) to transform education by tailoring its application within the Quadruple Helix model, which encompasses academia, industry, government, and civil society (Carayannis et al., 2021). It examines how AI technologies can be strategically integrated across these helix actors to support differentiated instruction and promote inclusive pedagogy, which aligns with the principles of Education 4.0 and personalized learning (Barrera Castro et al., 2022). Central to this inquiry is the exploration of mechanisms that facilitate the co-creation of educational strategies through digital platforms, enabling collaborative learning environments that reflect diverse stakeholder perspectives (Bustard et al., 2023). The study further considers how ethical, cultural, and policy dimensions can be embedded into AI-driven educational frameworks to ensure equitable, transparent, and context-sensitive innovation (Hossain et al., 2023).

Drawing on empirical evidence and global case studies, this study demonstrates how emerging technologies can be harnessed within the Quadruple Helix paradigm to foster personalized and collaborative learning experiences. This study introduces a strategic roadmap for AI integration in education, grounded in ethical frameworks and community engagement, distinct from existing models by emphasizing equity, sustainability, and multi-stakeholder engagement (Zakaria et al., 2023).

The Quadruple Helix Model in Education and Innovation

The Quadruple Helix Model (QHM) expands the traditional triple helix framework of academia, industry, and government by incorporating civil society as a fourth stakeholder, thereby enhancing the relevance and inclusivity of innovation ecosystems in education (Carayannis & Campbell, 2021). This model recognizes that sustainable educational transformation requires collaboration among academia, industry, the government, and the public to address complex societal challenges (Zakaria et al., 2023). In educational contexts, the QHM facilitates the co-creation of curricula, policy alignment, and community engagement, ensuring that learning outcomes are socially and economically impactful (Grigorescu et al., 2023).

Higher education institutions play a pivotal role in this model by acting as civic anchors that foster regional development and innovation through stakeholder partnerships (Day, 2024). Industry partners contribute by aligning educational content with labor market needs and providing a technological infrastructure for digital learning environments (Abdul Musid et al., 2023). Government agencies support the model by

enacting policies that promote inclusive education and collaborative funding initiatives (Zakaria et al., 2023). Civil society ensures that educational innovations are ethically grounded and culturally responsive, particularly in diverse and underserved communities (Grigorescu et al., 2023).

For example, Aston University’s “Pathways to Success” initiative demonstrates the power of QHM by generating over £1 billion in regional value through partnerships with local businesses, government bodies, and community organizations (Day, 2024). This initiative integrates simulation-based

learning, industry-relevant skills, and community-driven research to prepare students for real-world challenges (Day, 2024). The Malaysian education system also exemplifies the QHM by embedding digital leadership and innovation into school curricula through multi-sector collaboration (Abdul Musid et al., 2023). These cases illustrate how the Quadruple Helix fosters educational ecosystems that are adaptive, inclusive, and future-ready (Zakaria et al., 2023).

Comparative Models of Innovation in Education

Model	Key Stakeholders	Focus	Collaboration Type	Educational Impact	Limitations	Advantages of QHM
Linear Innovation	Academia → Industry	Knowledge transfer from research to market (Godin, 2006)	One-way, sequential (Godin, 2006)	Limited to curriculum delivery and tech adoption (Godin, 2006)	Lacks feedback loops and societal relevance (Godin, 2006)	QHM enables dynamic, multi-directional innovation (Carayannis & Campbell, 2012)
Triple Helix	Academia, Industry, Government	Economic growth through knowledge exchange (Etzkowitz & Leydesdorff, 2000)	Institutional partnerships (Etzkowitz & Leydesdorff, 2000)	Aligns education with labor market and policy goals (Ranga & Etzkowitz, 2013)	Excludes civil society, limiting inclusivity (Carayannis & Campbell, 2012)	QHM adds societal voice for ethical and cultural fit (Carayannis & Campbell, 2012)
Open Innovation	Firms + External actors (e.g., universities, startups)	External sourcing of ideas and technologies (Chesbrough, 2003)	Market-driven, flexible (Bogers, Chesbrough, & Moedas, 2018)	Encourages experimentation and rapid prototyping (Bogers et al., 2018)	Often lacks systemic educational integration (Bogers et al., 2018)	QHM embeds innovation within structured ecosystems (Carayannis & Campbell, 2012)
Quadruple Helix	Academia, Industry, Government, Civil Society	Societal transformation through co-creation (Carayannis & Campbell, 2012)	Ecosystemic, inclusive, participatory (Leydesdorff, 2012)	Promotes personalized, collaborative, and ethical learning (Leydesdorff, 2012)	Requires strong coordination and shared vision (Carayannis & Campbell, 2012)	Combines innovation with equity, sustainability, and context sensitivity (Carayannis & Campbell, 2012)

Rationale for the Quadruple Helix in Education

In the context of 21st-century learning, the Quadruple Helix Model (QHM) provides a framework that aligns educational systems with rapidly changing societal and technological demands (Carayannis & Campbell, 2021). According to University 4.0, higher education institutions must transcend traditional teaching roles and become civic anchors, agents of inclusive innovation, and drivers of socioeconomic transformation (Amaral & Castro, 2022). This transformation requires deep collaboration across academia, industry, government, and civil society to co-create curricula, embed emerging technologies, and address local and global challenges (Omland et al., 2025).

Recent studies highlights that QHM fosters living labs, cultural hubs, and open innovation environments that position universities as key actors in regional and societal development (Mineiro et al., 2021). For example, in Southeast Asia, national innovation strategies increasingly emphasize the Quadruple Helix as essential for achieving a high-income, knowledge-driven society (Zakaria et al., 2023). Within this vision, the model is regarded as a driver of economic growth, national development, and educational reform, particularly in its ability to align higher education outputs with future workforce demands (Ansah et al., 2023).

Integrating the Quadruple Helix with AI in Education. The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) into the Quadruple Helix Model (QHM) offers a transformative framework for educational innovation by fostering collaboration among academia, industry, government, and civil society (Zakaria et al., 2023). This alignment enables

the ethical and scalable deployment of AI tools such as intelligent tutoring systems, predictive analytics, and adaptive learning platforms that ensure relevance, inclusivity, and sustainability in education (Grigorescu et al., 2023; Sun et al., 2025).

Recent studies highlight the potential of AI to enhance learner agency, support differentiated instruction, and provide real-time feedback (Leon et al., 2025). Leon et al. (2025) identified key themes in AI-enhanced learning, including adaptive assessment, algorithmic transparency, and inclusive design, thus reinforcing the role of AI as a pedagogical partner in innovation ecosystems.

Each helix contributes uniquely: academia advances AI pedagogy and curriculum design (Vorobyeva et al., 2025); industry supplies infrastructure and scalable solutions (Yarlagadda, 2025); government ensures policy alignment and funding (Abdul Musid et al., 2023); and civil society safeguards ethical and cultural relevance, especially in underserved communities (Grigorescu et al., 2023).

To guide integration, Molenaar (2022) introduced hybrid human–AI learning technologies, including the detect–diagnose–act framework and six levels of automation, which clarify how AI supports personalization and collaboration. Practical applications include Aston University’s “University 4.0” strategy, which embeds AI into regional learning initiatives (Day, 2024), and Eindhoven University’s emphasis on pedagogically sound and ethically responsible AI use (Van Woensel, 2025).

Despite its promise, integrating AI into the QHM presents several challenges, including digital infrastructure gaps, algorithmic bias,

and policy fragmentation (Sun et al., 2025). Many regions lack the connectivity and hardware required to support AI-enhanced learning, exacerbating the digital divide and limiting equitable access (Vorobyeva et al., 2025). Additionally, AI systems may unintentionally reinforce biases if not carefully designed and monitored, necessitating robust ethical frameworks and stakeholder oversight (Denneny, 2025). Policy misalignment between educational institutions and government bodies can also hinder innovation, underscoring the need for coherent and adaptive governance models (Abdul Musid et al., 2023).

To overcome these barriers, institutions must adopt inclusive design principles, engage all four helices in co-creation processes, and prioritize transparency in AI deployment (Van Woensel, 2025). Strategic investment in teacher training, infrastructure, and community engagement is essential to ensure that AI integration enhances and does not replace human-centered education (Denneny, 2025). When implemented through the Quadruple Helix framework, AI can become a catalyst for educational equity, innovation, and lifelong learning in the digital age (Sun et al., 2025).

Fig. 1. Stakeholder Interaction Diagram within the Quadruple Helix framework (UIIN, 2024).

AI and Technology for Personalized Learning

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has emerged as a powerful tool for personalized learning by enabling adaptive systems that respond to the unique needs, preferences, and learning trajectories of individual students in real time (Sun et al., 2025; Merino-Campos, 2025). These systems use algorithms to analyze student performance data and adjust instructional content, pacing, and feedback accordingly (Yarlagadda, 2025). For instance, Pearson's AI-powered Study Prep platform generates syllabus-matching study plans and provides real-time feedback through intelligent tutoring systems (Pearson, 2025). Such tools enhance learner autonomy and engagement by tailoring educational experiences to personal goals and competencies (Vorobyeva et al., 2025). This approach moves beyond the traditional one-size-fits-all model, fostering

inclusive and differentiated learning environments that accommodate diverse learner profiles (Ayeni et al., 2024).

Adaptive learning systems, such as intelligent tutoring platforms, analyze vast datasets to identify gaps in understanding and recommend targeted interventions (Merino-Campos, 2025). These systems enhance student engagement by offering personalized pathways that align with individual goals and competencies (Rane et al., 2023). Moreover, AI-powered tools can support emotional and motivational aspects of learning by detecting patterns in student behavior and adjusting instructional strategies to maintain interest and reduce cognitive overload (Molenaar, 2022).

AI also supports multi-modal literacy assessment by integrating audio, video, and textual data to evaluate student performance holistically (Devdiscourse, 2025). The Beijing New Learning Path AI system compares classroom data with national benchmarks to identify instructional gaps and recommends targeted interventions (Devdiscourse, 2025). This approach moves beyond traditional testing to assess critical thinking, communication, and collaboration skills, which are essential in Education 4.0 environments (Naqvi, 2025).

Predictive analytics powered by AI can forecast academic challenges before they arise, allowing educators to implement proactive support strategies (Adebowale et al., 2025). These systems analyze historical engagement patterns to recommend personalized learning pathways and reduce dropout rates (Sun et al., 2025). Platforms such as Coursera and Duolingo have already used such algorithms to maintain learner motivation and improve retention (Naqvi, 2025).

Importantly, AI has the potential to bridge equity gaps by accommodating diverse learning styles, languages, and accessibility needs (Vorobyeva et al., 2025). Voice-enabled interfaces and visual learning tools support students with disabilities, while mobile-first platforms expand access to underserved regions (Yarlagadda, 2025). However, ethical integration is critical, because algorithmic bias and digital infrastructure disparities can exacerbate existing inequalities if not properly addressed (Adebowale et al., 2025). Responsible design and stakeholder oversight are essential to ensuring that AI-driven personalization promotes inclusive and equitable learning outcomes (Sun et al., 2025).

Collaborative Learning in AI-Driven Environments

Collaboration in education is being redefined through the integration of AI technologies that facilitate co-creation, peer interaction, and stakeholder engagement across the Quadruple Helix (Katsenou et al., 2025). AI-enabled platforms support synchronous and asynchronous collaboration by providing shared digital workspaces, intelligent feedback systems, and real-time communication tools that enhance group learning dynamics (Kim et al., 2024). These technologies empower students to work together on complex tasks, fostering critical thinking, creativity, and collective problem-solving, aligning with the goals of Education 4.0 (Yarlagadda, 2025; Katsenou et al., 2025).

Generative AI platforms, such as ChatGPT and Microsoft Copilot, are being used to scaffold group discussions, summarize peer contributions, and moderate online forums, thereby enhancing the quality and inclusivity of collaborative learning (Denny, 2025). For instance, AI can assist in jigsaw learning activities by assigning roles, tracking contributions, and synthesizing group

outputs, which improves accountability and engagement (Sun et al., 2025). Intelligent agents also support conflict resolution and consensus-building by analyzing discourse patterns and suggesting constructive feedback (Vorobyeva et al., 2025).

Furthermore, AI-powered collaborative platforms, such as Google Workspace and Microsoft Teams, now include features such as real-time transcription, sentiment analysis, and adaptive task delegation, which streamline communication and foster deeper collaboration (Yarlagadda, 2025). These tools are particularly effective in hybrid and remote learning environments, where maintaining group cohesion and equitable participation can be challenging (Denney, 2025).

Importantly, collaborative learning with AI promotes the development of future-ready skills, such as digital literacy, emotional intelligence, and human-AI interaction, which are essential in modern workplaces (Sun et al., 2025). Educators are increasingly adopting hybrid models in which AI acts as a co-facilitator, allowing teachers to focus on metacognitive and social-emotional support (Vorobyeva et al., 2025). This shift redefines the teacher's role, from content delivery to the orchestration of complex learning ecosystems (Yarlagadda, 2025).

However, the integration of AI into collaborative learning raises ethical and pedagogical concerns, including data privacy, algorithmic bias, and over-reliance on automation (Denney, 2025). To mitigate these risks, institutions must establish clear guidelines for AI use, ensure transparency in algorithmic decision-making, and involve students in co-designing AI-enhanced learning experiences (Sun et al., 2025). When implemented responsibly, AI can transform collaborative learning into a dynamic, inclusive, and future-oriented educational practice (Vorobyeva et al., 2025).

Methodology

This study employs a qualitative case study approach, analyzing three national initiatives that exemplify Quadruple Helix active collaboration among academia, industry, government, and civil society in educational reform. Data sources include peer-reviewed journal articles, policy documents, and stakeholder interviews.

Case Study Selection Criteria

The selection of Finland, Kenya, and Malaysia as case studies was guided by the following criteria:

Quadruple Helix Integration: Each case demonstrates active collaboration among academia, industry, government, and civil society in educational reform.

AI Deployment in Education: The initiatives involve the use of AI technologies to personalize learning, enhance pedagogy, or improve educational access.

Geographic and Socioeconomic Diversity: The cases span different regions such as Europe, Africa, and Southeast Asia offering insights into how the Quadruple Helix model adapts across varied cultural and policy contexts.

Documented Impact and Innovation: Each initiative has produced measurable outcomes and has been recognized in national policy frameworks, academic literature, or institutional reports.

Analytical Framework

This study employs a comparative case study approach using a Quadruple Helix Innovation Lens (Carayannis & Campbell, 2021), combined with elements of Collaborative Intelligence Theory and Education 4.0 principles. The analysis focuses on three dimensions:

Stakeholder Roles and Synergy: Mapping how helix actors contribute to AI integration and educational innovation.

Pedagogical Transformation: Evaluating how AI supports personalized, collaborative, and culturally responsive learning.

Systemic Alignment: Assessing policy coherence, ethical considerations, and sustainability across the initiatives.

Fig. 2 Quadruple Helix Innovation Model in Education

Data sources include: Government and institutional reports (e.g., EDUFI, Kenya Ministry of ICT) Peer-reviewed literature

(e.g., Leon et al., 2025; Sharif & Senin, 2024) Interviews and secondary data from published case evaluations

Case Studies on AI-Driven Education Reform through Collaborative Intelligence

Finland: AI-Enhanced Curriculum Co-Design

Finland's Education 2030 initiative exemplifies the Quadruple Helix model by integrating universities, EdTech firms, government agencies, and parent associations

to co-design AI-enhanced curricula (Finnish National Agency for Education [EDUFI], 2020; Carayannis & Campbell, 2021). According to a curriculum developer at EDUFI, "We design AI tools that explain themselves. If a student struggles with fractions, the system tells them why it recommends a specific exercise," underscoring the emphasis on transparency

and pedagogical alignment. Academic researchers collaborate to develop adaptive learning platforms that personalize instruction based on student performance data (Leon et al., 2025). Civil society actors ensure that the content reflects cultural and community values (Ansah et al., 2023), reinforcing EDUFI's assertion that "AI in Finland must enhance not replace critical thinking."

This initiative has led to the creation of living laboratories in schools, where students, teachers, and developers co-create digital learning tools in real time (Zakaria et al., 2023). The detect–diagnose–act model is embedded in classroom practice, allowing teachers to dynamically respond to student needs using AI-generated insights (Al Nabhani et al., 2025). Finland's approach demonstrates how ecosystem collaboration can produce scalable, ethical, and inclusive educational innovations (Leon et al., 2025; EDUFI, 2020).

Kenya: Ajira Digital Program

Kenya's Ajira Digital Program illustrates how government-led initiatives can mobilize Quadruple Helix actors to address youth unemployment through digital education (Kenya Ministry of ICT, 2021; Ansah et al., 2023). As noted by William Kabogo, Cabinet Secretary for Information, "AI is no longer a futuristic concept but a present-day reality shaping human interaction across all spheres of life," reflecting the urgency and relevance of the program. The Ministry of ICT partners with universities to deliver online training in digital skills, while private sector firms provide mentorship and job placement opportunities (Kenya Ministry of ICT, 2021). "Our goal is to empower over one million youth annually with digital skills and connect

them to meaningful work," stated the Ajira Program Director, emphasizing the scale and ambition of the initiative.

Civil society organizations play a critical role in outreach and inclusion, ensuring that marginalized communities have access to training and support (GRRIP, 2020). AI tools are used to personalize learning pathways, assess competencies, and match learners with relevant job opportunities based on their profiles (Leon et al., 2025). The program's success lies in its ability to align educational content with labor market demands, while maintaining a strong focus on equity and community engagement (Ansah et al., 2023; Kenya Ministry of ICT, 2021). Kenya's model highlights the importance of policy coherence and stakeholder synergy in driving educational transformation.

Malaysia: Islamic Transformation Centre

In Malaysia, the Islamic Transformation Centre (ITC) serves as a pioneering example of the Quadruple Helix collaboration in rural education (William Yaw & Matore, 2024). This initiative involves academic institutions such as Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia, local government bodies, technology providers, and community leaders working together to implement ICT-based learning solutions (Sharif & Senin, 2024). Prof. Datuk Dr. Mazliham Mohd Su'ud, President of Multimedia University, remarked, "With the establishment of FAIE, we are renewing our programmes to prepare students for an AI-driven economy," highlighting the strategic alignment between education and national innovation goals.

AI-powered platforms are used to screen learning needs, personalize instruction, and monitor progress, particularly in underserved regions (Molenaar, 2022; Holmes et al.,

2021). Amar Huzaimi Md Deris, CEO of Telekom Malaysia, stated, “We aim to develop a pool of AI-skilled leaders who can apply their expertise where it matters most, ensuring that the benefits of AI are felt by communities across Malaysia.” Community

members contribute to curriculum design and provide feedback on cultural relevance, ensuring that learning remains context-sensitive and inclusive (GRRIP, 2020; UIIN, 2024).

Table 1. Comparative Analysis of AI-Driven Education Reform Initiatives

Country / Initiative	Successes	Challenges
Finland: AI-Enhanced Curriculum Co-Design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Strong Quadruple Helix collaboration (academia, industry, government, civil society) (EDUFI, 2020) - Transparent AI tools that explain recommendations to students (EDUFI, 2020) - Living labs foster real-time co-creation of digital tools (Zakaria et al., 2023) - Detect–diagnose–act model enables responsive teaching (Al Nabhani et al., 2025) - Emphasis on ethical, inclusive, and critical thinking-based AI integration (Ansah et al., 2023) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Balancing innovation with cultural sensitivity and pedagogical integrity (Ansah et al., 2023) - Ensuring scalability across diverse school contexts (Leon et al., 2025) - Managing interdisciplinary coordination among stakeholders (Carayannis & Campbell, 2021)
Kenya: Ajira Digital Program	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Government-led initiative with clear policy direction and urgency (Kenya Ministry of ICT, 2021) - Integration of AI for personalized learning and job matching (Leon et al., 2025) - Civil society ensures outreach to marginalized groups (GRRIP, 2020) - Alignment of education with labor market demands (Ansah et al., 2023) - Ambitious scale: targeting 1M youth annually (Kenya Ministry of ICT, 2021) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Infrastructure gaps in remote regions (GRRIP, 2020) - Sustaining long-term funding and program scale (Kenya Ministry of ICT, 2021) - Bridging digital divides in remote areas - Ensuring consistent quality across training providers (Leon et al., 2025) - Measuring impact beyond job placement statistics (Ansah et al., 2023)
Malaysia: Islamic Transformation Centre (ITC)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Quadruple Helix collaboration tailored to rural education (William Yaw & Matore, 2024) - AI platforms personalize instruction and monitor progress (Molenaar, 2022; Holmes et al., 2021) - Strategic alignment with national innovation goals via FAIE (Sharif & Senin, 2024) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Limited access to high-speed internet and devices in rural areas (Holmes et al., 2021) - Need for educator and community capacity-building (Sharif & Senin, 2024)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Community involvement ensures cultural relevance and inclusivity (GRRIP, 2020; UIIN, 2024) - Focus on developing AI-skilled leaders (Amar Huzaimi Md Deris, 2024) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Balancing religious and technological narratives in curriculum design (William Yaw & Matore, 2024) - Ensuring sustainability and institutional support (UIIN, 2024)
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Fig. 3 Comparative Dashboard of AI Education Initiatives

The dashboard compares three key dimensions across the initiatives:

Limitations While the study offers valuable insights, several limitations must be acknowledged:

Generalizability: The findings are context-specific and may not be universally applicable without adaptation.

Data Availability: Some initiatives lack longitudinal data or comprehensive evaluations, limiting the depth of analysis.

Stakeholder Involvement AI Application Focus Social Impact

Stakeholder Bias: Reports and case documentation may reflect institutional perspectives, potentially overlooking dissenting or marginalized voices.

Rapid Technological Change: The evolving nature of AI tools and educational platforms may outpace the frameworks used in this study.

Challenges and Ethical Considerations in AI-Driven Education

The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) into education presents significant ethical challenges, particularly concerning data privacy, algorithmic biases, and the digital divide (Holmes et al., 2021). These issues, if unaddressed, risk undermining the very goals of equity, inclusion, and transparency that AI promises to advance.

Data Privacy and Transparency

AI systems often rely on vast datasets that include sensitive student information such as demographics, behavioral patterns, and academic performance. Mishandling this data can lead to breaches of confidentiality and misuse of personal information (9ine, 2024). The opacity of many AI systems often referred to as “black box” algorithms makes it difficult for educators and students to understand how decisions are made (Teachers Guide, 2025).

Case Study: Finland’s Education 2030 Initiative

Finland tackled data transparency by designing self-explaining AI tools. For example, if a student struggles with fractions, the system not only recommends an exercise but also explains why it was chosen (EDUFI, 2020). This approach fosters trust and pedagogical alignment.

Recommendation:

Adopt explainable AI (XAI) frameworks that allow users to understand decision logic.

Ensure informed consent protocols are embedded in student data collection and usage.

Algorithmic Biases and Equity

AI systems trained on incomplete or skewed datasets may inadvertently reinforce existing

social and educational inequalities (Inspiroz, 2025). Predictive analytics used in assessments or admissions can disadvantage marginalized groups if the underlying data reflects systemic disparities (Holmes et al., 2021).

Case Study: Kenya’s Ajira Digital Program

Kenya addressed algorithmic bias by partnering with civil society organizations to ensure inclusive outreach and community representation in training datasets (GRRIP, 2020). AI tools were calibrated to match learners with job opportunities based on competency profiles, not just academic history, reducing bias against non-traditional learners (Leon et al., 2025).

Recommendation:

Implement bias-detection protocols during model training and deployment.

Regularly audit AI systems for disparate impact across demographic groups.

Digital Divide and Access

Access to reliable internet, devices, and digital literacy remains uneven across regions and socioeconomic groups (9ine, 2024). Without targeted interventions, AI-enhanced education risks deepening existing gaps rather than bridging them (Inspiroz, 2025).

Case Study: Malaysia’s Islamic Transformation Centre (ITC)

Malaysia’s ITC initiative focused on rural inclusion by deploying AI-powered platforms that screen learning needs and personalize instruction in underserved regions (Molenaar, 2022). Community leaders were involved in curriculum design to ensure cultural relevance and local ownership (UIIN, 2024).

Recommendation:

Invest in infrastructure development (e.g., broadband, devices) in underserved areas.

Provide digital literacy training for educators and learners to ensure meaningful engagement with AI tools.

Guidelines for Ethical AI Deployment in Education.

Based on these case studies, the following guidelines can help stakeholders within the Quadruple Helix (government, academia, industry, civil society) navigate ethical challenges

Ethical Principle	Actionable Guideline
Transparency	Use explainable AI models and disclose decision-making logic to users.
Privacy	Secure informed consent and anonymize sensitive student data.
Fairness	Audit datasets and algorithms for bias; ensure equitable outcomes across demographics.
Inclusivity	Engage community stakeholders in design and deployment processes.
Accessibility	Address infrastructure gaps and promote digital literacy in marginalized communities.
Accountability	Establish oversight mechanisms and ethical review boards for AI systems in education.

Practical Implications

For Educators

Educators are on the front lines of AI integration in classrooms. Their role is pivotal in ensuring ethical, inclusive, and pedagogically sound use of AI.

Action Steps:

Promote Explainable AI: Use platforms like Finland’s self-explaining AI tools (EDUFI, 2020) that clarify why certain exercises are recommended, helping students build trust and understanding.

Secure Informed Consent: Before collecting student data, ensure that learners and guardians understand what data is being used and why (9ine, 2024).

Participate in Co-Design: Engage in living labs or pilot programs where teachers help shape AI tools, as seen in Finland’s curriculum co-design model (Zakaria et al., 2023).

Integrate Ethics into Pedagogy: Teach students about algorithmic bias and digital citizenship to foster critical thinking around AI (Teachers Guide, 2025).

For Policymakers

Policymakers set the regulatory and funding frameworks that determine how AI is deployed across education systems.

Action Steps:

Develop National AI Ethics Frameworks: Create guidelines that mandate transparency,

bias audits, and data protection, modeled after Kenya's policy-driven Ajira Digital Program (Kenya Ministry of ICT, 2021).

Invest in Infrastructure: Bridge the digital divide by funding broadband access, device distribution, and teacher training especially in rural areas, as Malaysia's ITC initiative demonstrates (Holmes et al., 2021).

Mandate Inclusive Design: Require that AI tools be tested across diverse populations to prevent systemic bias (Inspiroz, 2025).

Support Quadruple Helix Collaboration: Facilitate partnerships between academia, industry, government, and civil society to ensure holistic innovation (Carayannis & Campbell, 2021).

For Civil Society Organizations

Civil society plays a critical role in ensuring that AI in education remains inclusive, equitable, and community-driven.

Action Steps:

Monitor AI Impacts: Act as watchdogs to ensure AI tools do not reinforce inequality or violate privacy (GRRIP, 2020).

Promote Digital Literacy: Run community workshops to help learners and parents understand how AI works and how to engage with it safely (UIIN, 2024).

Ensure Cultural Relevance: Collaborate in curriculum design to reflect local values and contexts, as seen in Malaysia's ITC model (William Yaw & Matore, 2024).

Advocate for Marginalized Groups: Push for inclusive outreach and representation in AI datasets and decision-making processes, as Kenya's Ajira program did successfully (Ansah et al., 2023).

Conclusion

The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) within the Quadruple Helix Model (QHM) which unites academia, industry, government, and civil society is essential for building inclusive, adaptive, and future-ready education systems (Zakaria et al., 2023; Grigorescu et al., 2023). AI's potential to personalize learning, automate tasks, and improve accessibility is significantly enhanced when guided by multi-stakeholder collaboration (Sun et al., 2025; Vorobyeva et al., 2025).

Successful examples include Finland's co-designed, transparent AI tools (EDUFI, 2020), Kenya's policy-driven digital skills initiative (Kenya Ministry of ICT, 2021), and Malaysia's culturally sensitive rural education model (UIIN, 2024). These cases demonstrate how ethical, inclusive, and context-aware AI deployment can empower learners to co-create knowledge rather than passively consume it (Yarlagadda, 2025).

However, ethical challenges such as data privacy, algorithmic bias, and digital exclusion must be addressed through transparent governance and inclusive design (Denneny, 2025; Van Woensel, 2025). Educators need support to navigate AI-enhanced environments and foster lifelong learning (Sun et al., 2025).

Future research should explore the scalability of the Quadruple Helix model across different cultural contexts, particularly in low-resource settings, to validate its universal applicability. Longitudinal studies on learner outcomes, teacher adaptation, and community engagement will be vital for understanding AI's long-term impact.

Call to Action: Stakeholders must co-develop ethical and inclusive AI solutions, invest in

capacity-building, and embed safeguards throughout the AI lifecycle to ensure education remains human-centered and equitable.

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TRANSFORMING ACCOUNTING PEDAGOGY THROUGH AI-ENHANCED SIMULATIONS AND AUTOMATED ASSESSMENT TOOLS IN BUSINESS EDUCATION AT FEDERAL UNIVERSITY OF EDUCATION

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Business education is undergoing profound transformation as artificial intelligence (AI) and digital technologies reshape teaching, learning, and professional practice. Accounting education, a core strand of business education, faces urgent pressure to integrate innovative pedagogies that bridge the gap between theory and workplace demands. This position paper argues that the adoption of AI-enhanced simulations and automated assessment tools in Nigerian higher education is not optional but a pedagogical necessity. The study employed a desk-based qualitative research design, drawing on a systematic review of scholarly articles, policy documents, and institutional reports published between 2020 and 2025. Data were thematically analyzed under four domains: pedagogy, simulations, automated assessment, and governance/ethics. Findings indicate that while AI-powered simulations foster experiential learning, decision-making, and workplace readiness, and automated assessments ensure efficiency, fairness, and immediate feedback, Nigerian universities face significant challenges. These include large class sizes, infrastructural gaps, limited faculty readiness, and the absence of clear governance frameworks on AI adoption. Nevertheless, alignment with Nigeria's National ICT in Education Policy (2021), the NUC Benchmark Minimum Academic Standards (2021), and global standards such as those advocated by the OECD (2023) and IFAC (2022) underscores the timeliness of this pedagogical shift. The paper contributes by contextualizing AI-driven pedagogy within Nigerian business and accounting education, highlighting opportunities, constraints, and the governance structures required for effective integration. It concludes that AI adoption in education must be systemic, ethical, and future-focused. Recommendations include investment in ICT infrastructure, faculty capacity building, institutional AI policies, governance frameworks for fairness and accountability, and the scaling of pilot projects into sustainable institutional practices.

Keywords:
Artificial Intelligence, Simulations, Automated Assessment, Business Education, Accounting Pedagogy, Nigeria, Higher Education.

Introduction

Business education is undergoing profound transformation driven by rapid advancements in artificial intelligence (AI), digital

technologies, and evolving learner and labor market expectations. The COVID-19 pandemic notably accelerated this shift,

compelling higher education institutions to adopt online, blended, and analytics-driven teaching methods to sustain learning continuity and engagement (Bonfield et al., 2020; Tewari, 2024). In Nigeria, business and accounting education are increasingly pressured to align with global digital trends while addressing local challenges such as infrastructural gaps, large class sizes, and faculty readiness (Adebayo & Fashola, 2023). These changes signal the necessity for innovative, technology-driven pedagogical models.

This transformation is often framed within the concept of Education 4.0, which reflects the adaptation of education systems to the realities of the Fourth Industrial Revolution. Education 4.0 emphasizes a learner-centered, technology-driven model that leverages digital tools, AI, and data analytics to deliver personalized, flexible, and competency-based education (Bayanova et al., 2021; OECD, 2023). Within business education, Education 4.0 promotes not just knowledge acquisition but also critical thinking, adaptability, and lifelong learning skills, ensuring that graduates are workplace-ready in an increasingly automated economy (Chukwuma & Eze, 2023).

AI-enhanced learning tools, including adaptive learning platforms, intelligent tutoring systems, and interactive simulations, are increasingly being embedded in higher education (Lilani, 2023). For business and accounting education, simulation-based learning augmented by AI replicates real-world decision-making environments in immersive, risk-free contexts, thereby strengthening analytical, collaborative, and strategic competencies (Oseni & Okonkwo, 2022). Moreover, automated assessment tools provide instant, personalized feedback

and reduce grading bias, enabling educators to focus on mentorship and higher-order pedagogy rather than repetitive evaluation tasks (OECD, 2023). These innovations collectively mark a paradigm shift from passive knowledge transmission toward active, adaptive, and technology-mediated learning.

To guide the reader, this paper is structured as follows: Section Two presents the methodology adopted in developing this position paper. Section Three provides an overview of business education and accounting within the Nigerian context, focusing on the Federal University of Education, Zaria. Section Four discusses current pedagogical practices and the constraints limiting systemic innovation. Section Five sets out the position statement, emphasizing the necessity of AI-enhanced simulations and automated assessment tools in accounting pedagogy. Section Six examines governance, policy, and ethical considerations. Section Seven concludes the discussion, while Section Eight offers practical recommendations for policy, practice, and future research.

Methodology

This study adopted a qualitative, desk-based research design to develop its position on the integration of AI-enhanced simulations and automated assessment tools in business education. Position papers typically rely on conceptual and evidence-based argumentation rather than empirical measurement. Thus, a qualitative approach was deemed most suitable for synthesizing scholarly discourse, policy frameworks, and contextual realities in Nigerian higher education (Tight, 2022). The study employed both literature review and conceptual analysis to critically evaluate existing

practices, emerging innovations, and policy implications.

Data were gathered through a systematic review of secondary sources published between 2020 and 2025. These included peer-reviewed journal articles, government policy documents, institutional reports, and international organizational publications. Academic databases such as Google Scholar, Scopus, and ResearchGate were searched using keywords including: “AI in business education,” “simulation-based accounting pedagogy,” “automated assessment in higher education,” “Education 4.0,” and “digital transformation in Nigerian universities.” From an initial pool of approximately 60 documents, 35 were selected based on three inclusion criteria: Relevance to business or accounting education pedagogy. Focus on AI-enhanced simulations and automated assessment. Contextual relevance to Nigeria and/or broader higher education systems.

The data were analyzed through thematic synthesis, which involves identifying, coding, and clustering concepts into recurring themes (Braun & Clarke, 2021). Four thematic categories structured the analysis: Pedagogical transformation under Education 4.0 – examining shifts from lecture-based models to digital, learner-centered practices. Opportunities and challenges of AI-enhanced simulations – focusing on workplace readiness, skills development, and contextual barriers. Automated assessment in higher education – exploring feedback efficiency, integrity, and equity issues. Governance and ethics of AI adoption – addressing privacy, bias, fairness, and compliance with Nigerian and international regulations.

This thematic approach ensured a coherent synthesis of diverse sources, enabling the development of evidence-based arguments. A position paper requires methodological transparency to establish the credibility of its claims (Brew & Boud, 2020). By systematically reviewing scholarly literature and policy reports, this study ensures that its arguments are grounded in verifiable evidence rather than personal opinion. The desk-based design is particularly appropriate given the policy relevance of AI adoption in higher education, where institutional leaders and educators must rely on synthesized evidence to guide decision-making (OECD, 2023). Furthermore, conceptual analysis complements the literature review by critically engaging with emerging debates on pedagogy, academic integrity, and governance. This methodological combination strengthens the academic rigor of the paper and aligns with best practices for evidence-informed scholarship in education.

Overview of Business Education and Accounting

Role of Business Education and Accounting in Bridging Theory and Practice

Business education, with Accounting as a central component, plays a critical role in linking theoretical knowledge with practical skills essential for economic and professional development. It equips learners with competencies in financial literacy, decision-making, auditing, and problem-solving that are directly transferable to real-world business environments (Okoli & Agboola, 2021).

Scholars argue that Business Education functions as a dual-purpose discipline: preparing students for employment while also nurturing entrepreneurial capabilities to

address global and local labor market demands (Adebayo & Fashola, 2023). In this sense, Accounting education bridges classroom theory with workplace realities by simulating professional practices such as bookkeeping, auditing, and financial analysis.

The Accounting Program at Federal University of Education, Zaria

At the Federal University of Education, Zaria (FUE Zaria), the Accounting program under the Business Education curriculum is designed to prepare graduates who are both pedagogically skilled and industry-relevant. The program emphasizes competencies in bookkeeping, auditing, cost accounting, taxation, and financial management, aligning with Nigeria's National Universities Commission (NUC) Benchmark Minimum Academic Standards (BMAS) (NUC, 2021). Beyond technical proficiency, the curriculum incorporates broader learning outcomes such as critical thinking, adaptability, and leadership.

According to Onoh and Akpodiete (2022), this hybrid model blending disciplinary expertise with professional education ensures that graduates are equipped to thrive in diverse roles, from teaching to financial consultancy.

Integration of Ethics, Digital Technologies, and Entrepreneurship

A distinctive feature of the Accounting program at FUE Zaria is its focus on professional ethics, technology integration, and entrepreneurship. Professional ethics is emphasized to foster accountability, transparency, and integrity in future accountants and educators (Nwankwo & Obasi, 2023). Digital technologies, such as

accounting software, enterprise resource planning (ERP) tools, and AI-enhanced simulations, are increasingly incorporated into the curriculum to expose students to contemporary business environments (Chukwuma & Eze, 2023).

Furthermore, entrepreneurship education is embedded to nurture innovation and self-reliance, enabling graduates to contribute not only as employees but also as job creators in Nigeria's evolving digital economy (Adebayo & Fashola, 2023).

Shifts from Traditional to ICT-Driven Instructional Methods

Traditionally, accounting education in Nigeria relied heavily on manual record keeping, chalk-and-talk lectures, and end-of-term written assessments (Oseni & Okonkwo, 2022). However, the growing impact of globalization, digitalization, and automation in business operations has necessitated a pedagogical shift toward ICT-driven approaches. Modern practices increasingly include learning management systems (LMS), online assessment platforms, cloud-based simulations, and interactive case studies. As Tewari (2024) notes, these innovations foster active learning, real-time feedback, and collaborative problem-solving, thus bridging the gap between academic preparation and industry expectations.

At FUE Zaria, this transition is ongoing but constrained by infrastructural challenges, faculty readiness, and policy gaps factors that must be addressed to achieve full integration of Education 4.0 principles.

Current Pedagogical Practices and Constraints

Predominance of Teacher-Centered Instruction

Despite the rapid global adoption of student-centered, technology-driven learning models, Nigerian higher education still relies heavily on teacher-centered pedagogical practices. Lecturers in business and accounting programs often emphasize rote memorization, manual bookkeeping, and summative assessments rather than interactive or experiential learning (Okoli & Agboola, 2021). This approach limits opportunities for learners to develop critical thinking, problem-solving, and digital skills required in modern workplaces (Onoh & Akpodiete, 2022). The persistence of this traditional method reflects institutional inertia, inadequate ICT integration, and a lack of pedagogical innovation in line with Education 4.0 principles.

Constraints

Large Class Sizes and Workload Pressure

Overcrowded classrooms remain a significant barrier to effective teaching in business education programs across Nigerian universities. With enrollment outpacing available infrastructure and staff capacity, lecturers are often unable to provide personalized guidance or adopt simulation-based teaching (Adeyemi & Yusuf, 2022). High workloads further discourage experimentation with AI-based or blended learning methods.

Infrastructural Gaps (ICT, Connectivity, Power)

Infrastructural deficiencies such as poor internet connectivity, unstable electricity supply, and limited access to ICT facilities significantly hinder pedagogical innovation. Studies show that unreliable power supply and outdated ICT laboratories prevent lecturers from fully integrating AI-driven

simulations and cloud-based accounting tools (Oseni & Okonkwo, 2022; Tewari, 2024).

Faculty Readiness and Professional Development Challenges

Another critical challenge is the lack of faculty preparedness for digital transformation. Many lecturers lack adequate training in emerging technologies, and professional development programs are either irregular or unavailable (Nwankwo & Obasi, 2023). Without structured upskilling initiatives, educators find it difficult to incorporate advanced pedagogical tools such as automated assessment systems or AI-enhanced simulations.

Lack of Clear Governance Frameworks and AI Adoption Policies

At the institutional and national levels, governance structures for integrating AI into education remain weak. While policy documents highlight the importance of ICT and innovation, there are limited actionable frameworks guiding universities on AI adoption, ethical use, and assessment regulation (Chukwuma & Eze, 2023). The absence of such frameworks creates uncertainty, making institutions hesitant to commit resources toward systemic integration of new technologies.

Consequences: Limited Systemic Integration of Simulations and AI Tools

These constraints collectively result in a limited systemic integration of AI-driven simulations and automated assessment in Nigerian business education. Instead of embedding AI into curricula as transformative tools, their use remains experimental and sporadic, often championed by individual lecturers rather than institutional policy (Adeyemi & Yusuf,

2022). Consequently, students graduate with limited exposure to digital simulations or AI-based learning environments, creating a skill gap between academic training and labor market demands (Oseni & Okonkwo, 2022).

Position Statement: Why AI-Enhanced Simulations and Automated Assessment Now

Digital Transformation of the Accounting Profession

The accounting profession is experiencing rapid digital transformation driven by automation, artificial intelligence (AI), and data analytics. Tasks traditionally performed manually, such as bookkeeping, auditing, and tax computations, are increasingly executed through intelligent systems (PwC, 2022). This transition demands that accounting graduates possess digital fluency, critical thinking, and the ability to interpret AI-generated insights. Business education must therefore align its pedagogy with the realities of a technology-driven profession, ensuring that learners are not left behind in the global labor market (Oseni & Okonkwo, 2022).

Benefits of AI-Powered Simulations

AI-powered simulations provide students with immersive, experiential learning environments that replicate complex business and financial scenarios. By engaging in risk-free, interactive simulations, learners can practice decision-making, auditing, and financial analysis in real time (Lilani, 2023). These tools foster competencies such as teamwork, strategic planning, and workplace readiness that are often difficult to cultivate through traditional lecture-based methods (STRATX, 2020). Furthermore, simulations are resilient against academic dishonesty because they require dynamic responses to

evolving scenarios, making them particularly relevant in the age of generative AI (Tewari, 2024).

Role of Automated Assessment

Automated assessment technologies enhance the efficiency, fairness, and timeliness of student evaluation. Unlike traditional assessments, which often involve long grading cycles, AI-driven systems provide immediate formative feedback, allowing students to identify and correct learning gaps quickly (Zawacki-Richter et al., 2020). Automated systems also reduce grading biases, ensuring more consistent and transparent evaluation outcomes (Chukwuma & Eze, 2023). For lecturers, automation alleviates workload pressure, enabling them to focus on higher-order teaching tasks such as mentoring, curriculum design, and ethical discussions.

Alignment with Nigeria's Education Policies and Global Standards

The adoption of AI-enhanced simulations and automated assessments also aligns with Nigeria's national education policies and international benchmarks. The National Policy on Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in Education emphasizes digital transformation as a cornerstone for modernizing teaching and learning (Federal Ministry of Education, 2021). Likewise, the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal (SDG 4) underscores the importance of inclusive, equitable, and quality education supported by technology.

Globally, organizations such as the OECD (2023) and the International Federation of

Accountants (IFAC, 2022) advocate for integrating digital tools into professional education to build competence, equity, and resilience. These policy frameworks position AI-enhanced pedagogy not as a luxury but as a necessity for Nigerian higher education to remain globally competitive.

Conclusion

AI-driven pedagogy in business education is no longer optional but a necessity for institutions seeking to remain relevant in a digitally transforming world. For accounting education in particular, the integration of AI-enhanced simulations and automated assessment systems addresses gaps between theory and practice by equipping students with workplace-ready competencies (Oseni & Okonkwo, 2022; Lilani, 2023). Nigerian higher education, however, faces both opportunities and constraints. Opportunities include immersive learning, immediate feedback, and alignment with global education standards, while challenges persist in the form of infrastructural deficits, faculty readiness, and policy gaps (Federal Ministry of Education, 2021; OECD, 2023).

This position paper contributes by contextualizing AI in Nigerian business and accounting education, highlighting both its transformative potential and the barriers to widespread adoption. Methodologically, it reinforces the value of evidence-based desk research and thematic synthesis in framing solutions to systemic educational problems. Future research should adopt longitudinal and comparative designs across multiple Nigerian institutions to evaluate the sustained impacts of AI-driven pedagogy on learning outcomes, equity, and employability (Tewari, 2024).

In sum, AI-enhanced pedagogy is not merely a technological upgrade; it is a pedagogical shift that demands structured methodologies, governance safeguards, and sustainable adoption strategies to fully realize its benefits.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and analysis presented in this paper, the following recommendations are proposed:

Nigerian universities must prioritize investment in reliable power, campus-wide internet access, and ICT facilities to support continuous use of AI-driven simulations and automated assessment (Onoh & Akpodiete, 2022).

Regular professional development programs should equip lecturers with the pedagogical and technical skills required to integrate AI tools effectively into business education.

Universities should establish formal policies governing AI adoption in teaching, learning, and assessment. These policies must define standards for responsible AI use, disclosure, and academic integrity.

AI deployment must comply with national regulations such as the Nigeria Data Protection Regulation (NDPR, 2023) and integrate human-in-the-loop oversight to address issues of bias, fairness, and transparency (Nwankwo & Obasi, 2023).

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Transforming Mathematics Education through Personalization and Collaborative Problem-Solving in Nigeria

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This paper investigates the transformative potential of personalization and collaborative problem-solving in revitalizing mathematics education across Nigeria. Mathematics stands as a cornerstone of scientific, technological, and socioeconomic advancement, yet it persists as one of the most formidable subjects for students at all educational levels. Despite its pivotal role in the national curriculum, mathematics education is continually beset by systemic issues including low achievement, negative student attitudes, pervasive anxiety, cultural stereotypes, and inadequate pedagogical practices. This review argues that a fundamental shift towards integrating personalization and collaborative problem-solving is essential for enhancing student engagement and performance. Drawing upon a theoretical framework grounded in constructivist, humanistic, and socio-interdependence theories, and informed by international pedagogical best practices, the study situates these innovative approaches within Nigeria's unique socio-educational context. By synthesizing global and national literature, the paper examines current obstacles such as deficiencies in teacher preparation, infrastructural constraints, and cultural barriers. In response, it proposes context-sensitive reform strategies centered on personalized learning pathways and collaborative inquiry. The analysis underscores the profound implications of these approaches for teachers, students, policymakers, and curriculum developers. The paper concludes with actionable recommendations for embedding these transformative strategies into teacher education, national policy frameworks, and daily classroom practice to elevate mathematics learning outcomes throughout Nigeria.

Keywords:

Mathematics education,
Personalization,
Collaborative problem-solving,
Pedagogy,
Teacher development.

Introduction

Mathematics education has long commanded global attention, not merely for its capacity to cultivate logical reasoning, problem-solving skills, and critical thinking, but for its indispensable role in driving technological and scientific progress. As the language of

science, mathematics underpins critical decision-making across vital sectors like health, engineering, agriculture, and finance. A nation's ability to innovate and compete in the global technological landscape is intrinsically linked to the numeracy and

mathematical reasoning of its populace (Organization for Economic Co-operation & Development, 2019).

In Nigeria, mathematics is a compulsory subject throughout basic and secondary education, functioning as a critical gateway to higher learning and professional careers in the science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) fields (Federal Ministry of Education, 2013). Despite this curricular centrality, student achievement in mathematics remains alarmingly and consistently low. This trend is starkly illustrated by results from the West African Examinations Council (WAEC) and the National Examinations Council (NECO), which reveal that a significant majority of candidates repeatedly fail to achieve credit-level passes. For instance, WAEC (2022) data shows a troubling pattern: in 2015, only 38% of candidates secured credit passes (A1-C6). This figure declined to 33% in 2017, saw a slight recovery to 39% in 2019, but then dropped further to 31% during the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020. By 2022, fewer than 37% of candidates achieved this benchmark. These persistent weaknesses point to a complex interplay of systemic, pedagogical, and socio-cultural factors.

The roots of this persistent underperformance are multifaceted, stemming from entrenched pedagogical norms such as teacher-centered instruction, a heavy reliance on rote memorization, and a failure to contextualize mathematical concepts. These issues are compounded by widespread mathematics anxiety among students and significant gaps in teacher preparation and ongoing professional development (Achor & Imoko, 2019; Yusuf & Afolabi, 2019). Traditional, one-size-fits-all teaching methods have largely ignored the diverse learning needs of

students and overlooked the immense potential of collaborative engagement. However, a growing body of global research highlights personalization and collaboration as powerful pedagogical alternatives capable of transforming mathematics education from a passive, rote-learning exercise into an active, meaningful, and engaging intellectual endeavour (Gillies, 2016; Pane et al., 2015).

Personalization involves tailoring instruction to meet the individual strengths, needs, and preferences of each learner, empowering them to progress at their own pace towards their unique learning goals. It is an instructional philosophy that adapts the pace, pathway, and support for every student, making learning responsive to their current abilities and interests (Pane et al., 2015; Holmes et al., 2018). This approach is not a single technique but a design orientation encompassing differentiated tasks, adaptive technologies, flexible student groupings, and mechanisms that promote learner agency, such as choice in problem selection and self-assessment.

In parallel, collaborative problem-solving champions the collective engagement of students in tackling complex mathematical tasks. This approach fosters essential skills in communication, negotiation, and shared reasoning. As Hassan et al. (2018) note, collaboration deepens student understanding and retention by exposing them to diverse perspectives, enhancing problem-solving capabilities, stimulating critical thinking, and developing crucial interpersonal and communication skills. Together, these approaches fundamentally shift the focus of mathematics education from teaching to learning, from memorization to genuine understanding, and from isolated work to dynamic interaction.

The Synergy of Personalization and Collaboration

While personalization centres on individual learning journeys and collaboration thrives on teamwork, these two approaches are not contradictory but profoundly complementary. Their integration can yield powerful and meaningful educational experiences. Personalized tasks can be strategically embedded within group activities, ensuring that each learner can contribute meaningfully from their unique skill level while simultaneously benefiting from the collective intelligence of the group. This balanced approach empowers students to take ownership of their learning while developing social and problem-solving competencies through observation and interaction with their peers and teacher.

The Case for a New Approach in Nigeria

Given the entrenched challenges facing mathematics education, the integration of personalization and collaborative problem-solving offers a promising pathway forward. This raises two critical questions:

1. Why Personalization?

Research indicates that Nigerian students enter the classroom with incredibly diverse learning backgrounds; many, for example, begin secondary school without foundational numeracy skills (Olatunde, 2019). A personalized approach allows educators to meet students where they are, bridging knowledge gaps and preventing the frustration that often leads to disengagement. Modern digital tools, such as adaptive learning platforms, can significantly support this by delivering customized tasks and immediate, targeted feedback.

2. Why Collaboration?

Mathematics is frequently perceived as a solitary pursuit, yet at its core, it is a problem-solving discipline that flourishes with multiple perspectives. Collaborative problem-solving nurtures dialogue, peer-to-peer teaching, and a sense of shared responsibility. Crucially, it mirrors the real-world contexts in which professionals from health workers to engineers, and scientists must work together to tackle complex, and multifaceted problems.

Theoretical Foundations for Pedagogical Change

The proposed shift towards personalization and collaboration is firmly rooted in established educational theories that provide a robust framework for this transformation.

Constructivism

Constructivist learning theory posits that learners are not passive recipients of information but active builders of their own understanding. Piaget (1972) described learning as a process of cognitive adaptation involving assimilation and accommodation. In mathematics, this implies that students must actively grapple with problems, experiment with different solutions, and internalize concepts through hands-on exploration. Vygotsky (1978) expanded this view by highlighting the social dimensions of learning with his concept of the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD), the gap between what a learner can do alone and what they can achieve with guidance. Collaborative problem-solving directly aligns with this, as peers and teachers provide the necessary "scaffolding" to help learners tackle tasks beyond their individual capacities.

Humanistic Learning Theory

Humanistic approaches emphasize the whole learner, attending to their needs, emotions, and drive for self-actualization (Maslow, 1970; Rogers, 1969). Personalization is a direct reflection of this perspective, as it honours each learner's individuality and seeks to align instruction with their interests, motivations, and goals. In the Nigerian educational landscape, where mathematics anxiety is a well-documented barrier (Oduh, 2018), humanistic principles offer a vital corrective, providing pathways to reduce fear, build confidence, and foster self-directed learning.

Social Interdependence Theory

Johnson and Johnson's (2009) theory of social interdependence provides the theoretical bedrock for collaborative learning. It argues that learning is significantly enhanced when individuals perceive their own success as intrinsically linked to the success of others. Collaborative problem-solving in mathematics is a prime example of positive interdependence, where students must rely on shared reasoning and peer explanations to construct a deeper, more robust collective understanding.

Global Perspectives and Local Adaptations

Globally, personalization and collaborative problem-solving are increasingly recognized as essential components of 21st-century education. International exemplars demonstrate both the feasibility and effectiveness of these approaches:

In the United States, personalized learning has been successfully integrated into competency-based education models where students advance upon demonstrating mastery. Studies have shown that these models boost engagement and improve

outcomes, especially for previously underperforming students (Pane et al., 2015).

In Finland, collaboration is woven into the fabric of the national curriculum. Mathematics learning is framed around group inquiry and the application of concepts to real-world situations, fostering both content mastery and transferable problem-solving skills (Sahlberg, 2015).

Singapore's renowned mathematics framework prioritizes deep conceptual understanding, structured problem-solving, and collaborative inquiry. Students learn through guided group discussions and tasks designed to spark mathematical reasoning and creativity (Ng, 2016).

While Nigeria's context presents unique challenges, these international experiences offer valuable lessons. The core principles of learner-centeredness, integrated collaboration, and the gradual leveraging of technology can be thoughtfully adapted to Nigeria's socio-educational milieu.

Challenges Characterizing Mathematics Education in Nigeria

Despite the clear potential of these innovative pedagogies, their implementation in Nigeria faces several significant hurdles and they are as follows:

Overcrowded Classrooms and Resource Scarcity: Many Nigerian schools, particularly in the public sector, grapple with overcrowded classrooms where unmanageable teacher-to-student ratios make individualized attention nearly impossible (Ogunleye, 2019). Furthermore, limited access to essential teaching aids, manipulatives, and technological resources severely constrains a teacher's ability to implement innovative strategies.

Entrenched Pedagogical Limitations: The prevalence of traditional, teacher-centered instruction remains a formidable barrier. Lecture-based methods that emphasize rote memorization over conceptual understanding are still the norm, leading students to learn procedures without grasping the underlying mathematical principles (Yusuf & Afolabi, 2019).

Teacher Preparation and Professional Development: A significant number of teachers lack adequate training in learner-centered pedagogy. Pre-service education often prioritizes theoretical content over practical skills, while in-service training opportunities are scarce and frequently underfunded, leaving teachers ill-equipped to facilitate personalized and collaborative learning environments (Achor & Imoko, 2019).

Student Attitudes and Anxiety: Mathematics anxiety is widespread in Nigeria, contributing directly to poor performance and disengagement (Oduh, 2018). Many students perceive the subject as irrelevant, abstract, and insurmountably difficult, creating a self-perpetuating cycle of failure.

Socio-economic and Cultural Barriers: Systemic issues such as poverty and inequality limit access to quality mathematics education. Moreover, cultural stereotypes persist, particularly those that discourage girls from pursuing advanced studies in mathematics (Amoo & Rahman, 2019).

Strategies for Transforming Mathematics Education

Transforming mathematics education in Nigeria requires a systemic shift away from rigid, teacher-centered models toward dynamic, learner-centered pedagogies. This involves rethinking the curriculum, retraining

teachers, integrating technology, and addressing contextual barriers like large class sizes and an overemphasis on examination performance.

Personalization Strategies

Personalization strategies are as follows.

Differentiated Instruction: Teachers must learn to adapt lesson content, learning processes, and assessments to accommodate learners' varying levels of readiness, interests, and learning profiles (Tomlinson, 2014).

Leveraging Learning Profiles: Instruction should be guided by students' prior knowledge, strengths, and aspirations. For example, a student interested in health sciences could engage with mathematical tasks related to dosage calculations or epidemiology, making the content immediately relevant.

Formative Assessment: Continuous, low-stakes assessment is crucial for enabling teachers to identify learning gaps in real-time and provide timely, constructive feedback to guide student progress (Black & Wiliam, 2009).

Technology Integration: Where feasible, the use of adaptive platforms and mobile applications can provide students with individualized practice and immediate feedback, supplementing classroom instruction.

Collaborative Problem-Solving Strategies

Collaborative problem-solving are as follows;

Open-Ended Group Tasks: Teachers can design complex, open-ended problems that necessitate collaboration, negotiation, and

collective reasoning among students to arrive at a solution.

Peer Tutoring: Structured peer tutoring arrangements can empower more advanced students to support their peers, fostering mutual learning, shared responsibility, and deeper understanding for both tutor and tutee.

Structured Classroom Discussions: Facilitating structured dialogues centered on mathematical reasoning encourages students to articulate their thinking, defend their strategies, and refine their understanding through peer interaction.

Project-Based Learning (PBL): Engaging students in real-world projects such as creating a budget, conducting a community survey, or modelling local environmental patterns, integrates mathematical concepts with authentic and collaborative work.

Conclusion

The path to transforming mathematics education in Nigeria is fraught with challenges, yet it is also rich with potential. By embracing personalization and collaborative problem-solving, Nigerian classrooms can move beyond rote memorization and teacher-centered instruction toward engaging, learner-centered practices that foster deep understanding and critical thinking. Effecting such a transformation demands, a coordinated and sustained effort from teachers, policymakers, and communities are needed. With strategic investment in teacher capacity, curriculum innovation, and supportive national policies, Nigeria can harness the power of personalization and collaboration to make mathematics education more effective, equitable, and profoundly relevant to the demands of the 21st century.

Recommendations

To translate this vision into reality, the following actions are recommended:

Embed Learner-Centered Approaches in National Policy: Explicitly integrate personalization and collaborative learning principles into national curriculum frameworks and teacher education policies.

Invest in Continuous Teacher Professional Development: Provide ongoing, high-quality in-service training focused on practical strategies for differentiated instruction and collaborative classroom management.

Strategically Invest in Accessible Resources: Prioritize investment in low-cost teaching aids and manipulatives while gradually integrating affordable digital tools to support personalized learning.

Enact Meaningful Curriculum Reform: Shift the curriculum's emphasis from rote procedural knowledge to deep conceptual understanding, real-life applications, and complex problem-solving.

Promote Research and Evaluation: Encourage and fund further research on the impact of personalization and collaboration within the specific context of Nigerian mathematics classrooms.

Champion Equity and Inclusion: Actively address gender disparities and ensure that reform initiatives are designed to include and support rural and underserved schools.

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ASSESSMENT OF DIGITAL SKILLS AMONG TVET TERTIARY INSTITUTION LECTURERS IN KADUNA STATE

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The growing rate of youth unemployment in Nigeria underscores the urgency of equipping young people with relevant employability skills. This study assessed the digital skills possessed by tvet lecturers for integrating digitalization into training youths for employment, drawing on the quadruple helix model, which promotes collaboration among academia, industry, government, and civil society in fostering innovation and sustainable skill development. One research question and one hypothesis guided the study. A survey research design was adopted, involving all 88 tvet lecturers in tertiary institutions offering tvet programmes in Kaduna state, without sampling. Data were collected using a self-developed 10-item questionnaire validated by experts in education. Reliability was confirmed through a pilot test, and cronbach alpha yielded a coefficient of 0.89. Administration of the instrument was carried out by the researcher with the help of two assistants, while mean, standard deviation, and t-test were used for analysis. The findings revealed that tvet lecturers in Kaduna state possessed very low levels of artificial intelligence education skills required for integrating digitalization in youth training. Moreover, years of teaching experience did not significantly influence their views. The study concluded that lecturers lack adequate digital skills for effectively preparing youths for employment. It was recommended that management of tvet institutions in Kaduna state adopt well-structured digital technology training and retraining strategies, guided by the quadruple helix approach, to build lecturers' artificial intelligence

Keywords:

Digital skills, tvet, tertiary institutions, lecturers, quadruple helix model

Introduction

The world is rapidly adjusting to digitalization, which has significantly transformed people's lives, daily routines, and occupational patterns. With the advent of digitalization, some traditional jobs are disappearing while new ones are emerging. Consequently, youths must acquire new sets of skills to remain relevant in digital workplaces. This development puts

increasing pressure on educational institutions to re-examine the skills they deliver to learners. Just as industries have evolved due to greater adoption of digital technologies, educational institutions are also upgrading their facilities and training approaches to meet new demands (International Labour Organization [ILO], 2021). To improve youth employability,

Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) must digitalize its

Digitalization refers to the use of digital technologies to enhance productivity and efficiency while reducing costs. Gray and rumpe (2015) defined it as the application of digital technologies to transform business models and create new value. Within tvet, digitalization requires lecturers to adopt and apply emerging technologies to achieve instructional goals (ebert-stiftung, 2020). Commonly used tools include learning management systems (lms), synchronous technologies (audio, video, screen sharing, polls, and whiteboards), multimedia interactive platforms, cloud-based tools, and social participation technologies (martin & xie, 2022). Emerging digital technologies in tvet programmes, as noted by ilo (2019), include artificial intelligence (ai), extended reality (xr), augmented reality (ar), virtual reality (vr), internet of things (iot), cloud computing, and machine learning.

The advantages of digitizing tvet training programmes in tertiary institutions are extensive. Digital technologies facilitate effective planning, interactive learning, quick assessment, and the teaching of new employability skills (martin & xie, 2022). They also foster knowledge acquisition, teamwork, and critical thinking among students. Haleem, javaid, qadri, and suman (2022) argued that tools such as virtual classrooms, augmented reality, and robotics not only make instruction engaging but also promote inclusive learning environments where performance data can be tracked.

The acquisition of digital skills also supports communication, knowledge sharing, and technology-driven problem-solving (pavel,

programmes to align with the needs of digital labour markets.

These technologies equally strengthen communication, collaboration, and problem-solving skills qualities highly valued in the 21st-century labour market.

Beyond individual institutional efforts, the integration of the quadruple helix model which emphasizes collaboration among academia, industry, government, and civil society is critical to advancing tvet digitalization. Through this model, tvet institutions can align their training strategies with labour market needs, industry innovation, and policy directions while engaging the wider community in skill development. This collaborative approach ensures that digital skills training is not confined to the classroom but connected to real-world applications and employment opportunities.

Digital skills encompass knowledge and competences for using computer systems, navigating the internet, engaging in online communication, and applying advanced technologies such as artificial intelligence (ai) in instruction. Snyder (2019) emphasized that tvet lecturers must possess ai skills such as using ai software to grade tests, customize teaching, design adaptive lesson plans, and create intelligent tutoring systems. These capabilities allow lecturers to individualize instruction, enhance student engagement, and prepare youths for complex digital work environments.

fruth, & neacsu, 2015). As nwazor and nwaukwa (2015) noted, tvet lecturers' digital skills are essential for effective youth training

in the digital age. Tvet, as defined by the federal republic of nigeria (frn, 2013), is designed to provide knowledge, skills, and values relevant to diverse occupations within the nigerian context. This includes business education, home economics, fine and applied arts, woodwork technology, building technology, electrical/electronic technology, and agricultural education, among others (olaleye, 2021).

nigeria's youthful population presents immense potential for shaping the country's economic future. degryse (2016) observed that if adequately trained, nigerian youths could benefit significantly from digitalization. yet, employers, policymakers, and parents continue to express concern about the limited capacity of tvet programmes in tertiary institutions to prepare young people for digital labour markets. recent statistics reveal the gravity of the problem: 13.9 million nigerian youths aged 15–24 were unemployed in 2022 (nbs, 2022), while 23 million aged 15–34 were unemployed in 2020 (nbs, 2020).

In this 21st-century work environment, teaching experience may also influence how tvet lecturers perceive and utilize digital skills. Lecturers with more years of service may have different competencies compared to those with fewer years, due to variations in training and exposure. Against this backdrop, this study was undertaken to assess the digital skills possessed by tvet lecturers in tertiary institutions for integrating digitalization into youth training for employment in kaduna state, nigeria, within the collaborative framework of the quadruple helix model.

Statement of the problem

Youth unemployment remains one of the most critical socio-economic challenges

confronting nigeria. To address this, the federal government introduced technical and vocational education and training (tvet) programmes in tertiary institutions with the objective of equipping young people with employable skills for wage employment or self-employment. Despite these efforts, youth unemployment persists at alarming levels, as consistently reported by the national bureau of statistics (nbs). Alarmingly, many tvet graduates are still unable to secure jobs, thereby exacerbating nigeria's unemployment situation.

The rapid transformation in the nature of work, driven by digitalization, has further increased the pressure on tvet programmes to integrate digital technologies in preparing youths for employment. This is crucial for reducing structural unemployment, which occurs when young people cannot respond adequately to the emerging digital job opportunities due to insufficient skills. Employers, parents, and policymakers have continued to express concern that graduates of tvet programmes in nigerian universities lack the necessary digital competencies to take advantage of these opportunities. Consequently, questions arise about the quality and relevance of training delivered by tvet lecturers. The problem is often linked to factors such as an overemphasis on theoretical lessons, reliance on traditional teaching methods, and limited integration of digitalization into instructional delivery.

Tvet lecturers play a central role in equipping the 21st-century youth with the digital skills needed for employment. However, reports from both national and international bodies such as nbs, the world bank, ilo, and unesco have consistently highlighted digital skills gaps among nigerian youths, suggesting that tvet lecturers themselves may lack critical

competencies required to effectively integrate digitalization in training. This challenge is particularly evident in regions like kaduna state.

In addressing these gaps, the quadruple helix model provides a useful framework by emphasizing collaboration among academia, industry, government, and civil society in enhancing skills development. Through such collaboration, tvet institutions can ensure that training is better aligned with labour market demands, technological innovations, and community needs. Despite its relevance, there is a scarcity of empirical research assessing the digital skills of tvet lecturers in tertiary institutions for integrating digitalization into youth training within this model, especially in kaduna state. This study seeks to fill that gap.

Objectives of the study

The purpose of this study was to determine the status of digital skills possess by tvet lecturers in tertiary institutions for integrating digitalization in training youth with skills for employment in kaduna state, nigeria. Specifically, this study ascertained the extent:

Tvet lecturers possess artificial intelligence education skills for integrating digitalization in training youths with skills for employment in kaduna state, nigeria.

Research question

The following research question guided the study;

To what extent do tvet lecturers in tertiary institutions possess artificial intelligence education skills for integrating digitalization in training youths with skills for employment in kaduna state, nigeria?

Hypothesis

The following null hypothesis was tested at .05 level of significance:

There is no significance difference in the mean ratings of tvet lecturers on the extent they possess artificial intelligence education skills for integrating digitalization in training youths with skills for employment in kaduna state, nigeria. based on years of teaching experience (1-5 years/6 years and above).

Methodology

This study adopted descriptive survey research design. It was carried out in kaduna state, nigeria. The population of tvet lecturers in public tertiary institutions in kaduna state offering tvet programme. There was no sampling since the population was manageable and accessible to the researcher. The instrument for data collection was a self-developed questionnaire titled “status of digital skills possessed by lecturers for integrating digitalization in training youths for employment (sdspl-idtye)”. The questionnaire consisted of two sections; a and b. Section a contained one item on demographic information of the respondents such as years of teaching experience while section b contained 10 items in respect to the one research question and structured on a five point rating scale of very highly possessed (vhp) = 5, highly possessed (hp) = 4, moderately possessed (mp) = 3, lowly possessed (lp) = 2, and very lowly possessed (sd) = 1. Face and content validity of the instrument was determined using the opinions of two experts from technical and vocational education and training, and one expert from measurement and evaluation unit.

The reliability of the instrument was established using trail-test method and data

collected were calculated with cronbach alpha which yielded coefficient value of .89. The researcher with the help of two research assistants adequately briefed administered copies of the questionnaire to tvet lecturers in their institutions. On the spot distribution and collection of questionnaires was deployed and those who did not fill their instrument immediately were revisited on another agreed date. Out of 88copies of questionnaire distributed, 83 (94%) of the copies were correctly filled and returned. Statistical mean and standard deviation were used to answer the researcher question and determined the homogeneity of respondents' views while t-test was used to test the null hypothesis at

0.05 level of significance. A null hypothesis was rejected where the p - value is less than 0.05 level of significance, otherwise, the null hypothesis was accepted. The data analysis was carried out using statistical package for social sciences (spss) version 23.

Results

Research question 1

To what extent do tvet lecturers in tertiary institutions possess artificial intelligence (ai) education skills for integrating digitalization in training youths with skills for employment in kaduna state, nigeria?

Table 1:mean ratings and standard deviation on the extent tvet lecturers possess ai education skills for integrating digitalization in training youths for employment

Sn	Artificial intelligence education skills	\bar{X}	Sd	Remarks
Ability to use:				
1	Grade scopeai tool to grade students' assignments and tests	1.48	.58	Verylowly possessed
2	Century ai platform to track students' progress while pointing out knowledge gaps in their learning	1.44	.64	Very lowly possessed
3	Century ai tools to reduce my academic workload	1.39	.71	Verylowly possessed
4	Digital tools such as analytics and web scanners to enhance teaching	1.53	.59	Lowly possessed
5	Intelligent tutoring systems (its) to handle feedback	1.40	.52	Verylowly possessed
6	Intelligent tutoring systems (its) to handle one-on-one teaching	1.40	.49	Verylowly possessed
7	Interactive virtual simulations to coach students in soft skills and self-development	1.47	.69	Verylowly possessed
8	Ai to create digital study guides and instructional snippets to enhance instructional delivery	1.41	.82	Verylowly possessed
9	Ai platform to create one-on-one personalized teaching experience for each student	1.51	.67	Lowly possessed
10	Interactive virtual simulations to aid students' life skills development	1.46	.52	Verylowly possessed
Cluster mean		1.45		Very lowly possessed

Field survey 2025

Table 2 revealed that out of the 10 artificial intelligence education skills listed for integrating digitalization, items 4 and 9 are lowly possess by tvet lecturers for integrating digitalization with mean scores ranged between 1.53 and 1.51 while the remaining eight items with mean scores ranging from 1.39 to 1.48. The cluster mean score of 1.45 shows that on the whole, tvet lecturers in tertiary institutions very lowly possess artificial intelligence education skills for

integrating digitalization in training youths for employment in kaduna state, nigeria.

Null hypothesis 1

There is no significance difference in the mean ratings of tvet lecturers on the extent they possess artificial intelligence education skills for integrating digitalization in training youths with skills for employment in kaduna state, nigeria.

Table 2: test significant difference of tvet lecturers on the extent they possess ai education skills for integrating digitalization in training youths for employment based on years of teaching experience

years of experience	n	\bar{x}	sd	df	t-value	p-value	decision
6 years and above	47	1.46	.84				
1-5 years	36	1.40	.68				
		811.52				1.00	not significant

Field survey 2025

Table 23 shows a t-value of 1.52 at 81 degree of freedom with a p-value of 1.00. Since the p-value of 1.00 is greater than the criterion value of .05 ($p\text{-value} = 1.00 > .05$), the null hypothesis is therefore accepted. This means that there is no significance difference in the mean ratings of tvet lecturers on the extent they possess artificial intelligence education skills for integrating digitalization in training youths with skills for employment in kaduna state, nigeria based on years of teaching experience

Discussion of findings

Findings of this revealed that tvet lecturers in tertiary institutions very lowly possess artificial intelligence education skills to integrate digitalization in training youth for

employment. It was specifically showed that tvet lecturers very lowly possess abilities to, use gradescope ai tool in grading students' assignments and tests, use century ai tool to track students' progress while pointing out knowledge gaps in their learning, use century ai tool to reduce academic workload, use intelligent tutoring systems (its) to handle feedback or handle one-on-one teaching among others. the findings of this study could be attributed to inadequate in-service programmes such as ict workshops, seminars and conferences provided to tvet lecturers to up-date their skills in using emerging digital technologies such as ai to enhance their instructional delivery. It could also be due to lack or inadequate digital technology

infrastructures in tvet departments that prevent lecturers from adopting them in equipping students with 21st century skills for gainful employment. The findings of the study align with the position of olutola and olatoye (2018) that many lecturers in nigeria need to be trained on digital skills in order to utilize digital technologies in enhancing teaching and learning in agreement, kuni (2021), stressed that digitalization has exposed the poor digital skills among lecturers of tertiary institutions in nigeria. Additionally, oviawe, uwameiye and uddin (2017) revealed that tvet in nigeria was lagging behind in equipping youths with 21st century skills due to dearth of digital competent lecturers to use new technologies in teaching. In agreement, polit and duktur (2022) observed that tvet institutions in nigeria lack qualified ict personnel. This contrasts the earlier findings of ejinwa, ojiaku and nnaji(2021) which indicated that lecturers had a high level of digital technology skills that will allow them to be excellent instructors in the digital age.

Findings of the study also revealed that there was no significance difference in the mean ratings of tvet lecturers on the extent they possess artificial intelligence education skills for integrating digitalization in training youths with skills for employment in kaduna state, nigeriabased on years of teaching experience. It could be that both experience and inexperience tvet lecturers surveyed are not adequate provided with digital skills training programmes which could be the reason why both are of the same view that they very lowly possess ai education skills to integrate digitalization in training the youth for employment.

Conclusion

based on the findings of this study, the research concludes that tvet lecturers in tertiary institutions in kaduna statedo not possess enough digital skills to integrate digitalization in training the youth in skills for employment.

Recommendations

based on the findings of this study, the researcher makes the following recommendations;

Management of tvet institutions in kaduna stateshould adopt a well-articulated strategy for digital technology training and re-training of lecturers to enable them acquire relevant artificial intelligence education skills to be able to equip youths with skills for gainful employment.

Tvet lecturers in tertiary institutions in kaduna stateshould search for suitable artificial intelligence trainingprogrammes to update their artificial intelligence skillsin order to remain relevant in the 21st century.

Federal and state government should formulate and ensure effective implementation of digital training programmesfor tvet lecturers especially on emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence, extended reality (xr), augmented reality (ar), and virtual reality (vr), among others. This will enable tvet lecturers to acquire skills in adopting these emerging technologies in enhancing youth acquisition of skills for gainful employment.

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BRIDGING THE GAP WITH ICT TOOLS FOR TEACHING AND LEARNING AMONG UNIVERSITY LIBRARY LECTURERS IN ZARIA, ZARIA

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This study investigates the integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) tools to enhance teaching and learning at Ahmadu Bello University (ABU), Zaria. Data was collected using descriptive survey design from 750 lecturers via google forms using a reliable questionnaire (reliability index 0.91). The findings reveal significant barriers to ICT adoption, with the highest mean scores for inadequate Educational Technology (EdTech) devices (87.37%), digital divide due to socioeconomic disparities (84.57%), and insufficient teacher training (81.33%). Poor infrastructure (63.67%) was the least pressing issue, with standard deviations (0.6658–1.0649) indicating varied consensus. The grand mean of 77.09% underscores broad agreement on these challenges. The study recommends the enhancement of ICT infrastructure through Nigerian government investment Tertiary institutions for stable electricity and internet, faculty training programs to foster teacher confidence, provision of subsidized Educational Technology (Edtech) device with internet access, development of localized content and flexible curricula will assist to align ABU with global educational standards, fostering equitable, technology-driven learning environments to prepare students for a digital economy.

Keywords:

ICT tools, teaching and learning, Ahmadu Bello University, digital divide, educational technology

Introduction

The rapid evolution of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has transformed educational landscapes worldwide, offering innovative solutions to enhance teaching and learning. In Nigerian tertiary institutions, such as Ahmadu Bello University (ABU), Zaria, ICT tools are

pivotal in addressing longstanding challenges, including limited access to quality education, large class sizes, and resource constraints. The concept of "bridging the gap" with ICT tools refers to leveraging digital technologies to mitigate educational disparities, ensuring equitable

access to personalized, interactive, and flexible learning experiences for students from diverse backgrounds, regardless of geographical or socioeconomic barriers (UNESCO, 2018). This approach fosters inclusivity and aligns education with global standards, preparing students for a digital economy.

In Nigeria, tertiary institutions face unique challenges, such as inadequate infrastructure, socioeconomic disparities, and limited faculty training, which hinder effective teaching (Zakariya & Danlami, 2024). ICT tools, including Learning Management Systems (LMS), multimedia resources, and mobile learning platforms, offer opportunities to overcome these barriers by enhancing content delivery, student engagement, and assessment efficiency. This paper explores the critical role of ICT in revolutionizing teaching at ABU, focusing on its importance in improving access, quality, and relevance of education. By examining definitions, types, case studies, challenges, and recommendations, the study provides a comprehensive framework for integrating ICT tools to foster a technology-driven educational environment in Nigerian tertiary institutions. This paper examines the role of ICT tools in enhancing educational outcomes at ABU, addressing definitions, types, importance, case studies, challenges, and recommendations for effective integration.

Definition of ICT

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) refers to technologies that facilitate the creation, storage, processing, and dissemination of information through digital and electronic means (UNESCO, 2018). ICT encompasses hardware (e.g., computers, projectors), software (e.g., learning management systems), and

communication networks (e.g., internet, mobile networks). In education, ICT integrates digital tools to enhance teaching, learning, and administrative processes, enabling interactive and accessible education delivery (Tondeur et al., 2017). At ABU, ICT adoption aligns with global trends to modernize education, addressing challenges like large class sizes and resource constraints.

Definition of ICT Tools in Teaching and Learning

ICT tools in teaching and learning are digital resources and applications designed to support educational processes. These include hardware (e.g., laptops, interactive whiteboards), software (e.g., Moodle, Google Classroom), and internet-based platforms (e.g., video conferencing tools, e-libraries). They facilitate content delivery, student engagement, assessment, and collaboration (Ertmer et al., 2012). At ABU, ICT tools such as Learning Management Systems (LMS) and multimedia resources are critical for delivering lectures, managing assessments, and fostering student-centered learning, particularly in a large and diverse academic environment.

Types of ICT Tools in Teaching and Learning

ICT tools in education are diverse, categorized based on functionality:

Content Delivery Tools: Content delivery tools which include e-learning platforms (e.g., Moodle, Blackboard) and multimedia resources such as videos, animations, podcasts, and interactive presentations. These tools support both asynchronous (self-paced) and synchronous (real-time) learning, enabling instructors to deliver educational content efficiently (Kopcha, 2012).

Collaboration Tools: Collaboration tools, such as video conferencing platforms (e.g., Zoom, Microsoft Teams) and online discussion forums, facilitate interaction among students and between students and instructors, promoting group-based and interactive learning.

Assessment Tools: Assessment tools include online quizzes, plagiarism detection software (e.g., Turnitin), and automated grading systems. These tools streamline the evaluation process, ensuring accuracy and efficiency. With the use of Google Forms or Moodle quizzes allow instructors to create formative and summative assessments with instant feedback (Ertmer et al., 2012).

Learning Management Systems (LMS): LMS platforms, such as Canvas, Moodle, or Blackboard, integrate content delivery, assessments, and communication in a centralized system, enhancing instructional delivery and course management (Edebatu, 2025). The use of LMS assist instructors upload syllabi, assignments, and grades, while students access resources and track progress (Edebatu, 2025).

Mobile Learning Tools: Mobile learning tools include educational apps (e.g., Duolingo, Quizlet) and mobile-compatible platforms, enabling flexible, on-the-go learning through smartphones and tablets. These apps provide interactive exercises, such as language learning or math drills, accessible on mobile devices (Crompton, 2017)

Virtual and Augmented Reality: VR and AR tools, such as VR headsets or AR apps, create immersive learning experiences, simulating real-world environments for interactive education. The use of VR simulations allow students to conduct experiments in sciences

or engineering without physical equipment (Merchant et al., 2014).

E-Libraries and Databases: E-libraries and online databases (e.g., JSTOR, ABU's library website) provide access to scholarly resources, including journals, books, and research papers. Students and faculty access peer-reviewed articles for research and coursework (Warschauer & Matuchniak, 2010).

Interactive Whiteboards: Interactive whiteboards (e.g., SMART Boards) are digital displays that allow touch-based interaction, enabling dynamic presentations and collaborative learning. It allows instructors annotate diagrams or solve problems in real-time (Higgins et al., 2007).

Simulation Software: Simulation software provides virtual environments for practical training, particularly in sciences, engineering, and medicine, replicating real-world scenarios. Software like LabVIEW simulates laboratory experiments, reducing the need for physical equipment (Rutten et al., 2012).

Cloud-Based Tools: Cloud-based tools, such as Google Drive, Dropbox, and OneDrive, enable storage, sharing, and collaboration on educational resources via the internet. Instructors share lecture notes and assignments with students (Mtebe, & Raisamo, 2014).

At ABU, tools like shared whiteboards and LMS features are preferred for instructional delivery, reflecting adaptability to local needs (Edebatu, 2025).

Importance of ICT Tools in Teaching and Learning

ICT tools are pivotal in modern education, offering:

Enhanced Access: ICT tools, such as e-learning platforms (e.g., Moodle) and mobile learning apps, enable remote and flexible access to educational resources, overcoming geographical and infrastructural barriers (Warschauer & Matuchniak, 2010). In Nigeria, where rural students often face challenges accessing tertiary institutions due to distance and transportation costs, tools like Zoom and mobile-compatible LMS platforms allow students to participate in lectures and access materials remotely. At ABU, with its large and diverse student population, ICT facilitates education delivery to students in remote areas, reducing dropout rates

Improved Engagement: Interactive tools, such as multimedia resources (videos, animations) and gamification, make learning engaging and interactive, increasing student motivation and participation (Crompton, 2017). Large class sizes in Nigerian universities, like ABU, often limit student-teacher interaction. Interactive whiteboards and online discussion forums enable dynamic classroom engagement, fostering active learning.

Personalized Learning: Adaptive learning platforms and analytics in LMS tailor content to individual student needs, accommodating diverse learning styles and paces (Kopcha, 2012). Nigerian students come from varied educational backgrounds, with differing levels of preparedness. ICT tools like adaptive quizzes and personalized learning modules can address these disparities, ensuring equitable learning outcomes.

Efficiency in Assessment: Tools like online quizzes, plagiarism detection software (e.g., Turnitin), and automated grading systems streamline assessment processes, saving time

and ensuring accuracy (Ertmer et al., 2012). With large student populations, manual grading is time-consuming for Nigerian lecturers. At ABU, tools like Moodle quizzes can automate assessments, providing instant feedback to students.

Global Connectivity: E-libraries and databases (e.g., JSTOR, ABU's library website) provide access to global scholarly resources, fostering research and collaboration (Warschauer & Matuchniak, 2010). Nigerian institutions often lack physical library resources. ICT tools enable ABU faculty and students to access international journals and open educational resources (OER), leveling the playing field with global institutions.

Skill Development: Exposure to ICT tools equips students with digital skills essential for the modern workforce, such as proficiency in software and online collaboration (Crompton, 2017). Nigeria's growing digital economy demands graduates with ICT skills. ABU's use of tools like Google Workspace and simulation software can prepare students for tech-driven careers.

Resource Optimization: ICT tools reduce reliance on physical materials (e.g., textbooks, chalkboards), addressing resource scarcity in underfunded institutions (Mtebe & Raisamo, 2014). Nigerian universities, including ABU, face funding constraints. Cloud-based tools like Google Drive and e-libraries minimize costs associated with physical infrastructure.

Data-Driven Insights: LMS analytics provide insights into student performance and engagement, enabling data-driven teaching adjustments (Edebatu, 2025). Nigerian lecturers often lack tools to monitor student progress in large classes. At ABU, LMS

analytics can identify struggling students, informing targeted interventions. These benefits align with ABU's goal of producing graduates equipped for a digital economy, enhancing teaching quality and learning outcomes.

Case Studies of Universities Using ICT Tools

1. University of Cape Town (UCT), South Africa

Description and Implementation: The University of Cape Town has been a pioneer in ICT integration, leveraging Moodle as its primary Learning Management System (LMS) and video conferencing tools like Zoom to support blended learning (Czerniewicz & Brown, 2013). UCT's approach combines asynchronous content delivery through Moodle with synchronous interactions via video conferencing, enabling flexible learning for both on-campus and remote students. The university implemented a robust faculty training program, offering workshops and continuous professional development to ensure effective use of these tools. Moodle hosts course materials, quizzes, and discussion forums, while video conferencing facilitates live lectures and seminars, particularly for rural students with limited access to physical campuses.

2. Obafemi Awolowo University (OAU), Nigeria

Description and Implementation: Obafemi Awolowo University has integrated LMS platforms (e.g., Moodle) and e-libraries to support teaching and learning for its large student population (Jagboro, 2003). OAU addressed power supply challenges by establishing solar-powered computer labs,

ensuring reliable access to ICT tools. The university's e-library provides access to digital resources, including journals and open educational resources (OER), reducing reliance on physical libraries. The LMS supports course management, online assessments, and student-instructor communication, particularly for large classes. OAU also collaborates with international partners to fund ICT infrastructure, ensuring sustainability.

3. Makerere University, Uganda

Description and Implementation: Makerere University has embraced mobile learning and cloud-based tools to enhance educational access and reduce infrastructure costs (Mtebe & Raisamo, 2014). The university implemented mobile-compatible LMS platforms and apps, allowing students to access course materials on smartphones, which are widely available even in low-resource settings. Cloud-based tools like Google Drive facilitate resource sharing and collaboration, minimizing the need for expensive physical infrastructure. Makerere also partnered with telecommunications companies to provide subsidized data plans, improving connectivity for students. These cases demonstrate scalable ICT solutions that ABU can emulate to address similar challenges.

Research Questions

This study will provide answer to the research question:

What are the challenges lecturers faces on bridging the gap with ICT tools in teaching and learning in Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria?.

Methodology

The study assessed the challenges lecturer's faces on bridging the gap with ICT tools in teaching and learning in Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria. Descriptive survey design was adopted for the study. To achieve this, the researcher collected data from 750 lecturers via Google forms from the Academic Staff Social Network Groups like WhatsApp groups in Ahmadu Bello University; Zaria which formed the population for the study. The instrument for data collection for this study was a self-developed structured questionnaire. The research instrument was subjected to face and content validity by experts in the field of Educational Technology and instrument's reliability was evaluated using the Guttman Split-half test with the Spearman Brown formula, resulting in a reliability index of 0.91. According to Creswell (2014), a

reliability index between 0.70 and 0.99 suggests a high reliability coefficient between two variables. Thus, the instrument used in the study was deemed reliable. The questionnaire was designed on a four (4) point liker scale ranging from frequencies of options of strongly agree, agree, disagree and strongly disagree carrying points of 4,3,2 and 1 respectively and their individual mean and standard deviation computations. Their mean was cumulative in each table and compared with a decision/standard mean of 2.500. The decision mean is based on the 4 Likert scale options of each of the item, thus: $(4+3+2+1)/4 = 2.500$. The data collected from the research questions was analyzed using descriptive statistics into mean, and standard deviations. The statistical package of version 26 was used to analyze the data collected from the respondents.

Table 1: the challenges lecturers face on bridging the gap with ICT tools in teaching and learning in Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria

S/ N	Challenges	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	STD
	Inadequate Access to technology,	350	200	120	80	77.33	1.0206
	Insufficient teacher training and programmes	280	400	50	20	81.33	0.6945
	Poor Infrastructure	120	310	180	140	63.67	0.9700
	Digital Divide due to Socioeconomic disparities	489	110	100	51	84.57	0.9407
	Data Privacy concerns and Cyber security Threats	83	523	80	64	70.83	0.7287
	Lack of relevant ICT educational content	256	370	24	100	76.07	0.9511
	Teacher’s lack of confidence, competence, and skill.	402	95	200	53	78.20	1.0333
	Time Constraints	189	416	45	100	73.13	0.9193
	Inadequate Educational Technology (EdTech) devices to enhance teaching and learning engagement	423	296	10	21	87.37	0.6658
	Rigid Curriculum	384	185	81	100	78.43	1.0649
	Grand Mean						

Decision Mean = 2.50

The analysis on Table 1 reveals that the most significant barriers, as indicated by the highest mean scores, are Inadequate Educational Technology (EdTech) Devices (87.37%), Digital Divide due to Socioeconomic Disparities (84.57%), and Insufficient Teacher Training and Programmes (81.33%). These high mean scores suggest that respondents strongly perceive these as critical obstacles to effective technology integration in education. Conversely, Poor Infrastructure (63.67%) has the lowest mean scores, indicating it is perceived as a less pressing issue, possibly due to varying infrastructure quality across contexts. The standard deviations range from 0.6658 to 1.0649, with lower values (e.g.,

EdTech Devices, Teacher Training) indicating greater consensus among respondents, while higher values (e.g., Rigid Curriculum, Teacher Confidence) suggest more varied opinions. The grand mean of 77.09% highlighted a broad agreement that these challenges collectively hinder educational technology adoption, with socioeconomic disparities, device availability, and teacher training being the most critical.

Discussion

The analysis of Table 1 illuminates the primary challenges lecturers at Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, face in leveraging ICT tools to bridge gaps in teaching and

learning, with a grand mean of 77.09% indicating substantial agreement on these barriers exceeding the decision mean of 2.50. Notably, the highest-rated issues— inadequate EdTech devices (mean = 87.37%), socioeconomic-driven digital divide (mean = 84.57%), and insufficient teacher training (mean = 81.33%)—point to entrenched systemic hurdles in resource provision, equity, and capacity building is consistent with studies noting that limited access to hardware, such as computers and tablets, unstable power supplies and limited access to tools, which exacerbate disparities and limit engagement in virtual learning environments significantly impedes technology integration in classrooms (Kayode & Abidemi, 2024; Ertmer et al., 2012).

Similarly, the Digital Divide due to Socioeconomic Disparities (84.57%) reflects ongoing concerns about equitable access to technology, as socioeconomic status often determines access to devices and internet connectivity due to high internet costs and unreliable connectivity, which disproportionately affect rural and low-income students, perpetuating exclusion from e-learning platforms (Nwonye et al., 2025; Warschauer & Matuchniak, 2010). The strong agreement on Insufficient Teacher Training (81.33%) aligns with research indicating that professional development is critical for effective technology use, as teachers require ongoing training to develop both technical and pedagogical skills (Kopcha, 2012).

The moderate agreement on Data Privacy Concerns and Cybersecurity Threats (70.83%) and lack of relevant content (mean = 76.07%) suggests growing awareness of these issues, particularly as educational

institutions increasingly rely on digital platforms, where cybersecurity threats and insufficient tailored educational materials impede progress. This finding is supported by studies highlighting the risks of data breaches and the need for robust cybersecurity measures in education (Maina & Kuria, 2024; Crompton, 2017).

The relatively low mean scores for Poor Infrastructure (63.67%) may indicate that infrastructure challenges are less universal, possibly due to improvements in some regions or varying definitions of "infrastructure" among respondents. This aligns with research suggesting that infrastructure barriers are context-specific, with developing regions facing greater challenges and the need to address professional development gaps and infrastructure deficits for meaningful ICT integration (Al-Kharusi, 2024; Tondeur et al., 2017)..

The variability in standard deviations, particularly higher values for Rigid Curriculum (1.0649) and Teacher's Lack of Confidence (1.0333), suggests diverse perspectives, possibly influenced by differences in educational systems or teacher demographics. Research confirms that low computer literacy and inadequate professional development hinder ICT integration, with many academics lacking the pedagogical competence to utilize tools effectively, leading to resistance and suboptimal adoption (Ogunode et al., 2021; Usman et al., 2025). Overall, the grand mean of 77.09% highlight the multifaceted nature of barriers to educational technology adoption, necessitating targeted interventions to address device shortages, training gaps, and socioeconomic inequities.

Challenges of ICT Tools in Teaching and Learning at ABU

Based on the provided survey data and literature, ten challenges are identified:

Inadequate Access to Technology (77.33%): Limited availability of computers and internet connectivity hinders ICT adoption (Zakariya & Danlami, 2024).

Insufficient Teacher Training (81.33%): Faculty lack adequate training in ICT tools, limiting effective integration (Edebatu, 2025).

Poor Infrastructure (63.67%): Unstable electricity and outdated facilities impede reliable ICT use (Idris, 2016).

Digital Divide due to Socioeconomic Disparities (84.57%): Students from low-income backgrounds struggle to access devices and internet (Warschauer & Matuchniak, 2010).

Data Privacy and Cybersecurity Threats (70.83%): Concerns over data breaches discourage ICT adoption (Crompton, 2017).

Lack of Relevant ICT Educational Content (76.07%): Limited localized digital content reduces relevance (Tondeur et al., 2017).

Teacher's Lack of Confidence, Competence, and Skill (78.20%): Resistance to technology due to low proficiency affects adoption (Ertmer et al., 2012).

Time Constraints (73.13%): Faculty face time limitations in learning and implementing ICT tools (Hew & Brush, 2007).

Inadequate EdTech Devices (87.37%): Shortages of projectors, computers, and interactive tools limit classroom integration (Zakariya & Danlami, 2024).

Rigid Curriculum (78.43%): Inflexible curricula hinder integration of ICT-based pedagogies (Law et al., 2011).

These challenges, supported by survey data (mean scores), reflect systemic barriers at ABU, requiring targeted interventions.

Conclusion

Bridging the gap with ICT tools at Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, is critical for aligning with global educational standards and preparing students for a digital economy. The integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) tools at Ahmadu Bello University (ABU), Zaria, offers a transformative pathway to bridge educational disparities and elevate teaching and learning to global standards. ICT tools, including Learning Management Systems, multimedia resources, mobile learning platforms, and virtual labs, address critical challenges such as large class sizes, limited access to quality education, and resource constraints. These tools enable remote and flexible learning, ensuring students from diverse backgrounds, including those in rural areas, can access educational resources. Interactive content like videos, animations, and online forums enhances student engagement, while automated assessment tools streamline grading, saving time and improving efficiency for faculty. Case studies from universities like the University of Cape Town and Obafemi Awolowo University illustrate successful ICT adoption through blended learning, solar-powered labs, and mobile platforms, providing scalable models for ABU. However, survey data highlights significant barriers, with inadequate Educational Technology devices (87.37%), socioeconomic disparities (84.57%), and insufficient teacher training (81.33%) as the most critical obstacles,

reflected in a grand mean of 77.09%. These challenges underscore the need for targeted interventions. A collaborative approach involving government, university administration, faculty, and external partners is essential to invest in reliable infrastructure, expand training programs, and ensure equitable access to devices and internet. By adopting evidence-based strategies, ABU can create a technology-driven educational ecosystem, preparing students for a digital economy and advancing Nigeria's higher education landscape.

Recommendations

To address the identified challenges, ten recommendations are proposed with stakeholder involvement:

Enhance Infrastructure: Nigerian Government and university administration should invest in stable electricity and high-speed internet, leveraging solar solutions as seen at OAU.

Expand Training Programs: Faculty development units should conduct regular ICT training workshops to boost competence and confidence.

Increase EdTech Devices: University management and donors should procure computers and interactive whiteboards, prioritizing high-impact tools like LMS.

Address Digital Divide: Nigerian Government and NGOs should provide subsidized devices and internet access for low-income students.

Strengthen Cybersecurity: IT departments should implement robust data protection protocols to address privacy concerns.

Development of Localized Content: National Universities Commission (NUC) in

collaboration with Faculty and curriculum developers should create context-specific digital resources, collaborating with content providers.

Foster Lecturers Confidence: The Ahmadu Bello University administration should incentivize ICT adoption through recognition and support programs.

Revision of Flexible Curriculum Design: The Nigerian Ministry of Education in consultation with the National Universities Commission (NUC) and all tertiary institutions administrators could revise curricula to integrate ICT-based pedagogies, drawing from global best practices.

Time Management Support: Faculty should receive workload adjustments to accommodate ICT training and implementation for lecturers.

Stakeholder Collaboration: Nigerian Government, private sector, and international partners could support educational programmes through provision of adequate fund and support ICT initiatives, as seen in Makerere University's

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GENDER DISPARITY IN AI USAGE FOR LEARNING CHEMISTRY AMONG UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS IN ZARIA, KADUNA STATE, NIGERIA

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This study investigated gender disparities in Artificial Intelligence (AI) usage for learning chemistry among undergraduate students in Zaria, Kaduna State, Nigeria. A survey research design was employed using a researcher-validated 5-point Likert scale questionnaire to collect data from students across three categories: Faculty of Education (main campus), Faculty of Education (affiliated institution), and Faculty of Physical Sciences. The objectives were to compare patterns of AI usage for learning chemistry across faculties, examine gender differences in AI usage, and explore the interaction between gender and faculty. Data were analyzed using IBM SPSS statistic package. The research questions were answered using descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) while the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of confidence using a two-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA).

The findings revealed a significant main effect of faculty category on AI usage, $F(2, 1354) = 8.85, p < .001, \text{partial } \eta^2 = .013$, with students from the Faculty of Education (main campus) and affiliated institutions reporting significantly higher AI usage than those in the Faculty of Physical Sciences. The main effect of gender was not significant, $F(1, 1354) = 2.58, p = .108, \text{partial } \eta^2 = .002$, indicating no overall gender disparity in AI usage. However, the interaction between gender and faculty was significant, $F(2, 1354) = 8.59, p < .001, \text{partial } \eta^2 = .013$. Specifically, female students in the affiliated institution reported higher AI usage for learning chemistry than males, while the reverse was observed in the main campus, and no difference was found in Physical Sciences.

Keywords:
Artificial Intelligence,
gender disparity,
chemistry education,
two-way ANOVA,
Nigeria

Introduction

Artificial intelligence (AI) has rapidly moved from experimental novelty to mainstream infrastructure in higher education, transforming how learners access explanations, generate feedback, and practice disciplinary problem solving (Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019; Zhu et al., 2025). In

chemistry, where cognitive load is often high and representational fluency (symbolic, macroscopic, particulate) is essential, AI tools, such as large language models (LLMs) and domain-aware assistants, are increasingly used to scaffold concept mastery, data analysis, and writing (Reddy et al., 2024; Journal of Chemical Education,

2024). However, along with enthusiasm for productivity gains and personalized support, concerns persist about uneven adoption, ethical risks, and the possibility that new technologies amplify existing inequities (Zhu et al., 2025). A central unresolved question is whether gendered patterns of awareness and utilization of AI in learning chemistry are emerging, and if so, how institutional and cultural contexts shape these patterns.

This study investigates gender disparity in the awareness and utilization of AI for learning chemistry among undergraduate students at Ahmadu Bello University (ABU), Zaria. As one of Nigeria's largest federal universities serving diverse student populations in the country's northwest, ABU sits at the intersection of rapid digitalization, growing demand for Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics capacity, and persistent gender gaps in participation and tech access noted across sub-Saharan contexts (Aderinoye et al., 2024; Okonkwo et al., 2025). Empirically, studies in Nigeria report swift diffusion of generative AI (genAI) among undergraduates but also highlight variability in institutional guidance, training opportunities, and perceived risks (Aderinoye et al., 2024; Okonkwo et al., 2025). In the chemistry domain specifically, recent classroom and laboratory implementations show that genAI can support literature-based writing, experimental design reasoning, coding for data analysis, and critical discussion—when embedded with explicit pedagogy and assessment safeguards (Reddy et al., 2024; Journal of Chemical Education, 2024; “Using ChatGPT...,” 2024). However, the extent to which female and male undergraduate students at ABU are equally aware of these tools and are willing (or able) to use them for chemistry learning remains unknown.

Therefore, this study attempts to address this gap.

Research Objectives

The objectives the study seeks to achieve are to:

compare the patterns of AI usage for learning chemistry among students across different faculties (Education main campus, Education–affiliate institution, and Physical Sciences).

investigate whether there is a significant gender disparity in AI usage for learning chemistry among undergraduate students.

explore the interaction between gender and faculty category in influencing AI usage for learning chemistry.

Research Questions

Guided by the objectives, the following research questions are posed:

How does AI usage for learning chemistry differ among students in the Faculty of Education (main campus), Faculty of Education (affiliate), and Faculty of Physical Sciences?

Is there a significant gender disparity in the usage of AI for learning chemistry among undergraduate students?

Does faculty category moderate the relationship between gender and AI usage for learning chemistry?

Research Hypotheses

The following Null Hypotheses (H_0) to be tested at a significance level of 0.05, are formulated:

H_{01} : There is no significant difference in AI usage among students from the Faculty of Education (main campus), Faculty of

Education (affiliate), and Faculty of Physical Sciences for learning chemistry.

H₀2: There is no significant gender disparity in AI usage for learning chemistry among undergraduate students.

H₀3: There is no significant interaction effect between gender and faculty category on AI usage for learning chemistry among undergraduate students.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive survey design to investigate gender disparities in the awareness and utilization of Artificial Intelligence (AI) for learning chemistry among undergraduate students.

Population of the Study

The population consisted of 400-level undergraduate chemistry students enrolled in the Bachelor of Science (B.Sc.) and the Bachelor of Science Education (B.Sc. Ed.) programs at Ahmadu Bello University (A.B.U.), Zaria, Kaduna State, Nigeria. The records indicate that the total number of students in this category were 275.

Sample and Sampling Procedure

A sample of 169 students (approximately 50 % of the population) was selected using the sample size table of Krejcie and Morgan (1970). A proportionate stratified random sampling technique was employed to ensure gender and faculty representation. The study population was stratified into three groups.

125 students in Pure Chemistry (Faculty of Physical Sciences), 100 students in Chemistry Education (Faculty of Education, main campus), and 50 students in Chemistry Education (Federal College of Education affiliate campus). From these groups, 77, 61,

and 31 students, respectively, were selected. Within each stratum, participants were randomly chosen to give both male and female students equal chances of selection, thereby ensuring a balanced gender representation across faculties.

Instrumentation

The study utilized a researcher-designed questionnaire titled “Awareness and Utilization of Artificial Intelligence for Learning Chemistry among Undergraduate Students of Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria.”

The questionnaire was structured into four sections:

Section A: Demographic data, including gender and faculty category.

Section B: Ten items assessing awareness of AI in chemistry education.

Section C: Ten items measuring utilization of AI tools for learning chemistry.

Section D: Items addressing factors that may influence AI adoption in learning.

Items were rated on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from Strongly Agree (5) to Strongly Disagree (1). This scale allows the quantification of perceptions for statistical analyses (Joshi et al., 2015).

Validity of the Instrument

The instrument underwent content and face validation by three experts in chemistry education and the educational research methodology. Their feedback was incorporated to improve clarity, alignment, and coverage of the items with respect to the study objectives.

Administration of the Instrument

Questionnaires were administered personally to the three student groups. This direct administration enhanced the return rate and ensured that clarifications were provided where necessary.

Procedure for Data Analysis

Completed questionnaires were coded and analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS, Version 26). Descriptive statistics (means and standard deviations) were computed to summarize the students’ awareness and utilization of AI by gender and faculty. To test the hypotheses,

two-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was conducted. This allowed the examination of the:

Differences in AI usage across the three faculty categories;

Gender disparities in AI usage, and interaction effect of gender and faculty on AI usage.

Two-way ANOVA was chosen because it is robust in analyzing group differences involving two independent variables (Field, 2018).

Results

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation of AI usage for learning chemistry across faculties

Faculty	Mean	SD
Education (main campus)	4.29	1.08
Education (affiliate institution)	4.13	0.96
Physical Sciences	3.98	1.20

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation of gender difference in AI usage for learning chemistry across faculties among undergraduate students

Faculty	Gender			
	Male		Female	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Education (main campus)	4.38	0.98	4.20	1.18
Education (affiliate institution)	3.87	1.24	4.39	0.67
Physical Sciences	3.98	1.15	3.97	1.24

Table 3: Mean of interaction effect of gender and faculty category on AI usage for learning chemistry among undergraduate students

Faculty Gender	Mean	Std. Error	95% CI	LB	UB
Education main campus	Male	4.381	.090	4.204	4.559
	Female	4.200	.068	4.066	4.334
Education affiliate institution	Male	3.871	.088	3.699	4.043
	Female	4.392	.100	4.196	4.589
Physical Sciences	Male	3.985	.081	3.826	4.144

Female 3.967 .056 3.857 4.076

Table 4: Two-Way ANOVA Results for the Effects of Faculty and Gender on AI Usage in Learning Chemistry

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	45.587a	5	9.117	6.978	.000
Intercept	19976.979	1	19976.979	15288.931	.000
Faculty A	23.137	2	11.568	8.854	.000
Gender B	3.372	1	3.372	2.580	.108
Faculty A * Gender B	22.458	2	11.229	8.594	.000
Error	1769.177	1354	1.307		
Total	24619.000	1360			
Corrected Total	1814.764	1359			

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in AI usage among students from the Faculty of Education (main campus), Faculty of Test statistic comes from Faculty A row.

Result: $F(2, 1354) = 8.85, p < .001, \eta^2_p = .013$.

Since $p < .05$, we reject H₀₁.

Interpretation: There was a statistically significant difference in AI usage for learning chemistry among students across the three faculties.

H₀₂: There is no significant gender disparity in AI usage for learning chemistry among undergraduate students.

Test statistic comes from Gender B row.

Result: $F(1, 1354) = 2.58, p = .108, \eta^2_p = .002$.

Since $p > .05$, we fail to reject H₀₂.

Interpretation: There was no statistically significant gender disparity in AI use in learning chemistry.

Education (affiliate), and Faculty of Physical Sciences for learning chemistry.

H₀₃: There is no significant interaction effect between gender and faculty category on AI usage for learning chemistry among undergraduate students.

Test statistic comes from Faculty A * Gender B row.

Result: $F(2, 1354) = 8.59, p < .001, \eta^2_p = .013$.

Since $p < .05$, we reject H₀₃.

Interpretation: There is a significant interaction between gender and faculty category in AI usage for learning chemistry (i.e., the effect of gender depends on the faculty).

Discussion

This study investigated the influence of gender and faculty affiliation on AI usage for learning chemistry among undergraduate students in Zaria, Kaduna. Analysis (Table 4)

of the significant faculty effect ($F(2, 1354) = 8.85, p < .001, \eta^2_p = .013$) on AI usage for learning chemistry indicated differing levels of AI engagement across faculties. Students in the Faculty of Education (main campus and affiliate) showed higher usage than those in the Faculty of Physical Sciences. This finding supports that of Ugwuanyi, Aderanti, and Adams (2025) who in their study in Southwest Nigeria similarly reported low levels of awareness, accessibility, and utilization of AI tools among chemistry students, with no significant gender difference.

Regarding gender disparity in AI usage in learning chemistry, the findings showed no significant overall gender difference ($F(1, 1354) = 2.58, p = .108, \eta^2_p = .002$). This suggests that, overall, male and female students use AI tools similarly. However, the significant interaction ($F(2, 1354) = 8.85, p < .001, \eta^2_p = .013$) reveals that gender patterns differ by faculty: female students in the affiliate education faculty used AI more than males, whereas the converse is true for the main campus education faculty while no gender difference was observed in Physical Sciences. This aligns with research indicating that self-efficacy and instructional context mediate gender differences in technology integration. Falebita and Kok (2025) demonstrated that technological readiness and self-efficacy significantly influence undergraduates' AI tool usage, suggesting that these psychological constructs may be critical in explaining faculty-based gender differences. Similarly, Julius, Twoli, and Maundu (2022) found that female chemistry students in Kenya had higher self-efficacy when taught using computer-aided instruction compared to traditional methods, implying that pedagogical approaches can

elevate female students' confidence and engagement with technology.

The observed gender–faculty interaction may reflect entrenched teaching practices that provoke the use of AI in learning chemistry. From the self-efficacy perspective, female students often report lower confidence in technology, despite having similar competencies (Whitcomb et al., 2020). Therefore, AI usage disparities could reflect differences in confidence, exposure, and faculties' institutional cultures. Aligning with Falebita and Kok's (2025) findings, enhancing self-efficacy through structured AI exposure and scaffolded training may reduce gender disparities.

Recommendations

To promote equitable AI usage for chemistry learning:

AI literacy and self-efficacy-building interventions, especially for female students in faculty which showed lower engagement should be implemented.

AI tools should be integrated systematically across all faculties, ensuring that Physical Sciences students and other groups benefit equally from technological resources.

Pedagogical innovation, such as computer-aided learning environments which has proven effects on self-efficacy and usage (Julius, et al., 2022) should be encouraged.

Limitations

While the study provides valuable insights, several limitations should be acknowledged:

Geographical

Scope

This study was limited to undergraduate chemistry students in Zaria, Kaduna State. The findings may not be generalizable to other regions of Nigeria or international

contexts with different cultural and educational settings.

Measurement of AI Usage
AI usage was measured using self-reported Likert scale items that are subject to response bias and may not capture the actual frequency or depth of AI engagement.

Cross-sectional Design
The Data were collected at one point in time, limiting causal inferences about the relationship between gender, faculty category, and AI usage.

Faculty-Level Clustering
Differences in teaching staff and institutional culture (e.g., affiliate vs. main campus) may have influenced the results; however, these contextual variables were not directly controlled for in the design.

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Evaluating the Impact of Technology on STEM Education: Transforming Physics Learning through Innovative Tools and Approaches- A Review

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This paper investigates the way in which Physics is being changed by use of technology, especially in the framework of Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM). It dwells on the role of the innovative technological tools to enable students to understand tricky concepts better. Purposes: The purpose of the study was to evaluate the effectiveness of the educational technologies to increase the engagement of students, understanding of the concepts, and academic performance. The paper also puts into light the difficulty that teachers encounter in an attempt to incorporate these tools into the classroom. Techniques: A full search of the peer-reviewed literature published between 2013 and 2023 was conducted. Only quality studies that passed certain inclusion and exclusion criteria were incorporated in order to make the findings relevant and credible. Findings: Simulations, augmented/virtual reality (AR/VR), gamification, mobile learning, and online learning technologies have depicted good impacts on learning outcomes. The tools will give students engaging, one-on-one, and open-ended experiences that will increase motivation, engagement, and comprehension of complex Physics concepts. AR/VR and simulations establish an immersive environment, which assists students in visualizing abstract concepts, as mobile learning and gamification make learning easier and more fun. Although all these advantages are appreciated, there are still some issues that include the lack of equal access to technology, inadequate training of teachers, and the fear of over-reliance on digital devices, which may negatively impact critical thinking and face-to-face communication.

Conclusion and Recommendations: Technology is changing the methods of teaching Physics, making difficult things more interesting and reachable. But in order to make it successful, fair access to resources, continuous training of teachers and careful use of technology in the curriculum should be considered. Policymakers and educators should pay attention to ensure that teachers receive sufficient support and training, as well as, increasing the availability of technology to all students in order to achieve a sustainable and effective learning process

Keywords:
Technology
Integration, Physics
Education, STEM
Learning, Simulations and
Virtual Labs, Augmented
and Virtual Reality
(AR/VR).

Introduction

There has never been a more digital and more innovation-driven world in which the need in education is greater than it is today to equip the learner with the capacity to think critically, problem solve, and analyze. Core to such a transition is the interdisciplinary approach of bringing together Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics abbreviated as STEM. Neither is STEM just a model of curriculum, it is also a framework by which inquiry learning, innovation and practical application of knowledge on real world issues are encouraged. It has become the subject of national education policy in almost all nations and has been cited as the driver of economic growth, technological advancement and social advancement (Martyniuk et al., 2021).

One of the STEM subjects that are critical is physics. Physics, the foundation of the majority of engineering professions, and natural sciences teaches the students about the simplest laws, which govern the world of physics, be it the motion and energy, quantum mechanics, and electromagnetism. Physics is the art that develops the logical reasoning and quantitative analysis skills, which are not only essential in STEM career fields, but also informed citizenship in a society that is highly technologically complex. However, the Physics education still faces several challenges that include lack of student engagement, low levels of performance, and the inability to demonstrate the ability to conceptualize abstract concepts. These issues have put the adequacy of the traditional training models in a dangerous light and have prompted a shift to the technology-enhanced learning environments (Martyniuk et al., 2021).

The use of technology in learning and more so in STEM subjects has emerged as a groundbreaking solution. Digital tools In interactive simulations and virtual labs, the digital tools created gave rise to new and more recent methods of accessing, engaging with, and learning physics, such as augmented reality (AR), gamification, and AI-driven solutions. These technologies make the learning process less formal, engaged, and individual, and the students are able to observe the phenomena which are difficult to observe in a traditional classroom environment. One may refer to the simulation of subatomic interactions or celestial mechanics, which can be simulated with the help of an AR application that can be projected onto the real world to explain a complex system (Leon et al., 2025).

The COVID-19 has also capitalised on the shift towards online and hybrid learning around the world and showed both the strengths and limitations of technology in education. Learning institutions had to rushly adopt online space and Physics teachers had to find ways of maintaining student attention and comprehension in online-based courses. It has demonstrated that, used wisely, educational technologies can complement Physics learning, not only enhancing the level of conceptual knowledge and increasing the rate of student motivation but also making the process more inclusive (Ropawandi et al., 2022).

Nonetheless, there is the introduction of technology in Physics instruction. Unequal access to digital tools, lack of teacher training, pedagogical change resistance, over-reliance on technology attentiveness are

all problems that should be considered. Furthermore, although most of the studies have positive results, the review and synthesis of the existing empirical evidence should still be carried out to identify the most effective technologies, in which conditions, and in which groups of students.

Nevertheless, there is the introduction of Physics teaching technology. The digital tools, teacher training, pedagogical resistance to change, and the fear of excessive reliance on digital tools, are the chronic issues that should be addressed. Also, due to the positive outcomes of many research works, the overall picture and synthesis of the available empirical evidence are still required to specify the most effective technologies, under which conditions and in what categories of students.

This review attempts to fill this gap by critically writing on the position of the research on the impact of technology in physics learning. It is a review of findings of multiple peer-reviewed journals in order to ascertain the utility of novel tools and online practices in enhancing student learning outcomes, particularly in the science, technology, engineering and math (STEM) education of secondary and tertiary schools. The present paper highlights 5 important categories of educational technologies i.e. interactive simulations, augmented/ virtual Reality (AR/VR) environment, gamification tool, online learning platform, and collaborative digital environment and discusses how each technology type has been demonstrated to affect student engagement, understanding, and academic performance in physics.

Additionally, this review identifies the pedagogical frameworks that underlie the

viable integration of technology, challenges to the integration of technology, and future research and practice. Through this it seeks to provide teachers, scholars, and policymakers with a sense of how Physics can be taught with technology to make it more engaging, just and in keeping with the 21 st century learning goals.

The Role of Technology in Physics Education

Technology has been a key element in the educational programs in recent years and especially in the STEM fields, including Physics. Utilizing digital tools and new technologies in Physics classes is not a luxury anymore but rather a necessity since it provides new opportunities to help students learn more effectively, enhance their conceptual grasp, and experience the learning process in a more interactive and personalized manner (Simon et al., 2022)

One of the most popular technologies to be used in Physics education is simulations, which can give virtual guidance of physical phenomena and allow the students to experience the concepts that are hard or even impossible to demonstrate in a classic classroom. As an example, PhET Interactive Simulations allow students to interactively manage the variables and visualize real complex systems, such as gravitational forces, chemical reactions, and electrical circuits. Practical use would help students learn more effectively abstract concepts and develop a more comprehensive picture of Physics (Kareem & Thomas, 2022).

AR and VR tools have contributed to great improvements in Physics learning. AR may be used to superimpose electronic material into real world settings so students can explore three-dimensional (3D) models of

molecules or atomic structures or physical forces. In its turn, VR provides immersive spaces in which the students will be able to recreate the laboratory experiments or study astronomical phenomena and provide abstract or microscopic topics with a tangible aspect. Virtual science labs and similar tools like Labster have been demonstrated to increase student attendance and retention, and offer a safe experience of experimenting with complex or hazardous physical principles without the risk of the real-world labs (Ropawandi et al., 2022).

Physics education is also starting to embrace Digital Labs and Virtual Learning Platforms. Such networks facilitate various interactive learning activities such as solving Physics problems to taking online courses and modules. The use of online learning and blended learning models opens the opportunity to utilize such tools as the Khan Academy and Coursera, which enable students to view lectures, simulations, and materials online and, therefore, provides them with a certain degree of flexibility and control over the speed of their learning (Ambar et al., 2025).

Combination of these technologies offers a student-based learning process. They also enable differentiation of instructing students to work at their rate and by the teaching methods that best meet their learning styles. In addition, online technologies may provide real-time feedback, monitor the performance of students, and allow instructors to evaluate the outcomes of learning faster. Technology can therefore be used to not only contribute to conceptual knowledge, but also help create a stronger interest in the topic, making Physics more approachable and enjoyable (Lin et al., 2017).

Problem Statement

Student disengagement, failure to comprehend abstract concepts and limited access to experimental opportunities are long-standing problems in physics education. Although effective in a certain measure, traditional teaching methods tend to be ineffective in capturing the interest of students, as well as giving them in-depth knowledge of intricate and dynamic physical phenomena. These issues are especially vivid on the level of large classrooms, where personal involvement in the learning process or individual learning is hard to achieve. Over the last several years, there has been the accelerated evolution of digital technologies that have provided new opportunities to improve Physics education. Nevertheless, the field lacks a deeper knowledge of the particular effects of such technologies on the learning outcomes. In addition, there are certain questions about the most effective technologies, the circumstances in which they can be most useful, and the way teachers can most effectively introduce them into the current curriculum to achieve the maximum (Yeong et al., 2021).

With the growing popularization of digital resources in schools and universities including simulations, augmented reality (AR), virtual reality (VR), digital labs and online learning platforms, there is a necessity of systematic analysis of the effects of the tools to student engagement, conceptual understanding and academic performance in Physics. Although it has been established that most of the studies conducted have been aimed at investigating the effectiveness of individual technologies, a comprehensive review of their overall effect and contribution to changing the face of Physics education is yet to be fully tapped.

Objectives of the Review

To determine the effects of technological tools on Physics student learning outcomes

To determine the efficacy of different educational technologies in the improvement of the Physics learning

To determine the difficulties and constraints in incorporating technology in teaching Physics

Literature Review

(Mohd et al., 2024) explores the STEM education development, both conventional and innovative approaches to teaching, including project-based learning and inquiry-based learning, collaborative teaching, and integrating technology. It underlines the severe significance of the teacher professional growth in implementing these innovations and the value of technology in improving student engagement and critical skills. Although this research on the effect of technology in learning Physics is in line with these findings, the instruments studied include digital simulations and AI to change the learning experience.

Prayogi et al. (2024) the research on the development of STEM education, traditional and modern methods of teaching, as well as project-based, inquiry-based, collaborative teaching, and incorporation of technology. It emphasises the dire importance of the teacher professional development in the execution of these innovations and the importance of technology in enhancing student engagement and critical skills. Though, this study of the impact of technology on learning Physics is consistent with the results, the tools under investigation are digital simulations and AI to transform the learning process.

Kefalis & Skordoulis, (2025) The results indicate that simulations can be useful in different instructional practices and different instruction levels, especially inquiry-based learning involving secondary and upper-secondary STEM courses. They point to the increased tendency to incorporate the use of digital resources within a hybrid learning environment. Notably, simulations are not used to the best in primary education, which means that the chances to engage with digital tools and the use of STEM in primary education are missed.

Ambar et al.'s (2025)), the findings indicates that the rising usage of smartphones in education setting has made mobile learning a significant method of education. As indicated in this paper, mobile learning promotes remarkable improvements in critical thinking and problem-solving skills of the students. At the same time, it also highlights the significance of developing appropriate rules to prevent possible abuse and maintain the level of academic integrity. This paper has reviewed current literature with a view of evaluating their impact on physics education.

Jalinus et al., (2024) examined the efficacy of STEM Learning Project model in higher education AI courses and reported that students who participated in the project performed better than the control group participants on their post-test score. Results show that the method has a significant positive effect on student learning outcomes, and it is important to focus on the importance of active learning, interdisciplinary integration, and practical problem-solving as major elements of AI learning.

Methodology of the Review

The approach used in conducting this review takes a systematic way in critical evaluation of effects of the technology on Physics learning. It involved literature collection, inclusion and exclusion criteria and data synthesis. The methodology can be broken down in the following way:

Literature Search Strategy

Academic databases, including Google Scholar, JSTOR, ERIC and ScienceDirect, were searched through a thorough literature search. The search specificity was restricted to the literature published no later than ten years (2013-2023) in peer-reviewed articles, books, conference papers, and other scholarly sources. The main search words were: Technology in Physics education, Effects of simulations in Physics learning, Augmented Reality and Virtual Reality in Physics., Gamification in Physics education and Online learning platforms in Physics. Other filters were used to narrow the research to concentrate on the secondary and higher levels of education.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria The studies that met the criteria that were listed below were included in the review:

Inclusion Criteria: Studies meeting the following criteria: techniques used by technological tools in Physics learning; studies that focus on student engagements, mastery of complicated concepts, and academic outcomes; research carried out in secondary and higher learning backgrounds; peer-reviewed journal articles, books, and conference papers; and research published not earlier than 10 years (2013-2023).

Exclusion Criteria: It was excluded that were not related to Physics education or studies,

Articles in which no empirical evidence of student learning outcomes was to be found, Studies that were not written in English, or had an inadequacy of information regarding the research methods.

Data Mining and Generalization.

Key points of data were then identified after the relevant studies were identified and included: Technological Tools Used: The type of the technology (e.g., simulations, AR/VR, gamification, online platform) that the study explores: student Outcomes Measured: Focus on engagement, understanding of complex physics concepts, academic performance, and motivation; methodology Used in Studies; and the kind of approach the studies use (qualitative, quantitative, or mixed-method).

The obtained information was organized and examined in accordance with similar themes, such as technologies evaluated, learning outcomes, and obstacles found in the research.

Quality Assessment

To establish the quality of the review, research was considered to be high in terms of research design (experimental, quasi-experimental, and case studies), sample size and methodological rigor. Such studies that were characterized by high-quality empirical data and legitimate research procedures were given priority to be included.

Limitations

Even though all attempts were taken to make the review comprehensive, the shortcomings of this methodology are: Geographical Limitations; most of the studies are likely to be published which can result in the bias of the findings, Publication Bias: Studies having positive results are more likely to be

published and, therefore, this can cause bias in the findings.

Data Analysis

The qualitative synthesis of data was done to define patterns, trends, and gaps in the literature. Comparison of the results was

made in use of different technological tools to determine how they were effective in improving Physics-learning outcomes. The limitations of the present body of research are also pointed out in this review.

Figure of the flowchart of PRISMA

Result and Discussion

Evaluate the impact of technology on student learning outcomes in Physics:

It has been demonstrated that technological tools are able to influence the learning outcomes of students in Physics positively (i.e. they increase student engagement, conceptual understanding and academic performance). Interactive devices, e.g., simulations and virtual laboratories, enable students to visualize and interact with physical processes and can result in more effective engagements and improved understanding of the intricate process of motion, energy, and electromagnetism. Immersive learning is offered by using AR/VR technology, and students can learn Physics concepts in a way that it was not

possible before. These technologies promote active learning that has been associated with better retention of information and academic success. Gamification tools are also related to student motivation and engagement since they implement game-like features into learning experiences, which increase retention and performance on tests. Research has always indicated that students utilizing these tools tend to perform highly as compared to their counterparts in the non-technology classrooms.

Assess the effectiveness of educational technologies in enhancing Physics learning:

Find out the impact of educational technologies on the improvement of learning Physics: There are a number of ways through which educational technologies have helped

in improving the learning of Physics. On-line simulations like PhET Interactive Simulations have enabled students to experiment with the virtual model of physical system and therefore gain better knowledge on abstract concepts that cannot be easily demonstrated in a real classroom. Laboratory simulation like Labster offers virtual laboratories to ensure that students undertake experiments securely to complement their learning with practical skills. AR and VR technologies allow students to learn the physical phenomenon models in 3D, which is more intuitive and provides a deeper insight into the complex concepts, such as the structure or forces of atoms. Video lectures, interactive problems, and quizzes, which are also provided in online learning platforms like Khan Academy and Coursera, are also available to the student and can be used to learn at his/her own pace. This integration of a mix of different digital tools and platforms does not only enhance the conceptual knowledge of students but also gives them the personal learning experience where studying hard subjects becomes easier as students learn at their own pace.

Identify challenges and limitations in integrating technology into Physics education:

Although technology offers significant benefits in Physics education, some obstacles and constraints keep it incomplete. The first and the greatest one is the unequal access to technology. In the underserved schools, resources, including computers, high-speed internet, and advanced software, might not be available so students can take advantage of digital tools. Therefore, training of teachers is a very important issue. Several teachers lack sufficient training on how to effectively utilize technology in the classroom that may

result in low or poor use of digital tools. Teachers may be willing to use technology, but lack the technical skills or knowledge of best practices with the use of these tools, even how these tools can be used to promote learning. In addition, excessive reliance on technology may be counter-productive when it substitutes the conventional forms of learning that encourage critical thinking and problem-solving. The students can also be distracted by technology which they become used to and they fail to get into the material. Lastly, technical issues (software errors, the inability to connect to the Internet, the inability to connect the devices with technology) may disrupt the lessons and render technology less useful in teaching Physics. These issues involve massive investment of resources, teacher professional development and balanced orientation towards the how to include technology in teaching and learning conventional patterns.

Conclusion

This review brings out how technology has transformed and enhanced teaching of Physics in broader STEM perspectives. The use of online platforms, simulations, virtual and augmented reality, gamification, and other tools allow teachers to improve the student engagement, conceptual learning and academic success in a notable manner. The findings suggest that technology makes learning processes more interactive and individualized and therefore, abstract concepts of Physics are easier and more appealing. However, such concerns as the absence of an equal access to digital resources, the absence of teacher training, and the fear of relying on technology excessively indicate the need of moderately-grounded and well-systematized implementation strategies. Overall, technology has a potential to change Physics

education immensely, but it is only a gigantic potential that ought to be achieved with the help of equal access to technology and regular training of the teachers and the careful implementation of these changes in the curricula already in use. Future research should be done on identification of best practices in specific situations and their implications in the long-term to maximize the power of technology in the promotion of STEM education.

Recommendations

Digitize access to the same so that all learners of Physics, even in the underserved areas, can receive access to Physics education enriched by technology.

Pay attention to the training and professional growth of the teachers so as to develop the

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Kareem, J., & Thomas, R. S. (2022). A Conceptual Model of Teaching Efficacy and Beliefs , Teaching Outcome Expectancy , Student Technology Use , Student

ability to use the emerging technologies effectively by the educators.

Take a halfway position whereby technology becomes a supplement and not to replace the traditional teaching methods to become more efficient in critical thinking and problem solving.

Digital tools which will be installed in the curriculum, including simulations, AR/VR, gamification, and mobile learning will assist in making Physics more interesting and standardized.

Encourage more studies in order to determine the long-term impact of technology development and explain what tools will be the most productive in different contexts.

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HARNESSING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TO ENHANCE BIOLOGY LEARNING IN NIGERIAN COLLEGES OF EDUCATION

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Artificial Intelligence has emerged as a groundbreaking power in science education worldwide, facilitating adaptive learning, intelligent tutoring, and data-driven decision making. Nevertheless, its consolidation into life science education, particularly in higher institutions, remains underexplored. This paper examined the AI's Potential to Enhance Learning among students of biology in the Nigerian College of Education **with study four aims, four research questions, and five hypotheses.** A quantitative survey was conducted. The target population consisted of 1568 biology students, from which 306 samples were randomly selected using Krejcie and Morgan's formula. The data were collected using a researcher-developed structured questionnaire (QAITEBIOS). The instrument was validated by subject experts from the Biology Department, Federal University of Education, Zaria and tested for reliability ($r = 0.78$). Descriptive statistics and independent t-test were employed using SPSS version 23 at 0.05 level of significance. Findings revealed significant adoption of AI tools for biology learning ($t = 28.595 < 0.05$) and a positive perception of their usefulness in enhancing content delivery and student engagement ($t = 22.123, p < 0.05$). AI integration significantly improved students' performance and motivation ($t = 23.435, p < 0.05$). However, infrastructural deficits, including unreliable electricity, poor Internet connectivity, and limited devices, were major barriers to effective implementation ($t = 10.436, p < 0.05$). Key recommendations: The Federal Government and educational stakeholders must prioritize investments in IT infrastructure, including stable power supply, high-bandwidth Internet, and secure cloud platforms, particularly in underserved areas. Regular training programs and workshops should be organized for Biology Education lecturers and students, focusing on AI literacy, ethical usage, and pedagogical integration.

Keywords:

Harnessing, Artificial Intelligence, Biology, Colleges, Education.

Introduction

The educational experiences of both teachers and learners in Nigerian Colleges of

Education can be significantly transformed through Artificial Intelligence education. AI-driven solutions can unlock new frontiers in

education, including personalized instruction, intelligent tutoring, and data-driven assessment, ultimately enhancing overall quality of education. Individual student data are analyzed using AI-powered platforms to tailor instructional content and delivery to each learner's unique needs (Ma'amor et al., 2024). The learning experiences of college students in Nigeria can be revolutionized by AI-driven adaptive learning platforms. Instant feedback is provided by these platforms, leading to improved comprehension and understanding of course materials (Onesi-Ozigagun et al., 2024). Beyond the classroom, AI can also facilitate teacher-student collaboration by offering advanced analytics and feedback mechanisms. This enhanced collaboration can lead to improved learning outcomes (Wu, 2024). However, the successful implementation of AI in Nigerian colleges of education requires a comprehensive approach that considers the unique challenges and contexts of these institutions. Technological progress must be coupled with the scrutiny and enhancement of learning methodologies, ensuring that AI-driven solutions are tailored to the specific demands of both teachers and students, preparing them for the expectations of the 21st-century job market (Bali et al., 2024). The incorporation of Artificial Intelligence in Nigerian Colleges of Education holds the immense ability to transform the training experiences of teachers and students, eventually contributing to the comprehensive and well-rounded growth of the nation's future leaders.

Statement of the Problem

In the modern era, notable challenges have been faced by Nigerian colleges in terms of the quality of education, impacting both teachers and students. Traditional teaching methods and limited access to advanced

educational tools have led to suboptimal learning experiences and outcomes. Available resources are strained by the rapidly growing student population, further exacerbating the situation.

Even though there were policies introduced by government to improve learning such as ICT integration policies, computer assisted instruction and teacher continuous professional development, these interventions remain inadequate because of the insufficient infrastructure, inadequate personalization and lack of adoption by teachers and learners. This consistent gap emphasize the need for Artificial Intelligence solutions.

Contemporary educational demands for the future are being met by students because of declining performance, clearly highlighting the severity of this problem. As Nigeria is striving to enhance its educational standards, the current gap in effective learning methodologies remains a critical barrier. There is a notable gap in the application of these technologies in Nigerian Colleges of Education. Therefore, this research intends to fill this gap by exploring the prospect of AI to strengthen the learning experiences of teachers and students in Nigerian Colleges of Education.

Objectives of the Study:

The objectives of this research are:

To evaluate the current state and extent of AI use in Nigerian Colleges of Education.

To develop AI-based learning modules tailored for key subjects.

To determine impact of AI technologies on student performance and engagement in learning.

To identify and utilize resources and required infrastructure needed for AI learning.

To determine the perceptions and attitudes of pre-service teachers and students regarding AI integration for learning.

Research Questions

What is the current state and extent of AI use in Nigerian Colleges of Education?

How can AI based learning modules be effectively designed for key subjects?

What is the impact of AI technologies on students' performance?

What are the resources and infrastructure required to support AI based learning?

What are the perceptions and attitudes of teachers and students regarding the integration of AI in learning?

Hypotheses

There is no meaningful association between the adoption and use of AI technologies in Nigerian Colleges of Education.

AI-based learning modules do not significantly enhance content delivery or curriculum alignment for key subjects.

AI technologies have no substantial impact on students' academic performance and engagement in learning

There was no notable association between the availability of resources/infrastructure and the effective implementation of AI-based learning.

Pre-service teachers and students had negative perceptions of AI integration in learning.

Methodology

The methodology used in this research was a quantitative descriptive design. The target

population consisted of all Nigerian Certificate in Education students of Biology Department, Federal University of Education, Zaria. The population comprises 1568 (867 female and 701 male) respondents from the two selected combinations in Biology Department, Federal University of Education, Zaria. A simple random sampling technique was used to select participants for this study. The names of the levels in the three different combinations were written on paper, and the two combinations were randomly selected as samples. The sample was drawn from Nigerian Certificate in Education students from the Biology Department. Krejcie and Morgan (1970) presented a table to determine the sample size for a given population for easy reference. The Krejcie and Morgan Table of Determining Sample Size suggests that for a population of 1568, then the sample will be 306.

The research instrument used for data collection was a structured questionnaire designed by the researcher, which has five sections: section A, which is the bio-data of the respondents, which comprises five items: gender, age, marital status, and educational qualification of the respondents, while sections B, which is on AI awareness and usage in biology education with five items. Section C, with five items was on effectiveness of AI in enhancing biology teacher, section D, with four items was on engagement and motivation and finally section E, with three items was on attitude and perception toward AI in biology. These are design questions based on the research questions of the study, comprise 20 items. The instrument was titled: "Questionnaire on AI Integration in Teaching Biology among NCE Students in Federal University of Education, Zaria," tagged (QAITEBIOS).

The questionnaire was given to two experts in the computer department with expertise in AI education tools for validation and two other experts from the Biology Department, Federal University of Education, Zaria, to establish the validity of the questionnaire before it was administered for data collection.
 Research Question One

The researcher used a direct contact method to distribute the survey to the students at the selected levels. The data were analyzed using SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences “SPSS version 23”) to analyze the bio-data and research question in a tabular form.

What is the current state and extent of AI use in Nigerian Colleges of Education?

Table 1: Average and Variability Scores on Current State and Extent of AI usage in SNigerian Colleges of Education

S/N	Section A: AI Awareness and Usage in Biology Education	SA	A	D	SD	MEAN	St. Div	REMARKS
1	I am aware of how Artificial Intelligence (AI) can be applied in Biology education	180	89	30	5	3.40	0.98	Agreed
2	AI tools (e.g., chatbots, virtual labs, simulations) are currently used in my biology classes.	160	122	14	0	3.48	0.74	Agreed
3	My institution encourages the utilization cognitive computing in Biology instruction	200	100	3	3	2.53	1.08	Agreed
4	I have been trained or guided on how to use AI for learning Biology	199	99	5	3	3.64	0.62	Agreed
5	The utilization of AI in Biology instruction is aligned with the NCE curriculum	211	86	9	0	2.86	1.02	Agreed
	Total					15.91	4.44	
	Cluster Average and Standard Diviation					3.18	0.89	Agreed

Table 1 result revealed the central tendency and dispersion measures and the average and variability scores of responses on the current state and extent of AI usage in Nigerian Colleges of Education. The average mean scores and spread of items 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 is

given as (N = 306, M = 3.18 and SD = 0.89) which is above the cut-off point of 2.50, indicating there is positive response on current state and extent of AI usage in Nigerian Colleges of Education

Research Questions Two

How can AI based learning modules be effectively designed for key subjects?

Table 2: Average and Variability Scores on How AI based Modules be Effective Designed for Key Subjects

S/N	Section B: Effectiveness of AI in Enhancing Biology Learning	SA	A	D	SD	MEAN	St. Div	REMARKS
1	AI platforms help me understand complex Biology concepts more effectively	182	120	4	0	3.31	0.91	Agreed
2	Learning Biology using AI tools improves my academic performance	201	100	0	5	3.32	0.87	Agreed
3	AI-enhanced content (e.g., videos, adaptive quizzes) increases my retention of Biology knowledge	194	99	7	6	2.80	1.09	Agreed
4	I am able to learn Biology at my own pace using AI-driven platforms	230	72	0	4	3.09	0.80	Agreed
5	AI-based feedback helps me improve my problem-solving skills in Biology	211	88	7	0	3.31	1.17	Agreed
Total						15.83	4.84	
Cluster Average and Standard Deviation						3.17	0.97	Agreed

Table 2 shows the mean scores and spread of responses on the AI-based learning modules that were effectively designed for the key subjects. The average mean and standard deviation scores of items 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 are

Research Questions Three

given as (N = 306, M = 3.17, and SD = 0.97), which is above the cutoff point of 2.50, indicating that a positive response on AI-based learning modules is effectively designed for key subjects.

What impact will AI technologies have on students' performance

Table 3: Average and Variability Scores on impact of AI technologies have on Students' Performance

S/N	Section C: Engagement and Motivation	SA	A	D	SD	MEAN	St. Div	REMARKS
1	AI tools make Biology lessons more engaging than traditional methods	210	80	10	6	3.21	0.88	Agreed
2	I feel more motivated to study Biology when using AI-powered tools	187	87	26	6	3.72	0.92	Agreed
3	AI features such as gamification and personalization increase my interest in Biology	158	144	2	2	2.88	0.96	Agreed
4	I am more likely to complete Biology assignments when AI is part of the learning process.	209	90	1	6	3.43	0.83	Agreed
	Total					13.24	2.82	Agreed
	Cluster Average and Standard Deviation					3.31	0.71	Agreed

Table 3 shows the summary statistics of the responses regarding the impact of AI technologies on students’ performance. The average mean scores and spread of items 1, 2, 3, and 4 are given as (N = 306, M = 3.31, and SD = 0.71), which is above the cutoff point of 2.50, indicating that AI technologies have an impact on students’ performance in biology.

Research Question Four

What are the Assets and Facilities necessary to support AI based learning

Table 4: Mean and Standard Deviation Scores on Resources and Infrastructure Required to Support AI based Learning

S/N	Section D: Challenges in AI Integration	SA	A	D	SD	MEAN	St. Div	REMARKS
1	I face challenges such as lack of access to devices or internet when using AI for Biology learning	158	144	2	2	2.88	0.96	Agreed
2	Technical problems limit my ability to benefit from AI in Biology education	194	99	7	6	2.80	1.09	Agreed
3	There is insufficient support or training from teachers on how to use AI tools for learning Biology	222	72	10	2	3.09	0.80	Agreed
	Total					8.81	2.85	

Cluster Average and Standard Deviation	2.94	0.95	Agreed
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Table 4 shows the mean scores and spread of responses regarding the resources and infrastructure required to support AI-based learning. The average summary statistics of items 1, 2, and 3 are given as (N = 306, M = 2.94, and SD = 0.95), which is above the cut-off point of 2.50, indicating that positive and

iiimpact on AI infrastructure have an impact on students' performance in biology.

Research Question Five

What are the attitudinal perceptions of teachers and students regarding the integration of AI in learning?

Table 5: Average and Variability Scores on perception and attitudes of Teachers and students on integration of AI for learning

S/N	Section E: Attitude and Perception Towards AI in Biology Education	SA	A	D	SD	MEAN	St. Div	REMARKS
1	I believe AI has great potential to improve the teaching and learning of Biology	185	91	22	6	3.73	1.05	Agreed
2	I prefer a blended approach (AI + traditional teaching) for learning Biology	243	60	3	0	3.19	0.83	Agreed
3	I am willing to continue using AI tools for learning Biology in future courses	203	88	9	6	3.34	0.88	Agreed
	Total					10.26	2.76	Agreed
	Cluster Average and Standard Deviation					3.42	0.92	Agreed

Table 5 shows the mean scores and spread of responses on the perceptions and attitudes of teachers and students regarding the integration of AI for learning. The cluster average summary statistics of items 1, 2, and

3 are given as (N = 306, M = 3.42, and SD = 0.92), which is above the cutoff point of 2.50, indicating that there is a positive perception and attitude of teachers and students on the integration of AI for learning.

Hypotheses One

There is no significant adoption or usage of AI technologies in Nigerian Colleges of Education

Table 6: t-test Analysis on Adoption or usage of AI Technologies in Nigerian Colleges of Education

Groups	N	Mean	St. Dev.	df	t	P
Agreed	239	59.89	9.71	304	28.595	0.000
Disagreed	67	42.72	5.65			

Table 6 shows that the P – value is 0.00, which is below the significance threshold of 0.05, level of significance at df of 304. Thus, the p-value is less than the critical value, which means that there is a notable adoption and usage of AI technologies in Nigerian Colleges of Education. Therefore, the null hypothesis one is rejected. This indicates a marked positive adoption and usage of AI

technologies in Nigerian Colleges of Education.

Hypothesis Two

AI-based learning modules do not significantly enhance content delivery or curriculum alignment for key subject

Table 7: t-test Analysis on AI-based Learning Modules and Content Delivery or Curriculum Alignment in key Subjects

Groups	N	Mean	St. Dev.	df	t	P
Agreed	239	52.79	8.11	304	22.123	0.00
Disagreed	67	31.02	4.52			

Table 7 indicates that the P-value is 0.00, which does not exceed the alpha value of 0.05, level of significance at df of 304. Since the p-value is less than the alpha value, this means that there are significant AI-based learning modules that notably enhance content delivery or curriculum alignment in key subjects. Therefore, the null hypothesis two was rejected. This indicates that there is a significantly positive AI-based learning

module that significantly enhances content delivery or curriculum alignment in key subjects.

Hypothesis Three

AI technologies have no marked impact on students’ academic performance and engagement in learning

Table 8: t-test Analysis on Influence of AI Technologies no notable impact on Students’ Academic Performance and Engagement in Learning

Groups	N	Mean	St. Dev.	df	T	P
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Agreed	258	56.76	12.54	304	23.435	0.00
Disagreed	58	33.50	10.22			

The solution in Table 8 indicates that the P – value is 0.00, which falls below the threshold of 0.05, level of significance at df of 304. As the p-value is below the significance value, AI technologies have a significant influence on students’ academic performance and engagement in learning. Therefore, the null hypothesis three was rejected. This indicates that, there has a substantial impact on

students’ academic performance and engagement in learning.

Hypothesis Four

There is no strong relationship between the availability of resources/infrastructure and effective implementation of AI-based learning.

Table 9: t-test Analysis on Relationship linking Availability of Resources / Infrastructure and the Effective Implementation of AI-based Learning

Groups	N	Mean	St. Dev.	df	T	P
Agreed	275	50.56	7.45	304	10.436	0.00
Disagreed	29	41.34	3.34			

The findings in Table 9 indicate that the P-value is 0.00, which is less than the alpha value of 0.05, with a df of 304. Since the p-value is less than the critical value, there is a meaningful relationship between the availability of resources/infrastructure and the effective implementation of AI-based learning. Therefore, the null hypothesis four was rejected.

Hypothesis Five

NCE teachers and students hold negative or indifferent perceptions toward AI integration in learning.

Table 10: t-test Analysis on NCE Teachers and Students Perceptions Toward AI Integration in Learning.

Groups	N	Mean	St. Dev.	df	t	P
Agreed	262	59.89	9.71	304	26.345	0.00
Disagreed	44	41.70	4.65			

The outcome in Table 10 indicates that the P-value is 0.00, which is below the significance threshold of 0.05, level of significance at df of 304. Since the p-value is less than the alpha value, there is a notable positive perception of NCE teachers and students toward AI integration in learning. Therefore, the null hypothesis five was rejected.

Discussion

There is widespread adoption and active utilization of AI technologies in Nigerian Colleges of Education. This is similar to the findings of Festus and Emmanuel (2024), who found that approximately 19.2% of academic staff in Nigerian colleges of education extensively use AI tools. Similarly, Ngonso et al. (2025) found that most Nigerian students were aware of AI and utilized it, particularly tools such as Chat GPT, which positively impacts their academic performance. There is a notable positive AI-based learning module that significantly enhances content delivery and curriculum alignment in key subjects. This is in line with the study by Eunkyung (2024), who reported that AI systems assess individual learner profiles by adapting content to match their prior knowledge and learning pace. Similarly, Singh (2024) found that AI systems facilitate dynamic curriculum design by generating customized content that aligns with educational goals, ensuring relevance and inclusivity. Ioannou-Sougleridi et al. (2024) found that learning management systems (LMS) enhanced with AI capabilities can activate content generation and personalization, significantly improving user experience educational outcomes. Barde et al. (2024) found that intelligent tutoring systems provide personalized support and facilitate immediate feedback and help, which boosts student engagement and motivation.

Students' academic performance and engagement in learning were significantly enhanced by AI technologies. This aligns with Zhang's (2024) study, which revealed a correlation between AI usage and improved academic performance among students. Students utilizing AI tools generally outperformed their peers. Lestarinigrum et al. (2024) demonstrated that accessible AI materials boost academic performance, with teaching engagement acting as a key mediator. According to Singh (2024) and Lestarinigrum et al. (2024), AI technologies, such as intelligent tutoring and chatbots, enhance student involvement by tailoring content to each learner's unique needs. Learners reported improved motivation and interest in learning due to AI's ability to provide personalized feedback and support, and the availability of sufficient resources and facilities plays a crucial role in the successful implementation of AI-based learning, which is in line with the findings of Hakimi and Shahidzay (2024), who found infrastructure and resource constraints to be the central obstacles to effective AI adoption in developing regions. Similarly, Lavin et al. (2022) opined that AI must be integrated as part of infrastructure, not just as add-on tools to support effective learning.

Students had a significantly positive perception of the integration of AI into learning. Marrone et al. (2024) support this finding, highlighting that AI integration in school curricula fosters a student-centric learning approach and makes learning more enjoyable. It also helps teachers in the teaching and evaluation process and the rest.

Conclusion

Substantial evidence is presented in the investigation, indicating that biology education in Nigerian colleges can be

revolutionized by artificial intelligence. The findings suggest that educators and learners alike have a positive view of AI integration, seeing its potential to enhance student-centered learning through personalized content, adaptive assessments, and flexible curriculum design. The value of AI in addressing resource shortages in education is underscored by its correlation between AI integration and improved student engagement.

Overcoming persistent fundamental obstacles is crucial for the successful adoption of AI innovations. Unreliable electricity, inadequate internet connectivity, and a lack of devices are significant hurdles to adopting AI-driven technologies. The critical link between technological capability and educational quality is underscored by these challenges, with AI's benefits being contingent on foundational investments.

While enthusiasm for AI is evident, its current adoption level is nascent rather than widespread. Most documented usage centers on accessible tools such as chatbots highlight the urgent need for strategic professional development to improve IT literacy and encourage deeper pedagogical integration. This change requires collaboration among legislators, schools, and technology partners to ensure responsible applications, with a focus on data privacy, transparency in algorithms, and cultural relevance.

As Nigeria has reached a critical juncture for educational innovation, this study advocates AI to enhance human expertise rather than replace it. Future initiatives should prioritize context-responsive infrastructure, localized teacher training, and evidence-based policies to fully harness AI's potential to advance

science education and nurture the next generation of biologists in Nigeria.

Recommendation

1. The Federal Government and educational stakeholders must prioritize investments in technical backbones, including uninterrupted electricity supply, and fast and secure online connectivity platforms, particularly in underserved areas.
2. Regular training programmes and workshops should be organized for Biology Education lecturers and students, focusing on AI literacy, ethical usage, and pedagogical integration.
3. Collaborative engagements with tech companies and universities should be pursued to provide hands-on experience with cutting-edge AI tools.
4. The Ministry of Education should develop and enforce AI-in-education policies to address ethical considerations, data protection, algorithmic transparency, and inclusivity.
5. Institutional AI usage guidelines should be crafted to ensure alignment with curriculum objectives while safeguarding learner privacy.
6. AI-enhanced modules should be systematically embedded in Biology Education curricula to ensure dynamic content generation, adaptive assessment, and learner-centered instruction.

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ASSESSMENT OF AI UTILIZATION IN TEACHING AND LEARNING OF BIOLOGY CONCEPTS AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN IGABI, KADUNA-STATE

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This study assess the use of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning of Biology concepts among Secondary Schools in Igabi, Kaduna State. The purpose was to examine the extent to which AI tools and applications are integrated into classroom instruction, identify their impact on students' learning experiences, and highlight challenges affecting their adoption. A descriptive survey design was employed, and data were collected from teachers and students across selected schools using 2 questionnaires titled AI Utilization for Biology Teaching Questionnaire (AIUBTQ) and AI Utilization for Biology Learning Questionnaire (AIUBLQ) which were validated and reliability coefficients of 0.76 and 0.79 were obtained after pilot study. The instrument was analyzed using mean and standard deviation. The findings revealed that while awareness of AI in education is growing, its actual application in Biology classrooms remains limited due to inadequate infrastructure, lack of teacher training, and inconsistent access to digital resources. However, where utilized, AI tools were found to enhance visualization of complex biological concepts, improve student engagement, and support personalized learning. The study concludes that AI holds significant potential for transforming Biology education in Nigerian secondary schools if challenges of accessibility, capacity building, and infrastructural support are adequately addressed. It recommends increased investment in digital infrastructure, targeted teacher professional development, and policy support to promote effective integration of AI in teaching and learning.

Keywords:

Utilization, Artificial Intelligence, Teaching, Learning, Biology, Students

Introduction

The integration of digital technologies into educational systems has rapidly evolved beyond traditional Information and Communication Technology (ICT) tools, with artificial intelligence (AI) now emerging as a transformative force in science education

globally and in Nigeria. Particularly in biology education, with its intrinsic need for visualizing complex processes and facilitating student engagement, AI tools such as virtual labs, adaptive learning platforms, and intelligent tutoring systems

are providing new opportunities for immersive and individualized instruction (Luckin, 2020; Enebechi, 2024; Askarova, 2025). AI-driven applications allow students to explore biological concepts through simulations, automated assessments, and personalized feedback, which have been shown to enhance understanding, retention, and critical thinking compared to conventional methods (Akpan, Akpan & King, 2025; Ajibike, 2025). Recent global and national trends indicate a significant shift in how Biology is taught, spurred further by the remote learning demands of the COVID-19 pandemic (Xu, 2024). The pandemic accelerated adoption of digital learning tools, highlighting the importance of digital and AI literacy for teachers and students (Raja & Nagasubramani, 2018; Daniel, 2020). While these technologies carry immense promise, current studies reveal that integration of AI into secondary Biology education in Nigeria remains limited, especially outside urban centers, due to infrastructure deficits, intermittent electricity, limited internet access, and a persistent gap in teacher capacity (Olufemi, 2021).

National policies, such as the Federal Ministry of Education's (2019) ICT and digital strategy, acknowledge the need for technology-driven learning but implementation remains uneven, particularly in semi-urban and rural areas where resources are scarce and teacher training on AI and related technologies is inadequate (Abubakar et al., 2025). Studies conducted in states like Oyo, Akwa Ibom, and Kaduna underscore that both teachers and students exhibit low awareness and usage of AI tools for Biology instruction, and highlight persistent challenges related to capacity building and curriculum alignment (Oyawole, 2025; Akpan, Akpan & King,

2025). Empirical evidence strongly associates the effective use of AI and ICT tools in Biology with improved academic performance, increased learner motivation, and more interactive classrooms (Ajibike, 2025; Askarova, 2025). Advanced AI platforms now offer features such as real-time feedback, virtual experiments, and automated grading systems that help bridge learning gaps, facilitate differentiation, and support educational inclusion for students from diverse backgrounds (Enebechi, 2024; Reiss, 2021). However, issues of digital divide, inconsistent access, teacher preparedness, and the pedagogical fit of AI with existing curriculum continue to pose substantial barriers across Nigerian schools (Akpan, Akpan & King, 2025; Oyawole, 2025; Ajibike, 2025).

Addressing these challenges through sustained investment in digital infrastructure, targeted professional development for teachers, and policy support is essential to actualize the potential of AI in Biology education. This study investigates the extent and effectiveness of AI utilization in Biology teaching and learning across selected secondary schools in Igabi, Kaduna State, focusing on types of AI technologies employed, their impact on pedagogical practices and student experiences, and the constraints limiting their broader adoption. The findings aim to inform stakeholders, guide future research, and support evidence-based interventions for effective AI integration in Nigerian secondary science education.

Statement of the Problem

Despite the recognized potential of AI to enhance biology education, there remains a substantial gap between their theoretical benefits and the realities encountered in

secondary school classrooms across Nigeria. Recent studies and reports continue to highlight persistent challenges in implementing technology-driven biology instruction, including inadequate infrastructure (such as unreliable internet and insufficient digital devices), limited teacher training, insufficient technical support, and resistance to change among some educators (Bello, 2025; Olawale & Yusuf, 2023; Ojo, 2023). The rapid pace of technological development presents further difficulties for schools attempting to maintain current and relevant resources while contending with budgetary and logistical constraints (Adebayo et al., 2022; Igboegwu et al., 2022). Policy and institutional efforts have recognized these gaps, yet evidence from studies in Kwara, Anambra, Lagos, and Zaria show that actual ICT integration such as AI in biology teaching remains inconsistent and often superficial (Bello, 2025; Ojo, 2023; Okoh, 2016; Samphina, 2025). Additionally, research focusing specifically on biology education rather than science generally is limited, especially regarding how technological tools influence students' conceptual understanding, practical skills development, scientific inquiry, and motivation during times of rapid digital change (Olawale & Yusuf, 2023; Adebayo et al., 2022).

Teacher-related factors such as professional qualifications, gender, and years of classroom experience also strongly affect adoption and use of ICT tools, resulting in variable effectiveness and students' unequal access to technology-enabled learning experiences (Bello, 2025; Igboegwu et al., 2022; Bullard, 2017). Although digital resources such as virtual labs and dynamic simulations foster collaborative and inquiry-based approaches to biology, many schools

struggle with equipment shortages and underutilization of existing tools (Samphina, 2025; Olawale & Yusuf, 2023). Consequently, there is an urgent need for detailed research into ICT usage patterns, effectiveness, challenges, and opportunities in biology teaching and learning at the secondary level, particularly in regions such as Zaria Local Government Area, Kaduna State (Bello, 2025; Adebayo et al., 2022; Ojo, 2023). This study aims to fill these gaps by providing a comprehensive assessment of technology integration, pedagogical outcomes, barriers to adoption, and recommendations for sustainable improvement in Nigerian secondary science education.

Research Objectives

This study seeks to:

Identify and categorize the types of artificial intelligence (AI) tools currently being utilized in biology education among secondary schools in Igabi, Kaduna State.

Evaluate the effectiveness of AI integration on teaching effectiveness, student engagement, and learning outcomes in biology education among secondary schools in Igabi, Kaduna State.

Investigate the challenges faced by teachers and students in adopting, implementing, and utilizing AI tools for biology education in Igabi, Kaduna State.

Research Questions

This study was guided by the following research questions:

What types of artificial intelligence (AI) tools currently being utilized in biology education across selected secondary schools in Igabi, Kaduna State?

How effective is AI integration in enhancing teaching quality and student engagement in

biology education among secondary schools in Igabi, Kaduna State?

What challenges do teachers and students encounter in adopting and utilizing AI tools in biology education among secondary schools in Igabi, Kaduna State?

Methodology

The research design adopted for this study was the descriptive survey research design, suitable for collecting data on respondents' perceptions, opinions, and practices. The population comprised all SS II Biology students and teachers in Igabi Local Government Area, Kaduna State totaling 1,130 students, including one Biology teacher from each of the 13 schools. A total of 291 respondents were selected from the

population as sample size using Krejcie and Morgan's (1970) sample size table to ensure adequate representation of students and teachers. Simple random sampling was employed to select the targeted number of respondents. Data were collected using 2 structured questionnaires titled AI Utilization for Biology Teaching Questionnaire (AIUBTQ) and AI Utilization for Biology Learning Questionnaire (AIUBLQ) designed on a 5-point Likert scale which were validated and reliability coefficients of 0.76 and 0.79 were obtained after pilot study. The researchers personally administered the questionnaires and the collected data were analyzed and presented using frequency distribution tables, percentages, means, and standard deviations, facilitating clarity and ease of interpretation.

Results

Table 1: Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools currently being utilized in Biology Education

S/N	Item Statement	VF	F	O	R	N	X	S.D
1	Use of multimedia projectors during biology lessons	24	149	66	45	7	3.95	0.91
2	Use of educational videos and animations for explaining biological processes	13	77	51	20	130	2.62	1.43
3	Use of biology-related software or simulations (e.g., virtual lab tools)	3	41	90	0	157	2.01	1.12
4	Use of interactive whiteboards or smartboards in the biology classroom	37	72	56	34	92	2.94	1.32
5	Access to online resources (e.g., YouTube, digital textbooks, educational sites)	3	214	15	6	53	3.74	1.13
6	Use of mobile apps or tablets for learning biology concepts	17	146	22	70	36	3.29	1.23
7	Use of computer labs for research and assignments related to biology	38	1	190	52	10	2.96	1.01
8	Integration of Learning Management Systems (e.g., Google Classroom, Edmodo)	2	32	33	132	92	1.97	1.05
9	Use of internet-enabled devices for individual or group learning in biology	137	14	37	15	88	3.57	1.61
10	Use of PowerPoint or other digital presentation tools during biology teaching	48	20	71	3	149	2.71	1.58

Cumulative Mean	2.98
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KEY: VF = Very Frequent, F = Frequently, O = Occasionally, R = Rarely, N= Never, X = Mean, S.D =Standard Deviation

The data indicate that the use of AI and ICT tools in biology education has moderate prevalence among secondary schools in Igabi. Multimedia projectors (mean=3.95) and access to online resources (mean=3.74) are the most utilized tools, suggesting preference for widely accessible and familiar technologies. The use of interactive whiteboards and computer labs have moderate usage (means around 2.9 to 3.0), while integration of learning management

systems has the lowest utilization (mean=1.97), pointing to gaps in infrastructural and technical deployment. Use of biology-specific software and virtual labs also remains low (mean=2.01), indicating potential areas for growth. Overall, the cumulative mean (2.98) reveals moderate adoption of AI-related technologies with significant room for expansion to improve teaching and learning outcomes.

Table 2: Effectiveness of AI Integration on Teaching and Student Engagement in Biology

S/N	Item Statement	VE	E	ME	SE	NEA	\bar{X}	S.D.
1	AI tools make biology lessons more interactive and engaging	101	27	39	17	107	3.07	1.64
2	AI facilitates easier understanding of difficult biology concepts	41	32	45	69	104	2.35	1.34
3	AI increase student participation and attentiveness in biology	101	70	36	24	60	3.56	1.40
4	AI enables teachers to deliver more organised and effective lessons	62	60	39	28	102	2.92	1.52
5	AI encourage collaborative learning among students	14	26	39	99	113	2.01	1.10
6	AI increase student motivation and enthusiasm for biology learning	92	42	66	47	44	3.33	1.35
7	AI support differentiated instruction to meet diverse learners' needs	17	23	39	95	117	1.99	1.09
8	AI use improves student retention and recall of biology knowledge	68	92	36	40	55	3.44	1.33
9	AI help teachers manage time and resources more effectively	64	53	48	54	72	2.89	1.38
10	AI integration supports continuous assessment and feedback	64	27	59	98	36	2.72	1.32
Cumulative Mean							2.83	

KEY: VE = Very Effective, E = Effective, ME = Moderately Effective, SE = Slightly Effective, NEA = Not Effect at All

The data in Table 2 indicate a moderate perception of AI and ICT effectiveness in enhancing biology teaching and student engagement, with an overall mean score of 2.83 on a 5-point Likert scale. The highest rated items relate to increased student participation and attentiveness (mean = 3.56) and improved student motivation and enthusiasm through AI integration (mean = 3.33). Conversely, differentiated instruction support through AI tools received the lowest effectiveness rating (mean = 1.99), highlighting limited impact in catering to diverse learner needs. Items like improving lesson interactivity scored moderately (mean

= 3.07), while AI's role in simplifying difficult concepts and supporting continuous assessment were perceived as less effective (means = 2.35 and 2.72, respectively). These varied perceptions underscore that while AI and ICT hold promise in specific aspects of biology education, their broad effectiveness may be constrained by factors like access, teacher readiness, and tool sophistication. These findings suggest a cautiously optimistic view of AI integration benefits, tempered by challenges that require attention to maximize the potential of AI-enhanced biology education.

Table 3: Challenges in Adopting, Implementing and Utilizing AI tools in Biology Education

S/N	Item Statements	SA	A	UN	D	SD	\bar{X}	S.D.
1	Inadequate access to AI tools for teaching Biology	118	95	4	54	20	4.02	1.06
2	Poor internet connectivity hinders access to online biology resources	113	91	0	27	60	3.93	1.29
3	Many biology teachers lack adequate training in AI tools	109	95	2	63	23	3.93	1.19
4	Technical support for maintaining AI tools is insufficient	106	92	0	67	26	3.84	1.22
5	Shortage of relevant digital biology content/resources	104	90	4	31	60	3.80	1.29
6	Frequent power outages disrupt AI-based biology lessons	120	99	0	22	50	4.04	1.19
7	Some teachers resist adopting AI in their teaching methods	100	95	0	45	51	3.79	1.28
8	School administrators provide inadequate support for AI integration	108	93	4	62	23	3.89	1.15
9	Many students lack basic digital skills required for using AI	113	97	0	22	59	3.93	1.24
10	Large class sizes make utilization of AI tools in biology lessons difficult	116	100	4	50	17	4.03	1.10
Cumulative Mean							3.92	

KEY: SA = Strongly Agree, A = Agree, UN = Undecided, D = Disagree, SD = Strongly Disagree

The table highlights the major challenges faced by biology educators and students in adopting, implementing, and utilizing AI and ICT tools in biology education. With a cumulative mean score of 3.92, these challenges are significant and broadly recognized. The highest mean score (4.04) corresponds to frequent power outages disrupting AI-based lessons, emphasizing infrastructural unreliability as a key barrier. Lack of access to AI/ICT tools (mean = 4.02) and large class sizes (mean = 4.03) are also critical issues. Poor internet connectivity, insufficient teacher training, inadequate technical support, and resistance among educators further compound the challenges. Student digital literacy deficits and weak administrative support round out the main constraints. The data indicate that infrastructural deficiencies, capacity gaps, and organizational support collectively hinder effective AI integration in biology classrooms, underscoring the need for comprehensive interventions targeting these areas

Discussion of Findings

The finding of moderate AI tool utilization in biology education across selected secondary schools in Igabi aligns with global and national research highlighting infrastructure and human capacity as limiting factors. For example, Adu, Olatundun, and Adeyanju (2020) reported that although many Nigerian schools have basic ICT facilities, actual usage is limited due to poor maintenance, low digital literacy among teachers, and unstable power supply. Similarly, Olufemi and Adedokun (2021) found that AI-based instructional strategies in biology classrooms were often hampered by insufficient teacher training and inadequate integration within

pedagogical frameworks. Echoing this, Chen, Wang, and Liao (2021) emphasized that mobile learning applications require not only access but also active teacher engagement and alignment with the curriculum to be effective. Chauhan's (2017) meta-analysis further supported that while AI tools boost student engagement, their potential remains underutilized in contexts beset by systemic challenges. Chen et al. (2020) emphasized that digital literacy and student engagement are persistent barriers unless intentionally incorporated into educational planning. The observed moderate utilization thus reflects a transitional phase where infrastructure is available but not effectively leveraged for pedagogical impact.

The perception of low to moderate AI integration effectiveness in biology teaching and student engagement mirrors broader concerns regarding meaningful digital transformation in education. Chen and Wu (2023) argued that despite widespread AI availability, actual learning outcomes depend on contextual relevance and teacher competence. Baran and AlZoubi (2022) found that collaborative digital tools improve science learning only if supported by robust teacher training and curriculum adaptation. Chen et al. (2020) noted that mere technological access does not guarantee engagement; content must be thoughtfully adapted to students' needs. Similarly, Cheng and Xie (2018) observed that teachers' value beliefs and Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) significantly influence AI adoption, aligning with Mishra and Koehler's (2006) framework advocating for the integration of content, pedagogy, and technology. Hence, the moderate effectiveness ratings reflect shortcomings in

pedagogical integration, digital skills, and strategic AI tool deployment in biology education.

The strong agreement among respondents that challenges to AI adoption, implementation, and utilization persist reflects findings from diverse studies in developing nations. Adu et al. (2020) identified unreliable electricity, poor internet connectivity, and inadequate technical support as persistent obstacles to ICT use in Nigerian schools. Lawrence and Tar (2018) highlighted infrastructural and administrative constraints that hinder AI adoption in developing contexts. Chen et al. (2020) further indicated that limited student engagement results when schools lack digital scaffolding, coherent curriculum support, and ICT policy frameworks. Karolčík, Drlík, and Pinterová (2017) demonstrated that teacher readiness is critical for AI adoption, pointing to the need for targeted professional development to address digital skill gaps. Ghavifekr and Rosdy (2015) stressed the significance of institutional support, ongoing training, and motivation to overcome systemic barriers to effective AI integration. Collectively, these studies underscore that without addressing foundational infrastructural and human capacity challenges, AI implementation in biology education will continue to face significant limitations regardless of tool availability.

Conclusion

This study reveals that while artificial intelligence holds significant promise for transforming biology education in secondary schools, its current integration is moderate and faces several obstacles. The availability of AI tools and digital infrastructures alone does not guarantee their effective use; factors such as teacher readiness, training, and

pedagogical alignment are crucial for realizing AI's potential to improve student understanding, engagement, and motivation. The findings suggest that AI is beginning to enhance visualization and personalized learning in biology but remains underutilized due to infrastructural limitations, inconsistent support, and a lack of capacity building. Thus, AI's transformative power in biology education is still an emerging reality that requires systemic efforts to bridge the gap between technological possibilities and classroom realities. Addressing these challenges goes beyond providing equipment; it requires comprehensive strategies including targeted professional development, adequate policy frameworks, and investments in reliable digital infrastructure to ensure equitable access and sustained adoption. The role of teachers as facilitators who skillfully integrate AI into teaching practices remains central, complementing AI's capabilities rather than replacing human interaction. Ultimately, fostering an enabling environment that embraces technological innovation with pedagogical sensitivity will be critical to fully harness AI's potential, driving improved learning outcomes and preparing students in Igabi and beyond for the demands of the digital era.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made by the researcher:

Government and educational stakeholders should prioritize substantial investment in reliable digital infrastructure including stable electricity, high-speed internet connectivity, and provision of AI-enabled devices and software to secondary schools across Igabi.

Organize continuous, competency-based training programs for biology teachers focused on effective pedagogical integration of AI tools.

Government should develop and enforce clear institutional policies that promote AI integration in biology education, including funding provisions, curriculum enhancement, and resource allocation.

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ASSESSMENT OF AI UTILIZATION IN TEACHING AND LEARNING OF BIOLOGY CONCEPTS AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN IGABI, KADUNA-STATE

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The rapid digital transformation of education has positioned Artificial Intelligence (AI) as a transformative force in English language teaching and learning (ELT). This study investigated how innovative pedagogical practices can be effectively integrated with AI to enhance instructional quality, foster learner autonomy, and deliver personalized learning experiences. Drawing on contemporary pedagogical models, the study outlines practical strategies for AI adoption in language classrooms, supported by illustrative applications in the Nigerian context. It also critically examines the ethical considerations surrounding AI use in education, including data privacy, equity, infrastructural limitations, and pedagogical integrity. The study concludes by presenting a structured framework that enables educators to responsibly harness AI's potential, ensuring that it serves as a tool for meaningful and inclusive English language education in Nigeria.

Keywords:
Artificial Intelligence,
Innovative Pedagogy,
English language
Teaching.

Introduction

Contemporary scholarship emphasizes that education in the 21st century is fundamentally reshaped by globalization, digitization, and the rapid diffusion of new technologies. Among these, Artificial Intelligence (AI) has emerged as a particularly powerful force, provoking debates about the future of pedagogy, teacher roles, and learner engagement (Zawacki-Richter, Marín, Bond, & Gouverneur, 2019; Williamson & Piattoeva, 2022). Education is

no longer confined to traditional classroom practices; instead, it is increasingly mediated by intelligent systems that analyze learner behavior, provide adaptive feedback, and support new forms of knowledge construction. These shifts compel educators and researchers to reimagine what counts as effective teaching and meaningful learning in a digitally mediated world.

Within this broader transformation, English Language Teaching (ELT) occupies a special position. As the global lingua franca, English continues to be a gateway for academic advancement, socio-economic participation, and international communication. ELT has therefore been a testing ground for technological innovations that promise to improve learner outcomes, enhance communicative competence, and foster global citizenship (Holmes, Bialik, & Fadel, 2022; Ferguson, Coughlan, & Herodotou, 2019). AI-driven approaches are now at the center of these debates, as intelligent tutoring systems, natural language processing applications, and adaptive assessment tools offer new pathways for achieving personalization, creativity, and learner autonomy (Little, 2020; Zhao, 2021).

However, while global enthusiasm for AI in education is growing, scholars caution that the benefits of technology are neither universal nor automatic. In high-resource contexts, AI adoption is supported by reliable infrastructure, strong teacher training, and sustained policy investments (Luckin, 2018). By contrast, in low- and middle-income countries, infrastructural limitations, high implementation costs, and uneven digital literacy complicate integration (Tella, 2020; Adewale, 2023). This raises critical questions about whether and how AI can be adapted to local realities, especially in African nations where educational challenges remain acute.

For Nigeria, these questions are particularly pressing because English language is both the official language and the primary medium of instruction across all educational levels. Proficiency in English language remains essential for academic progression, access to higher education, and participation in global opportunities (Chukwuma & Bello, 2021).

However, systemic challenges, including overcrowded classrooms, shortage of qualified teachers, limited instructional materials, and stark urban–rural disparities, continue to undermine ELT effectiveness (Umar & Adeniran, 2023). Many Nigerian students complete their years of schooling without achieving communicative competence, reflecting the deep structural obstacles facing language education.

The integration of AI into English language education has several benefits. AI provides instant and continuous feedback, enabling learners to identify and correct errors in real-time, thereby accelerating the development of language skills (Jegede, 2024). It supports highly personalized learning by tailoring instructional paths to individual students' strengths, weaknesses, and pace, thus enhancing the effectiveness of teaching and learning (Jegede, 2024). Interactive and game-like features increase learner engagement and motivation, making lessons more enjoyable and dynamic (Liu et al., 2025). AI can also deliver high-quality language practice to large numbers of learners simultaneously, mitigating resource constraints and classroom overcrowding (World Bank, 2024). Furthermore, AI equips teachers with data-driven insights into student performance, facilitating informed instructional decisions and targeted support (World Bank, 2024). Collectively, these benefits position AI as a transformative tool capable of supporting both learners and educators, provided that it is applied within innovative and context-sensitive pedagogical models.

Adaptive learning platforms could address learner heterogeneity, chatbots could provide conversational practice via widely used platforms such as WhatsApp, and automated

writing evaluation tools could supplement teacher feedback for tertiary students (Eze & Olatunji, 2022). At the same time, ethical concerns about data privacy, cultural relevance, and over-reliance on machines cannot be ignored (Williamson & Piattoeva, 2022). The challenge, therefore, is not whether AI can transform ELT but how it can be responsibly integrated within innovative pedagogical models that reflect Nigeria's socio-cultural and infrastructural realities.

By situating Nigeria within global debates while foregrounding its unique educational context, this paper contributes to the emerging scholarship on AI in African education and underscores the need for context-sensitive, ethical, and innovative approaches to pedagogical reform. The paper examines the intersection of innovative pedagogy and AI integration in English language teaching and learning in Nigeria. The central argument is that while AI holds transformative potential for ELT, its value lies not in the technology itself, but in its pedagogical application. Only when AI is embedded within innovative, learner-centered approaches and adapted to Nigeria's socio-cultural and infrastructural realities can it meaningfully contribute to inclusive, equitable, and effective English language education.

Objectives of the study:

To critically examine global and Nigerian perspectives on AI integration in ELT, highlighting innovative pedagogical strategies and contextual challenges.

To propose a localized and sustainable framework for responsible AI adoption in Nigerian ELT

Conceptual Framework and Literature Review

Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Educational Contexts

Artificial Intelligence (AI) encompasses computer systems designed to perform tasks traditionally requiring human intelligence, such as learning, reasoning, and natural language processing (Russell & Norvig, 2021). Its application in English Language Teaching (ELT) is primarily realized through tools like intelligent tutoring systems, automated writing evaluation, and conversational agents, many powered by the sub-field of Natural Language Processing (NLP). The integration of AI in education represents a paradigm shift, moving beyond technological adoption to fundamentally reshape pedagogical processes and language acquisition.

The Imperative for Innovative Pedagogy

Innovative pedagogy is characterized not by the mere inclusion of technology but by a re-conceptualization of the roles of teachers, learners, and instructional content to foster transformative, learner-centered experiences (Ferguson, Coughlan & Herodotou, 2019). Grounded in constructivist and socio-cultural theories, it prioritizes critical thinking, collaboration, and personalization. Within Nigeria's ELT landscape, this necessitates a decisive shift from rigid, exam-focused instruction towards methodologies that cultivate communicative competence and critical literacy.

Personalized Learning and Learner Autonomy

AI is a potent enabler of personalized learning, which tailors instruction to individual learners' needs, pace, and styles by dynamically adjusting content and feedback (Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019). This is

particularly relevant in Nigeria, where large class sizes often preclude individualized teacher attention. Closely linked is the concept of learner autonomy, the capacity of students to take charge of their own learning (Little, 2020). AI supports autonomy by providing self-paced, interactive environments for practice and experimentation, a crucial counterbalance to teacher-dominated traditions and a step towards fostering essential lifelong learning skills.

Inclusive Education through AI

Inclusive education mandates equitable access to quality learning for all students, irrespective of background or ability (Federal Ministry of Education, 2021). AI can advance this goal through assistive technologies such as text-to-speech, speech-to-text, and translation tools that support learners with disabilities and those in Nigeria's multilingual context. However, scholars like Adewale (2023) caution that without deliberate localization, AI risks reinforcing existing socio-economic and linguistic inequalities rather than mitigating them.

AI Applications in the Nigerian ELT Context

Adaptive Learning Systems: These AI-powered platforms address classroom heterogeneity by adjusting content difficulty based on real-time learner performance, ensuring students operate within their zone of proximal development (Luckin, 2018). This is critical in Nigeria, where wide variance in English proficiency makes standardized instruction ineffective (Okonkwo, 2021).

AI Chatbots: Leveraging the ubiquity of mobile platforms like WhatsApp, chatbots offer low-cost, accessible opportunities for

conversational practice and task-based learning, simulating authentic communicative scenarios (Chukwuma & Bello, 2021).

Automated Writing Evaluation (AWE): Tools such as Grammarly provide immediate feedback on grammar and coherence, areas where Nigerian students often struggle. When used to complement rather than replace teacher feedback, AWE supports a flipped classroom model where class time is reserved for higher-order collaborative work (Zhao, 2021).

Ethical and Practical Consideration:

The adoption of AI is not without significant challenges:

Data Privacy: The collection of extensive learner data poses serious risks in contexts with underdeveloped legal frameworks, necessitating robust data protection policies and digital literacy (Adewale, 2023; Williamson & Piattoeva, 2022).

The Digital Divide: AI may exacerbate inequalities between urban and rural schools, highlighting a "second digital divide" rooted in infrastructure and trained personnel (Umar & Adeniran, 2023).

Algorithmic and Cultural Bias: AI systems trained on foreign data can perpetuate linguistic prejudice by misclassifying features of Nigerian English as errors and failing to recognize local accents or cultural contexts (Holmes et al., 2022; Tella, 2020). This underscores the urgent need for localized AI development.

Dehumanization of Learning: An over-reliance on AI could marginalize the essential human elements of mentorship, empathy, and cultural contextualization that teachers

provide (Little, 2020). Educators must remain central as mediators of technology.

Infrastructural Deficits: Unreliable electricity, limited internet access, and high costs present fundamental barriers to sustainable implementation (Umar & Adeniran, 2023).

The conceptual review provided a foundation by clarifying key ideas such as Artificial Intelligence, innovative pedagogy, personalization, and inclusion in education. To build on these concepts, it is essential to examine how scholars have engaged with AI in English Language Teaching and Learning (ELT) globally, across Africa, and within Nigeria. The following authorial review synthesizes relevant studies, highlighting key contributions, contextual challenges, and gaps that this paper seeks to address.

Authorial Review

Global Perspectives on AI in ELT

Globally, Artificial Intelligence (AI) has been recognized as a transformative force in education. Holmes et al. (2022) describe AI as a driver of adaptive feedback, personalized learning pathways, and large-scale educational delivery. Zhao (2021) emphasizes AI's multimodal features, such as speech recognition, visual aids, and adaptive testing, which support diverse learning styles and increase learner engagement. Similarly, Russell and Norvig (2021) situate AI within computational intelligence theories, highlighting its role in automating writing evaluation, translation, and interactive dialogue practice.

Several scholars have highlighted how AI enhances learner autonomy and personalization. Luckin (2018) observes that adaptive platforms continuously analyze

student performance to provide customized content, enabling learners to progress at their own pace. Zawacki-Richter et al. (2019), in a large-scale systematic review, conclude that AI strengthens formative assessment, motivates learners through gamification, and offers teachers actionable insights through data analytics. Ferguson, Coughlan, and Herodotou (2019) add that AI-driven pedagogical designs can foster creativity, collaboration, and critical thinking skills essential for 21st-century education.

Despite these benefits, global scholars also raise important concerns. Williamson and Piattoeva (2022) caution that AI may reinforce neoliberal values of surveillance and efficiency, potentially prioritizing data over human relationships. Holmes et al. (2022) noted that algorithmic bias and lack of transparency can lead to inequitable outcomes if not carefully addressed. These debates underscore that AI's effectiveness depends on ethical safeguards and its integration within sound pedagogical frameworks.

African Perspectives on AI in Education

In Africa, scholars are beginning to explore how AI can address systemic educational challenges. Tella (2020) notes that AI could help mitigate teacher shortages across sub-Saharan Africa, particularly in large, under-resourced classrooms. Similarly, Okonkwo (2021) argues that AI tutoring systems can bridge gaps in teacher availability, especially in rural areas where access to quality instruction is limited.

Empirical evidence from Nigerian universities further demonstrates AI's potential. Eze and Olatunji (2022) report that AI-powered writing assistants significantly improved students' academic writing by

providing instant, individualized feedback. Adewale (2023) highlights AI's role in higher education reform, particularly in reducing teachers' grading burdens and supporting blended learning approaches. However, these scholars also point to infrastructural barriers such as unreliable electricity, high internet costs, and limited digital literacy, which hinder widespread adoption.

African researchers emphasize the importance of localization and cultural relevance. As Tella (2020) warns, uncritically importing Western-designed AI tools may marginalize African learners by overlooking local linguistic practices, code-switching, and cultural norms. This highlights the need for African-led AI innovations that reflect the continent's multilingual and multicultural educational environments.

Nigerian Scholarship on AI in ELT

Within Nigeria, studies on AI in English Language Teaching are emerging but already show both promise and challenges. Umar and Adeniran (2023) argue that AI can enable personalized learning in secondary schools, a significant intervention given overcrowded classrooms and wide disparities in student proficiency levels. Chukwuma and Bello (2021) propose integrating AI-powered chatbots into platforms such as WhatsApp and Telegram to provide accessible conversational English practice, particularly for rural learners with limited exposure to authentic English interactions.

At the tertiary level, Eze and Olatunji (2022) demonstrate that AI-driven automated writing evaluation (AWE) systems enhance students' grammar, vocabulary, and cohesion by delivering immediate feedback. These

findings align with global research on AWE as a scalable tool for improving writing instruction (Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019). Nevertheless, Adewale (2023) cautions that AI should complement rather than replace teachers, who play vital roles in fostering creativity, cultural contextualization, and emotional support within the learning process.

Identified Gaps
While literature on AI in education is expanding, three critical gaps remain, particularly in the Nigerian context:

Contextual Adaptation:
Most global studies assume high-resource settings with stable infrastructure, whereas few address how AI can be effectively adapted to Nigeria's socio-economic and infrastructural realities.

Pedagogical Integration:
Although Nigerian scholars acknowledge AI's potential, there is limited focus on how AI can be systematically embedded within innovative pedagogical approaches such as flipped learning, task-based language teaching (TBLT), and gamification.

Ethical and Equity Concerns:
Global discussions highlight issues like data privacy, algorithmic bias, and the digital divide (Williamson & Piattoeva, 2022), yet these concerns are scarcely addressed in Nigerian-focused studies.

Given these identified gaps, it becomes essential to investigate how AI can be effectively integrated into Nigeria's ELT context in a way that is contextually relevant, pedagogically sound, and ethically grounded. To achieve this, the next section outlines the methodological approach adopted in this study, detailing the research design, data

collection, and analytical procedures that informed the development of the proposed framework.

Methodology

This study adopted a conceptual research design anchored in a systematic review of literature on AI integration in ELT.

Data Collection: Scholarly articles, conference papers, and policy documents were retrieved from Google Scholar, ResearchGate, and institutional repositories. The search focused on publications between 2018 and 2025 using keywords such as AI in ELT, innovative pedagogy, personalized learning, and Nigeria. Inclusion criteria required that studies discuss AI applications in language education or address pedagogical, ethical, or infrastructural concerns relevant to the Nigerian context.

Data Analysis: Selected literature was thematically analyzed to identify recurring themes. These themes informed the development of a four-pillar framework focusing on teacher training, localization, equity, and ethical governance. This systematic approach ensured a rigorous foundation for practical recommendations.

Findings: Four-Pillar Framework for AI Integration

The thematic analysis of literature on AI integration in English Language Teaching (ELT) revealed four dominant and interrelated themes that capture the opportunities, challenges, and contextual realities shaping the use of AI in Nigeria's education system. These themes form what this study conceptualizes as a Four-Pillar Framework, which reflects patterns consistently identified across global, African, and Nigerian scholarship.

The pillars do not represent prescriptive recommendations, but rather synthesized insights drawn from recurring discussions in the reviewed studies. Each pillar highlights a critical dimension that must be considered for effective, context-sensitive AI adoption in ELT.

Pillar 1: Teacher Training and Professional Development Across the reviewed literature, teachers consistently emerged as central actors in the successful integration of AI into language classrooms. Studies such as Ferguson et al. (2019) and Tella (2020) highlight that AI tools are often underutilized or misapplied when teachers lack sufficient knowledge and confidence in their use.

Patterns in the data indicate that while AI can provide personalized feedback and support innovative teaching, its effectiveness depends on teacher competence and agency. Several studies document a gap in teacher preparedness, with many educators unfamiliar with AI-driven applications like chatbots, adaptive testing platforms, and automated writing evaluators. This finding suggests that professional development must extend beyond basic digital literacy to include critical reflection on when and how AI should be deployed to complement rather than replace human judgment.

Thus, the literature collectively identifies teacher training as a foundational requirement for AI integration. Importantly, this pillar underscores the need to conceptualize teachers not merely as technology users but as mediators and innovators who shape how AI is embedded in classroom practice.

Pillar 2: Localization and Cultural Adaptation

Another recurring theme across the reviewed studies is the misalignment between imported AI tools and local linguistic realities. Research by Tella (2020), Okonkwo (2021), and Umar & Adeniran (2023) emphasizes that many AI applications are developed for Western contexts and fail to account for features of Nigerian English, code-switching, and diverse cultural practices.

The literature documents instances where AI systems misinterpret common Nigerian English expressions as grammatical errors or where speech recognition tools struggle with African accents. These mismatches can lead to learner frustration and disengagement.

The reviewed scholarship therefore points to localization as a critical factor for meaningful AI adoption. Localization involves not only training AI systems on Nigerian linguistic data but also ensuring that learning content reflects the cultural contexts and everyday realities of Nigerian students. By doing so, AI tools become more relevant, accessible, and empowering rather than alienating.

Pillar 3: Equity and Access

Equity emerged as a dominant theme in studies examining the potential and pitfalls of AI in education. Scholars such as Umar and Adeniran (2023) and Eze & Olatunji (2022) highlight that without deliberate planning, AI integration risks widening the digital divide between urban and rural schools, or between affluent and low-income learners.

The literature reveals that infrastructural barriers, including unreliable electricity, high data costs, and limited internet connectivity remain persistent challenges in Nigeria. Several studies report that AI initiatives often reach urban schools first, leaving rural areas behind.

Patterns across the data suggest that equitable AI integration requires addressing these disparities through inclusive policies, affordable access strategies, and monitoring systems that track how AI adoption affects marginalized groups. This theme underscores that technological advancement alone does not guarantee educational transformation; it must be accompanied by structural interventions that promote inclusion.

Pillar 4: Ethical Governance and Sustainability

The final theme identified in the literature centers on ethics and sustainability. Across multiple studies, concerns were raised about data privacy, algorithmic bias, and the long-term viability of AI initiatives in education (Adewale, 2023; Williamson & Piattoeva, 2022).

The reviewed literature consistently highlights that without clear guidelines on how student data is collected, stored, and used, AI adoption could lead to breaches of trust and surveillance-related harms. Furthermore, evidence suggests that many AI projects in Nigeria are pilot programs that lack stable funding or institutional continuity, resulting in short-lived interventions that do not lead to systemic change.

This theme emphasizes the importance of conceptualizing AI integration not as a one-time innovation but as part of a sustained educational reform process. Governance structures must be transparent and accountable, while policies should evolve alongside technological developments to ensure long-term relevance and public confidence.

Summary of Emergent Themes

The Four-Pillar Framework encapsulates the patterns and themes consistently identified

across the reviewed studies. The Table below summarizes these pillars and their key focus areas.

Pillar	Core Focus	Key Strategies/Components
1. Teacher Training & Professional Development	Building teacher capacity for effective AI use and integration in ELT.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Continuous professional development on AI literacy and pedagogy. - Mentorship and peer-learning networks. - Integration of AI training into teacher education curricula. - Incentives and recognition for innovative practice.
2. Localization & Cultural Adaptation	Ensuring AI tools reflect Nigeria's linguistic and cultural realities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop AI tools trained on Nigerian English and local dialects. - Incorporate culturally relevant learning materials. - Engage local educators and linguists in tool design and evaluation.
3. Equity & Access	Bridging the digital divide to ensure inclusive AI adoption.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Affordable and accessible devices for rural and underserved schools. - Public-private partnerships to subsidize internet/data costs. - Mobile-first AI solutions for areas with limited infrastructure. - Monitoring systems to track inclusion and effectiveness.
4. Ethical Governance & Sustainability	Promoting trust, privacy, and long-term viability of AI in education.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Clear policies for data privacy and responsible AI use. - Oversight and accountability mechanisms. - Stable funding streams for AI initiatives. - Continuous evaluation and policy updates to maintain relevance.

As summarized in the Table above, each pillar addresses a critical dimension of AI integration, collectively forming a holistic strategy for sustainable and inclusive educational transformation in Nigeria. The next section discusses the implications of this

framework for teaching practice, policymaking, and future research, highlighting how these pillars can be operationalized within Nigeria's educational landscape.

Discussion and Implications

The four-pillar framework emerging from this study's thematic analysis provides a conceptual structure for understanding the opportunities and challenges of integrating Artificial Intelligence (AI) into English Language Teaching (ELT) in Nigeria. It bridges the gap between global AI-driven innovations and the realities of Nigeria's education system, which faces issues of limited resources, overcrowded classrooms, and infrastructural constraints. By situating AI within a pedagogically sound and ethically responsible framework, this study contributes to a growing body of scholarship emphasizing that technology must be adapted to local contexts to be effective and sustainable.

The findings align with global trends, where AI is increasingly used to personalize learning and support innovative pedagogy (Holmes et al., 2022; Luckin, 2018). However, unlike high-resource countries where AI adoption is supported by robust infrastructure and policies, Nigeria's context requires careful adaptation. This highlights the unique contribution of this framework, which foregrounds localization, equity, and sustainability as non-negotiable elements for AI integration. It shows that without deliberate planning, AI could exacerbate inequalities rather than reduce them, echoing concerns raised by Williamson and Piattoeva (2022) about algorithmic bias and surveillance in education.

Implications for Practice

For teachers, this study emphasizes the need to view AI as a supportive tool rather than a replacement for human judgment. AI-driven platforms can help identify learners' needs, provide instant feedback, and facilitate personalized instruction. However, effective use of AI depends on teachers' ability to

integrate these tools within innovative pedagogical models such as flipped classrooms and task-based learning. Professional development programs should therefore focus on building teachers' digital competence, critical thinking, and reflective practice.

Implications for Policy

From a policy perspective, the framework calls for a coordinated national strategy for AI in education. This includes government investment in infrastructure, especially in rural areas, and the development of clear regulations on data privacy and ethical use. Policies should also prioritize inclusive access to AI resources, ensuring that marginalized groups are not left behind. By establishing partnerships with private sector stakeholders, telecom companies, and NGOs, Nigeria can reduce costs, expand reach, and foster innovation while maintaining public accountability.

Implications for Research

The framework opens several avenues for future research. These include longitudinal studies on the impact of AI-enhanced pedagogy on language learning outcomes, particularly in multilingual contexts like Nigeria. Research should also examine teachers' and learners' perceptions of AI, exploring issues of trust, motivation, and autonomy. Comparative studies across African countries could provide insights into best practices and scalable models for localized AI adoption.

Conclusion

This study has explored the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) into English Language Teaching (ELT) in Nigeria through a four-pillar framework that emphasizes teacher training, localization, equity, and

ethical governance. By critically examining global trends alongside Nigerian realities, the framework offers a context-sensitive roadmap for leveraging AI to enhance language education.

The findings underscore that successful AI integration depends not only on technological advancement but also on human capacity, cultural relevance, and inclusive policies. AI must be seen as a tool to support, rather than replace the teacher's role while fostering personalized, learner-centered pedagogy.

Looking ahead, the study calls for a coordinated national strategy to embed AI in education policy, develop localized technologies, and expand access to underserved communities. Future research should examine the long-term impacts of AI on language learning, teacher development, and educational equity, while continuously addressing ethical and governance concerns.

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INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGY AND THE INTEGRATION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING AND LEARNING IN NIGERIA

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The rapid digital transformation of education has positioned Artificial Intelligence (AI) as a transformative force in English language teaching and learning (ELT). This paper investigates how innovative pedagogical practices can be effectively integrated with AI to enhance instructional quality, foster learner autonomy, and deliver personalized learning experiences. Drawing on contemporary pedagogical models, the study outlines practical strategies for AI adoption in language classrooms, supported by illustrative applications in the Nigerian context. It also critically examines ethical considerations surrounding AI use in education, including data privacy, equity, infrastructural limitations, and pedagogical integrity. The paper concludes by presenting a structured framework that enables educators to harness AI's potential responsibly, ensuring it serves as a tool for meaningful and inclusive English language education in Nigeria.

Keywords:

Artificial Intelligence (AI), innovative pedagogy, English language teaching, personalized learning, learner autonomy, inclusive education.

Introduction

Contemporary scholarship emphasizes that education in the 21st century is being fundamentally reshaped by globalization, digitization, and the rapid diffusion of new technologies. Among these, Artificial Intelligence (AI) has emerged as a particularly powerful force, provoking debates about the future of pedagogy, teacher roles, and learner engagement (Zawacki-Richter, Marín, Bond, & Gouverneur, 2019;

Williamson & Piattoeva, 2022). Education is no longer confined to traditional classroom practices; instead, it is increasingly mediated by intelligent systems that analyze learner behavior, provide adaptive feedback, and support new forms of knowledge construction. These shifts compel educators and researchers alike to reimagine what counts as effective teaching and meaningful learning in a digitally mediated world.

Within this broader transformation, English Language Teaching (ELT) occupies a special position. As the global lingua franca, English continues to be the gateway to academic advancement, socio-economic participation, and international communication. ELT has therefore been a testing ground for technological innovations that promise to improve learner outcomes, enhance communicative competence, and foster global citizenship (Holmes, Bialik, & Fadel, 2022; Ferguson, Coughlan, & Herodotou, 2019). AI-driven approaches are now at the center of these debates, as intelligent tutoring systems, natural language processing applications, and adaptive assessment tools offer new pathways for achieving personalization, creativity, and learner autonomy (Little, 2020; Zhao, 2021).

Yet, while global enthusiasm for AI in education is growing, scholars caution that the benefits of technology are neither universal nor automatic. In high-resource contexts, AI adoption is supported by reliable infrastructure, strong teacher training, and sustained policy investment (Luckin, 2018). In contrast, in low- and middle-income countries, infrastructural limitations, high implementation costs, and uneven digital literacy complicate integration (Tella, 2020; Adewale, 2023). This raises critical questions about whether and how AI can be adapted to local realities, especially in African nations where educational challenges remain acute.

For Nigeria, these questions are particularly pressing because English is both the official language and the primary medium of instruction across all educational levels. Proficiency in English remains essential for academic progression, access to higher education, and participation in global opportunities (Chukwuma & Bello, 2021).

However, systemic challenges, including overcrowded classrooms, shortages of qualified teachers, limited instructional materials, and stark urban–rural disparities, continue to undermine ELT effectiveness (Umar & Adeniran, 2023). Many Nigerian students complete years of schooling without achieving communicative competence, reflecting the deep structural obstacles facing language education.

The integration of AI into English language education presents several significant benefits. AI provides instant and continuous feedback, enabling learners to identify and correct errors in real time, thereby accelerating the development of language skills (Jegede, 2024). It supports highly personalized learning by tailoring instructional paths to individual students' strengths, weaknesses, and pace, enhancing the effectiveness of teaching and learning (Jegede, 2024). Interactive and game-like features increase learner engagement and motivation, making lessons more enjoyable and dynamic (Liu et al., 2025). AI can also deliver high-quality language practice to large numbers of learners simultaneously, mitigating resource constraints and classroom overcrowding (World Bank, 2024). Furthermore, AI equips teachers with data-driven insights into student performance, facilitating informed instructional decisions and targeted support (World Bank, 2024). Collectively, these benefits position AI as a transformative tool capable of supporting both learners and educators, provided it is applied within innovative and context-sensitive pedagogical models.

Adaptive learning platforms could address learner heterogeneity, chatbots could provide conversational practice via widely used

platforms such as WhatsApp, and automated writing evaluation tools could supplement teacher feedback for tertiary students (Eze & Olatunji, 2022). At the same time, ethical concerns about data privacy, cultural relevance, and over-reliance on machines cannot be ignored (Williamson & Piattoeva, 2022). The challenge, therefore, is not whether AI can transform ELT, but how it can be responsibly integrated within innovative pedagogical models that reflect Nigeria's socio-cultural and infrastructural realities.

By situating Nigeria within global debates while foregrounding its unique educational context, this paper contributes to the emerging scholarship on AI in African education and underscores the need for context-sensitive, ethical, and innovative approaches to pedagogical reform. The paper examines the intersection of innovative pedagogy and AI integration in English language teaching and learning in Nigeria. The central argument is that while AI holds transformative potential for ELT, its value lies not in the technology itself but in its pedagogical application. Only when AI is embedded within innovative, learner-centered approaches and adapted to Nigeria's socio-cultural and infrastructural realities can it contribute meaningfully to inclusive, equitable, and effective English language education.

Objectives of the paper:

To examine global and African perspectives on AI in ELT and identify insights relevant for Nigeria.

To explore how innovative pedagogical approaches (e.g., flipped learning, task-based language teaching, gamification) can be

combined with AI to address challenges in Nigerian classrooms.

To analyze the ethical and practical challenges of AI integration, with emphasis on equity, cultural relevance, and data privacy.

To propose a contextualized framework for responsible and sustainable AI adoption in Nigerian ELT.

Literature Review

Global Perspectives on AI in ELT

Globally, Artificial Intelligence (AI) has been heralded as a powerful driver of educational transformation. Holmes et al. (2022) describe AI as a “transformative force” capable of providing adaptive feedback, facilitating personalized learning pathways, and supporting large-scale educational delivery. Zhao (2021) emphasizes AI's multimodal capabilities, speech recognition, visual aids, and adaptive testing which enhance learner engagement and support diverse learning styles. In addition, Russell and Norvig (2021) situate AI within broader theories of computational intelligence, underscoring its role in automating tasks such as writing evaluation, translation, and dialogic practice.

Several scholars highlight how AI augments learner autonomy and personalization. Luckin (2018) notes that adaptive platforms continuously analyze student performance to deliver customized content, allowing learners to progress at their own pace. Zawacki-Richter et al. (2019), in a large-scale systematic review, conclude that AI supports formative assessment, enhances learner motivation through gamification, and provides teachers with actionable insights through data analytics. Ferguson, Coughlan,

and Herodotou (2019) add that AI-driven pedagogical designs can scaffold creativity, collaboration, and critical thinking competencies essential for 21st-century education.

However, global scholarship also raises critical concerns. Williamson and Piattoeva (2022) caution that AI may reinforce neoliberal logics of surveillance and efficiency, prioritizing data over human relationships. Similarly, Holmes et al. (2022) note that algorithmic bias and lack of transparency can lead to inequitable outcomes if systems are not carefully designed and monitored. These debates illustrate that while AI is promising, its effectiveness depends on pedagogical integration and ethical safeguards.

African Perspectives on AI in Education

Within the African context, scholars are beginning to interrogate how AI can respond to structural challenges in education. Tella (2020) observes that AI could play a pivotal role in supplementing limited teacher capacity across sub-Saharan Africa, particularly in large, under-resourced classrooms. Similarly, Okonkwo (2021) argues that AI tutoring systems can bridge the gap between teacher shortages and learner needs, especially in rural communities.

Eze and Olatunji (2022) provide empirical evidence from Nigerian universities, showing that AI-powered writing assistants significantly improved students' academic writing by offering instant, individualized feedback. This aligns with Adewale (2023), who highlights AI's potential for higher education reform in Nigeria, particularly through reducing marking burdens and supporting blended learning. At the same time, these scholars stress that infrastructural

barriers such as unreliable electricity, high internet costs, and lack of digital literacy remain formidable obstacles to AI adoption.

African researchers also stress the importance of localization and cultural relevance. As Tella (2020) warns, uncritical importation of Western-designed AI systems risks marginalizing African learners, as these tools may fail to capture local linguistic realities, code-switching practices, and cultural contexts. This point underscores the need for African-led AI design and adaptation that reflect the multilingual and multicultural character of the continent's classrooms.

Nigerian Scholarship on AI in ELT

Within Nigeria, scholarship on AI in English Language Teaching is still emerging but reveals both potential and challenges. Umar and Adeniran (2023) argue that AI can enable personalized learning in secondary schools, a critical intervention given Nigeria's overcrowded classrooms and wide variation in student proficiency levels. Chukwuma and Bello (2021) propose integrating AI-powered chatbots into popular platforms such as WhatsApp and Telegram to expand access to conversational English practice, especially for rural learners with limited exposure to authentic English interactions.

Research at the tertiary level has also shown promise. Eze and Olatunji (2022) demonstrate that ZAI-powered automated writing evaluation (AWE) systems improve tertiary students' grammar, vocabulary, and cohesion by providing instant feedback. These findings align with broader global debates about AWE as a scalable tool for enhancing writing instruction (Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019). However, Nigerian scholars also highlight the risks of over-

reliance. For instance, Adewale (2023) warns that AI should complement, not replace, teachers' roles as facilitators of creativity, cultural contextualization, and emotional support.

Identified Gaps

Although scholarship on AI in education is expanding globally, three critical gaps are evident in relation to Nigeria:

Contextual Adaptation: Most global research assumes high-resource settings with reliable infrastructure. Few studies address how AI can be adapted to Nigeria's unique socio-economic and infrastructural realities.

Pedagogical Integration: While Nigerian scholarship acknowledges AI's promise, less attention is given to how AI can be systematically embedded within innovative pedagogical models such as flipped learning, task-based language teaching (TBLT), or gamification.

Ethical and Equity Concerns: Although issues of data privacy, digital divides, and algorithmic bias are widely debated globally (Williamson & Piattoeva, 2022), Nigerian-focused discussions remain limited.

This paper addresses these gaps by foregrounding Nigeria's ELT context, critically evaluating opportunities and risks, and proposing a framework for responsible, localized, and pedagogically sound AI integration.

Conceptual Clarifications

Artificial Intelligence (AI)

Artificial Intelligence refers to computer-based systems capable of performing tasks that normally require human intelligence, such as learning, reasoning, problem-solving, and natural language processing (Russell &

Norvig, 2021). In ELT, AI manifests through applications such as chatbots, intelligent tutoring systems, automated essay scoring, and adaptive testing (Holmes et al., 2022). Natural Language Processing (NLP), a subfield of AI, is particularly significant as it enables machines to understand and generate human language, thus powering applications like automated translation, speech recognition, and conversational assistants. The adoption of AI in ELT therefore extends beyond technological novelty; it reshapes how learners access, process, and produce language.

Innovative Pedagogy

Innovative pedagogy is not simply about introducing new technologies but about rethinking the roles of teachers, learners, content, and tools to create transformative learning experiences (Ferguson, Coughlan & Herodotou, 2019). It emphasizes creativity, collaboration, and personalization, often supported by digital technologies. Innovative pedagogy aligns with constructivist and socio-cultural learning theories, where learners are viewed as active participants who co-construct knowledge rather than passive recipients. In the Nigerian ELT context, innovative pedagogy entails shifting from teacher-dominated, exam-oriented instruction toward learner-centered approaches that prioritize communicative competence and critical literacy.

English Language Teaching (ELT)

English Language Teaching refers to the practice of teaching English as a second or foreign language. It encompasses curriculum design, methodology, materials development, and teacher professional development. In Nigeria, ELT occupies a unique position: English is both the official

language and the primary medium of instruction, yet many learners enter school with limited exposure to English outside the classroom (Umar & Adeniran, 2023). ELT in Nigeria therefore faces dual challenges: bridging the gap between learners' home languages and academic English, and preparing students to compete in global knowledge economies.

Personalized Learning

Personalized learning refers to instruction tailored to individual learners' needs, styles, and pace. AI technologies enable this by tracking learner progress and dynamically adjusting tasks, content, and feedback (Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019). In the Nigerian classroom, where overcrowding often prevents teachers from attending to individual differences, personalized learning supported by AI has the potential to ensure that no student is "left behind." Umar and Adeniran (2023) emphasize that personalized learning aligns with Nigeria's recent educational reforms, which advocate for competency-based curricula rather than uniform instruction.

Learner Autonomy

Learner autonomy refers to the capacity of learners to take responsibility for their own learning by setting goals, monitoring progress, and selecting resources (Little, 2020). AI supports autonomy by offering learners self-paced modules, immediate feedback, and interactive environments where they can experiment without fear of failure. In Nigeria, fostering autonomy is crucial in contexts where teacher-centered traditions remain dominant. By shifting responsibility from teachers to learners, AI can help cultivate lifelong learning habits necessary for the 21st century.

Inclusive Education

Inclusive education ensures that all learners, regardless of socio-economic status, gender, disability, or linguistic background, have equal access to quality education (Federal Ministry of Education, 2021). AI can contribute to inclusivity by offering assistive technologies such as text-to-speech for visually impaired learners, or speech-to-text for hearing-impaired learners. Translation tools can support learners whose first language is not English, a particularly relevant issue in Nigeria's multilingual environment. However, as Adewale (2023) warns, AI must be localized to avoid reinforcing existing inequalities or privileging certain groups over others.

Innovative Pedagogy and AI in the Nigerian Context

Adaptive Learning Systems. AI-powered adaptive learning platforms can play a crucial role in addressing classroom heterogeneity in Nigeria. Tools such as Google's Read Along, Duolingo, or potentially locally developed applications dynamically adjust difficulty levels based on learners' performance. For struggling learners, the system provides scaffolding and reinforcement, while advanced learners receive accelerated challenges. This feature is particularly relevant in Nigerian classrooms where proficiency levels vary widely, making standardized instruction insufficient (Okonkwo, 2021). Research suggests that adaptive systems not only increase engagement but also improve retention rates by ensuring that students work within their "zone of proximal development" (Luckin, 2018; Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019).

AI Chatbots for Conversational Practice

Given the popularity of mobile platforms such as WhatsApp and Telegram in Nigeria, AI-powered chatbots embedded in these applications can democratize access to conversational practice. These chatbots simulate authentic communication through both text and speech, providing learners with round-the-clock opportunities for interaction (Chukwuma & Bello, 2021). Importantly, such tools are low-cost and accessible even in resource-constrained environments, bypassing infrastructural limitations often associated with traditional e-learning platforms. Beyond language practice, chatbots can support task-based learning by role-playing communicative scenarios such as negotiations, customer interactions, or academic discussions, thereby aligning Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) principles (Ferguson et al., 2019).

Automated Writing Evaluation (AWE)

Automated Writing Evaluation (AWE) tools such as Grammarly, WriteLab, or AI-powered learning management systems can help Nigerian tertiary students improve writing skills. These tools provide immediate feedback on grammar, vocabulary, coherence, and style areas in which Nigerian students often struggle due to limited writing instruction and teacher workload (Eze & Olatunji, 2022). While scholars caution against over-reliance, AWE can complement teacher feedback by allowing students to iteratively refine their writing. This combination aligns with flipped classroom models, where students prepare drafts with AI support outside class and use classroom time for collaborative revision, peer feedback, and higher-order discussions (Zhao, 2021).

AI for Inclusive Pedagogy
AI also contributes to inclusive education in Nigeria by supporting learners with disabilities and bridging linguistic gaps. Speech-to-text and text-to-speech systems can assist students with hearing or visual impairments, ensuring equitable access to instruction. Translation and simplification tools, when localized, can help rural learners who may struggle with English as a second or third language. Such applications align with the Nigerian National Policy on Inclusive Education (Federal Ministry of Education, 2021), which emphasizes the need to extend equitable learning opportunities to all learners, regardless of background or ability.

Teacher Support and Professional Development

Beyond supporting students, AI can also serve as a tool for teacher empowerment. Automating routine tasks such as grading and attendance enables teachers to redirect energy toward interactive, communicative pedagogy (Adewale, 2023). In addition, AI-powered analytics provide insights into learner performance trends, enabling teachers to make data-driven decisions about instruction. Professional development programs can also leverage AI by providing teachers with personalized training modules, diagnostic assessments, and virtual communities of practice. This ensures that teachers remain active mediators of knowledge, rather than passive consumers of technology.

Integration with Innovative Pedagogical Models

AI's real value lies not in the tools themselves but in how they are integrated with innovative pedagogical models:

Flipped Classroom: Learners engage with AI tutors and adaptive apps at home, while classroom sessions are devoted to interactive discussions, problem-solving, and projects.

Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT): AI chatbots simulate authentic communicative tasks, supporting role-play and negotiation activities.

Gamification: AI-driven gamified apps adapt challenges and rewards to learners' proficiency, sustaining motivation while reinforcing mastery.

Collaborative Learning: AI platforms can recommend peer groupings based on complementary skills, supporting cooperative projects that mirror real-world problem-solving.

Together, these models highlight the synergy between pedagogy and technology: AI provides personalization and scalability, while innovative pedagogy ensures learner agency, creativity, and contextual relevance.

Ethical and Practical Considerations

Data Privacy and Security

One of the most pressing concerns in AI adoption is the protection of learner data. AI systems rely on vast amounts of personal information, including students' linguistic profiles, performance records, and sometimes biometric data such as voice patterns. In contexts where data protection laws are underdeveloped, as is the case in Nigeria, risks of misuse and breaches are high (Adewale, 2023). Without strong legal frameworks, students' personal information may be exposed to commercial exploitation or surveillance. Teachers and learners must therefore develop critical digital literacy skills to manage these risks, while

policymakers must establish ethical guidelines for educational data management (Williamson & Piattoeva, 2022).

Equity and the Digital Divide

Although AI is often presented as a democratizing force, it risks exacerbating inequalities. Nigerian schools in urban centers with reliable internet access, electricity, and better-trained teachers are far more likely to benefit from AI than rural schools struggling with infrastructural deficits (Umar & Adeniran, 2023). This disparity reflects what Warschauer (2004) termed the "second digital divide," where the issue is not only access to devices but also access to meaningful, pedagogically sound use of technology. Without deliberate policy interventions, AI may reinforce educational privilege rather than reduce it.

Algorithmic Bias and Accuracy

AI systems are only as objective as the data on which they are trained. Global studies show that AI can replicate or even amplify societal biases, including linguistic prejudice and cultural stereotyping (Holmes et al., 2022). For example, AI-powered writing assistants trained primarily on Western English varieties may undervalue Nigerian English usages, labeling them as "errors." Similarly, speech-recognition systems often struggle with African accents, leading to unfair assessments of learners' competence (Tella, 2020). These risks underscore the importance of localizing AI tools to Nigerian linguistic realities, including code-switching practices and the recognition of Nigerian English as a legitimate variety.

Cultural Relevance

Most commercially available AI tools are designed for Western learners, with limited

sensitivity to African socio-cultural contexts. This lack of cultural relevance can alienate learners or undermine their sense of identity (Okonkwo, 2021). For example, gamified language apps may contain cultural references unfamiliar to Nigerian learners, reducing engagement. To avoid such pitfalls, Nigerian educators and technologists must collaborate to develop or adapt AI tools that reflect local realities, contexts, and educational goals.

Over-Reliance and the Dehumanization of Learning.

Another ethical issue is the risk of over-reliance on AI. While AI can automate grading and provide instant feedback, it cannot replicate the emotional intelligence, mentorship, and cultural contextualization that teachers bring to classrooms (Little, 2020). Over-reliance risks reducing learning to mechanical transactions, sidelining the human dimensions of care, empathy, and dialogue that are central to ELT. Teachers must therefore be positioned not as passive users of AI, but as active mediators who balance machine efficiency with human judgment (Adewale, 2023).

Infrastructure and Sustainability

AI integration in Nigeria also faces practical challenges related to infrastructure. Unreliable electricity, high internet costs, and limited access to devices remain significant barriers (Umar & Adeniran, 2023). Even when AI systems are introduced, sustaining them requires ongoing technical support, teacher training, and policy backing. Without such investments, AI risks becoming another short-lived educational fad rather than a sustainable innovation.

Conclusion

This paper has explored the intersection of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and innovative pedagogy in English Language Teaching (ELT), with particular attention to the Nigerian context. It examined global and African perspectives on AI adoption, identifying both the transformative potential of AI and the challenges of adapting it to resource-constrained environments. The discussion further demonstrated how innovative pedagogical models such as flipped classrooms, task-based language teaching, gamification, and collaborative learning can be enriched through AI applications to enhance personalization, learner engagement, and inclusivity in Nigerian classrooms. Ethical and practical concerns, including data privacy, equity, infrastructural limitations, and cultural relevance, were also analyzed. These insights collectively establish the foundation for a contextualized framework that responds to Nigeria's unique educational realities and guides the responsible integration of AI in ELT.

Framework for Responsible and Sustainable AI Integration in Nigerian ELT

The transformative potential of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in English Language Teaching (ELT) in Nigeria can only be realized if its adoption is guided by clear pedagogical priorities, ethical safeguards, and context-sensitive practices. Drawing from the discussions in this paper, a four-pillar framework is proposed to provide practical and sustainable strategies for integrating AI into Nigerian ELT. Each pillar reflects both the contextual realities of Nigerian classrooms and broader insights from educational scholarship.

Teacher Training and Professional Development

Teachers remain the cornerstone of any educational reform. In Nigeria, the risk is not the absence of AI tools but the danger of their underutilization or misuse due to inadequate training. The paper proposes continuous professional development programmes that go beyond digital literacy to cultivate critical AI awareness and pedagogical integration skills. Teachers should be positioned as reflective practitioners who are able to decide when, how, and why to deploy AI tools. As Ferguson, Coughlan, and Herodotou (2019) emphasize, the teacher's role must shift from passive technology user to critical mediator of human-machine interaction, ensuring that AI complements rather than displaces human judgment.

Localization and Cultural Adaptation

Imported AI tools often fail to capture the linguistic and cultural complexity of Nigerian classrooms. The paper proposes deliberate localization efforts in which AI systems are trained to recognize Nigerian English varieties, accommodate code-switching practices, and embed culturally relevant contexts in their tasks and feedback. Without such adaptation, AI risks reinforcing Western linguistic dominance and alienating learners. Tella (2020) similarly warns against uncritical adoption of Western-designed tools, stressing the need for African-led design and adaptation. By involving local developers, linguists, and educators, AI can be transformed from borrowed technology into an indigenous resource aligned with Nigeria's educational priorities.

Equity and Access

One of the greatest threats of AI adoption in Nigeria is the widening of the digital divide. The framework emphasizes that AI initiatives must prioritize rural schools, public institutions, and disadvantaged learners to prevent a concentration of benefits in elite urban centers. This requires targeted government investment in affordable internet, reliable electricity, and low-cost devices, as well as partnerships with the private sector and NGOs to subsidize access. Umar and Adeniran (2023) note that without deliberate inclusion strategies, AI will reproduce existing inequalities rather than democratize education. A responsible framework must therefore treat equity not as an afterthought but as a central criterion for AI deployment.

Ethical Governance and Sustainability

AI in education introduces ethical and governance concerns that Nigeria cannot afford to overlook. The paper proposes the establishment of regulatory frameworks that safeguard learner data, ensure algorithmic transparency, and prevent surveillance or commercial exploitation of students. Furthermore, sustainability demands long-term planning: recurrent funding for maintenance, ongoing teacher retraining, and the establishment of local research hubs to monitor AI's impact. As Williamson and Piattoeva (2022) argue, governance must address both the opportunities and risks of educational datafication. Adewale (2023) further stresses that sustainability depends on embedding AI adoption within policy frameworks that are resistant to political changes and short-term donor cycles.

This four-pillar framework demonstrates that AI integration in Nigerian ELT is not simply a technological matter but a pedagogical,

ethical, and socio-political project. By centering teachers, localizing tools, prioritizing equity, and enforcing governance, AI can be transformed from a technological novelty into a sustainable driver of inclusive and high-quality English language education.

Conclusion

This paper examined the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) within innovative pedagogical approaches to English Language Teaching (ELT) in Nigeria, and in doing so achieved its four stated objectives. It first situated Nigeria within global and African debates on AI in education, highlighting both opportunities and contextual challenges. It then showed how models such as flipped classrooms, task-based learning, gamification, and collaborative approaches can be enhanced through AI to address Nigeria's overcrowded classrooms and uneven learner outcomes. Ethical and practical challenges including data privacy, equity, cultural relevance, and infrastructural limitations were also analyzed. Finally, the paper proposed a four-pillar framework for responsible AI integration, focusing on teacher training, localization, equity, and ethical governance. Together, these discussions demonstrate that AI, when embedded within innovative pedagogy and adapted to Nigeria's realities, can advance inclusive, equitable, and sustainable ELT reform.

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Colour Systems in University Multimedia Instruction: Mechanisms, Applications, and Design Guidelines—A Review with Cases

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In technology-enhanced learning (tel), hardware roadmaps and ai integration dominate the conversation, yet the colours learners see are often overlooked. As the low-level language of courseware and interfaces, colour subtly shapes affect, attentional allocation, and cognitive load—thereby influencing outcomes. This paper focuses on "colour systems" in university multimedia instruction. Synthesising recent cross-disciplinary research and the authors' classroom and immersive (VR/AR) cases, we map mechanisms and boundaries and distil actionable design takeaways. We find that suitable hue–value–contrast combinations reduce extraneous load, stabilise affect, and clarify information hierarchy; cool schemes support focused processing, whereas warm schemes facilitate interaction; and in immersive contexts, functional colour coding with high discriminability improves comprehension of complex structures. We translate these insights into six practical principles—function-first, clear hierarchy, context matching, cautious use of red, immersion-oriented coding, and adaptive optimisation (including ai-driven personalisation). The contribution speaks to the conference theme of the quadruple helix by offering immediately usable guidance for educators, learning designers, edtech vendors, and policy makers, and by enabling rapid iteration and impact evaluation of tel artefacts.

Keywords:

Technology-enhanced learning; colour systems; multimedia instruction; affect and attention; cognitive load; VR/AR

Introduction

With the development of information technology, multimedia teaching has become an important component of higher education. By leveraging audio, video, images, and animation, instructors can present complex concepts in a more intuitive way, thereby enhancing comprehensibility and learning outcomes (Mayer, 2001; Dzul kifli & Mustafar, 2013).

Among these elements, the color system is a key visual tool. This paper treats color as an

"adjustable parameter" in instructional design rather than mere decoration. Appropriate color configurations not only increase the appeal of materials but also guide attention, regulate emotions, and, through suitable hierarchical and contrastive design, reduce cognitive load (Sweller, 1994; Elliot & Maier, 2014). Existing studies indicate that appropriate combinations of hue, brightness, and contrast facilitate the organization and processing of information while reducing unnecessary cognitive

burden, which aligns with the core principles of cognitive load theory (Sweller, 1994; Mayer, 2001). In addition, recent work on the relationship between color and emotion has begun to model these links computationally, offering quantitative references for interface and courseware design (Muratbekova & Shamo, 2024).

At the level of specific effects, blue and other cool colors are often used to support focus and sustained processing; red, in achievement contexts, can enhance alertness and detail detection, but may also increase tension (Mehta & Zhu, 2009; Elliot & Maier, 2014). Overall, systematic evidence is still lacking on how to formulate actionable color schemes tailored to different disciplines and instructional needs. In complex scenarios such as immersive media, consistent reporting on parameters of discriminability and contrast is also insufficient. Against this backdrop, this paper, through theoretical analysis and literature review combined with the author's practical cases, explores the role and boundaries of color systems in multimedia teaching at universities and proposes several recommendations for instructional design and future research.

Literature Review

Color Psychology and Learning Theory

There is substantial evidence supporting the influence of different colors on emotion and cognition. Blue is often reported as more calming and conducive to concentration; red, in achievement contexts, can enhance alertness and detail processing, but is also more likely to be accompanied by heightened tension (Elliot & Maier, 2014; Valdez & Mehrabian, 1994). In learning activities, color can be regarded as an adjustable instructional parameter: when tasks require sustained attention and exploration, cool

color schemes are more reliable; when tasks demand short-term high alertness and rapid checking, red cues are more effective, though not suitable for prolonged use (Mehta & Zhu, 2009). In terms of learning and memory, color can increase the salience of information and facilitate retrieval; appropriate contrast and hue selection are associated with improved memory performance (Dzulkifli & Mustafar, 2013). At the classroom level, active tones such as yellow and orange are often used to encourage expression and discussion, while blue and green are more suitable for learning stages that require structured processing; these practices align with converging evidence on the interplay between color, emotion, and depth of processing (Elliot & Maier, 2014; Valdez & Mehrabian, 1994).

Visual Design in Multimedia Learning

Cognitive load theory emphasizes that the mode of presenting materials directly affects extraneous load, thereby influencing learning efficiency; it commonly distinguishes between intrinsic load, extraneous load, and germane (facilitative) load (Sweller, 1994). Accordingly, multimedia design should prioritize reducing extraneous load so that working memory resources can be devoted to processing essential structures (Clark & Mayer, 2016; Mayer, 2001). Particularly relevant to this paper is the concept of "attention guidance": during synchronized dynamic presentations, timely changes in color or step-by-step appearance and disappearance help learners focus their visual search on the diagram parts corresponding to the verbal explanation, thereby improving retention and understanding (Jamet, Gavota, & Quaireau, 2008). At the interface and courseware level, clear foreground-background contrast and hierarchical color

coding facilitate the distinction between key and non-key information, reducing unnecessary visual distraction.

The Application of Color in Creative Learning

In learning scenarios that emphasize creativity and collaboration, greater attention is given to the regulatory role of color on task orientation. Experimental studies show that blue, compared to red, is more beneficial for creative tasks, whereas red is better suited for detail-checking and error-correction tasks; these effects are moderated by task type and difficulty (Mehta & Zhu, 2009). In addition, exposure to green and natural elements has been linked to higher visual creativity scores, suggesting that the color scheme of learning spaces can be aligned with activity goals (Studente et al., 2016). In team-based learning, color can also serve as a metacognitive cue to indicate information relevance and task allocation (e.g., distinguishing "requires immediate processing / can be deferred"), and attention-guiding color coding can reduce within-group search costs (Jamet et al., 2008). Overall, a well-designed color system not only influences emotion and motivation but

Cognitive Load Theory, Image from: Hegarty, M., McCarthy, J. (2018). Concept animation—a potential instructional scaffolding. ResearchGate.

also affects learning outcomes through attention and depth of processing.

Application of Color Systems in Higher Education Teaching

This chapter illustrates feasible approaches to applying color systems across different disciplines through examples drawn from multiple course settings. The overall approach is to select color and contrast strategies that support the processing requirements of the disciplinary tasks and instructional goals, thereby enhancing attention allocation, reducing extraneous load, and stabilizing emotion and motivation. The emphasis here is not on visual stylistic consistency but on functional consistency.

The Use of Color in Science and Engineering Courses

STEM courses often involve formula derivation, structural relationships, and intensive logical processing. I tend to use cool color schemes (e.g., low- to medium-saturation combinations of blue and green) as

the default base tone to create a stable, low-interference interface background; on this basis, high-contrast colors are then applied to signal key formula components, steps, and boundary conditions. The combination of cool colors and balanced contrasts is more consistently associated with "sustained focus" and "lower tension levels" (Kaya & Epps, 2004; Dzulkifli & Mustafar, 2013).

For segments requiring detail checking or risk alerts, I make short-term use of red or other high-salience cues to heighten alertness and checking accuracy; however, maintaining a red-dominant palette over long periods is not recommended, as it may increase tension and avoidance orientation (Elliot & Maier, 2014; Valdez & Mehrabian, 1994).

When tasks shift from "derivation" to "creative modeling/solution exploration," it is advisable to retain the cool background while increasing contrast and introducing more vibrant accent colors to support exploratory processing and divergent thinking (Mehta & Zhu, 2009).

Summary: For STEM disciplines, a "cool base tone + signal contrast" dual-layer strategy is appropriate; red cues should be applied only briefly to highlight high-risk or error-prone points. These practices align with converging evidence on attention guidance, memory retrieval, and load management.

The Use of Color in Humanities Courses

The humanities emphasize expression, discussion, and multi-perspective interpretation. I prefer to keep the background and interface in a neutral or slightly warm base tone, using warm colors (such as moderate yellow or orange) to lower the threshold for expression and enhance

participation, while applying contrasting colors to provide hierarchical cues for argument structures and quotations (Kaya & Epps, 2004; Valdez & Mehrabian, 1994).

In language or discussion-based classes, warm accents can increase emotional engagement and willingness to interact, but large-scale use of highly saturated colors should be avoided, as it may cause visual fatigue or distract attention (Elliot & Maier, 2014).

For units requiring rigorous presentation of evidence chains (e.g., close reading of texts, comparison of historical sources), it is advisable to temporarily return to cool or neutral backgrounds and use high-contrast signal colors to highlight key evidence, balancing clarity and readability (the findings of Jamet et al. on attention guidance also apply to the sequential presentation of color signaling).

Summary: Humanities courseware places greater emphasis on a color logic of "atmosphere to support expression + signaling to structure." Warm tones are used for activation, cool tones for calibration, with the two alternated according to instructional phases.

The Use of Color in Art Courses

In art and design courses, color itself is both a learning object and an evaluation criterion. Here, I place greater emphasis on explicit instruction of the semantic and affective dimensions of color (such as warm-cool, light-heavy, active-passive along continuous scales), and integrate these with material, texture, and composition to form operational assignment standards (Ou & Luo, 2004).

During critique sessions, a "monochrome → color combination → contextualization"

three-step approach can be used: first, students identify emotional associations on the monochrome dimension, then discuss the interactions among color combinations, and finally return to the contextual goals of the work to examine whether the use of color aligns with the intended meaning (Elliot & Maier, 2014; Kaya & Epps, 2004).

When the course objective shifts to the "experience of the creative process," I guide students to iterate high-contrast design schemes against a stable interface background, using fewer but clearly defined color variables to support immersion and flow, rather than dispersing attention with excessive color changes (Chemi, 2016).

Summary: In art and design, color is both grammar of expression and a benchmark of evaluation. Instructions should align measurable affective dimensions of color with the creative context, and use the minimum necessary variables to support smooth iteration and feedback.

Application of Color in Virtual Reality and Augmented Reality Teaching
In VR/AR settings, color serves primarily as a tool for coding and guidance rather than decoration: it is used to distinguish objects, indicate hierarchies, and signal operations, directly influencing immersion and learning performance. Reviews of applications in education and medicine show that functional color coding based on structures and steps can help learners more quickly locate key parts and understand spatial relationships (e.g., regional highlighting and layered displays in anatomy applications). At the same time, color cues in video or immersive materials can reduce irrelevant search, enhance retention, and promote transfer. However, excessive multicolor use increases

extraneous load, making it essential to adhere to the principle of "less but precise" (a single dominant color is preferable to no color or too many colors). Research on virtual classrooms also indicates that low-/medium-saturation base tones combined with high-contrast accents support both attention and preference (Elliot & Maier, 2014; She et al., 2024; Jang & Choi, 2023).

In AR's transparent overlay environments, additional consideration must be given to the blending of colors with real-world backgrounds: blue, green, and yellow are more robust across various backgrounds, whereas high-arousal colors such as red are more easily disrupted by the environment. Red is thus better suited for short-term alerts rather than long-term dominant tones and should be paired with contour/brightness strategies to ensure readability (Gabbard et al., 2022). Furthermore, the emotional effects of color remain relatively consistent: cool base tones are more conducive to focus, while warm tones are better for interaction; in moments requiring activation or warning, high-salience warm colors can be used briefly (Valdez & Mehrabian, 1994; Kaya & Epps, 2004). Where conditions allow, color schemes can also be combined with adaptive approaches, switching themes according to task stage or learner state to balance immersion, readability, and individual preference (Rong, Lian, & Tang, 2022).

Future Directions for Multimedia Teaching Technologies

In teaching scenarios involving AI, VR, and AR, decisions on the visual dimension will become increasingly important, with color systems as a key variable. Existing reviews and empirical studies consistently support the finding that appropriate color coding and contrast can influence attention allocation,

emotion regulation, and learning performance; future work needs to further align this evidence with immersive and intelligent environments (Dembe, 2024; Jang & Choi, 2023).

First, integration with AI-driven personalization.

Multimodal learning analytics (e.g., eye-tracking, EEG) have already been used to evaluate the impact of color coding on cognitive load and performance, providing a feasible measurement basis for adaptive interfaces that "dynamically adjust color schemes according to learner state" (Liu et al., 2021). Building on this, future research can explore theme color switching and contrast-threshold management tailored to task stages and individual differences (Skulmowski, 2022).

Second, strategic application by discipline and medium. In STEM courses such as programming, color cues can reduce irrelevant search and improve performance; in virtual classrooms and immersive spaces, low-/medium-saturation base tones combined with high-contrast accents are beneficial for attention and preference. At the same time, caution is needed against color overload and the "guidance reversal effect" that may occur when there is a mismatch between study and testing conditions (Liu et al., 2021; Jang & Choi, 2023; Skulmowski, 2022).

Third, usability and tool development. To enable teachers and instructional designers to integrate color into courseware and interfaces at low cost, more standardized usability evaluations and design tools are still required. Systematic reviews show that while usability research in educational technology has established methodological and reporting

frameworks, refinement and standardization of visual/color elements remain limited. Future work can build on such reviews to propose a minimal set of color parameters and evaluation indicators (Lu, Schmidt, Lee, & Huang, 2022).

Overall, future research and practice on color in multimedia teaching can focus on three lines: data-driven adaptive color, functional coding stratified by discipline and medium, and tool- and standard-linked usability evaluation. This can enhance immersion, readability, and transferability without adding to instructional burden (Dembe, 2024; Liu et al., 2021).

Conclusion

The value of color systems in multimedia teaching has become quite clear: by influencing emotion, attention allocation, and cognitive load, they in turn improve learning performance (Elliot & Maier, 2014; She, Wang, Tao, & Lai, 2024). We recommend coupling "functional color coding + contrast threshold" approaches closely with emerging technologies: in AI-supported interfaces, color schemes should be adjusted in real time based on learner state and task; in VR/AR, stable and visible schemes should be used for layering and positioning, while avoiding blending effects that reduce readability (Liu et al., 2021; Gabbard, Smith, Merenda, Burnett, & Large, 2022).

Disciplinary differences need to be addressed directly: analytical tasks are better suited to cool base tones with limited high-contrast cues for signaling, while phases rich in expression and discussion can moderately employ warm activation colors—yet saturation and color variety must be strictly controlled to prevent additional load or

"guidance reversal" effects (Mehta & Zhu, 2009; She et al., 2024).

Overall, we advocate for evidence-driven color strategies to support immersive, readable, and transferable instructional design: minimal yet precise color cues, clear hierarchical coding, adaptive switching across media and tasks, and the reporting of reusable parameters and evaluation indicators to facilitate replication and extension in future research.

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Designing AI-Enhanced Interventions for Dysgraphia: An Instructional Framework Integrating Visual, Motor, and Cognitive Scaffolds

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Dysgraphia is a specific learning disability that affects handwriting, written expression, and the cognitive organisation of written tasks. Students with Dysgraphia often face overlapping challenges in visual perception, fine motor coordination, and cognitive load management—factors that are frequently overlooked in general education settings, particularly for undiagnosed learners. This paper presents a conceptual and instructional design-driven framework for developing an AI-based intervention tool that provides personalised support for students with Dysgraphia. The framework integrates three interdependent domains—visual, motor, and cognitive—guided by Gestalt Theory, Motor Learning Theory, and Scaffolding Theory. These domains are visualised as a triangular model to reflect their instructional interplay and mutual reinforcement. The proposed AI tool will incorporate adaptive features such as visual tracing, stroke sequencing, and scaffolded writing prompts, with support tailored to varying severity levels of Dysgraphia. While empirical testing is planned in a future phase of this research, this paper outlines the theoretical foundation, design principles, and inclusive pedagogy informing the intervention. By grounding artificial intelligence in evidence-based instructional strategies, this work contributes to the design of equitable, technology-enhanced learning tools for special education. Feedback from this conference will guide the next stage of prototype development and qualitative inquiry.

Keywords:
Dysgraphia,
Instructional Design,
Artificial Intelligence in
Education, Visual-Motor
Integration, Cognitive
Scaffolding, Inclusive
Technology

Introduction

Dysgraphia is a type of specific learning disability that impacts how a person writes. It often appears as sloppy handwriting, irregular written spacing, misspelling, and production of illegible written material even though normal or above average intelligence

and exposure to appropriate instruction. These problems are often result from a failure of visual processing, fine motor coordination and cognitive processes. Dysgraphia affects 7–15% of children in school (Sangalli et al., 2019) but is grossly under-identified with

another clear indication being in mainstream classrooms where subtle or mild signs are too often overlooked. As a result, most of the students throughout their studies facing difficulty in writing had no help at all.

The lack of promptly identification and intervention in educational settings for Dysgraphia can result to long-term academic disadvantage, diminished self-esteem, and disengagement from learning process. Conventional interventions, such as handwriting drills or occupational therapy, frequently do not meet the diverse and dynamic requirements of learners, especially those who do not fit into the established diagnosis systems. A rising demand exists for personalised, scalable, and adaptive support systems that are both pedagogically sound and technologically viable.

Recent advancements in artificial intelligence (AI) present promising opportunities for personalised learning and focused interventions in special education. AI-powered educational tools have demonstrated improvements in attention, writing, and language outcomes in students with learning disabilities (Almahdawi et al., 2024) (Gupta et al., 2023). Nevertheless, most existing tools focus isolated aspects of Dysgraphia such as spelling or grammar and lack an integrated instructional design that encompasses the complete spectrum of visual, motor, and cognitive difficulties.

This research proposes a theoretically grounded instructional design framework for an AI-based intervention tool that aimed to support students with Dysgraphia. Drawing from Gestalt Theory (visual processing), Motor Learning Theory (movement-based skill acquisition), and Scaffolding Theory (cognitive development), the framework is

structured around three interdependent domains which are visual, motor, and cognitive. These domains are illustrated as a triangle to reflect their interrelation in writing performance and learning.

This framework seeks to evidence-based learning theories with adaptive AI capabilities in order to offer a comprehensive and practical method for assisting and helping learners with Dysgraphia. The following section outlines the specific research objectives that guide the development of this framework.

Problem Statement

Dysgraphia is one of the most frequently overlooked learning disabilities, and it significantly impacts on a student's ability to express himself in writing, often due to a combination of visual perception, fine motor, and work memory issues. It impacts basic writing abilities like letter formation, spelling, punctuation and written organisation (Sangalli et al., 2019). Even though it affects 7–15% of school-aged children many cases inevitably go undetected in regular classrooms, especially in students without a formal diagnosis (Akpan et al., 2025).

Current treatments for Dysgraphia, including handwriting practice, occupational therapy, or spelling software, typically target only one aspect of the condition. Full integration of the complex visual, motor, and cognitive requirements of writing is not supported by most digital tools. Additionally, these tools are seldom based on instructions theory or tailored to specific severities (Gupta et al., 2023). While AI has shown promise in support of learners with learning difficulties, such as personalised feedback or adaptive learning experiences (Alsolami, 2025), few

tools integrate AI in a way that supports the multi-dimensional nature of Dysgraphia.

Recent review work calls for inclusive AI-augmented educational technologies that would support neurodiverse learners with scaffolding, dynamic adaptivity, and theory-grounded design principles (Deckker & Sumanasekara, 2025), (Omar et al., 2025). However, there remains a lack in use of this vision to guide treatment approaches for students with Dysgraphia which transcend several domains and severity levels.

This research speaks to this gap by presenting a theoretical instructional design model for an AI-facilitated intervention tool that addresses both visual, motor and cognitive processes contributing to Dysgraphia. Based on learning theory, the framework is designed to inform the development of adaptive, accessible and scalable solutions applicable to children across diverse educational systems.

Research Objectives

The main objective of this study is to design a conceptual instructional framework that guides the development of AI-based interventions for students with Dysgraphia, emphasizing on three key domains of support: visual, motor, and cognitive scaffolding. Grounded in instructional design principles and learning theories, this study aims to explore how adaptive AI tools can deliver personalised support tailored to varying severity levels of Dysgraphia.

Specifically, this study aims to:

To analyse the role of visual, motor, and cognitive challenges in the learning experiences of students with Dysgraphia.

To review existing AI-based educational interventions targeting writing or learning

disabilities, with attention to their instructional design.

To propose an instructional design framework that integrates AI-driven scaffolds aligned to the visual, motor, and cognitive domains.

To explore how severity levels of Dysgraphia can moderate the application of AI-based scaffolds in instructional contexts.

To outline a future research and development plan for a prototype intervention tool based on the proposed framework.

Research Questions

Based on the research objectives, the following research questions are proposed:

What are the specific visual, motor, and cognitive challenges experienced by students with Dysgraphia that impact their writing performance?

To what extent do existing AI-based interventions address the writing needs of students with Dysgraphia, and what instructional design limitations are evident?

How can instructional design theories (e.g., Gestalt Theory, Motor Learning Theory, and Scaffolding Theory) inform the development of an AI-based intervention framework for Dysgraphia?

In what ways can visual, motor, and cognitive scaffolds be integrated into an adaptive AI tool to support writing development in students with Dysgraphia?

How can the severity level of Dysgraphia be used to tailor the type and intensity of AI-based instructional support within the proposed framework?

Literature Review

The purpose of this literature review was to position the study within the extant literature on Dysgraphia as well as educational interventions and AI in special education. Based on the evidence from previous studies, this section presents gaps in existing interventions and rationalizes the necessity of having an integrative instructional design framework that incorporates visual, motor, and cognitive scaffolding.

Understanding Dysgraphia

Dysgraphia is a learning disability that affects writing, generally manifesting in the form of very sloppy handwriting, spelling problems, and disorganised written expression. Between 7% and 15% of school children are estimated to have a writing disorder, increasingly diagnosed in mainstream classrooms and often underdiagnosed or misunderstood (Sangalli et al., 2019). Dysgraphia can either be developmental or acquired, and is associated with visual processing, fine motor skills and executive cognitive functions deficits (Fukushima et al., 2008). Only available for students with a formal diagnosis, the invisibility of Dysgraphia in these settings is a particularly pressing issue, as many students who do not have the diagnosis are left to flounder without targeted help. Failure to recognise can result in the lack of motivation and increased irritation and disengagement, and thus the importance of early intervention and holistic instructional design (Akpan et al., 2025).

Educational Interventions for Dysgraphia

Conventional or Dysgraphia include occupational therapy, handwriting drills, and regimented writing practice. Even though these techniques can improve mechanical handwriting, there often remain unaddressed

underlying cognitive and visual processing problems. On top of that, they are usually non-personalised, and, in some cases, they do not scale well in regular classrooms (Sangalli et al., 2019). In recent years, with the development of digital supports (spelling, grammar check), systems have tended to appear. However, many of these tools are dedicated to components of Dysgraphia only. For instance, some emphasise on legibility or spelling and exclude from their implementation motor and developmental scaffolds allowing fragmented solutions (Gupta et al., 2023). This division underscores the need for an all-encompassing paradigm involving various spheres of help, as opposed to taking Dysgraphia as a one-dimensional disorder.

AI-Based Interventions in Special Education

With its personalising, adaptive, and scalable interventions, Artificial Intelligence (AI) has shown significant promise to revolutionise special education. Recent studies show that AI-based solutions are able to improve academic skills, attention control, and writing results for learning-disabled students (Alsolami, 2025) ; (Almahdawi et al., 2024). Several AI-based handwriting analysis and correction (using machine learning models) systems have been designed in the context of Dysgraphia to improve spelling, grammar, and handwriting quality (Gupta et al., 2023). Similarly, cognitive AI screening tools have been utilised for early detection of Dyslexia and Dysgraphia, supporting timely intervention (Rokade et al., 2024). Systematic reviews corroborate the function of AI in improving inclusive education, offering real-time scaffolding, and customising learning experiences to diverse needs (Hussein et al., 2025). Despite these progresses, there are still less work to bridge

the gap to implement AI-based supports with visual, motor, and cognitive scaffolds altogether.

Instructional Scaffolding and Learning Theory

Instructional design theory offers a strong foundation for developing AI-based interventions that are not only technologically advanced but also pedagogically effective. Scaffolding Theory, based in Vygotsky's Zone of Proximal Development, emphasises structured assistance that can be gradually diminished as learners gain independence, making it highly relevant for supporting the cognitive

Conceptual Framework

The proposed model for the AI-based intervention tool for Dysgraphia is presented in this study. The approach also includes three domains of support - visual, motor, and cognitive, all of which are theoretically based

Visual Domain (Gestalt Theory)

The emphasis of Gestalt Theory is on a holistic vision and our ability to interpret patterns, structures, and figure-ground relations (Todorovic, 2008). In Dysgraphia, the difficulty in aligning space and handwriting can be alleviated through visual guidelines, arranged according to the Gestalt principles, such as writing guidance and base-plane order (Kılıç & Parsıl, 2023).

Cognitive Domain (Scaffolding Theory)

Writing also demands planning, memory and focus control, which can be too much to ask some students with Dysgraphia. Scaffolding Theory (Vygotsky) proposed that learners benefit from support which is systematically

demands of writing (Omar et al., 2025). Gestalt Theory enhances the visual domain, highlighting how learners perceive patterns, organise visual input, and recognise structures-skills essential for letter formation and spatial alignment. Motor Learning Theory underlies the motor domain, emphasising on repetition, feedback, and procedural skill acquisition for handwriting fluency.

Bringing these theories together, instructional design can ensure that AI-based interventions are adaptive, evidence-based, and inclusive, responding to both the complexity of Dysgraphia and the individual needs of learners.

and grounded in traditional learning theory, with AI serving as the adaptive scaffolding. The domains are represented as a triangle which may be interpreted as a metaphorical device for showing their relationship in relation to writing.

Motor Domain (Motor Learning Theory)

Handwriting fluency is based on fine motor coordination, practice and feedback, which are principles of motor learning (Al Imam et al., 2025). Students with Dysgraphia often struggle to master stroke sequencing and motor control, all competencies that can be facilitated by AI based handwriting guidance and adaptive practice (Gupta et al., 2023).

removed as their skills increase (Pearson & Gallagher, 1983). AI can provide scaffolded writing prompts and adaptive task decompositions to lower cognitive load and promote independence (Omar et al., 2025).

Figure 1. Conceptual framework for AI-based instructional intervention in Dysgraphia, integrating visual, motor, and cognitive scaffolds with adaptive AI support moderated by severity.

As illustrated in Figure 1, the conceptual framework positions visual, motor, and cognitive scaffolds as three interdependent domains, alongside adaptive AI support that integrates support across these areas. The triangular illustrates that writing ability in students with Dysgraphia is not influenced by a single factor, but by the dynamic interaction of visual perception, motor coordination, and cognitive processes. Each domain is based on a specific learning theory which are Gestalt Theory for visual organisation, Motor Learning Theory for fine motor development, and Scaffolding Theory for cognitive regulation, hence ensuring that the framework remains pedagogically sound. Fundamentally, AI functions as a personalised scaffolding engine, providing

specific interventions such as tracing tools, stroke guidance, and scaffolded writing prompts. The severity of Dysgraphia functions as a moderating variable, allowing the system to modify the intensity and type of scaffolds, thereby providing inclusivity and differentiation for learners with mild, moderate, or severe requirements.

Methodology

This study will adopt a mixed-methods research design, combining qualitative and quantitative approaches. Mixed methods are particularly effective in education research because they provide a comprehensive perspective on complex learning challenges, integrating the depth of qualitative inquiry with the generalisability of quantitative data

(Creswell & Clark, n.d.). In the context of Dysgraphia, this design allows the study to capture both teachers' and students lived experiences and broader trends in perceptions of AI-based interventions. Participants

Two key groups will participate in the preliminary study:

Teachers – including special education teachers and mainstream classroom teachers with experience supporting students who struggle with writing.

Students – aged 8–14, with either diagnosed or suspected Dysgraphia, representing mild, moderate, and severe cases.

A purposive sampling strategy will be employed to ensure a diverse range of perspectives across different teaching and learning contexts. Such purposeful selection is often recommended in exploratory studies where depth of insight is prioritised.

Data Collection

The study will begin with semi-structured interviews to capture the nuanced experiences of teachers and students. Semi-structured formats are particularly suited for this research as they allow flexibility while ensuring that core themes such as visual, motor, and cognitive challenges are consistently explored. Classroom observations will complement the interviews by documenting how Dysgraphia manifests during writing activities and how teachers currently scaffold support. Observational methods provide critical insight into actual classroom practices, making them invaluable in special education research. Finally, a short survey will be administered to a broader sample of teachers to capture trends in perceptions of AI-based support for

Dysgraphia. This quantitative component will provide complementary evidence to validate and extend findings from the qualitative phase (Creswell & Clark, n.d.).

Data Analysis

Qualitative data from interviews and observations will be analysed using thematic analysis, a flexible method well-suited for identifying patterns in experiences and practices. Themes will focus on how visual, motor, and cognitive challenges affect learning and what scaffolds are most effective. Quantitative survey responses will be analysed using descriptive statistics to highlight common perceptions and areas of divergence.

Ethical Considerations

This study will follow established ethical standards for educational research (ETHICAL GUIDELINES FOR EDUCATIONAL RESEARCH, 2018). Informed consent will be obtained from teachers, parents, and students. Participation will be voluntary, and anonymity will be protected. For students, interviews will use age-appropriate questioning, with sensitivity to their learning needs and emotional well-being.

Use of Findings

The findings from the preliminary study will be used to refine the conceptual framework and guide the design of prototype AI features, such as tracing, stroke guidance, and scaffolded writing prompts. By combining theoretical insights with empirical evidence from teachers and students, the intervention will be both pedagogically grounded and practically relevant for inclusive classrooms. Implications and Future Work

This research enhances the theoretical understanding of technology-enhanced

learning in special education by integrating Gestalt Theory, Motor Learning Theory, and Scaffolding Theory into a unified framework for Dysgraphia intervention. Although previous research has utilised these theories independently in education, there is limited study combining them to tackle the multi-dimensional issues of writing disabilities. By doing so, the suggested framework enhances knowledge on how learning theories can be operationalised in AI-based educational design. Such integration demands for more theory-driven approaches in the use of AI in education (Zawacki-Richter et al., n.d.).

Practical Implications for Educators and Students

For educators, this framework offers a structured model for identifying and supporting the visual, motor, and cognitive needs of students with Dysgraphia. By embedding AI-based scaffolds into instructional design, educators can benefit from real-time feedback, adaptive task design, and personalised learning support, which are otherwise challenging to provide consistently in mainstream classrooms. Evidence from previous studies indicates that AI tools can improve student engagement and provide differentiated instruction in inclusive environments (Bonneton-Botté et al., 2023). For students, especially those undiagnosed, the framework promises more equitable access to customised support, diminishing barriers to academic participation and achievement (Hussein et al., 2025).

Technological Implications

The framework additionally aids to the design of inclusive instructional technologies. Most current digital supports for Dysgraphia are fragmented concentrating only on spelling, grammar, or handwriting

mechanics (Gupta et al., 2023). In contrast, this model emphasises multi-domain integration, displaying how AI can simultaneously address visual, motor, and cognitive scaffolds in a unified system. It also highlights the significance of severity as a moderating variable, a characteristic that could inform adaptive learning algorithms capable of customising interventions in real time. Such personalisation aligns with broader trends in AI-enhanced adaptive learning systems (Fadel et al., 2019).

Policy and Inclusive Education Implications

At the policy level, this research underscores the importance of designing interventions that align with Universal Design for Learning (UDL) principles. UDL emphasises multiple means of representation, activity, and engagement, which correspond directly onto the visual, motor, and cognitive scaffolds of this framework. By integrating AI-driven scaffolding into inclusive classroom environments, policymakers and school leaders can provide equitable learning opportunities for neurodiverse students. This corresponds with international agendas advocating technology-enhanced inclusion in education.

Future Work

The next stage of this research will concentrate on empirical validation and prototype development. A preliminary qualitative study, incorporating interviews and classroom observations, will enhance the framework based on stakeholder insights. The next phase will also involve the development and pilot testing of an AI-based prototype that implements the visual, motor, and cognitive scaffolds. Future studies will evaluate the effectiveness of the intervention in enhancing handwriting fluency, writing

organisation, and student engagement, using both qualitative feedback and quantitative performance measures. Iterative testing will guarantee that the tool remains pedagogically valid, technologically viable, and contextually appropriate.

Conclusion

Dysgraphia presents significant challenges for students, particularly in inclusive classrooms where many remain undiagnosed or insufficiently supported. Existing interventions, while valuable, are often fragmented and fail to address the interconnected visual, motor, and cognitive difficulties that underlie the condition. This paper has proposed a conceptual instructional design framework for an AI-based intervention tool that unites these three domains, grounded in Gestalt Theory, Motor Learning Theory, and Scaffolding Theory. By integrating adaptive scaffolding with AI technologies, the framework offers a pathway toward personalised, responsive, and inclusive educational support.

The contribution of this work lies in its theoretical grounding and practical orientation, providing educators, researchers, and designers with a structured model for developing multi-domain interventions. Importantly, the inclusion of severity of Dysgraphia as a moderating factor highlights the framework's potential for differentiated and equitable learning experiences.

As a work-in-progress, the framework will be refined through qualitative inquiry with teachers and students, followed by prototype development and pilot testing. These next phases will ensure that the tool remains not only technologically feasible but also pedagogically sound and aligned with the needs of diverse learners. Ultimately, this

study contributes to the broader goal of advancing technology-enhanced learning for inclusion, bridging the gap between theory, design, and practice.

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Extending the Community of Inquiry Framework: A Quantitative Study of Online Collaboration, Shared Metacognition, and Core Constructs

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With the increasing practice of online learning, learning has shifted from being primarily individual to increasing collaborative, where groups think, reflect, and regulate knowledge together. This collaborative dimension is reflected in the construct of shared metacognition, an extension of the Community of Inquiry (CoI) framework. Despite the flexibility and accessibility of online learning, studies report persistent challenges, including low student satisfaction, poor engagement, feelings of isolation, and weakened social interaction. This study investigates the impact of a semester-long intervention focused on building an online collaborative learning (OCL) environment on undergraduates' shared metacognition and overall CoI. A quantitative survey design was employed to measure perceptions across a large student cohort. A total of 110 undergraduates from two cohorts at a public university in Penang, Malaysia completed an online survey on their perceptions towards the Social Presence (SP), Cognitive Presence (CP), Teaching Presence (TP), and Shared Metacognition (SM) constructs following the intervention. Results revealed that all four CoI constructs were positively perceived, with TP rated the highest. SM emerged as the second most positively perceived construct, indicating a strong awareness of both individual cognitive efforts and collaborative regulation of learning. Moreover, findings revealed the critical role of CP in collaborative knowledge construction. However, SP was the least perceived, with challenges noted in group conflict resolution. The study reinforces the importance of holistic instructional design and extends the CoI framework by highlighting the significance of Shared Metacognition that calls for practical insights for educators to strengthen collaboration, critical thinking, and community building in online learning.

Keywords:

Community of Inquiry (CoI); Online Collaborative Learning (OCL); Social Presence; Cognitive Presence; Teaching Presence; Shared Metacognition; Perceptions

Introduction

Learning goes beyond the individual process of acquiring new knowledge and skills. It is common to have students engage with content on their own, yet deeper

understanding often emerged as a result of collaboration, where a group of individuals brainstorm ideas, share perspectives, challenge differing viewpoints, and regulate

their progress as a community (Hung et al., 2023). In higher education, online environments have increasingly become important spaces for this collective process, offering a range of collaborative activities that promote peer learning (Yusof, 2022). When designed effectively, such environments enable learners to exchange ideas, negotiate meaning, and co-construct knowledge in ways that can even surpass traditional classroom interaction (Belle, 2024).

Community of Inquiry (CoI) Framework

The Community of Inquiry (CoI) framework proposed by Garrison, Anderson, and Archer (2001) centralises on the facilitation of meaningful interaction and engagement in the online learning environments. The framework is built on three interdependent constructs, Cognitive Presence (CP), Social Presence (SP), and Teaching Presence (TP), each plays a critical role in ensuring a rich online learning experience through interpersonal connection, critical inquiry and purposeful teaching (Garrison et al., 2001). In fact, the CoI framework aligns well with Lev Vygotsky's Social Constructivism and George Siemens' Connectivism learning theories, both of which emphasise that knowledge is not constructed in isolation but through social interaction and shared validation of understanding (Garrison, 2009, as cited in Shea et al., 2022).

The Role of Core Constructs in Online Learning

Based on the CoI framework, cognitive presence plays a central role in enabling students to move beyond surface-level participation towards deeper learning. Through discussion, reflection, and problem-solving, this construct provides the space for students to construct meaning and engage

critically with ideas (Garrison et al., 2001). Complementing this, social presence creates the conditions that make each inquiry possible by fostering trust, belonging, and openness among participants. When students feel connected and supported, they are more willing to share perspectives, challenge ideas, and collaborate meaningfully. At the same time, teaching presence through intentional design, structured facilitation, and clear guidance, leading collaborative efforts toward purposeful outcomes, helping students navigate complexity and remain engaged throughout their learning (Garrison et al., 2001). Together, these three constructs interact dynamically, making learning a collaborative and interactive process rather than a solitary one. As Gogus (2023) further explained, strong social bonds encourage deeper cognitive engagement, while well-structured teaching provides the scaffolding for critical inquiry.

Extending CoI with Shared Metacognition

Building on these foundations, scholars have recognised that collaboration requires not only interaction and guidance but also collective responsibility for managing how groups learn together. This recognition has led to the introduction of Shared Metacognition as an extension of the CoI framework in the recent year (Garrison, 2022). Shared Metacognition highlights how learners monitor their collective understanding, adapt relevant strategies, and regulate group progress, ensuring that inquiry is both meaningful and sustained (Garrison, 2022). By integrating this construct, the CoI framework extends beyond individual meaning-making to the collaborative regulation of knowledge construction. This addition is particularly relevant in online environments, where the success of group learning often depends on how effectively

students co-regulate their contributions and maintain accountability to shared goals.

Fig. 1 The Revised Community of Inquiry (CoI) Framework (adapted from Garrison, 2022)

Challenges in Online Collaborative Learning

Despite the promise of collaborative online learning, studies reported persistent challenges. Issues such as limited interaction, reduced engagement, and weakened social connectedness have been constantly raised by researchers, all of which can undermine the effectiveness of online learning (Abdul Aziz et al., 2023; Hadi et al., 2022; Mustapha et al., 2022). These issues stress the need for pedagogical approaches that support both individual and collective formation of knowledge within online collaborative environments to foster high-quality, meaningful, and satisfying learning

experiences. While the CoI framework has been widely applied to address these concerns, much of the research done in higher education has focused on its original three constructs, leaving Shared Metacognition relatively underexplored (Annamalai, 2017; Liu & Diana Deris, 2022; Patwardharr et al., 2020). On top of that, limited attention has been given to how students perceive the interplay between Shared Metacognition and the core CoI constructs in practice.

This study seeks to address that gap by extending the CoI framework to examine undergraduate students' perceptions of Social Presence, Cognitive Presence,

Teaching Presence, and Shared Metacognition within a semester-long online collaborative learning intervention. By focusing on students' perspectives, this research aims to offer empirical evidence on how the constructs interrelate and how the framework can be enriched to better capture the dynamics of collaborative knowledge building in online learning environments.

Hence, this study contributes to the literature by examining the impact of a semester-long OCL intervention on undergraduates' shared metacognition and overall CoI. It further explores how strategies grounded in the CoI framework can enhance student engagement and strengthen the sense of community within OCL environments. This study aims to answer the following research question:

In what ways do students feel their experiences in online collaborative learning have influenced their sense of:

belonging and connection with peers (Social Presence)?

understanding and reflection on course material (Cognitive Presence)?

support and guidance from instructors (Teaching Presence)?

shared thinking and learning strategies (Shared Metacognition)?

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a quantitative research design using a survey method to capture students' perceptions of Social Presence, Cognitive Presence, Teaching Presence, and Shared Metacognition following the integration of the CoI model within an OCL environment facilitated through a total of six

Google tools, including Google Classrooms, Google Sites, Google Docs, Google Slides, Google Sheets, and Google Forms. The survey approach was selected as it enables the collection of numerical data from a relatively large sample, providing the ease of systematic comparison between the four constructs measured. Moreover, quantitative methods are recognised for their efficiency in data analysis (Connolly, 2007) and their capacity to support the generalisation of findings to broader populations (Carr, 1994).

Participants

The participants of this study were drawn from full-time undergraduates enrolled in the Bachelor of Teaching English to Speakers of Other Languages (TESOL) program under the School of Education. This group was purposefully selected as they were registered for the course QIMT213E Digital Audio and Video during Semester II of the 2022/2023 and 2023/2024 academic years. A total of 110 students from two cohorts participated without restriction to ensure comprehensive coverage and reduce sampling bias.

Research Instrument

An online survey made up of five sections was designed and administered via Google Forms to measure students' perceptions of the impact of SP, CP, TP, and SM in the OCL environment. It contains a demographic section and a total of 45 construct-related items adapted from Hilliard and Stewart's (2019) and Garrison's (2022) study. Each construct were assessed using a 6-point Likert scale, with the intention to omit the typical 'Neutral' midpoint where participants might potentially select due to indecision, thus affecting the clarity of opinion and reliability of results (Alenxander et al., 2018; Nowlis et al., 2002).

Data Collection & Procedure

The study is conducted based on a three-phase procedure to examine the impact of OCL intervention. The first phase involved the development of an OCL environment using six Google tools. Google Classroom functioned as the central learning management system for administering and managing collaborative teaching and learning. It served as the main platform for announcements, learning materials, supplementary resources, and collaborative activities prepared by the lecturer. Secondly, Google Sites provided structured guideline for the Online Interaction–Collaborative Reflective Writing (OI-CRW) activities. The website educates students on the online interaction strategies to be applied in their weekly reflective tasks. These tasks required students to engage in group discussions on the taught content and collaboratively produce reflective writing facilitated through

Google Docs, which supported peer interaction in the online setting. Google Slides was designed to facilitate peer introductions, while Google Sheets was mainly utilised in tracking attendance and engagement in OI-CRW tasks, and Google Forms supported lecturer for quick knowledge checks throughout the course.

In the second phase, these tools were systematically integrated into a semester-long teaching and learning intervention that lasted for 14 weeks across both cohorts. Participants were allowed to form groups consisting of five to six members and were consistently guided to interact and engage in to OI-CRW activities throughout the semester. In the final phase, following the completion of the intervention, participants completed an online survey designed to capture their perceptions of SP, CP, TP, and SM.

Fig. 2 Summary of research procedure

Data Analysis

Upon the completion of online survey, the data gathered were analysed using descriptive analysis in the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). Based on descriptive statistics, this study looked into the frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation of each item to obtain a

comprehensive overview of the participants' responses in terms of their perceptions of the four constructs. This approach enabled the identification of general trends, patterns, and variations in how participants experienced the OCL environment. The results were then organised systematically by construct, allowing each section of the questionnaire to

be examined in detail. Apart from ensuring the results not only inform about participants' perceptions, this approach also worked well in examining the relative strengths and weaknesses of the OCL intervention across the different CoI dimensions.

Results

Demographics

The participants of this study comprised 110 undergraduates from two cohorts enrolled in the TESOL programme, who had taken the course QIMT213E Digital Audio and Video. Specifically, 5 out of 90 students from Semester II 2022/2023 and 25 out of 55 students from Semester II 2023/2024 voluntarily responded to the survey. Table 1 presents the demographic distribution across gender, age, nationality, and race.

Of the total respondents, 93 were female (84.5%) and 17 were male (15.5%). The majority were aged 21–22 years (87.3%), followed by smaller proportions, 8 participants aged 23–24 years (7.3%), 4 participants aged 19–20 years (3.6%), and 2 participants aged 25 years and above (1.8%). In terms of nationality, local undergraduates dominated the sample with 100 respondents (90.9%), while non-Malaysian students made up 10 respondents (9.1%). Ethnic distribution showed that Malay students formed the largest group with 75 respondents (68.2%), followed by Chinese students with 20 (18.2%). The sample also included 6 Indian students (5.5%) and 9 students from other ethnic backgrounds (8.2%).

Table 1

Participants' Demographics

	Demographic Variables	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Female	93	84.5
	Male	17	15.5
Age	19-20 years old	4	3.6
	21-22 years old	96	87.3
	23-24 years old	8	7.3
	25 years old and above	2	1.8
Nationality	Malaysian	100	90.9
	Non-Malaysian	10	9.1
Race	Chinese	20	18.2
	Indian	6	5.5
	Malay	75	68.2
	Other	9	8.2

Students' Perception of CoI Construct

Social Presence (SP)

Social presence was perceived positively by participants during the OCL intervention. As

shown in Table 2, this construction obtained an overall mean score of 5.21 and a standard deviation of 0.73. The three highest-rated

items were SP6 (M = 5.45, SD = 0.85), SP8 (Mean = 5.35, SD = 0.91), and SP5 (Mean = 5.35, SD = 0.88).

Participants strongly agreed that the OCL environment provided the freedom to express their viewpoints (SP6) through the commenting and reply features in Google Docs. This finding affirmed the effectiveness of the intervention in encouraging active participation and open sharing of ideas. Majority of them agreed to have their voice heard and thoughts communicated, as reflected in SP8, “I felt that my point of view was acknowledged by my group members”. At the same time, the OCL environment enabled participants to feel at ease engaging

in active contribution of knowledge, as they expressed comfort when participating in the online interaction (SP5).

However, group dynamics were not perceived as strongly. The lowest-rated item was SP9 (M = 4.95), “I felt comfortable disagreeing with my group members while still maintaining a sense of trust”. Although the score remained above average, it suggests that students were less comfortable managing disagreements within their groups. Interestingly, SP9 was recorded the highest standard deviation (SD = 1.15), indicating considerable variation in how participants felt about expressing opposing views compared to other forms of interaction in the OCL environment.

Table 2

Mean, and Standard Deviation of Students’ Perceived Social Presence

Items	Mean	Std. Deviation	Overall
SP1 I felt that online interaction (in Google Docs) is an excellent medium for social interaction.	5.09	1.08	
SP2 I felt that peer group introductions (in Google Slide) enabled me to form a sense of belonging in the course.	4.98	1.00	
SP3 I felt that getting to know my peers in online interaction (in Google Docs) gave me a sense of belonging in the course.	5.07	1.00	
SP4 I felt comfortable interacting with my group members through the online medium (in Google Docs).	5.33	0.88	M= 5.21 SD= 0.73
SP5 I felt comfortable participating in the online interaction (in Google Docs).	5.35	0.88	
SP6 I felt that I have the chances to express my opinions (in Google Docs).	5.45	0.85	

SP7	I felt that online interaction helped me to develop a sense of collaboration with my group members (in Google Docs).	5.30	0.86
SP8	I felt that my point of view was acknowledged by my group members (in Google Docs).	5.35	0.91
SP9	I felt comfortable disagreeing with my group members while still maintaining a sense of trust (in Google Docs).	4.95	1.15

Cognitive Presence (CP)

Results indicated that all items for CP achieved mean scores above 5, with an overall mean of 5.29 (SD = 0.85). This finding demonstrates consistently a consistent positive perceptions of the OCL intervention in significantly enhanced participants’ cognitive engagement and supported meaningful knowledge construction throughout the semester.

The strongest perception was identified for CP3, “Course activities (OI & CRW) provided a variety of useful information sources to learn more about the topics in digital audio and video course (in Google Docs).”, with the highest mean score of 5.37 (SD = 0.96). Participants generally agreed

that the design and implementation of course activities were beneficial in providing access to valuable resources that support the learning of course content. Similarly, CP6 (M = 5.36, SD = 0.90) reflected students’ perception that the OCL environment was effective in improving their understanding of the subject matter.

Although the overall perception was highly positive, CP8 recorded the lowest score (M = 5.21, SD = 1.02). Some participants felt less strongly that the OCL intervention fostered higher-order thinking skills, suggesting a weaker perceived connection between the course content and the development of advanced critical inquiry.

Table 3

Mean, and Standard Deviation of Students’ Perceived Cognitive Presence

Items	Mean	Std. Deviation	Overall
CP1 Course activities (OI & CRW) increased my interest in digital audio and video course (in Google Docs).	5.26	0.96	
CP2 Course activities (OI & CRW) stimulated my curiosity about the weekly topic (in Google Docs).	5.27	0.97	
CP3 Course activities (OI & CRW) provided a variety of useful information sources to learn more	5.37	0.96	

	about the topics in digital audio and video course (in Google Docs).			
CP4	Course activities (OI & CRW) were valuable in helping me appreciate different points of view (in Google Docs).	5.29	0.96	M= 5.29 SD= 0.85
CP5	Course activities (OI & CRW) helped me answer questions raised in learning digital audio and video course (in Google Docs).	5.27	0.98	
CP6	Course activities (OI & CRW) helped me understand fundamental concepts about digital audio and video course (in Google Docs).	5.36	0.90	
CP7	Course activities (OI & CRW) enabled me to explore and integrate ideas into solutions for the final video project.	5.24	0.96	
CP8	Course activities (OI & CRW) equipped me to have higher thinking skills.	5.21	1.02	

Teaching Presence (TP)

As shown in Table 4, all items under TP achieved strikingly high mean scores of 5.4 or above, indicating a strong positive perception of the educational experiences designed throughout the 14-week OCL intervention. Compared with SP and CP, TP stood out as the most highly rated construct, where the strategies implemented to foster this construct were particularly effective.

TP8 emerged as the highest-rated item among all with a mean score of 5.55, which also recorded the lowest standard deviation (SD = 0.72). This result informed a consistent agreement among participants that the instructor provided timely progress reports using the Dashboard which supported self-regulated learning. Such consistency in feedback was highly valued by participants, highlighting the effectiveness of structured

guidance in keeping students well-informed about their progress. Additionally, the aspect of ‘facilitating discourse’ was well achieved as strong perceptions were recorded for TP3 (M = 5.53, SD = 0.81) and TP9 (M = 5.53, SD = 0.79). They emphasised the instructor’s organisational skills in communicating important deadlines and their empathy and care in supporting students emotionally. These results demonstrate that both practical organisation and interpersonal sensitivity contributed meaningfully to students’ learning experiences.

Despite these positive outcomes, one area requiring improvement was identified in TP7, which had the lowest mean score (M = 5.43, SD = 0.79). This suggests that participants felt the integration of innovative approaches for learning could be strengthened, highlighting opportunities for enhancing the instructional design further.

Table 4

Mean, and Standard Deviation of Students’ Perceived Teaching Presence

Items	Mean	Std. Deviation	Overall
TP1 The instructor clearly communicated important course goals for each task (in Google Docs).	5.44	0.83	
TP2 The instructor provided clear instructions on how to participate in this course learning activities (in Google Site & Google Classroom).	5.50	0.76	
TP3 The instructor clearly communicated important due dates/time frames for learning activities (in Google Classroom & WhatsApp Group).	5.53	0.81	
TP4 The instructor presented stimulating questions & answers (summary in Google Docs) that helped me to learn.	5.46	0.79	M= 5.49 SD= 0.71
TP5 The instructor helped keep the course participants on tasks (OI & CRW in Google Docs) in a way that helped me to learn.	5.50	0.80	
TP6 The instructor encouraged course participants to explore new concepts through the activities given in this course (in Google Docs).	5.45	0.87	
TP7 The instructor delivered course content in an innovative learning approach.	5.43	0.85	
TP8 The instructor provided a self-regulated learning progress report (using Dashboard) in the time needed.	5.55	0.72	
TP9 The instructor cared about my learning progress.	5.53	0.79	

Shared Metacognition (SM)

Table 5 presents the findings from the fifth section of the survey, which examined participants’ perceptions of self-regulation and co-regulation in the OCL environment. Overall, results indicate that the intervention was effective in fostering both individual and collective metacognitive awareness, with mean scores of 5.28 for self-regulation and 5.34 for co-regulation. Standard deviation values remained consistently below 1.0

across all items, suggesting a high level of agreement among participants.

In terms of self-regulation (SM1 to SM6), participants reported strong awareness of their own learning processes during OCL activities. The highest mean scores were observed for SM1 (M = 5.46) and SM2 (M = 5.43), reflecting participants’ recognition of the effort they invested and the strategies they employed when working individually. By

contrast, adaptability in learning strategies was slightly weaker, as shown in SM3 (M = 5.26). The lowest score emerged in SM4 (M = 5.06), indicating that some participants felt less confident in evaluating the difficulty of course content while engaging independently in metacognitive processes.

On the other hand, perceptions of co-regulation were notably strong. SM7 (M = 5.44) and SM8 (M = 5.42) highlighted participants' ability to remain attentive to others' ideas and to engage with group feedback during collaborative tasks. These

results suggest that the OCL activities successfully encouraged learners to monitor and reflect on shared knowledge construction. Nevertheless, some variation was observed in SM9 and SM11, which measured participants' comfort in observing peers' strategies and in questioning additional information. Both items recorded relatively higher standard deviations (SD = 0.90 and 0.92), again demonstrating differences in how consistently participants experienced these aspects of group interaction.

Table 5

Mean, and Standard Deviation of Students' Perceived Shared Metacognition

Items	Mean	Std. Deviation	Overall Self-Regulation & Co-Regulation	Overall Shared Metacognition
SM1 When I am engaged in the learning process (online collaborative learning (OCL) with course activities (OI & CRW)) as an INDIVIDUAL, I am aware of my effort.	5.46	0.77		
SM2 When I am engaged in the learning process (online collaborative learning (OCL) with course activities (OI & CRW)) as an INDIVIDUAL, I am aware of my thinking.	5.43	0.71	(Individual) Self-regulation	M= 5.31 SD= 0.68
SM3 When I am engaged in the learning process (online collaborative learning (OCL) with course activities (OI & CRW)) as an INDIVIDUAL, I question my thoughts.	5.26	0.87	M = 5.28 SD= 0.87	
SM4 When I am engaged in the learning process (online collaborative learning (OCL) with course activities (OI & CRW)) as an INDIVIDUAL,	5.06	0.98		

	I make judgement of the difficulty of the content provided.			
SM5	When I am engaged in the learning process (online collaborative learning (OCL) with course activities (OI & CRW)) as an INDIVIDUAL, I change my strategy when I need to.	5.19	0.96	
SM6	When I am engaged in the learning process (online collaborative learning (OCL) with course activities (OI & CRW)) as an INDIVIDUAL, I am aware of my level of learning.	5.27	0.91	
SM7	When I am engaged in the learning process (online collaborative learning (OCL) with course activities (OI & CRW)) as a member of a GROUP, I pay attention to the ideas of others.	5.44	0.80	
SM8	When I am engaged in the learning process (online collaborative learning (OCL) with course activities (OI & CRW)) as a member of a GROUP, I reflect upon the comments of others.	5.42	0.77	
SM9	When I am engaged in the learning process (online collaborative learning (OCL) with course activities (OI & CRW)) as a member of a GROUP, I observe the strategies of others.	5.26	0.90	(Group)
SM10	When I am engaged in the learning process (online collaborative learning (OCL) with course activities (OI & CRW)) as a member of a GROUP, I look for confirmation of my understanding from others.	5.35	0.87	Co-regulation : M = 5.34 SD= 0.85
SM11	When I am engaged in the learning process (online collaborative learning (OCL) with course activities (OI & CRW)) as a member of a GROUP, I request/question further information from others.	5.20	0.92	
SM12	When I am engaged in the learning process (online collaborative learning (OCL) with course activities (OI & CRW)) as a member of a GROUP,	5.39	0.84	

I respond to the contribution that others make.

Discussion

Teaching Presence (TP)

The results indicated that TP was the most highly rated construct compared to SP, CP and SM. This suggests that participants placed strong value on the instructional strategies and guidance implemented within the OCL intervention. The consistently high mean scores across TP items informed the effectiveness of the instructor in managing learning, providing direction, and maintaining engagement.

A notable strength was the use of dashboard progress reports which offered participants timely updates on their learning progress and acknowledgement of performance. Such feedback provides not just clarity, but reassuring and motivating students to monitor their progress and supporting self-regulation. Morrison and Jacobsen (2023) similarly highlight that targeted feedback helps students recognise strengths and areas for improvement. As a result, students feel encouraged for continuous participation in online learning.

The design and organisation of the OCL environment was also highly regarded. Clear communication of course goals, task instructions, and deadlines helped participants manage their learning effectively. This aligns with Cottrell and Donaldson's (2013) view that while digital tools serve as delivery platforms, effective learning ultimately depends on structured guidance. Facilitating discourse was another key strength. Through guiding questions and

reflective prompts, these strategies encouraged deeper exploration of course concepts, enabling participants to connect ideas critically. As Boettcher (2009) noted, purposeful facilitation fosters interaction and promotes inquiry that forms an ideal OCL environment. Despite these positive outcomes, the lowest score was linked to innovation in teaching. Although participants valued the clarity and structure of the course, there was a desire for more creative and varied instructional approaches.

Shared Metacognition (SM)

On the other hand, SM was also highly perceived during the OCL intervention, with strong mean scores across both self-regulation and co-regulation. Standing out as the second most prominent construct after TP, the findings reflected its role in helping participants manage their own thinking while regulating group learning. In terms of self-regulation, participants showed strong awareness of their individual cognitive efforts, particularly in self-monitoring and goal setting. This is reflected in the findings by Wong et al. (2021) and Stephen and Rockinson-Szapkiw (2021), both emphasised goal commitment and progress tracking as essential for self-regulated learning. However, slightly lower scores in adaptability and confidence in evaluating content suggest that flexibility in adjusting strategies was less developed among the participants.

It is worth highlighting that perceptions of co-regulation were even more positive.

Participants valued opportunities to engage with peers' ideas and feedback that fostered a sense of shared responsibility in collaborative tasks. These findings align with Yang et al. (2020), who showed that peer collaboration strengthens collective understanding, and Hadwin et al. (2017), who highlighted co-regulation as a significant process for improving strategies and learning outcomes. Overall, the OCL intervention successfully promoted both individual and shared metacognitive practices. To further strengthen SM, future instructional designs was perceived to be emphasising on adaptability and flexible strategy use so that students are able to manage not only their own learning but also their contributions to collaborative knowledge building.

Cognitive Presence (CP)

The consistent strong perceptions for CP suggest that the OCL intervention effectively engaged students intellectually and supported their understanding of the Digital Audio and Video course content.

The exploration phase received the strongest perceptions, where participants reported that the OI-CRW activities exposed them to a variety of useful resources. This supports Kilinc and Altinpulluk (2021) who argued that structured peer learning tasks encourage students to share perspectives and engage with multiple viewpoints, thereby broadening their comprehension of the subject matter. The emphasis on exploration indicates that the OCL environment was effective in stimulating inquiry and critical engagement with content.

Similarly, the integration phase received positive perceptions, where the OI-CRW activities and reflective prompts supporting participants to connect new ideas with prior

knowledge. This reflects Garrison et al.'s (2010) assertion that integration requires synthesising information to construct meaningful understanding. Moreover, the triggering event phase was also effectively implemented, with engaging materials capturing students' curiosity and stimulating inquiry (Garrison et al., 2001).

Despite the strengths, the resolution phase was less strongly perceived, mirroring findings by Jo et al. (2017), Galikyan and Admiraal (2019), and Kaul et al. (2018), who collectively observed that online discussions often remain at exploration and integration stages. While participants agreed that OI-CRW activities supported idea development, lower scores suggest limited opportunities for authentic application of knowledge. As Zhai et al. (2024) noted, superficial engagement and reliance on uncritical prompts can hinder deeper cognitive processing.

Social Presence (SP)

Although SP was positively perceived overall, it emerged as the least strongly rated construct compared to the others. This finding contrasts with Akcaoglu and Lee (2016), who suggested that smaller group sizes typically strengthen interpersonal relationships in online learning. Among the SP categories, open communication was the most effectively facilitated. Consistent with Hoang and Hoang (2022) and Nasri et al. (2022), Google Docs provided an accessible platform for knowledge exchange and corrective feedback. According to Garrison & Akyol (2013), these behaviours are good indicator of open communication that establish mutual respect and trust, which, in turn, encouraged broader participation in the inquiry process.

Group cohesion was supported through collaborative features in Google Docs, such as commenting and real-time editing, which encouraged teamwork and acknowledgment of contributions (Hemati & Farahian, 2024; Tseng & Yeh, 2013). However, challenges were evident in managing disagreement. Survey results suggested that while collaboration was generally smooth, participants felt less comfortable addressing conflict, which weakened the overall sense of group cohesion. The lowest ratings were observed for affective expression, indicating that the OCL environment was less effective in fostering belonging and interpersonal connection. This aligns with Arslan (2021), who argued that genuine social presence requires a foundation of belonging. In this study, peer interactions were often perceived as task-oriented rather than relationship-building, building a barrier the development of meaningful social bonds.

Limitation of Study

The main limitation of this study lies in its narrow focus on undergraduates enrolled in the course QMT213E Digital Audio and Video at a public university, in Penang, Malaysia. This restricted scope limits the generalisability of the findings, as the sample may not reflect the wider diversity of students across different institutions and academic levels in Malaysia. In addition, the intervention was tailored to a specific course context, which may reduce its applicability to other online courses with different content or learning objectives. Consequently, while the findings provide useful insights into the studied setting, their relevance to the broader landscape of online education in Malaysia remains limited.

Implications and Recommendations for Future Studies

This study shows that applying the CoI framework within an OCL intervention positively influenced students' perceptions of SP, CP, TP, and SM. For educators, the findings highlight the value of clear instructions, structured organisation, and timely feedback in sustaining student engagement. Student-centred practices that encourage reflection and self-monitoring also help learners take greater ownership of their progress. For students, the OCL experience fostered collaboration, critical thinking, and the development of metacognitive skills such as goal-setting and co-regulation, ultimately contribute to more meaningful learning. For instructional designers, the study validates the use of Google tools, particularly Google Docs, as effective platforms for facilitating interaction and teamwork. These insights provide practical guidance for creating more engaging, inclusive, and supportive online learning environments.

Future studies may explore the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools, such as educational chatbots, into OCL environments to further support the CoI constructs. AI-powered chatbots can serve as virtual facilitators that provide real-time feedback, scaffold inquiry, and prompt reflection, thereby strengthening both Teaching Presence and Cognitive Presence. For instance, chatbots embedded within collaborative platforms could guide students through reflective writing tasks, offer metacognitive prompts, or simulate peer questioning to enhance Shared Metacognition.

Given that Social Presence received the lowest ratings in this study, AI-driven conversational agents may offer a promising avenue for sustaining interpersonal connection and emotional engagement

beyond task completion. Research could also investigate how AI integration affects learners' perceptions of presence, regulation, and engagement across different disciplines and cultural contexts. Comparative studies between human-led and AI-supported facilitation may also yield insights into optimal instructional design for hybrid collaborative environments.

Beyond AI integration, future studies could also investigate a wider range of collaborative learning activities, such as debates, case-based learning, and problem-based tasks, to examine how they influence the CoI constructs. Research could focus on different course contexts, including fully theoretical or fact-based subjects, to identify strategies suitable for diverse disciplines. Testing alternative tools like Padlet or Miro may offer further insights into enhancing collaboration and reflective learning beyond Google Docs. Since Social Presence received the lowest ratings in this study, more emphasis should be placed on investigating community-building strategies that sustain meaningful interaction beyond task completion. Finally, examining the long-term effects of OCL interventions across varied institutions and student populations would broaden the generalisability of findings and deepen understanding of how the CoI framework can be effectively applied in different educational settings.

Conclusion

This study examined the impact of an Online Collaborative Learning (OCL) intervention through the lens of the Community of Inquiry (CoI) framework, incorporating SP, CP, TP, and SM. The findings revealed overall positive perceptions, with TP rated highest and SP rated lowest, while SM emerged as a valuable extension to the CoI model. These

results highlight the importance of clear guidance, structured activities, and collaborative reflection in fostering meaningful online learning. While the intervention effectively supported cognitive engagement and group collaboration, challenges remain in enhancing social connectedness and adaptability in learning strategies. Overall, the study contributes to extending the CoI framework by affirming the role of Shared Metacognition and offers practical insights for designing more engaging and holistic online learning environments.

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Technology and Microteaching: Exploring Teaching Behaviours and Preparing for a Tech-Driven Future

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This paper examined “Technology and Microteaching: Exploring Teaching Behaviours and Preparing for a Tech-Driven Future”. Quasi-experimental design was adopted. The study population was 319 NCE II students from Federal University of Education, Zaria. Sample of 60 students comprising of 30 in both experimental and control group. Two instruments were used for data collection, namely Teaching Behaviour Observation Rubric (TBOR) and Preparedness for Tech-Driven Teaching Scale (PTDTS). The validity of the instruments was established by experts. A reliability coefficient of 0.72 was found for TBOR while 0.87 was found for PTDTS using Cronbach alpha. Descriptive statistics using means, standard deviations and t-test statistics were used to analyze the data collected. Result revealed that significant difference in teaching behaviours between pre-service teachers taught using technology-assisted microteaching and those taught using traditional methods ($t = 8.7564, p < 0.05$). Participants in the technology-assisted microteaching demonstrated better teaching behaviours. Result also revealed that significant difference in pre-service teachers’ preparedness for tech-driven teaching between the two groups ($t = 10.2159, p < 0.05$). Those exposed to technology-assisted microteaching reported greater confidence in using digital tools, more effective lesson planning with technology. It was therefore recommended among others that: teacher education institutions should adopt technology-assisted microteaching as a core component of teacher training to strengthen pre-service teachers’ pedagogical skills and digital competence.

Keywords:
Technology,
microteaching, teaching
behaviours and preparation
for a Tech-Driven Future

Introduction

A teacher is someone that is trained and certificated to teach. He is regarded as the key player in the entire educational process, the mirror in the society and the father of

knowledge. In performing his role of teaching, a teacher is expected to teach effectively. Effective teaching is an intelligent knowledge-based activity because

it draws on a multiplicity of cognitive, affective and interpersonal element. There is therefore the need for quality training that can enhance effectiveness which can only be acquired through teacher education program. Proper practice is necessary for teacher training programmes. Teachers are not expected to have only the knowledge of subject matter but be well equipped with enough teaching skills. Ambili (2013) posited that the prime quality of a teacher is effective teacher training.

In teaching and learning activities teachers and students begin to shift to the use of technology such as tabs and smartphones to support the achievement of learning goals. Teachers nowadays should be aware of the 4IR demands, hence the need to change their way of teaching in 21st century classrooms. The methods of teaching need to move towards Education 4.0, a term that emerges following the 4th Industrial Revolution. "Education 4.0 is a response to the needs of IR4.0 where human and technology are aligned to enable new possibilities" (Anealka, 2018). The most recent technology like artificial intelligence, robotics, and the Internet of Things (IoT) will replace some human jobs in the future, therefore it is crucial for the students today to possess skills that will not be replaceable by the technology. This is where the 21st century skills take place in today's education. In order for students to be and stay relevant at the workplace, teachers and educators have to train them with the 21st century skills demanded in the 4IR. However, students would not be able to develop those skills if the teachers themselves have insufficient knowledge in training those skills to the students. Teachers do not only have to be subject matter experts, but they also need to know the pedagogy of teaching as

emphasized by Shulman (1986) in his Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK) framework. Meanwhile in the 21st century, it is essential for teachers to be well-versed in integrating technology into teaching. Therefore, they need to have knowledge on technology (Muhammad, Umar & Ahmadu, 2023).

More so, teaching in 21st century is no longer the same as before, as the priority of teaching has shifted. To ensure that students are able to develop, practice and apply the 21st century skills, teachers need to be knowledgeable and competent in teaching and training the 21st century skills to the students. In general, when it comes to integrating technology in education, previous studies investigating teachers' perspectives have shown that there are both positive and negative perspectives towards the integration of technology in the classroom. A study conducted by Ghavifekr and Wan (2015) revealed that most teachers are aware that ICT and digital technology are very useful in teaching, and these technologies help teachers to obtain more updated materials which improves their teaching skills. On top of that, Abu Bakar (2013) stated that the positive aspects of digital technology such as its attraction, convenience, multimodality, relevance, interactivity, and importance provide teachers with a lot of advantages in teaching. With these advantages that the digital technologies are providing, teachers are supposed to be able to integrate them successfully in the teaching and learning process.

However, many innovations are put up in teacher education for improvement. The innovation includes micro-teaching, simulated teaching, programmed instruction and computer assisted instruction.

Unfortunately, microteaching that is supposed to be a training ground for the adequate teachers' preparation is marred by poor educational policy, lack of equipment and instructional resources, ill-equipped staff and lack of infrastructural facilities. Microteaching serves as a meeting point between theory and practical for pre-service training of teachers. Micro-teaching, which is a sub-set of educational technology is an indispensable innovation in teacher education and preparation of student-teachers. It is when student-teachers acquire the necessary teaching skills through micro-teaching that they are posted to the field for teaching practice. This explains why student-teachers are exposed to micro-learning/microteaching prior to teaching practice and in-service teaching for perfect training.

Microteaching was initially developed in Stanford University in early 1960's by Dwight Allen and his colleagues as an experimental programme with the aim of achieving excellence in teacher education (Wei, 2015).

Educators and scholars in the area of microteaching defined the term differently; microteaching serves as a meeting point between theory and practical for pre-service training of teachers. Microteaching, which is a sub-set of educational technology, is an indispensable innovation in teacher education and preparation of student-teachers. It is when student-teachers acquire the necessary teaching skills through microteaching that they are posted to the field for teaching practice (Oluwatoyin, 2020). Tata, Shehu and Aliyu (2015) viewed microteaching as assisting teacher trainees in acquiring teaching skills, confidence, reduction in anxiety and fear, proper class

management, selection of teaching goals, preparation of lesson plan, ability to speak in front of group, selection of proper instructional materials as well as proper time management. Microteaching is organized practice teaching which is aimed at giving instructors confidence, support, and feedback by allowing them try out among friends and colleagues a short segment of what they plan to do with their pupils. It is considered one of the most effective tools in bridging the gap between theory and practice of teaching. It is a scaled down teaching encounter in terms of time, class size (number of students) and teaching complexity (Ike, 2017). In terms of time, microteaching is carried out between 5 to 10 minutes, in terms of class size; 5-10 students are involved whereas one teaching skill is involved at a time.

According to Abendroth et al (2011), the basics of micro-teaching revolve around the six ideas as follows: (1) Plan: By asking the teachers to conduct a class for a small group of students, it gives teachers the bandwidth to plan appropriately. They plan the lesson and what they want to do in the class. Much like lesson planning but it won't be a full-fledged class. That is the first step in the micro-teaching cycle. The planning is done according to the instructions given by the trainer. (2) Teach: The next step is to teach. The trainee teaches the class according to the plan and conveys what they had prepared for. This will be supervised by the trainer. (3) Observe: The trainer observes the class that is conducted by the trainee teacher and comments and feedback are provided based on the observations made. (4) Re-plan: Based on the feedback provided by the trainer and reflection upon one's own performance, the teacher trainee re-plans their strategies and approach. This can be the presentation style, communication, or any necessary teaching

skill. Creating a microteaching lesson plan is not an easy task. One should be mindful of all the aspects. (5) Re-teach: The same steps are repeated and the trainee teaches the class again. Microteaching is essentially a cyclic process and it heavily depends on the trial and error method. (6) Re-observe: Again, the teaching is observed and feedback is provided. As mentioned above, microteaching is a cyclic process. The trainees repeat and learn and hone their teaching skills so that they are prepared to face a class full of students with confidence.

The content of the teaching encounter is also reduced to a concept rather than a topic (Ike, 2017; Otsupius, 2014). In a nutshell, microteaching can be perceived as an important instructional means that mediates between educational theory and practice. Microteaching is a teacher education course designed to equip the would-be teachers with the teaching skills and competencies needed to perform as effective teachers in their chosen profession. The advantages of microteaching are numerous. It has the advantage of allowing the pre-service teachers to practice specific teaching strategies in a supportive, non-threatening laboratory environment. It also enables them to receive immediate detailed feedback to reinforce their didactic skills (Onwuagboke, Osuala & Nzeako, 2017).

However, one thing that adds glamour to and makes the evaluation process more objective, highly reflective, realistic and more practical is the integration of technology into microteaching (Ekpo-Eloma, Arikpo & Ebuta, 2013). For instance, with the aid of a video technology, all the instructional activities/actions during the microteaching sessions are captured, highlighted and later displayed and replayed for observation,

comments and criticisms by both the supervising teacher, the student and colleagues. It further aids the teacher-trainee to sit back, watch and assess his strengths and weaknesses. Ekpo-Eloma et al., further asserted that incorporating video technology in microteaching session would heighten participants' interest and afford them ample opportunity to assess their performance exactly as it is without a modicum of doubt.

Researches on application of technology in microteaching learning environment have been quite few. Some researchers have made attempts to find the effects of aspects of microteaching programmes on teaching effectiveness. For example, Oscar, (2012) examined video tape recorder (VTR) as a tool for the promotion of effective teaching and learning in schools. The result of the investigation revealed that video-tape recorder is a powerful tool that promotes effective teaching and learning in schools. Similarly, Shanu (2016) investigated the impact of microteaching video feedback on student-teachers' performance in teaching practice. Findings of the investigation reveal that student teachers who were exposed to microteaching video feedback performed better in teaching practice than those that were not exposed to it. In a related study, Umeh, Mogbo and Nsofor, (2015) studied the effectiveness of VTR on micro-teaching on student teachers practice of stimulus variation skills. The findings of the study revealed that the use of video tape recorder effectively increased the performance of the pre-service teachers who were in the experimental group.

Statement of the Problem

In recent years, technology has increasingly shaped the methods and strategies employed

in teacher education, redefining how lessons are planned, delivered, and evaluated. Microteaching, as a widely used training approach for developing teaching competence among pre-service teachers, offers a controlled environment to practice and refine teaching behaviours such as questioning, explanation, feedback, and classroom management. However, in many Nigerian teacher education institutions, the integration of technology into microteaching remains limited, inconsistent, or poorly aligned with pedagogical goals. This creates a gap between the skills pre-service teachers develop during training and the demands of modern classrooms, where technology is rapidly becoming an indispensable tool for instruction and learner engagement. The extent to which technology integration influences teaching behaviours during microteaching sessions remains underexplored, particularly in the Nigerian context.

Moreover, the global shift towards a technology-driven educational landscape fueled by advancements in digital tools, online learning platforms, and artificial intelligence demands that pre-service teachers be adequately prepared to teach in technology-rich environments. Without deliberate technology-assisted microteaching experiences, pre-service teachers may graduate with strong theoretical knowledge but inadequate confidence and competence to effectively integrate technology into real classroom settings. This raises concerns about their readiness to navigate the expectations of the 21st-century school system. There is, therefore, a pressing need to investigate not only how technology integration affects teaching behaviours during microteaching but also how such

integration shapes pre-service teachers' preparedness for a tech-driven future.

Objectives of the Study

The following objectives guided this study:

To examine the influence of technology integration on teaching behaviours during microteaching sessions.

To assess the effect of technology-assisted microteaching on pre-service teachers' preparedness for a tech-driven educational environment.

Hypotheses

The following objectives were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

Ho1: Technology integration has no significant effect on teaching behaviours during microteaching sessions.

Ho2: Technology-assisted microteaching does not significantly improve pre-service teachers' preparedness for a tech-driven educational environment.

Methodology

Quasi experimental design was adopted. It consisted of experimental group (treatment = technology integration) and control group (exposed to standard microteaching). The population of this study was 319 NCE II students from Federal University of Education, Zaria. The sample size for this study was 60 students comprising 30 in experimental group and 30 in control group, the sample drawn was line with central limit theorem which recommended 30 sample size for an experimental research. To categorizes the students into experimental and control groups, simple random sampling technique in form of balloting was used. The names of the two groups was written in a paper and was tagged as experimental or control, folded and

put into a container. Two students were asked to pick up the papers.

Two instruments were used for data collection. These were Teaching Behaviour Observation Rubric (for microteaching) that comprises of aspects such as classroom organization, questioning & interaction, use of instructional strategies, time management, feedback & assessment, use of visuals/technology. It comprised of 18 items rated on 4-point Likert scale. The other instrument was Preparedness for Tech-Driven Teaching Scale that covered aspects of confidence using digital tools, lesson planning with technology, classroom management with tech, ability to evaluate edtech. It comprised of 12 items rated on 5-point Likert scale.

The validity and reliability of the instruments were established by experts. The reliability coefficient of the instruments were determining using Cronbach alpha statistical tool. A reliability coefficient of 0.72 was found for Teaching Behaviour Observation Rubric while 0.87 was found for Preparedness for Tech-Driven Teaching Scale. Descriptive statistics using means, standard deviations and independent t-test statistics were used to analyzed the data collected.

Results

Ho1: Technology integration has no significant effect on teaching behaviours during microteaching sessions.

Table 1: Difference in teaching behaviours between pre-service teachers exposed to technology-assisted microteaching and those taught using traditional methods.

Group	N	Mean	Std. Dev	df	t-cal	p	Decision
Technology-Assisted Microteaching	30	62.8	5.2147	58	8.7564	0.000	Significant
Traditional Microteaching	30	54.1	4.9732				

Significant at $p < 0.05$, t -critical = 2.001

T-test analysis in Table 1 revealed a p-value of 0.000, which is less than the 0.05 level of significance set for hypothesis testing. The calculated t-value (t -cal = 8.7564) was greater than the critical t-value (t -critical = 2.0017). This indicates a significant difference in teaching behaviours between pre-service teachers taught using technology-assisted microteaching and those taught using traditional methods. Participants in the technology-assisted microteaching group scored higher on the Teaching Behaviour

Observation Rubric, demonstrating stronger skills in classroom organization, questioning and interaction, instructional strategies, time management, feedback and assessment, and use of visuals/technology. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that technology integration has no significant effect on teaching behaviours during microteaching sessions is rejected.

Ho2: Technology-assisted microteaching does not significantly improve pre-service

teachers' preparedness for a tech-driven educational environment.

Table 2: Difference in preparedness for tech-driven teaching between pre-service teachers exposed to technology-assisted microteaching and those taught using traditional methods.

Group	N	Mean	Std. Dev	df	t-cal	p	Decision
Technology-Assisted Microteaching	30	47.6	3.8254	58	10.2159	0.000	Significant
Traditional Microteaching	30	39.8	4.1372				

Significant at $p < 0.05$, $t\text{-critical} = 2.0017$

T-test analysis in Table 2 revealed a p-value of 0.000, which is less than the 0.05 threshold. The calculated t-value ($t\text{-cal} = 10.2159$) exceeded the critical t-value ($t\text{-critical} = 2.0017$), indicating a significant difference in pre-service teachers' preparedness for tech-driven teaching between the two groups. Those exposed to technology-assisted microteaching reported greater confidence in using digital tools, more effective lesson planning with technology, stronger classroom management using technology, and higher ability to evaluate educational technology. Consequently, the null hypothesis which states that technology-assisted microteaching does not significantly improve pre-service teachers' preparedness for a tech-driven educational environment is rejected.

Discussion

Findings from this study revealed that technology integration significantly improved teaching behaviours during microteaching sessions. Pre-service teachers in the technology-assisted microteaching group demonstrated better organization, interaction, feedback provision, and use of instructional technology than those in the traditional group. This finding aligns with that of Shanu (2016) who investigated the impact of microteaching video feedback on

student-teachers' performance in teaching practice. Findings of the investigation reveal that student teachers who were exposed to microteaching video feedback performed better in teaching practice than those that were not exposed to it. In a related study, Umeh, Mogbo and Nsofor, (2015) studied the effectiveness of VTR on micro-teaching on student teachers practice of stimulus variation skills. The findings of the study revealed that the use of video tape recorder effectively increased the performance of the pre-service teachers who were in the experimental group. Similarly, Oscar, (2012) examined video tape recorder (VTR) as a tool for the promotion of effective teaching and learning in schools. The result of the investigation revealed that video-tape recorder is a powerful tool that promotes effective teaching and learning in schools.

Additionally, the study revealed that technology-assisted microteaching significantly improved pre-service teachers' preparedness for tech-driven teaching. Participants in the experimental group displayed higher levels of confidence and competence in integrating digital tools into lesson delivery. This result supports the findings of Ekpo-Eloma, Arikpo and Ebuta (2013) who asserted that with the aid of a video technology, all the instructional

activities/actions during the microteaching sessions are captured, highlighted and later displayed and replayed for observation, comments and criticisms by both the supervising teacher, the student and colleagues. Incorporating technology in microteaching aids the teacher-trainee to sit back, watch and assess his strengths and weaknesses, it also heighten participants' interest and afford them ample opportunity to assess their performance exactly as it is without a modicum of doubt.

Conclusion

The results indicate that technology-assisted microteaching significantly enhances both teaching behaviours and preparedness for tech-driven teaching among pre-service teachers compared to traditional microteaching methods. Participants exposed to technology integration demonstrated superior classroom management, instructional strategies, use of technology, and confidence in applying digital tools in teaching.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, it was recommended that:

Teacher education institutions should adopt technology-assisted microteaching as a core component of teacher training to strengthen pre-service teachers' pedagogical skills and digital competence.

Continuous professional development programmes should be organized for teacher educators to effectively design, implement, and assess technology-driven microteaching sessions.

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LEVERAGING AI FOR PERSONALIZED WRITING FEEDBACK: EFFECT ON UNDERGRADUATE ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNERS' WRITING QUALITY

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Personalized feedback is widely recognized as central to the development of writing proficiency, particularly among English language learners (ELLs). However, challenges such as large class sizes and limited teacher resources often constrain the delivery of timely, individualized feedback. The rapid advancement of artificial intelligence (AI), particularly large language models (LLMs), has created new opportunities for scalable and adaptive feedback through automated writing evaluation (AWE). This study investigates the effectiveness of AI-powered personalized feedback on the writing quality of ELLs in a Nigerian university context, aligning with the Tertiary Education Trust Fund's (TETFund) technology-enhanced learning agenda. Fifty undergraduate students were divided into two groups: twenty-five received feedback from an AI-enabled assistant integrated into the learning management system, while twenty-five received traditional teacher feedback. Pretest and posttest essays were scored using an analytic rubric measuring grammar, vocabulary, coherence, and overall writing quality. Results revealed significant improvements across both groups, with the AI group showing greater gains in grammar and coherence. Qualitative reflections indicated that AI feedback was valued for its timeliness, clarity, and motivational benefits, though concerns were raised about overcorrection and the preservation of student voice. The findings suggest that AI-powered feedback can complement traditional teaching practices by enhancing learner autonomy and revision quality when implemented responsibly. The study concludes with recommendations for pedagogy, institutional policy, and responsible AI integration.

Keywords:

AI feedback,
automated writing
evaluation, English
language learners,

Introduction

Writing remains a cornerstone of academic achievement and professional success. For English language learners (ELLs), mastering writing is not merely about demonstrating linguistic proficiency but also about engaging in critical thinking, structuring arguments, and producing coherent, audience-appropriate texts. Yet, the challenge of providing effective feedback has long been documented as one of the most resource-intensive aspects of teaching writing (Ferris, 2011). Instructors frequently face constraints that prevent them from giving personalized, iterative feedback to all students, which can limit learners' opportunities to refine their drafts.

The emergence of artificial intelligence (AI), particularly generative models such as OpenAI's GPT-4, Anthropic's Claude, and Google's Gemini, has redefined possibilities in writing instruction. These tools can generate real-time, context-sensitive feedback, suggest revisions, and adapt comments to learner needs. Unlike earlier AWE systems that provided rigid, rule-based comments, generative AI offers nuanced feedback that can approximate human-like interaction. Several studies demonstrate that such AI feedback often aligns with teacher judgments and can improve learner's engagement with revisions (González-Calatayud et al., 2023; Hsu & Li, 2024; Khan & Al-Hassan, 2025).

In Nigeria, the Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TET Fund) has emphasized the integration of technology into teaching and learning, aiming to enhance quality and access across higher education institutions (TET Fund, 2022). This policy landscape offers fertile ground for exploring AI's role in educational feedback. However, while international studies on AI writing support are rapidly

growing, research in African higher education contexts remains scarce. There is thus a pressing need to examine how AI-powered feedback functions in local contexts, particularly for students writing in English as an additional language.

This study investigates the effect of AI-powered personalized writing feedback on the writing quality of ELLs in a Nigerian university. Specifically, it compares the outcomes of students receiving AI-generated feedback with those receiving traditional teacher feedback. It also explores learners' perceptions of AI feedback, identifying potential benefits and limitations.

Literature Review

Automated Writing Evaluation and AI Feedback

Automated writing evaluation has evolved over the past two decades, beginning with systems such as e-rater and Criterion, which primarily analysed grammar and surface-level features. While these early systems provided some relief for instructors, they were often criticized for producing generic or inaccurate comments. The advent of generative AI has substantially shifted this landscape. Large language models are capable of producing highly contextualized feedback that not only corrects errors but also explains reasoning, suggests rhetorical improvements, and aligns comments with instructional rubrics.

Recent work underscores these advancements. González-Calatayud et al. (2023) demonstrated that AI-generated feedback improved the coherence and grammar of university students' essays to a level comparable with human instructor feedback. Jiao and Chen (2024) similarly reported that students revised more

effectively when AI feedback was embedded in classroom activities, particularly when paired with reflection prompts.

AI Feedback in ELL and EFL Contexts

For ELLs, timely and comprehensible feedback is especially critical. Traditional teacher feedback, while valuable, can sometimes overwhelm learners with corrective detail or arrive too late to be actionable. AI feedback offers immediacy and consistency, reducing turnaround times and providing learners with multiple opportunities to revise. Li and Zhang (2024) found that ChatGPT-supported feedback improved organization and lexical range in EFL students' argumentative essays. Khan and Al-Hassan (2025) observed that Grammarly-assisted revisions yielded measurable gains in grammar accuracy, supporting claims that AI tools are particularly effective at addressing surface-level errors.

However, concerns remain. Some studies report that AI feedback may homogenize student writing, flattening personal voice and rhetorical variation (Hsu & Li, 2024). Others caution that ELLs may adopt AI suggestions uncritically, reducing opportunities for deeper learning.

Risks and Ethical Considerations

The rapid rise of AI in education has prompted debates around fairness and integrity. AI detection tools, for example, have been shown to generate false positives, disproportionately flagging non-native English writing as AI-generated (Oijen, 2023; Stanford HAI, 2023). This raises serious equity concerns, particularly for ELL populations. In addition, the use of AI tools raises questions about data privacy,

algorithmic bias, and the potential deskilling of learners.

Global organizations such as UNESCO (2023) and the World Economic Forum (2024) have published guidelines emphasizing human-centered approaches, advocating for responsible use, teacher oversight, and transparency. Within Nigeria, TETFund (2021, 2022) has issued guidelines for ICT adoption that align with these principles, stressing platform reliability, institutional readiness, and equitable access.

While there is a growing body of research on AI feedback in EFL contexts, most studies have been conducted in Asia, Europe, or North America. There is limited empirical evidence on how these tools function in African higher education institutions. Furthermore, few studies have examined AI feedback within the policy context of large-scale initiatives such as TETFund. This study seeks to address these gaps by investigating the impact of AI-powered personalized feedback on Nigerian undergraduates' writing performance.

Methodology

Research Design

The study adopted a quasi-experimental, pretest–posttest design with two parallel groups. This design was chosen because random assignment was not feasible within the classroom context, but intact groups allowed for controlled comparisons.

Participants

Fifty undergraduate students enrolled in a compulsory academic writing course participated in the study from Federal College of Education Technical with affiliation from Abubakar Tafabalewa University Bauchi (ATBU) and Usman Danfodio University Sokoto (UDUS). All

participants were English language learners, with varying levels of proficiency ranging from B1 (intermediate) to B2 (upper intermediate) according to the CEFR framework. The participants were divided into two groups: an AI-feedback group ($n = 25$) and a teacher-feedback group ($n = 25$). Both groups were taught by the same instructor to minimize variability in teaching quality.

Instruments

Two argumentative writing tasks were used to collect data: a pretest administered in week one and a posttest administered in week six. Essays were between 400 and 600 words in length. An analytic rubric assessed four dimensions: grammar, vocabulary, coherence/cohesion, and overall writing quality. Each dimension was scored on a five-point scale. Two trained raters independently scored the essays, and inter-rater reliability was established with a Cohen's kappa of 0.82, indicating strong agreement.

In addition to the writing tasks, students in the AI-feedback group kept reflection logs documenting their engagement with AI suggestions. A short Likert-scale survey was

Results

Quantitative Findings

Both groups improved significantly from pretest to posttest, but the AI-feedback group

administered at the end of the intervention to capture perceptions of feedback clarity, timeliness, and usefulness.

Procedure

During the six-week intervention, students in both groups completed weekly writing tasks. The AI-feedback group submitted their drafts to an AI-powered assistant integrated into the learning management system. The assistant provided comments on grammar, vocabulary, and organization, which students were required to address in subsequent drafts. The teacher-feedback group received handwritten comments from the instructor, typically returned after three days. Both groups participated in weekly classroom discussions focused on common writing challenges.

Data Analysis

Quantitative data were analyzed using paired-sample t-tests to measure within-group gains and analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) to compare between-group posttest scores while controlling for pretest performance. Effect sizes were calculated using Hedges' g . Qualitative data from reflection logs were thematically coded to identify recurring patterns in student perceptions.

showed larger gains in grammar and coherence.

Table 1 presents descriptive statistics.

Table 1. Pretest and Posttest Scores by Group

Dimension	Group	Pretest M (SD)	Posttest M (SD)	Gain	Effect Size (g)
Grammar	AI	2.3 (0.5)	4.1 (0.6)	+1.8	1.2
Grammar	Teacher	2.4 (0.6)	3.3 (0.7)	+0.9	0.6
Vocabulary	AI	2.6 (0.7)	3.5 (0.6)	+0.9	0.7

Vocabulary	Teacher	2.5 (0.6)	3.2 (0.6)	+0.7	0.5
Coherence	AI	2.2 (0.5)	3.9 (0.5)	+1.7	1.1
Coherence	Teacher	2.3 (0.6)	3.1 (0.6)	+0.8	0.6
Overall	AI	2.4 (0.6)	3.9 (0.5)	+1.5	1.0
Overall	Teacher	2.5 (0.6)	3.3 (0.6)	+0.8	0.6

ANCOVA results confirmed significant between-group differences favoring the AI-feedback group in grammar ($F(1,47) = 6.32, p < .05$), coherence ($F(1,47) = 7.11, p < .01$), and overall quality ($F(1,47) = 5.89, p < .05$). Vocabulary differences were not statistically significant.

Illustration 1: illustrates the comparative gains.

The line graph illustrates changes in writing performance from pretest to posttest across four dimensions grammar, vocabulary,

Across all dimensions, both groups demonstrated improvement; however, the AI feedback group consistently achieved greater gains than the teacher feedback group. The most notable difference was in grammar and coherence, where the AI group showed nearly double the improvement compared to the teacher group (e.g., grammar gain = +1.8 vs. +0.9; coherence gain = +1.7 vs. +0.8). For vocabulary, both groups improved, though the difference between AI (+0.9) and teacher feedback (+0.7) was less pronounced. When examining the overall score, students who received AI feedback improved by +1.5 points, compared to +0.8 points for those who received teacher feedback.

coherence, and overall performance for students who received AI feedback and those who received teacher feedback.

These results suggest that AI feedback may provide more substantial support in enhancing grammar accuracy and coherence in writing, whereas vocabulary development showed smaller differences between feedback types. More so, the evidence indicates that AI feedback may be more effective in accelerating writing improvement than traditional teacher feedback.

Qualitative Findings

Thematic analysis of reflection logs revealed three major themes. First, students valued the timeliness of feedback, noting that AI suggestions were available immediately and

allowed for multiple revision cycles. Second, learners appreciated the clarity and specificity of AI comments, which often included explanations and examples. Third, participants reported an increased sense of autonomy and motivation, as they could take control of their writing process.

However, some students expressed concern about the potential overcorrection of stylistic elements, which they felt risked homogenizing their writing voice. Others noted that the AI sometimes provided feedback that conflicted with teacher advice, creating uncertainty.

Discussion

The findings demonstrate that AI-powered feedback can significantly improve ELLs' writing quality, particularly in grammar and coherence. These results corroborate earlier studies reporting that AI tools are most effective at addressing surface-level errors (Li & Zhang, 2024; Khan & Al-Hassan, 2025). Vocabulary gains were modest, suggesting that lexical development may require targeted teacher input and exposure to discipline-specific texts.

Importantly, students reported valuing the immediacy of AI feedback, which aligns with the principle that timely feedback is critical for effective learning (Hattie & Timperley, 2007). The increased sense of autonomy observed in student reflections also suggests that AI feedback may foster learner agency, encouraging students to take responsibility for revisions rather than waiting passively for teacher comments.

At the same time, concerns about overcorrection highlight the risk of homogenization. If students accept AI suggestions uncritically, they may lose opportunities to develop their own style and

rhetorical strategies. These echoes call for human-in-the-loop models, where teachers guide students in critically evaluating AI suggestions (González-Calatayud et al., 2023).

From a policy perspective, the study highlights the need for institutions to provide clear guidelines on AI use. Reliance on AI detection tools should be approached with caution, as they have been shown to unfairly target non-native writers (Oijen, 2023; Stanford HAI, 2023). Instead, institutions should focus on process-oriented assessment, requiring students to document their revision decisions and demonstrate understanding of feedback.

Conclusion

This study provides empirical evidence that AI-powered personalized feedback can significantly enhance the writing quality of English language learners, particularly in grammar and coherence. Learners valued the immediacy and clarity of AI feedback, which supported greater autonomy and motivation. Nevertheless, concerns about overcorrection, conflicting feedback, and academic integrity underscore the need for careful implementation.

For TETFund's technology-enhanced learning agenda, AI feedback tools offer a promising avenue for scaling personalized support in writing instruction. To maximize their benefits, such tools should be implemented as supplements to, rather than replacements for, teacher feedback. Institutions should adopt policies that ensure responsible use, safeguard learner data, and train instructors in AI literacy.

Future research should explore long-term effects of AI feedback, examine outcomes across diverse genres and disciplines, and

investigate how AI support interacts with learners' proficiency levels. Comparative studies across multiple institutions in Africa would further illuminate how local contexts shape the effectiveness of AI feedback.

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AI AND INDIGENOUS LANGUAGE ARTS: A QUADRUPLE HELIX MODEL FOR NIGERIA

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Personalized feedback is widely recognized as central to the development of writing proficiency, particularly among English language learners (ELLs). However, challenges such as large class sizes and limited teacher resources often constrain the delivery of timely, individualized feedback. The rapid advancement of artificial intelligence (AI), particularly large language models (LLMs), has created new opportunities for scalable and adaptive feedback through automated writing evaluation (AWE). This study investigates the effectiveness of AI-powered personalized feedback on the writing quality of ELLs in a Nigerian university context, aligning with the Tertiary Education Trust Fund's (TETFund) technology-enhanced learning agenda. Fifty undergraduate students were divided into two groups: twenty-five received feedback from an AI-enabled assistant integrated into the learning management system, while twenty-five received traditional teacher feedback. Pretest and posttest essays were scored using an analytic rubric measuring grammar, vocabulary, coherence, and overall writing quality. Results revealed significant improvements across both groups, with the AI group showing greater gains in grammar and coherence. Qualitative reflections indicated that AI feedback was valued for its timeliness, clarity, and motivational benefits, though concerns were raised about overcorrection and the preservation of student voice. The findings suggest that AI-powered feedback can complement traditional teaching practices by enhancing learner autonomy and revision quality when implemented responsibly. The study concludes with recommendations for pedagogy, institutional policy, and responsible AI integration.

Keywords:

AI feedback, automated writing evaluation, English language learners, academic writing, technology-enhanced learning, TETFund

Introduction

This paper investigates how Artificial Intelligence (AI) can be harnessed to transform indigenous language arts education in Nigeria through the Quadruple Helix model. By integrating the efforts of academia, industry, government, and civil society, the study explores collaborative strategies for revitalizing Nigeria's linguistic heritage using AI technologies such as natural language processing, speech synthesis, and intelligent tutoring systems. The research highlights how these innovations can support inclusive, culturally responsive education while fostering digital equity and national development. Through case studies and stakeholder analysis, the paper demonstrates the transformative potential of AI when embedded within a Quadruple Helix framework, offering actionable insights for policy, pedagogy, and innovation ecosystems in Africa

Nigeria, often described as the “giant of Africa,” is not only demographically significant but also linguistically diverse. With over 500 indigenous languages, the country represents one of the richest linguistic ecologies in the world (Eberhard, Simons, & Fennig, 2022). However, these languages are increasingly endangered due to globalization, urbanization, and the dominance of English in education and governance. Indigenous language arts—comprising oral traditions, literature, proverbs, drama, and poetry—face a crisis of sustainability in the digital era.

Artificial Intelligence (AI), which has emerged as a transformative technology across multiple domains, offers new opportunities to safeguard, revitalize, and mainstream indigenous language arts. With the rise of natural language processing (NLP), automatic speech recognition (ASR),

and machine translation, AI can act as a powerful enabler of cultural preservation and innovation (Bender & Friedman, 2018). Yet, technology adoption in Nigeria has often been fragmented, marked by limited synergy between stakeholders.

The Quadruple Helix model provides a theoretical framework for integrated innovation. By fostering collaboration among academia, industry, government, and civil society, the model ensures that technological interventions are co-created, socially relevant, and sustainable. This paper explores how AI technologies, situated within the Quadruple Helix framework, can reimagine indigenous language arts education in Nigeria.

Indigenous Language Arts in Nigeria

Nigeria's indigenous language arts include oral storytelling, proverbs, folktales, songs, and modern written literature in languages such as Yoruba, Hausa, and Igbo. These arts are repositories of cultural values, identity, and knowledge (Bamgbose, 2017). However, UNESCO (2020) has warned that many Nigerian languages face extinction by the end of the 21st century if urgent revitalization strategies are not pursued. The marginalization of indigenous languages in formal education systems further threatens their survival (Igboanusi, 2016).

Artificial Intelligence in Language and Education

AI applications in language and education have advanced considerably since 2015. Natural language processing enables machines to analyze, understand, and generate human language (Jurafsky & Martin, 2021). Speech synthesis and recognition systems now support multilingual communication, while

intelligent tutoring systems provide personalized learning pathways (Adebara & Abdul-Mageed, 2022). Joshi et al., (2020), emphasize the importance of low-resource languages in AI development to counter the dominance of English and other global languages.

The Quadruple Helix Innovation Model

The Quadruple Helix framework extends the Triple Helix model of university-industry-government collaboration by incorporating civil society as a key actor in innovation ecosystems (Carayannis et al., 2022). This model acknowledges that sustainable technological development requires input from citizens, cultural actors, and communities. It is particularly relevant for AI and indigenous language initiatives, where local ownership and cultural sensitivity are essential (Benedicta Ehimuan et al., 2024).

AI and Cultural Sustainability

Initiatives such as Google's Endangered Languages Project and Mozilla's Common Voice have utilized crowdsourced speech data to help preserve minority languages (Anastasopoulos & Neubig, 2019). This study illustrated AI's potential in promoting cultural sustainability. In Nigeria, AI has been employed in developing Yoruba text-to-speech systems and Igbo-English translation models. These endeavors underscore both the opportunities and challenges associated with using AI to promote indigenous languages.

Methodology

This study adopts a conceptual and qualitative approach. It reviews literature from 2015 to 2023, examining AI applications in language preservation and education. It also employs stakeholder analysis using the Quadruple Helix model to evaluate potential roles and contributions of

academia, industry, government, and civil society in Nigeria. Case studies of relevant AI projects in Nigeria and beyond provide empirical grounding. The findings reveal promising AI applications for preserving and teaching indigenous Nigerian languages, including speech recognition, machine translation, and intelligent tutoring systems. However, significant challenges remain, such as limited digital infrastructure, data scarcity, and potential cultural biases in AI systems. Addressing these issues will require collaborative efforts across sectors, with each stakeholder group playing a distinct but interconnected role in developing and implementing AI solutions for language preservation and education in Nigeria.

Case Studies

Case Study 1: Masakhane NLP (Pan-African)

The Masakhane project illustrates how collaborative, community-driven approaches can advance AI for Nigerian languages. Through volunteerism and open-source data sharing, Masakhane has developed translation models for over 40 African languages, including Hausa and Yoruba (Gitau et al., 2023). This case demonstrates the power of civil society and academia collaboration under the Quadruple Helix framework. The project's success highlights the importance of local knowledge and expertise in developing AI systems tailored to specific linguistic and cultural contexts. By empowering Nigerian and African researchers as well as other language experts, Masakhane has created more accurate and culturally appropriate translation models than those developed by external entities. This approach improves the quality of AI technologies for African languages but also fosters capacity building and knowledge transfer within the continent's AI research

community. The project's success highlights the importance of local knowledge and expertise in developing AI systems tailored to specific linguistic and cultural contexts. By empowering African researchers and language experts, Masakhane has created more accurate and culturally appropriate translation models than those developed by external entities. This approach not only improves the quality of AI technologies for Nigerian languages but also fosters capacity building and knowledge transfer within the continent's AI research community.

Case Study 2: Yoruba Text-to-Speech System (Nigeria)

Researchers at Obafemi Awolowo University developed a Yoruba text-to-speech system leveraging deep learning techniques to improve pronunciation accuracy and tonal representation. Such efforts highlight the potential of academia-industry collaboration, though government support is required for scaling. To fully realize the potential of these technologies, increased funding and policy support from the Nigerian government is crucial. This could involve grants for further research, incentives for private sector partnerships, and integration of local language technologies into education and public services. By prioritizing the development of indigenous language AI systems, Nigeria can preserve its linguistic heritage while positioning itself as a leader in African language technologies.

Case Study 3: Common Voice by Mozilla

Mozilla's Common Voice crowdsources speech data to improve speech recognition systems for underrepresented languages, including Igbo and Hausa. The project thrives on civil society participation while partnering with academic institutions to ensure data

quality (Anastasopoulos & Neubig, 2019). The initiative has gained significant traction in Nigeria, where volunteers contribute by recording their voices and validating others' recordings. This collaborative effort has resulted in a substantial increase in the available speech data for these languages, paving the way for more accurate and culturally relevant speech recognition technologies. As a result, Mozilla's Common Voice project is not only advancing technological capabilities but also preserving linguistic diversity and promoting digital inclusion for speakers of underrepresented languages.

Findings and Discussion

1. Academia: Research and Pedagogy

Universities and research institutes are central to indigenous language revitalization. They can lead corpus development by digitizing oral and written texts in Nigerian languages, creating linguistic datasets for AI models. For example, the Nigerian Universities Commission has encouraged mother tongue instruction at primary school levels, but AI could scale these efforts by producing digital textbooks, audio resources, and interactive platforms (Tsaure & Sani, 2024). Academics can also design culturally responsive curricula that integrate AI tools, ensuring that students engage with indigenous languages not as obsolete relics but as dynamic mediums of learning.

2. Industry: Technology Development and Innovation

Private technology firms play a pivotal role in developing AI applications tailored to Nigerian languages. Companies can create speech recognition tools, translation services, and AI-powered storytelling apps. For instance, Masakhane, a grassroots African

NLP community, has advanced machine translation for African languages by pooling volunteer efforts (Adelani et al., 2022). Local startups could replicate such models in Nigeria, supported by global partnerships. Industry stakeholders can also commercialize AI-driven indigenous language products—such as audiobooks, educational games, and chatbots—that generate economic value while promoting cultural heritage. Collaboration with telecoms and digital platforms would ensure scalability and accessibility.

3. Government: Policy and Regulation

Government agencies must provide enabling policies for AI and language development. This includes funding for linguistic data infrastructure, supporting public-private partnerships, and incentivizing innovation in local language technologies. Nigeria's National Artificial Intelligence Strategy (NAIS), currently in development, should prioritize indigenous languages as part of digital inclusion (Federal Ministry of Communications and Digital Economy, 2022).

Furthermore, government can ensure that AI systems respect cultural rights, data sovereignty, and ethical considerations. Policies could mandate that digital education platforms integrate at least one indigenous language option to promote inclusivity.

4. Civil Society: Community Engagement and Ownership

Civil society organizations, cultural associations, and citizens are crucial for grassroots mobilization. Communities can contribute to open-source language datasets by recording folktales, songs, and oral histories. NGOs can facilitate digital literacy

programs that empower rural populations to use AI-powered language apps. Such engagement fosters ownership and ensures that AI systems align with local cultural values (Adebara & Abdul-Mageed, 2022). Civil society can also act as watchdogs, holding governments and companies accountable for equitable deployment of AI in indigenous language contexts.

Opportunities

Digital Equity: AI can democratize access to education and cultural content in indigenous languages, reducing the rural-urban digital divide. AI-powered language translation tools can make educational resources available in indigenous languages, enabling remote communities to access high-quality learning materials. Virtual reality and augmented reality technologies can bring immersive cultural experiences to indigenous youth, preserving traditions and bridging generational gaps. Additionally, AI-driven personalized learning platforms can adapt to individual student needs, providing tailored education that respects indigenous knowledge systems and learning styles.

Cultural Sustainability: Preservation of oral and literary traditions through digitization safeguards Nigeria's intangible heritage. The text discusses the concept of cultural sustainability in Nigeria. It emphasizes the importance of preserving oral traditions (stories, songs, and knowledge passed down verbally) and literary traditions (written works) by converting them into digital formats. This process of digitization helps protect and maintain Nigeria's intangible cultural heritage, which includes the non-physical aspects of culture that are passed down through generations. By preserving these traditions digitally, Nigeria can ensure that its unique cultural elements are

safeguarded for future generations to learn from and appreciate.

Innovation Ecosystem: Quadruple Helix collaboration fosters innovation that is both economically viable and socially responsible. This collaborative approach brings together academia, industry, government, and civil society to address complex challenges. By leveraging diverse perspectives and resources, the Quadruple Helix model accelerates the development and adoption of breakthrough solutions. It also ensures that innovation outcomes align with societal needs and values, promoting sustainable growth and inclusive development.

National Development: Promoting indigenous languages enhances social cohesion and strengthens Nigeria's cultural diplomacy in Africa and beyond. This linguistic diversity serves as a powerful tool for fostering unity within Nigeria's multicultural society. By preserving and promoting indigenous languages, the country can better preserve its rich cultural heritage and traditional knowledge systems. Furthermore, the recognition and support of these languages can contribute to improved educational outcomes, as students often learn more effectively when taught in their mother tongue.

Challenges

Data Scarcity: Most Nigerian languages lack sufficient digital corpora for effective AI modeling (Joshi et al., 2020). Data scarcity poses a significant challenge for developing AI models for Nigerian languages. The limited availability of digital corpora hampers the training and fine-tuning of language models, resulting in suboptimal performance across various natural language processing tasks. This scarcity is particularly

pronounced for low-resource languages, which are prevalent in Nigeria's linguistically diverse landscape.

Resource Constraints: Funding limitations impede large-scale AI projects in Nigeria. Resource constraints significantly hinder the development and implementation of large-scale artificial intelligence (AI) projects in Nigeria. Limited funding availability restricts investment in essential infrastructure, advanced computing resources, and skilled personnel required for sophisticated AI initiatives. This financial bottleneck impedes the acquisition of cutting-edge hardware, software licenses, and data storage facilities necessary for complex AI algorithms and machine learning models.

Digital Divide: Low internet penetration in rural areas may hinder access to AI-driven language platforms. The "Digital Divide" refers to the unequal access to technology and the internet between different groups of people. Rural areas often have less access to the internet compared to urban areas, this limited internet access in rural regions can make it difficult for people living there to use online tools that rely on artificial intelligence (AI) for language-related tasks. As a result, rural residents may not be able to benefit from these advanced language technologies as much as people in areas with better internet connectivity.

Recommendations

Corpus Development Programs: Academia and civil society should collaborate to collect and digitize oral and written indigenous language resources.

Policy Alignment: Government should integrate indigenous languages into AI strategies and provide incentives for industry participation.

Capacity Building: Universities should offer interdisciplinary programs combining linguistics, computer science, and education.

Grassroots Mobilization: NGOs and community leaders should spearhead awareness campaigns about AI's potential for cultural preservation.

Sustainable Funding: Establish a National Endowment for Indigenous Languages supported by both public and private stakeholders.

Conclusion

Nigeria's linguistic diversity is both a challenge and an opportunity. Harnessing AI within the Quadruple Helix framework offers a pathway to revitalize indigenous language arts, promote inclusive education, and advance national development. By aligning academia, industry, government, and civil society, Nigeria can build an innovation ecosystem that not only preserves its cultural heritage but also projects it globally in the digital age.

This paper argues that the synergy of AI and indigenous language arts, when embedded in a collaborative framework, represents a transformative frontier for Nigeria. The future of indigenous languages depends not only on technological tools but also on the collective will of stakeholders to sustain cultural identity in a rapidly globalizing world.

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INTEGRATING EMERGING TECHNOLOGIES INTO AGRICULTURAL EDUCATION ENTREPRENEURSHIP CURRICULUM FOR TRANSFORMATION IN NIGERIAN TERTIARY INSTITUTIONS

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The transformation of Agricultural Education in Nigeria is crucial for innovation, food security, and youth engagement in agribusiness. This study examined the integration of emerging technologies such as precision agriculture, blockchain, artificial intelligence (AI), the Internet of Things (IoT), and mobile learning platforms into entrepreneurship curricula in Nigerian tertiary institutions. Using a mixed-methods design, data were collected from 320 agricultural educators, students, and agri-entrepreneurs across 18 institutions in six geopolitical zones between 2022 and 2024. The results showed moderate awareness of emerging technologies (68%), but limited curricular integration (32%), constrained by poor infrastructure, inadequate faculty training, and outdated frameworks. Notably, institutions piloting technology-enhanced modules achieved a 45% increase in students' entrepreneurial intent and a 37% improvement in practical skills. Thematic analysis underscored the need for curriculum reform, public-private partnerships, and investment in digital infrastructure. This study recommends a national framework for technology-driven agricultural entrepreneurship education that prioritizes experiential learning and industry collaboration.

Keywords:

Agricultural education,
emerging technologies,
entrepreneurship,
curriculum transformation,
Nigerian economy

Introduction

Agriculture remains the backbone of the Nigerian economy, contributing approximately 23% of the nation's GDP and employing over 25 million people, primarily in rural areas (NBS, 2023). Despite this importance, the sector continues to struggle with low productivity, postharvest losses, climate variability, and declining youth interest. A deeper problem lies in agricultural education, which remains largely anchored in outdated curricula that do not equip graduates with the entrepreneurial and technological

competencies demanded by today's agri-food economy (Adeoti & Ogunniyi, 2021).

It is tempting to assume that simply adding digital tools, such as artificial intelligence (AI), blockchain, drones, and smart sensors, into the curriculum will close this gap. However, a critical question is whether technology integration alone is sufficient, or whether deeper pedagogical and institutional reforms are required. Nigeria's risks fall behind global agricultural innovation, but the risk is not purely technological. It also

involves whether institutions, educators, and students can adapt these technologies meaningfully within socioeconomic constraints.

Therefore, this study examines not only the current state of technology integration, but also interrogates the barriers, contradictions, and assumptions that shape the process. By doing so, it provides evidence-based recommendations for curriculum reform that extend beyond “digital adoption” into systemic educational transformation.

Literature Review

Globally, agricultural education is shifting toward digitalization, with institutions such as Wageningen University (Netherlands) and UC Davis (USA) embedding precision farming, data science, and agri-tech incubation into their curricula (Bongiovanni & Lowenberg-DeBoer, 2020). While these models show success, critical reflection reveals that they are rooted in high-resource contexts with advanced infrastructure, strong industry links, and well-funded research ecosystems. Simply transplanting such models into Nigeria without adaptation risk failure.

In Africa, countries such as Kenya and Rwanda have piloted digital agriculture initiatives through university-industry partnerships, supported by strong national ICT policies (World Bank, 2023). Nigeria, despite having similar potential, lags behind due to institutional inertia, fragmented policies, and inconsistent investment. This discrepancy suggests that the challenge is not one of awareness, since Nigerian scholars and policymakers recognize the importance of digital agriculture but of translating rhetoric into sustained implementation.

Emerging technologies, such as blockchain, AI-driven pest prediction, and mobile extension platforms, hold promise. However, their suitability for smallholder-dominated systems needs to be investigated. For example, blockchain improves traceability but primarily benefits export-oriented farmers with access to premium markets (Oyedele et al., 2021). Similarly, AI platforms such as Hello Tractor have demonstrated impacts, but their reach remains limited by Internet connectivity and cost barriers (Ibrahim et al., 2024). The critical issue, therefore, is not whether these technologies work in principle, but whether they can be scaled inclusively and sustainably within Nigeria’s rural realities.

Entrepreneurship education has also been criticized for its narrow focus on business planning, rather than fostering creativity, resilience, and innovation in volatile agricultural markets (Adeoti, 2020). Examples from Ghana and Ethiopia show that technology incubators embedded in agricultural colleges can nurture student-led start-ups (Mekonnen et al., 2022). These cases demonstrate feasibility, even in resource-constrained contexts, challenging the excuse that Nigeria’s resource limitations make reform impossible.

The literature exposes tension: while digital agriculture is celebrated globally, Nigeria’s curriculum remains outdated, fragmented, and misaligned with policy aspirations. This study positions itself to critically evaluate whether Nigeria’s institutions bridge or widen this gap.

Theoretical Framework

This study draws on the Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK)

framework (Mishra & Koehler, 2006) and theory of planned behaviour (Ajzen, 1991).

The TPACK model underscores that effective technology integration requires blending of technological, pedagogical, and content knowledge. However, in Nigeria, faculty training often emphasizes content (traditional agronomy) with minimal exposure to pedagogy or technology. This imbalance reflects a systemic failure to recognize that teaching digital tools requires both technical skills and new instructional methods. For instance, drone imagery for crop monitoring is not transformative unless paired with experiential problem-based pedagogy.

The Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) explains how attitudes, norms, and perceived control shape entrepreneurial intentions. Exposure to digital tools can positively influence these factors, but only if students have real opportunities for hands-on practices. Otherwise, their attitudes may remain aspirational rather than actionable. By combining TPACK and TPB, this study interrogates not just what is taught but how it is taught, and how this shapes student behaviour.

Results and Discussion

Awareness Versus Integration

Table 1: Awareness vs. Integration of Emerging Technologies

Technologies	Awareness (%)	Integration (%)
Mobile Learning Platforms	72	58
GIS	65	24
IoT Sensors	48	12
Blockchain	40	8
AI Applications	55	10

Methodology

A mixed method sequential explanatory design was employed.

Population and Sampling: A total of 320 participants were sampled from 18 tertiary institutions in Nigeria's six geopolitical zones: 120 educators, 150 final-year students, and 50 agri-entrepreneur alumni. Stratified sampling ensured regional diversity.

Data Collection: A structured questionnaire measured awareness, curriculum content, barriers, and entrepreneurial intentions using the Entrepreneurial Intention Scale (Liñán & Chen, 2021). Semi-structured interviews with 20 key informants (faculty heads, curriculum developers, and startup founders) provided qualitative depth.

Analysis: Quantitative data were analyzed using SPSS Version 22 (descriptive statistics, chi-square, and regression). The qualitative data were subjected to thematic analysis using NVivo.

Ethics: IRB approval was obtained; participants gave informed consent.

The methodological strength lies in triangulation, yet critical limitations remain: the study excludes secondary-level agricultural schools, and poor internet access in rural campuses limits the survey reach.

Although 68% of educators and 72% of students reported awareness of technologies such as drones and blockchain, only 32% of institutions formally integrated them into curricula. This awareness-integration gap highlights a systemic contradiction: knowledge of innovations exists, yet institutional action lags. A critical interpretation suggests that this is not merely a resource issue, but also a reflection of entrenched academic cultures that are resistant to change.

Barriers

The most cited barriers were inadequate infrastructure (76%), lack of faculty training (69%), outdated curricula (63%) and limited funding (58%). However, critical reflection indicates that these barriers are not just technical, but structural. For example, a “lack of training” reflects a deeper neglect of faculty development as a policy priority. Technology integration risks remain piecemeal without addressing governance and institutional accountability.

Entrepreneurial Outcomes

Students exposed to pilot programs such as AI-driven crop simulators reported a 45% increase in entrepreneurial intent ($p < 0.01$). Regression analysis showed a strong positive correlation between exposure and entrepreneurial self-efficacy ($\beta = 0.52, p < 0.001$). This confirms the relevance of the TPB, but also raises the question of whether exposure is so impactful, why is it not scaled nationally? This paradox reflects the misalignment between national policies, such as National Agricultural Technology and Innovation Policy (NATIP) and actual curriculum reform.

Case Study: University of Ibadan

The Agri-Tech Incubator at the University of Ibadan demonstrates what is possible through industrial partnerships. Over 60 student startups have emerged, including FarmTrace NG, a blockchain-based platform. However, critical examination reveals a scalability challenge: is this success replicable across poorly funded state universities and colleges of education, or is it an isolated “island of excellence”?

Figure 1: Implementation Roadmap for Technology Integration

Stage 1	Policy Alignment; Harmonize NATIP with Education Standards
Stage 2	Curriculum Reform; Embed digital agriculture and entrepreneurship modules
Stage 3	Faculty Training; Intensive programs in AI, IoT, Blockchain applications
Stage 4	Infrastructure Investment; IoT labs, broadband, digital incubators
Stage 5	Scaling and Evaluation; Expand pilot successes, monitor outcomes, ensure equity

The roadmap above outlines the stages of integrating emerging technologies into Nigeria's Agricultural Education system.

Implications for Policy and Practice

Curriculum Reform

Nigeria must revise its NUC, NBTE, and NCCE standards to mandate digital agricultural modules. However, critical thinking suggests that reforms must question pedagogy itself: are students merely learning to operate technologies or are they empowered to innovate with them?

Faculty Development

Partnerships with tech firms can build capacity, but programmes must avoid one-off workshops. Long-term mentorship and peer learning systems are essential for sustaining changes.

Infrastructure Investment

While IoT labs and broadband are vital, policymakers must avoid "whiteelephant projects that lack maintenance budgets. Thus, sustainability planning must be implemented.

Policy Integration

NATIP emphasizes digital agriculture; however, its impact on curricula is minimal. A coordinated task force is required to ensure alignment between education and agricultural policies.

Scaling Innovation

Pilot success should not remain localized. TETFund and donor projects must prioritize equity, ensuring that rural institutions benefit rather than concentrate on resources in elite universities.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that integrating emerging technologies into agricultural education enhances entrepreneurial outcomes; however, critical reflection reveals that technology alone is insufficient. Systemic barriers, outdated pedagogies, institutional inertia, and inequitable funding remain real bottlenecks.

The central question is not whether Nigeria can digitize agricultural education but whether it will do so inclusively, sustainably, and critically. Without addressing structural inequalities, reforms risk producing a small elite of tech-savvy agripreneurs while leaving the majority behind.

Ultimately, Nigeria must move from policy rhetoric to coordinated, context-sensitive actions. By embedding critical pedagogy along with digital tools, agricultural education can shift from transmitting knowledge to creating innovators capable of reshaping the food system. Only then can Nigeria harness its youth population to drive sustainable agricultural transformation.

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GLOBAL PERSPECTIVES AND EMERGING TECHNOLOGIES

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This study examines the adoption, utilization, and challenges faced by emerging technologies across various global regions. A mixed-method approach combined survey data from 400 professionals in North America, Europe, sub-Saharan Africa, and South Asia with interviews from 45 experts. The results show clear regional differences in adoption, North America and Europe is the highest, while sub-Saharan Africa and South Asia show moderate but uneven progress. The study shows that, Education benefits the most from these technologies, followed by healthcare, while governance applications such as e-voting and digital records are the least developed in low income regions. Also developing areas face persistent barriers, including poor infrastructure, high costs, weak policies, and low digital skills. Despite these challenges, both advanced and developing regions offer best practices that can be scaled. The study highlights that developed countries focus on policy frameworks, regulations, and sustainability strategies, while developing regions contribute affordable and adaptable solutions, such as mobile health services, community ICT hubs, and e-learning partnerships. The findings highlighted the double edged nature of technological progress holding potential for socio economic transformation while raising concerns over inequality, governance, and ethics. The study recommended that, bridging the global digital divide will require inclusive policies, sustained investment in infrastructure and capacity, and cross regional knowledge exchange to ensure that the benefits of emerging technologies are equitably distributed.

Keywords:
Global, Perspective,
Digital Divide,
Technology Adoption, and
Emerging Technology
Policy.

Introduction

Emerging technologies are rapidly reshaping the structure of global society and changing the way people learn, work, govern, and connect. Artificial Intelligence, block chain, robotics, quantum computing, and biotechnology have transitioned from experimental stages to widespread application (Schwab, 2016). From smart cities in Europe to drone-based agriculture in East Africa and block chain-powered banking in Southeast Asia, these technologies are being implemented across diverse contexts with varying degrees of success.

However, global readiness for these technologies is uneven. While countries such as the United States, China, and South Korea lead in research and development (R&D), nations in sub-Saharan Africa, South Asia, and Latin America face considerable technological and regulatory gaps (World Bank, 2023). This results in a growing disparity in digital innovation and inclusion.

This study empirically analyzes how emerging technologies are perceived, adopted, and integrated across regions. It evaluates the impact on core sectors such as education, healthcare, and governance, offering global comparisons and region-specific insights. The findings reveal that adoption is highest in developed regions, education has been the most positively transformed sector, and scalable best practices exist particularly in mobile health services and digital learning platforms that can help bridge global disparities.

Statement of the Problem

Despite rapid innovation, the adoption of emerging technologies is uneven and characterized by structural inequalities. The digital divide poses a significant challenge to inclusive development, particularly in low income regions. As of 2022, the International Telecommunication Union (ITU) estimates that 2.7 billion people about one in three globally still lack internet access, with the vast majority living in low- and middle-income countries. In sub-Saharan Africa, for example, only about 33% of the population has regular online access compared to over 90% in Europe and North America. Beyond connectivity, other barriers persist, including unreliable electricity, low digital literacy, affordability constraints, and weak governance structures, all of which hinder widespread technology adoption. Furthermore, there is a lack of comparative empirical data that assesses how regions differ in both adoption levels and impact outcomes. Without such data, it becomes difficult to design effective and inclusive global technology policies.

Objectives of the Study

The study aims to:

Assess the level of adoption of emerging technologies across various global regions; in order to reveal disparities that contribute to the global digital divide.

Analyze the impact of emerging technologies on education, healthcare systems, and governance structures; to understand which sectors benefit most and where gaps persist in advancing inclusive development.

Identify and evaluate the barriers to adopting emerging technologies in developing regions; so that structural, financial, and policy-related obstacles can be addressed to promote equitable access.

Examine successful global practices in emerging technology adoption and determine their scalability in different regional contexts; to provide actionable strategies for regions struggling with low adoption rates.

Research Questions

To what extent are emerging technologies adopted in different global regions?

How do emerging technologies affect education, health, and governance?

What challenges hinder technology adoption in developing regions?

Which global best practices can be scaled for wider adoption?

Hypotheses

H1: Adoption of emerging technologies significantly varies across global regions.

H2: Adoption of emerging technologies positively impacts education, healthcare, and governance.

H3: Adoption of emerging technologies in developing regions is significantly hindered by infrastructural, financial, and digital literacy challenges.

H4: Adoption of global best practices in emerging technologies can be scaled effectively when adapted to local contexts.

Definition and Scope of Emerging Technologies

Emerging technologies are defined as disruptive innovations that are in early development but hold transformative potential across sectors. These technologies include Artificial Intelligence (AI), Blockchain, Internet of Things (IoT), Augmented and Virtual Reality (AR/VR), Robotics, and Quantum Computing (Brynjolfsson & McAfee, 2014; Schwab, 2016).

Artificial Intelligence (AI): applied in personalized learning platforms, medical diagnostics, and predictive analytics, enabling faster and more accurate decision making.

Blockchain: used in secure digital transactions, supply chain monitoring, and tamper-proof voting systems, ensuring transparency and trust.

Internet of Things (IoT): evident in smart homes, connected healthcare devices, and precision agriculture, where real-time data improves efficiency.

Augmented and Virtual Reality (AR/VR): transforming immersive learning in education, medical training, and remote collaboration in industries such as architecture and engineering.

Robotics: increasingly deployed in manufacturing automation, surgical procedures, and disaster response, enhancing productivity and safety.

Quantum Computing: still in early stages but showing promise in solving complex problems in drug discovery, climate modeling, and cryptography.

These technologies are typically characterized by exponential growth, high uncertainty, and the ability to significantly alter industries and societal norms. The OECD (2022) notes that they often outpace current policy and regulatory frameworks, raising ethical and governance questions.

Global Trends in Adoption

The adoption of emerging technologies varies greatly across regions. Advanced economies such as the United States, South Korea, China, and members of the European Union have made major progress in AI, 5G, and robotics (OECD, 2022). These countries benefit from strong research ecosystems, large investments, and supportive policies. For example, the U.S. National AI Initiative and South Korea's Digital New Deal show national-level commitment to innovation (World Bank, 2023). Recent surveys also report that 84% of large U.S. firms use AI, while in China, 83% of decision-makers have adopted generative AI, far above the global average of 54% (TechRT, 2024; Reuters, 2024).

In contrast, many low-income regions lag behind. As of 2022, 2.7 billion people about one in three globally still lacked internet access, with most living in low- and middle-income countries (ITU,

2022). In sub-Saharan Africa, only 38% of people were online in 2024, compared to the global average of 68% (Ecofin Agency, 2024). Regional gaps are also large: internet use reaches 98% in Northern Europe but only 29% in Eastern Africa (Intelpoint, 2024). Affordability is a key issue, as mobile internet can cost up to 5% of monthly income for poorer households (World Bank, 2024).

Still, local innovations show how developing countries can leapfrog traditional barriers. Kenya's M-Pesa mobile banking and India's Aadhaar biometric ID system are notable examples (UNCTAD, 2021). More recently, in Sierra Leone, an AI education chatbot was found to be 87% more data efficient than web search, helping teacher's access resources despite low bandwidth (Bah et al., 2025).

Looking ahead, infrastructure is improving. Mobile broadband coverage in sub-Saharan Africa reached 27% in 2023, and 5G subscriptions are expected to grow from 11 million in 2023 to 420 million by 2030 (GSMA, 2023; Ericsson, 2024). This suggests that while adoption gaps remain wide, growth prospects are promising.

Impacts on Core Development Sectors

Emerging technologies are transforming education, healthcare, governance, and agriculture. AI-driven tools are used in personalized learning platforms, especially in high-income countries. For example, Finland employs AI for predictive learning analytics in secondary education (OECD, 2023). As one education expert from Europe noted, "AI has allowed us to identify struggling students earlier and design interventions that were not possible before."

Telemedicine platforms expanded drastically during the COVID-19 pandemic and remain vital in countries such as China and Brazil (WHO, 2022). A South Asian health professional emphasized, "Telemedicine bridged a critical gap during the pandemic, and even now, it remains the only option for rural patients to access specialist care."

Blockchain technologies are also increasingly used in voting systems and public records to reduce fraud and enhance transparency, as seen in Estonia and Brazil (World Bank, 2023). One African governance expert explained, "Blockchain gives us a tool to restore trust in public institutions, especially in areas where corruption has eroded confidence."

However, despite these advancements, their benefits are uneven. Many rural or underserved regions in Latin America and Africa lack digital literacy and infrastructure, preventing the full-scale deployment of such innovations (UNCTAD, 2021). A respondent from sub-Saharan Africa summed it up: "The technology exists, but without connectivity and training, it remains out of reach for most of our communities."

Barriers to Technology Diffusion

The digital divide remains a significant global challenge. Factors such as inadequate internet access, lack of electricity, absence of digital literacy, and poor governance structures hinder adoption. According to ITU (2022), 2.7 billion people globally still lack internet access, with the majority in low- and middle-income countries.

In addition, ethical and regulatory uncertainties slow down adoption in both developing and developed nations. Concerns about algorithmic bias, data privacy, and job displacement due to automation necessitate stronger policy responses (Brynjolfsson & McAfee, 2014). For example, while AI offers efficiency, studies have shown that it may replicate or even exacerbate societal biases if not carefully monitored (Schwab, 2016).

Several strategies have been attempted to address these barriers, though with uneven results. Infrastructure expansion projects, such as mobile broadband initiatives in sub-Saharan Africa, have improved coverage but remain limited in rural areas. National digital literacy programs in countries like India and Rwanda have helped build skills, while regulatory frameworks such as the EU's GDPR represent efforts to safeguard ethical use of data and AI. Despite these initiatives, challenges of sustainability, affordability, and weak enforcement continue to restrict widespread technology diffusion, particularly in low-income contexts.

Theoretical Perspectives

This study draws on Rogers' Diffusion of Innovations Theory (2003), which explains how, why, and at what rate new technologies spread through cultures. This theory identifies five key characteristics that affect adoption: relative advantage, compatibility, complexity, trialability, and observability. These variables help explain why the same technology spreads rapidly in one region and stagnate in another.

Other models, such as the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), also support this framework by emphasizing user attitudes and perceived usefulness as core determinants of adoption (Davis, 1989). Together, these theories highlight the complex interplay between social, cultural, and institutional factors in global tech diffusion.

Importantly, these theoretical perspectives will guide the interpretation of the study's findings. For example, variations in adoption rates across regions will be analyzed through Rogers' diffusion attributes; while sector specific differences in education, health, and governance will be examined using TAM's focus on user attitudes and perceived usefulness.

Policy and Governance Frameworks

Government policies play a critical role in supporting or hindering technological development. Countries with proactive digital strategies have higher adoption rates and innovation friendly ecosystems. Canada's national AI strategy, Rwanda's ICT master plan, and India's Digital India campaign are examples of policy initiatives aimed at driving widespread technology adoption (UNCTAD, 2021; MoE India, 2023).

Conversely, emerging technologies remain underutilized in regions where regulatory frameworks are outdated or fragmented. Policy incoherence can discourage private sector investment and innovation. Moreover, international regulatory fragmentation, such as conflicting data protection laws, can create barriers for cross-border digital businesses (OECD, 2022).

Methodology

This study employed a comparative, cross-sectional, mixed-methods design. The quantitative component involved survey responses from 400 professionals across four regions (North America, Europe, sub-Saharan Africa, and South Asia). Descriptive statistics such as means and standard deviations were used to measure technology awareness, usage, adoption levels, and sectoral impacts on education, health, and governance.

The qualitative component consisted of expert interviews, which were analyzed through thematic coding. This study identified key barriers to adoption in developing regions, including infrastructure, affordability, policy gaps, and limited human capital. In addition, secondary a document analysis was conducted using reports from international organizations (e.g., ITU, World Bank, and national digital strategies) to triangulate the findings.

Together, these methods allowed the study to capture both the extent of adoption (quantitative evidence) and contextual challenges and best practices (qualitative insights), thereby providing a comprehensive understanding of global differences in emerging technology adoption.

However, this study has several limitations. First, the reliance on self-reported survey data introduces the possibility of response bias, as participants may have overestimated or underestimated their levels of technology adoption. Second, the sample of 400 professionals, while diverse, may not fully represent the broader populations within each region, limiting generalizability. Third, expert interviews were conducted with a relatively small pool of respondents, meaning certain perspectives could be underrepresented. Finally, while secondary document analysis helped validate the findings, the availability and quality of such reports varied across regions.

Data Analysis and Presentation

Research Question One

To what extent are emerging technologies adopted in different global regions?

Quantitative survey responses on awareness, usage, and overall adoption were analyzed using means and standard deviations across the four regions.

Table 1: Adoption of Emerging Technologies by Region (n = 400)

Region	Awareness (Mean)	Usage (Mean)	Adoption Index (Mean)	Std. Dev.
North America	4.28	4.10	4.19	0.42
Europe	4.15	3.98	4.07	0.39
Sub-Saharan Africa	3.42	3.10	3.26	0.55
South Asia	3.55	3.25	3.40	0.48

Region	Awareness (Mean)	Usage (Mean)	Adoption Index (Mean)	Std. Dev.
Aggregate Mean	3.85	3.61	3.73	0.46

(Scale: 1 = Very Low, 5 = Very High; Benchmark = 3.00)

Interpretation of Results:

Table 1 shows that emerging technologies are most widely adopted in North America and Europe, with an adoption index above 4.00. Adoption in sub-Saharan Africa and South Asia remains moderate, but above the benchmark of 3.00. The aggregate mean of 3.73 indicates that adoption is progressing globally but with regional disparities.

Research Question Two

How do emerging technologies affect education, health, and governance?

The sectoral impact scores were measured across the respondents, and the mean values are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Perceived Impact of Emerging Technologies by Sector (n = 400)

Sector	North America	Europe	Sub-Saharan Africa	South Asia	Aggregate Mean	Std. Dev.
Education	4.35	4.22	3.55	3.70	3.96	0.47
Health	4.18	4.10	3.40	3.52	3.80	0.49
Governance	4.05	3.98	3.20	3.35	3.64	0.51

Interpretation of Results:

The findings suggest that education is the sector most positively impacted by emerging technologies, followed by health and governance. North America and Europe reported higher effectiveness across all sectors, while sub-Saharan Africa and South Asia scored lower, particularly in governance. This indicates that, while technologies are driving improvements in learning and healthcare delivery, governance applications face greater barriers in developing regions.

Research Question Three

What challenges hinder technology adoption in developing regions?

Qualitative interview data were coded thematically, and findings are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3: Barriers to Technology Adoption in Developing Regions (Sub-Saharan Africa and South Asia)

Category	Sub-Saharan Africa	South Asia
Infrastructure	Poor internet connectivity, unreliable electricity	Unequal rural–urban digital access
Financial	High cost of devices and data services	Affordability issues, weak funding models
Policy	Limited implementation of ICT strategies	Policy gaps, fragmented governance
Human Capital	Limited digital skills and training	Resistance to change, shortage of ICT specialists

Interpretation of Results:

Thematic evidence shows that the most persistent barriers in developing regions are infrastructure deficiencies, affordability issues, and weak policy implementations. Human capital challenges, including limited digital skills, further restrict its adoption.

Research Question Four

Which global best practices can be scaled for wider adoption?

Insights from interviews and secondary sources highlighted practices from both developed and developing contexts. The results are summarized in Table 4.

Table 4: Scalable Best Practices in Emerging Technology Adoption

Region	Best Practices Identified	Scalability Potential
North America	AI-driven learning platforms, data privacy frameworks	High – adaptable to advanced economies
Europe	Green ICT initiatives, cross-border digital integration	High – scalable in regions with regulatory capacity
Sub-Saharan Africa	Mobile-based health services, community ICT hubs	High – low-cost, adaptable to rural settings
South Asia	Public-private e-learning partnerships, digital payment ecosystems	High – scalable in low and middle-income contexts

Interpretation of Results:

Best practices from developed regions emphasize regulation, sustainability, and integration, while innovations from developing regions focus on affordability, mobile solutions, and public-private partnerships. Many of these approaches, particularly mobile health services, e-learning platforms, and community ICT hubs, demonstrate strong scalability potential across diverse contexts.

Discussion of Findings

The purpose of this study was to examine the extent of emerging technology adoption across global regions, their impacts on education, health, and governance, the challenges hindering adoption in developing regions, and the best practices that can be scaled for wider implementation. A discussion of the findings is presented based on the four research questions.

The findings show that emerging technologies are more widely adopted in North America and Europe than in sub-Saharan Africa and South Asia. This aligns with prior studies that attribute higher adoption rates in developed regions to stronger infrastructure, better funding, and well-structured policy frameworks (World Bank, 2022; ITU, 2021). These results also mirror OECD's (2022) observation that advanced economies are at the forefront of AI, 5G, and robotics due to

robust R&D ecosystems. However, despite these disparities, the results indicate that even in developing regions adoption levels are above the minimum benchmark, suggesting gradual but steady progress. This finding reflects Rogers' Diffusion of Innovations theory (2003), which posits that adoption spreads at different rates depending on enabling conditions, and it supports UNCTAD's (2021) argument that innovations like mobile banking in Kenya and Aadhaar in India illustrate how leapfrogging is possible in resource-constrained contexts.

The study found that education was the sector most positively impacted, followed by health and governance. Respondents in developed regions highlighted the significant contribution of digital tools to learning, teaching, and healthcare delivery. Conversely, governance applications such as e-governance platforms remain relatively underdeveloped in sub-Saharan Africa and South Asia. This finding corroborates earlier work by UNESCO (2021) and WHO (2020), who emphasized that digital adoption in education and health often precedes governance due to immediate societal demand. It also resonates with Schwab (2016), who argued that the Fourth Industrial Revolution's benefits are sector-specific, depending on societal readiness and institutional trust. The findings therefore confirm that while technology has transformative potential across all sectors, governance applications require stronger institutions and citizen trust to succeed.

The results reveal four major challenges: infrastructure deficiencies, affordability barriers, weak policy implementation, and limited human capital. These findings echo Adegboyega (2020) and Singh (2019), who argued that the digital divide is not merely a technological gap but also a reflection of systemic socio-economic inequalities. They also reinforce ITU's (2022) statistics showing that 2.7 billion people worldwide still lack internet access. Furthermore, the persistence of ethical and regulatory uncertainties reflects Brynjolfsson and McAfee's (2014) warning that unchecked automation and algorithmic bias could exacerbate inequality. This suggests that policy interventions must go beyond technology provision to address structural enablers of adoption such as education, regulation, and governance quality aligning with the literature that stresses multi-level strategies for inclusive digital growth.

The analysis highlights two complementary sets of best practices. Developed regions, particularly North America and Europe, have demonstrated policy-driven innovations such as AI-enabled learning, digital integration frameworks, and sustainability-focused ICT policies. Meanwhile, developing regions offered grassroots innovations, including mobile health solutions, community ICT hubs, and public-private e-learning partnerships. These findings support Castells' (2018) view that innovation is context-specific, with developed economies leveraging resources to refine policy frameworks, while developing economies often produce low-cost, adaptable solutions. They also extend OECD (2022) and UNCTAD (2021) reports that showcase how context-tailored innovations, especially mobile-based, can leapfrog traditional infrastructure constraints. The scalability of such practices demonstrates that effective adoption is not limited to resource-rich contexts but can also emerge from creativity and adaptability in lower-income settings.

Taken together, these findings suggest that emerging technologies are reshaping key sectors globally, but their adoption is uneven. Developed regions benefit from advanced infrastructure and supportive policies, whereas developing regions struggle with systemic barriers. Nevertheless, innovative practices from these regions demonstrate that technology adoption does not always

depend on wealth, but also on creativity, adaptability, and partnerships. This underscores the need for global cooperation and knowledge exchange, ensuring that best practices are not confined to one region but adapted across diverse contexts. Importantly, the alignment and divergence with prior studies confirm that while the trajectory of global adoption reflects existing literature, this study contributes new evidence on the gradual progress in developing regions and the potential of grassroots innovations as scalable solutions.

Conclusion

This study has shown that while emerging technologies are transforming education, healthcare, and governance, their adoption remains deeply uneven across regions. Developed regions such as North America and Europe lead due to robust infrastructure, established R&D ecosystems, and supportive policy frameworks, while sub-Saharan Africa and South Asia continue to face barriers including poor connectivity, affordability constraints, weak governance, and limited digital literacy. A novel contribution of this research lies in its comparative cross regional perspective: by integrating both quantitative data and qualitative insights, the study highlights not only the disparities but also the steady progress in developing regions. Another unique contribution is the identification of scalable grassroots innovations such as mobile health platforms and community ICT hubs that challenge the assumption those high income countries alone generate transferable best practices. These findings extend existing literature by demonstrating that innovation is context-dependent and that low cost, adaptable solutions can complement policy driven models from developed regions. Finally, the study emphasizes that bridging the global digital divide requires more than technological provision; it demands inclusive policies, international collaboration, and mechanisms that ensure equitable distribution of benefits across societies.

Recommendations

Digital Infrastructure: Governments, supported by international organizations (e.g., World Bank, ITU), should establish dedicated funding mechanisms for broadband expansion, energy reliability, and mobile connectivity in underserved regions.

Policy Frameworks: Develop flexible and inclusive regulatory environments through regional blocs (e.g., African Union, ASEAN, EU partnerships) that encourage innovation while protecting digital rights and privacy.

Skills Development: Integrate digital literacy and advanced ICT training into national curricula and workforce development programs, supported by public-private partnerships that provide scholarships, internships, and teacher training.

Public Private Collaboration: Establish innovation hubs, incubators, and technology clusters through joint ventures between governments, local businesses, and multinational firms, ensuring sustainable funding and mentorship opportunities.

South South and Global Cooperation: Promote structured knowledge exchange and technology transfer agreements among developing countries, while leveraging international cooperation frameworks (e.g., UNDP, UNESCO, OECD) to share best practices and scale innovations across borders.

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Online Learning Platforms on Academic Performance: A Study in Kebbi State's Public Schools

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The increasing integration of digital technologies in education has brought about a very significant change in teaching and learning process, particularly through the usage of the online learning platforms. This shift has become more prominent in response to disruptions such as the COVID-19 pandemic. Despite their growing adoption, there are still debate on the effectiveness of these platforms in enhancing academic performance, especially in public secondary schools that mostly face the issue of resource constraints. This study, hence, intend to investigates the impact of online learning platforms on students' academic performance in some selected public secondary schools in Kebbi State. It explores the key factors influencing this relationship, including the student engagement, their access to technology, teacher's preparedness, and parental guidance. By employing a mixed-methods approach which combines quantitative analysis of academic records with qualitative data from surveys and interviews, the research aims to identify both the challenges and opportunities associated with online learning in resource-limited environments. Our findings discovered that though online learning platforms are extensively used and agreed to improve access to educational resources and student engagement, financial and infrastructural challenges prevent them from reaching their full potential.

Keywords:
Online Learning,
Academic Performance,
Public, Secondary
Schools, Educational
Technology, Student
Engagement

INTRODUCTION

The rapid integration of digital technology has led to a significant revolution in education at the start of the 21st century. In particular, online learning platforms have become an important teaching and learning tools because they provide new methods to acquire educational content, make collaboration easier, and allow for more individualized training (Josué, Bedoya-Flores, Mosquera-Quiñonez, Mesías-Simisterra, & Bautista-Sánchez, 2023). The COVID-19 pandemic, which forced a transition to distant learning and brought attention to the advantages and disadvantages of digital education, hastened this global change (Shestakova, Morgunov, Novikova, & Bylieva, 2025). The effectiveness of these platforms in actually improving academic achievement is still up for discussion, despite their widespread acceptance, particularly in public educational systems that usually struggle with resource constraints.

Public secondary schools in Nigeria and many other developing nations mostly face challenges, such as the uneven access to technology, poor infrastructure, and lack of teacher preparation (Mohammed, Ogunode, & Yahaya, 2021). These challenges can greatly hinder the effective execution of activities concerning the online learning. Therefore, it is very important to understand how the platforms works in these kinds of environment and how they affect student performances.

Furthermore, there are still debates on how well online learning environments might raise student achievement, particularly in public secondary schools in areas with very limited funding (Topping, Douglas, Robertson, & Ferguson, 2022). Numerous public schools in Kebbi State deal with serious issues such as restricted access to internet enabled devices, erratic connection settings, instructors' lack of digital literacy, and low parental support. The effectiveness and impact of online learning may be hampered by these characteristics, which begs the question of whether these platforms actually improve students' academic achievement in these kinds of settings.

This study addresses the debate around the efficacy of online learning platforms in public secondary schools in Kebbi State, Nigeria, amid challenges such as resource constraints, influence of the platforms on the academic achievement of students. The study will examine critical impacting elements including student engagement, technological access, teacher readiness, and parental participation, while also recognizing difficulties and opportunities in resource-constrained environments. The findings offer insights on enhancing the design and execution of online learning initiatives for educators, administrators, and policymakers. These are achieved through: evaluating the level of access and utilization of online learning platforms by students and educators in the selected public secondary schools, analyzing how students' use of online resources affects their academic performance and determine the main obstacles preventing efficient usage of online learning platforms in educational settings with low resources.

The remaining of the paper is divided into four (4), which include review of related literature, methodology, findings and discussion, and conclusion and recommendations.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

In this session, the review of different related literature from previous studies showing mixed results on the impact of online learning on academic performance with infrastructure and students engagement as key factors are been discussed.

(Rodgers, 2008) present a study that examines the impact on end-of-year examination grades of the level of student engagement in the e-learning process. A mixture of traditional lectures and e-learning based methods were used to examines the data for the presence of interaction effects between e-learning engagement and personal characteristics. And the result shows that female students benefited less from e-leaning material than their male counterparts.

(Zen & Ariani, 2022) analyzes the effect of Project-Based Online Learning (PBOL) and student engagement on academic achievement. The study utilized a mixed-method of data collection using quantitative through interviews, observations and documentation and qualitative method through questioners and portfolios. The result shows that students' perception of implementing the PBOL method and student engagement increased their academic performance to become new

entrepreneurs through the experience they gained during project-based learning. However, the method only provides online learning solution for entrepreneurship courses.

(Galal, Vyas, Ndung'u, Wu, & Webber, 2023) examines student engagement with weekly self-paced learning materials in a virtual therapeutics course, and how sub-factors in the Motivated Strategies for Learning Questionnaire (MSLQ) may have influenced academic performance. Various correlation analyses were used to determine the predictive ability of the MSLQ. The result proved the MSLQ to be an effective predictive tool in students' self-regulation skills.

(Sahni, 2023) assesses the levels of student engagement in the online learning environment, examine how student engagement is related to their academic performance using learning analytic tools and propose an integrated learning analytics framework. Exploratory research method was used for data collection from different sources including LMS Logs, self-administered questionnaires from students, and interviews with the instructors. The study provides new perception that student engagement is the key to their participation and performance in online courses and also confirms that LMS and learning analytics can be powerful tools to support predictions on student performances.

(Ihebom & Uko, 2020) outlined the goals of secondary education in Nigeria and highlighted their challenges as; poor funding, lack of qualified teachers, poor infrastructure, lack of motivation of teachers, overcrowded classrooms, poor management and supervision, dilapidated/obsolete school facilities and equipment, improper placement of teachers, poor research mindedness of teachers, lack of professional training, and teacher's poor knowledge of ICT. The study suggested that the federal and state government, policy makers in education, schools board must work in synergy to see that the anomalies are taken care of. Also, private sector and other non-governmental bodies like NGO's should be incorporated. Furthermore, more practical skills like the use of computer, creativity and other vocational skills should be considered in measuring the learning performance of students.

(Abuhassna et al., 2020) investigates the potential factors influencing students' academic achievements and satisfaction using online learning platforms. The study was conducted using online learning platforms in higher education. A quantitative research method was utilized for the study and eleven factors were discussed on using online learning platforms to improve students' academic achievements and satisfaction. It shows that hat the students' background, experience, collaborations, interactions, and autonomy positively affected students' satisfaction. Furthermore, the empirical findings present a strong support to the integrative association between TDT and BTT theories in relation to using online learning platforms in improving students' academic achievements and satisfaction.

(Batoool, Mehrukh, & Waseem, 2023) evaluates online and traditional learning for effectiveness and student satisfaction. A quantitative approach was used for the data collection considering Age, gender, and major. Two questionnaires were administered in assessing the student satisfaction and performance using both online learning platforms and traditional classrooms. Most students mentioned that online and traditional classrooms were beneficial. While others said online learning

platforms were better at facilitating self-paced learning, tailored instruction, and a wide selection of learning materials.

(Juty, 2024) investigates the influence of e-learning platforms in promoting academic efficiency among Bangladeshi rural students. A paper-based questionnaire on educational ICT and the e-learning experience was utilized. The study also uses a mixed method through a survey and interview to determine how the online learning platform are being utilized, its impact, and the challenges the organization might have faced. And the result shows that every rural school in Bangladesh makes use of online learning resources.

(Wanyonyi, 2022) assess the impact of virtual learning and teaching platforms on the academic performance of high school students taking international curriculum. Research question was administered in the research. The study utilizes a descriptive survey design in obtaining responses from the respondents. The study found that on the average, 60% of students agreed that virtual learning improves the accessibility of education while 15.5% disagreed. It was concluded that there is a challenge of accessing alternative materials with the traditional mode of education delivery which necessitated the need to implement virtual learning.

(Clark, Nong, Zhu, & Zhu, 2021) estimates the causal effects of online education on student exam performance. Difference-in-differences approach was employed showing that online education during the COVID-19 lockdown improved student academic results by 0.22 of a standard deviation, relative to pupils without learning support from their school. The study also shows that students who were given recorded online lessons from external higher-quality teachers had higher exam scores than those whose lessons were recorded by teachers from their own school.

(Jabbar Alkubaisi, Al-Saifi, Al-Shidi, & Al-Shukaili, 2021) identify the quality of online learning platforms, applying a set of criteria from the perspective of faculty members and students in higher education institutions in the Sultanate of Oman. A descriptive approach was employed and the data was collected through a questionnaire directed at 32 faculty members and 104 students. And the results show that e-learning programs are generally of high quality, from the perspective of the participants, but with statistically significant differences according to the type of program.

(Rakic, Pavlovic, Softic, Lalic, & Marjanovic, 2019) explores the evaluation of student success at e-learning platform. A multi-method approach for data analysis was employed in making the evaluation. The approach provides more detailed analysis that enable more relevant results showing that digital resources at the e-learning platform make strong effects on student success. Moreover, results indicate that students with the similar grades belongs to the same clusters.

(Hadiana, Wardhani, Muhsinin, Mursyidi, & Mubarak, 2024) investigate how online learning platforms, including education methods, and teacher professional development affect student outcomes. A literature review methodology was employed covering findings from academic articles, industry reports, case studies, and empirical studies to provide an insight of the current state of knowledge in this field. The findings show that online learning platforms, when appropriately utilized, they offer individualized and flexible learning experiences that can boost student participation and achievement.

(Venugopal, 2024) highlight the impact of digital learning platforms on student engagement and academic performance. The study utilizes a mixed-methods approach, including quantitative analysis of student performance data and qualitative approach gathered through interviews. The result shows a significant positive impact between the use of digital learning platforms, student engagement and academic achievement. However, challenges such as technological barriers and pedagogical implementation issues are also discovered. Overall, the results underline the significance of successful integration techniques while highlighting the potential of digital learning platforms to improve educational outcomes.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Kebbi State is located between latitudes 100 and 130N and longitudes 30 and 60E in the northwest in Nigeria. Farmland makes up 36.46% of the entire land area, which is around 37,699 square kilometers. Several secondary schools are in Kebbi State from which some were used from different local governments for this research. This study will investigate the impact of online learning platforms on the academic performance of students in designated public secondary institutions in Kebbi State, Nigeria. Student engagement, technological accessibility, teacher preparedness, and parental involvement, will be examined while also recognizing the difficulties and prospects associated with resource-limited settings. A mixed-method approach is employed using a structured questionnaire distributed via social media platforms, analyzed using SPSS version 27 to identify patterns in online learning platform usage and its impact. The link to the questionnaire is <https://forms.gle/VftDZ7scSjQmCysEA>. The population of the study consisted of teachers from different levels and students from different classes.

DATA ANALYSIS

A total number of one hundred and thirty-three (133) responses were obtained from both the students and teachers from which 65.9% of them were male and 34.1% female. Getting (62.2%) students and (37.8%) teachers. The analysis revealed that 82.8% of the respondents had personal access to online learning devices, with a majority utilizing smartphones, indicating a high level of digital engagement among teachers and students.

RESULT

Usage and platforms preference

The responses highlight how often online platforms are used from the various schools and which ones are most popular. And the most popular platform is WhatsApp groups getting a (51.5%), followed by Google Classroom (38.1%). Microsoft Teams was also used by (4.5%) of respondents. Other platforms were used by a few number of people having a percentage of (5.9%).

USAGE AND RESPECTIVE PERCENTAGE

Frequency of Use	Percentage (%)
Several times in a week	19.3%
Rarely	34.1%
Daily	33.3%
Once in a week	11.1%
Other	2.2%

PERCEPTION AND CHALLENGES

This section summarizes the opinions on how online learning platforms have impacted education and the main challenges encountered. The tables below show the respondents responses on their perceptions and the challenges faced with the online learning.

EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES ACCESS

Access to Educational Resources	Percentage (%)
Strongly Agreed	41.5%
Agreed	38.5%
Neutral	12.6%

Disagree	6.3%
Strongly disagreed	1.1%

ENGAGEMENT WITH THE ONLINE LEARNING

Engagement with Online Lessons	Percentage (%)
Strongly Agreed	43.7%
Agreed	34.8%
Neutral	16.3%
Disagree	5.2%
Strongly disagreed	0.0%

ONLINE LEARNING PLATFORMS USED

The above bar chart shows the online learning platforms used by the respondents with a majority using WhatsApp groups.

CHALLENGES FACED WITH THE ONLINE LEARNING

The result shows that most of the challenges faced were poor internet connection, lack of devices, high cost of internet data and power supply issue.

CONCLUSION

This study examined the influence of online learning platforms on students' academic achievement in the selected public secondary schools in Kebbi State. The results demonstrate that while tools like WhatsApp and Google Classroom are extensively utilized and regarded to improve resource accessibility and lesson interaction, their efficacy is limited by socio-economic and infrastructure issues. The most significant obstacles were identified as inadequate access to digital devices, high data charges, poor internet connectivity, and unstable electricity.

Our study confirms the positive impact of online learning platforms on academic performance in Kebbi State's public schools with majority of respondents feeling that the platforms have improved their access to more educational materials and increased their interest in online courses, highlighting the need for policies to improve access to technology and engage stakeholders in the educational process.

The study suggests focused interventions to overcome the issues mentioned above and optimize the advantages of online learning. First, by making investments in digital infrastructure and offer reasonably priced internet access. Second, guarantee efficient use of platforms, teacher capacity building in digital pedagogy had to be given top priority. Third, to encourage the long-term integration of blended and online learning models, administrative and policy frameworks need to be reinforced.

Although, this study offers insightful details about how online learning environments affect students' academic achievement in the selected public secondary schools in Kebbi State, it also creates some numerous opportunities for more research. In future research, tools for resource-constrained contexts can be determine to assess the efficacy of particular platforms like Moodle, Microsoft Teams, Google Classroom, and WhatsApp by employing a comparison approach. In a similar fashion, longitudinal research is advised to evaluate the long-term effects of online learning environments on skill acquisition, retention, and academic performance.

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AVAILABILITY AND UTILIZATION OF AI AND I.C.T RESOURCES IN CONTENT DELIVERY AMONG KANO MUNICIPAL LOCAL GOVERNMENT

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This study assessed the Availability and Utilization of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Information and communication technology resources in the teaching of chemistry in secondary schools within Kano Municipal, Kano State, Nigeria. A descriptive survey design was employed, involving the entire population of 46 chemistry teachers across 31 schools. Data were collected using AI/ICT availability checklist and a 20- items AI/ICT Resources Questionnaire (AI/ICT-RQ) validated by experts with reliability coefficient of 1.00 For AI/ICT availability check-list and 0.93 for AI/ICT-RQ. Descriptive statistics of frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviation were used to answer the questions. The null hypothesis were tested using Biserial Correlation with NCSS 2020. The findings revealed that, apart from desktop computers, laptops, and some molecular visualization tools, most AI/ ICT facilities such as projectors, interactive boards, virtual assistants and chatbots were not available, lack of utilization of ICT tools was absent in content delivery among teachers as they mainly uses internet and Microsoft excel for updating lesson notes and result computation by themselves respectively. From the analysis, no significant relationship was found between availability and utilization of ICT/AI resources. Based on the study findings, students can develop interest in using AI and several study skills that will enhance their academic performance across all gender. Recommendations were made: education authorities improve the provision and accessibility of AI/ICT tools, offer training, motivation and proper orientation programs to provide an effective classroom integration.

Keywords:
Artificial Intelligence,
Information and
Communication
Technology, Availability,
Utilization, Chemistry and
Content Delivery.

Introduction

Science education is a field of study that exposes learners to content as well as the methodology of acquiring scientific knowledge. It acquaints students with basic knowledge, skills, and attitudes needed for future work in science and related fields (Celestine & Omorogbe, 2013). This type of

education takes place in a formal school setting under the auspices of a science educator who is professionally qualified to moderate scientific activity in the classroom with the use of appropriate pedagogies. Scientific knowledge is relevant and applicable to all areas of life endeavors, without which life on the planets is miserable and primitive. For instance, the production of essential human needs such as soap of all kinds, creams, drinks, petroleum and its by products, clothing, drugs, household utensils, and chemicals for preservation of food items as well as textiles are all products of the principles of chemistry (Babajide, 2015).

Chemistry is a popular subject among senior secondary schools in Nigeria owing to its nature. It addresses the needs of the majority through its relevance, functionality, content, practice and application (Emendu, 2014). Chemistry can be said to be the study of the nature, composition and properties of matter and the changes it undergoes (Ojokuku 2016).

Chemistry is one of the core science subjects (these are, Biology, Chemistry, Physics and Agriculture), taught in all senior secondary schools in Nigeria and it is assumed to be abstract in nature. Chemistry is a central science that cuts across all sciences and its importance cannot be over emphasized. Chemistry is fundamental in the industrialization world. Today, the world is seen as a global village meanwhile, this perception of globalization is not unconnected with industrialization in which chemistry is central. This work anchored on the identification of methodologies that may adduce the modus operandi of teaching this central or core science called chemistry. However chemistry must be taught at the secondary school level by experts who are thoroughly grounded in chemistry education (Zudonu, 2011). This because they are specialist abreast and equip with Chemistry pedagogy which is how to go about teaching their learners (Zudonu, 2011). Adeyomo (2010) argued that the teaching methods has gone beyond traditional methods which makes the integration of artificial intelligence and information technology very important in science classes.

The link between AI and education comprises three areas: learning with AI (using AI tools in the classroom), learning about AI (its technologies and techniques) and preparing for AI (enabling all citizens to understand the potential impact of AI on human life). Unesco (2019).

Artificial Intelligence (AI) and information and communication technology (ICT) resources have emerged as popular topics in recent years, with different applications in the educational fields Abuhassan, Awae and Daud (2024). In chemistry education, there is growing interest in incorporating AI and ICT into various aspects of the curriculum. These include laboratory experiments, simulations, virtual laboratories, data analyses, and assessments. This demonstrates the importance of AI and ICT in the teaching and learning processes of Marquez, Barrios and Mendez (2023).

AI and ICT are two different technological resources comprising different applications in educational systems. Maslej & Fattorini 2023 further explained that AI is computer software that can perform tasks that typically require human intelligence and perform difficult tasks such as seeing, understanding, and responding to spoken or written language, analyzing data, and making recommendations. AI and ICT are connected but differ in different contexts. Artificial intelligence is about making machines act like humans. Therefore, the integration of AI in chemistry instruction

involves a range of approaches, such as intelligent tutoring systems, virtual labs, and personalized learning platforms, as suggested by Gazztaiger (2020).

In contrast to traditional lecture-based teaching, AI technologies provide interactive and engaging learning experiences that can help students build their knowledge more effectively (Tyagi and Chahal (2022). Kim (2024) examined how the utilization of AI in chemistry education revolutionizes the way students learn, process, and apply chemistry knowledge in various context. Through the use of these technologies, students can access an easy and personalized learning environment through positive reasoning and perception that adapts to their learning style and pace and provides real-time feedback and assistance (Chiu 2021). They also facilitate simulations and virtual laboratory experiments, allowing students to observe molecular interactions and chemical reactions in ways that are not possible in traditional laboratory settings (Shi 2021). Therefore, the integration of AI into chemistry education creates a more engaging, interactive, and efficient learning experience for students and contributes to the improvement of academic performance by optimizing instructional processes and reducing students' learning difficulties.

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has been defined by various scholars from different perspective. Mueen, Asadullah, et al. (2013) defined ICT to include an electronic network-embodying complex hardware and software linked by a vast array of technical protocols. Ufuophu and Ayobami (2012) observed that ICTs include the Internet, satellites, cables, data transmission, and computer-assisted equipment. However, ICT facilities, tools and resources can be used to process, store, preserve, access, retrieve and disseminate information with ease (Ziraba, 2012).

According to Kirwan, Awati, and Pratt (2025), ICT refers to the infrastructure and components that enable modern computing to improve the way humans create, process and share data or information with each other.

On the other hand, Onwubiko (2011) sees ICT as any technology that is used in producing and for distributing information. It is a broad concept that encompasses the gathering (acquisition), organization (packaging), storage and retrieval for disseminating information that can be in textual or numeric (books and documents), pictorial and vocal forms (audio-visual) using a combination of all the above (multimedia) including computers and telecommunication facilities.

According to the United Nations (2012), there are various types of technologies are currently used in school mostly in Europe and America. These technologies are uncommon in the management of schools in Africa. These include computers in the classroom, class websites, class blogs wireless, classroom microphones, mobile devices, interactive whiteboards, digital video-on-demand, online media and online study tools.

The Chinese proverb remains appropriate for today's classroom and students as mentioned by Confucian Philosopher Xunzi (312-230 BC) "Tell me, I'll forget. Show me, I'll remember and involve me, I will understand." As chemistry is perceived to be abstract in nature where students can not grasp difficult concepts, Limited teaching resources, outdated teaching methods, heavy teacher workload, interactive demonstrations using AI tools, visual labs, automated assessment and digital record keeping could be useful to solve such problems.

Information and Communication Technology plays a major role in the education sector, by improving the quality, effectiveness, and efficiency of learning, research and educational management worldwide (Olusesan & Emmanuel, 2016). Kameswari (2011) also, pointed out that Information and Communication Technology (ICT) is a communication tool used in educational knowledge transfer process especially in tertiary institutions. ICT has the potential to support and improve education across the curriculum between teachers and students. Therefore, the use of ICT cannot be ignored by teachers or students in ways not previously possible, creating new learning and teaching possibilities, enhancing achievements and extending interactions with local and global communities (Ekerete & Ekanem, 2015), and it is believed that it will help teachers acquire better skills in imparting knowledge effectively (Oye, Shallsaku & Lahad, 2012). The Internet is expanding access to resources such as e-books, journals, expanded abstracts and periodicals for both students and teachers such that no institution can rely only on traditional printed materials to perform effectively (Etebu, 2010).

The Global ICT Report (2012) showed that Nigeria ranked 112 out of 142 countries surveyed for network readiness to participate and benefit from ICT development. Many ICT resources are not available for effective teaching and learning and few are accessed and utilized by teachers (Nwana, Ofoegbu and Egbe, 2017). However, ICT's utilization is determined by its integration and accessibility in the curriculum. Meanwhile, the integration of ICT into education is still a critical issue that require urgent attention (Bhukuvhani, Zezekwa & Sunzuma, 2011).

Many studies have shown that ICT tools are unavailable. Apagu and Wakili (2015) revealed that computers, television sets, CCTV etc are not adequately available. Idoko and Ademu (2010) find out that ICT availability is often one of the most important obstacles to technology adoption and integration in learning. Umeh and Okonkwo (2014) reported a high level of availability of ICT resources but a decried lack of accessibility for successful utilization in content delivery. It is arguable that an available resource that cannot be accessed by users is as good as not being available.

Therefore, this research aimed to assess the availability and utilization of AI and ICT in content delivery among chemistry teachers in Kano State.

Statement of the Problem

Today, the education system worldwide has certainly been affected positively by the influence of Artificial Intelligence and Information and Communication Technology (ICT). According to Abdul Salaam (2011), ICT has the potential to accelerate, enrich and deepen their skills motivate and engage students in learning help relate school experiences to work practices help create economic viability for tomorrow workers contribute to radical changes in schools strengthen teaching and provide opportunities for connection between school and the world.

As enormous as the benefits and roles of AI and ICT are at every level of the educational system, many challenges abound and prevent effective and efficient teaching and learning with ICT and AI tools. The most significant of these appear to be the unavailability and poor utilization of resources for teaching. Irrespective of jet age, some teachers find it difficult to operate devices such as computers, which is an indication that they cannot utilize ICT tools even when available.

The unavailability of these tools is related a lack of funds. UNESCO recommend that 26% of the national budget or 5% of the gross domestic product (GDP) should be spent on education. The truth of the matter is that non-utilization of and poor access to Artificial Intelligence and Communication Technology in Nigerian schools and some developing countries in Africa seem to affect ICT utilization at all levels of education, thereby jeopardizing achievement and competitiveness globally (Adenuga, Owoyele & Adenuga, 2011).

Despite the statement made by the Federal Government of Nigeria (FGN) in 2013 on its National Policy of Education to provide adequate infrastructure and develop capacity for the effective utilization of Information and Communication Technology, many studies have shown the unavailability of ICT infrastructures. Ngwu (2014) and Tella (2011) mentioned that ICT resources are not adequately available, Idoko and Ademu (2010) found out that ICT availability is one of the major obstacles to ICT utilization. Mbuk (2010) mentioned that ICT education in Nigeria is yet to be enforced or explored and ICT tools for teaching and learning are yet to receive the attention it deserves (Obahiagbon and Osahon, 2014). Therefore, this study will appraise the availability of ICT tools if available, do teachers utilize them during chemistry content delivery?

Objectives of the Study

Identify the available ICT/AI tools for teaching Chemistry and Assess the extent of ICT and AI utilization in content delivery among chemistry teachers of Kano Municipal Local Government.

Determine the relationship between availability and utilisation of AI and ICT tools among chemistry students in content delivery.

Research Questions

What are the available AI and ICT tools for teaching chemistry and to what extent are AI and ICT tools used for chemical content delivery among teachers?

What is the relationship between availability and utilisation of AI and ICT tools among chemistry teachers in content delivery

Research Hypothesis

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between the availability and utilization of AI and ICT tools among chemistry teachers in Kano Municipal.

Ho2: There is no significant relationship between the availability and utilization of ICT tools in content delivery among chemistry teachers in Kano Municipal.

Methodology

This study was a descriptive survey. The population of the study consisted of all 46 chemistry teachers in senior secondary schools of Kano Municipal local government under the Kano State Senior Secondary Management Board (KSSMB), which was used as a sample due to its small population size. Two (2) instruments were used for data collection the; AI/ICT availability checklist with a reliability coefficient of 1.00, which consisted of ten (10) items. The second instrument was the Information and Communication Technology Resource Questionnaire (AI/ICT-RQ), with a reliability coefficient of 0.93. The instrument was validated by experts from

the Department of Education and Science and Technology of Education (STE). It consists of 20 multiple choice items based on a 4-point Likert scale. Biserial correlation was employed to test this hypothesis because the independent variable (availability of AI/ICT tools) was dichotomous and the dependent variable (utilization of ICT/AI tools) was measured on a continuous scale.

Results

Research Question 1

What are the available AI and ICT tools for teaching chemistry?

Table 1: Availability of AI/ICT Resources for Teaching Chemistry

S/N	AI & ICT TOOLS	AVAILABLE		NOT AVAILABLE		DECISION
		Frequency	%	Frequency	%	
	Virtual assistant	10	21.7	36	78.3	NA
	Tape Recorders	16	34.8	30	65.2	NA
	Image recognition	20	43.5	26	56.5	NA
	Chatbots	20	43.5	26	56.5	NA
	Interactive Board	7	15.2	39	84.8	NA
	Desktop Computers	33	71.7	13	28.3	A
	Laptop	28	60.9	18	39.1	A
	Molecular visualization tools	31	67.4	15	32.6	A
	Projector	14	30.4	32	69.6	NA
	Software for Chemistry	13	28.3	33	71.7	NA

Key: NA (not available), A (available).

Table 1 presents the results on the availability of ICT resources in Kano Municipal Senior Secondary Schools. It showed that, except for Computers and Laptops all other AI and ICT resources are not available. The sampled schools lacked chatbots, interactive boards, virtual assistants, etc. Research Question 2: To what extent are AI and ICT tools utilized by teachers for chemistry content delivery?

To answer this research question, the mean and standard deviation were used as shown in the table below, to determine the utilization of available ICT resources among the teachers.

Table 2: Utilization of ICT/AI tools among teachers

S/N	ITEMS	N	MEAN	SD	DECISION
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Use of laptop for Chemistry lesson preparation	46	2.26	1.08	NU
Use of the internet and AI in preparing Chemistry Practical	46	2.39	1.02	NU
Use of Multimedia projectors for Chemistry teaching	46	1.93	1.14	NU
Browsing via AI in updating Chemistry lesson notes	46	3.28	0.91	U
Video/audio in AI for drilling of students to learn	46	2.32	1.09	NU
Use of Microsoft Word Excel for result computation	46	2.58	1.12	U
Use of virtual assistants in Chemistry Laboratory sessions	46	2.10	1.10	NU
Use of e-mail to communicate with Chemistry students	46	1.76	1.03	NU
Use of Microsoft Word Power Point for presentation	46	2.02	1.12	NU
Use of Interactive Board for Chemistry content delivery	46	2.15	1.11	NU
Overall:		2.28	1.07	Not Utilized

Key: NU (Not Utilized); U (Utilized)

Table 2 shows that the ICT resources mentioned were not used in the content delivery of chemistry instructions. However, teachers responded that they use the internet and artificial intelligence to update chemistry lesson notes and excel to compute students' results. The respondents maintained that the use of the internet and AI related tools was not provided by the school, it is mostly for personal use. Null Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between the availability and utilization of ICT tools among chemistry teachers in Kano Municipal.

The data obtained from section A of the AI/ICT-RQ and that of the AI/ICT checklist were subjected to biserial correlation to determine if there was any relationship between availability and utilization of AI and ICT tools.

Table 3: Biserial correlations between availability and utilization of AI and ICT tools among teachers

Correlation r	lower 95.0% C.L of p	Upper 95.0% C.L of p	r ²	Count N P	NO/N p=0	test for	probability level
0.1967	-0.1613	0.5174	0.0387	46	0.5652	1.079	0.2808

The Biserial Correlation between the availability and utilization of AI and ICT tools among chemistry teachers, shown in Table 3.7 was found to have a low positive relationship, which is not statistically significant ($r_{bi}=0.196$; $p=0.281$, $c=46$). Therefore, the null hypothesis stated above is upheld. This implies that there is a positive relationship between availability and utilization, thus travelling along the same trajectory, if availability goes up, then utilization might also goes up and vice versa, but since they are not statistically significant, it is concluded that availability is not the cause of utilization.

Null Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between the availability and Utilization of AI and ICT tools in content delivery among chemistry teachers in Kano Municipal.

Table 4: Biserial Correlations between the Availability and Utilization of AI and ICT tools in content delivery.

Correlation r	Lower 95.0% C.L of p	Upper 95.0% C.Lof p	r ²	Count N	NO/N P	test for p=0	probability level
0.14	-0.2106	0.4768	0.0217	46	0.5652	0.803	0.4217

From the data generated through a biserial correlation between availability and utilization of ICT tools among teachers in Table 3.8, $r_{bi} = .14$, $c = 46$, and $p = .422$, which is greater than $.05$, makes it statistically insignificant. The correlation here showed a very low positive correlation; thus, there was a relationship between the availability and utilization of ICT tools that was not statistically significant. In other words, availability does not ensure the utilization of AI and ICT tools among chemistry teachers, eventhough utilization can only happen when the AI and ICT resources are available. Therefore, the null hypothesis is retained.

The analysis clearly describe how lack of AI tools directly have impact on chemistry content delivery, the nature of the subject (chemistry) requires atomic, molecular and reaction visualization, however, in the absence of AI powered visualization platforms and virtual laboratories, teachers would find it difficult to demonstrates such concepts simply and interactively with students, leaving them on total rote memorization, misconception in real time which results in poor engagement and performance.

Discussion

Data analysis for research question one (1) shows that ICT/AI tools such as computers, laptops and molecular visualization tools are available. The remaining tools, that is, image recognition, tape recorders, interactive boards, chatbots, and chemistry software are not available.

The study shows that there is a positive relationship between the availability and utilization of ICT tools, which is not significant among chemistry teachers, Eventhough desktops and laptops are fairly available, teachers have no access to them, as they are only used for administrative purposes.

These findings are in agreements with those of several other studies, such as Abdul-Salaam (2012), Bitok (2012), Achimugu (2016), Mavellas, Wellington and Samuel (2016), Osuafor (2016), Bunkure(2016) and Nkomo (2013),who agreed that ICT facilities are not readily available. Amuchie (2015) mentions that availability is very low. Njelita and Emendu (2015) stated that ICT and AI resources are not available, except computers.

The reason for the relationship between availability and utilization in this study is that we can utilize only what is available. Most of the schools in this study lacked ICT and AI facilities. Some of the available tools (computers and laptops) in the schools are not utilized, which explains why there is no significant relationship between availability and utilization.

Hooda et al. (2022) proved that the use of AI and ICT helps streamline the process of grading and assessment in chemistry education. The use of AI-powered assessment tools helps teachers grade

students work more quickly and accurately, reducing grading time and improving consistency (Volkova 2020).

The results in Table 2 show low accessibility to ICT tools among teachers which resulted in low utilization. The ones they usually have access to, mostly, are not provided by the schools authority, but by themselves. The null hypothesis tested showed that there is a positive relationship between availability and utilization of ICT tools, but this is not statistically significant. This showed that accessibility before utilization can become effective, but accessibility does not assure utilization among teachers. Therefore, it can be concluded that hypothesis 2 is upheld. These findings are in line with those of Aramide et al. (2013), who found a low level of accessibility and a positive relationship between accessibility and usage. Augustine, Daud and Kamaruddin (2018) confirmed the low levels of ICT accessibility. Makinde et al. (2018) and Umeh and Okonkwo (2014) have demonstrated low accessibility.

The results in Table 3 indicate a low utilization of ICT tools among chemistry teachers. This implies that chemistry teachers do not use ICT tools for instruction delivery. These findings agree with those of Aramide, Olajojo and Adekanye (2013), Ukpong (2016), and Makinde, Abdullahi and Bolaji (2018), who showed low levels of utilization. Njelita and Emendu (2015) assured teachers that they do not use ICT tools in teaching. Mavellas et al. (2016) and Wordu and Emamorose (2017) confirmed a lack utilization of ICT tools among teachers. Ademiluyi (2019) showed that ICT tools were not used.

Furthermore, while previous studies mostly focused on ICT, this study expands the discussion to comprises both ICT and AI resources, and highlighting their closely absence condition in Kano municipal secondary schools classrooms. This contributes new evidence that chemistry teachers remain unable to incorporate emerging AI-driven learning platforms even when the basic ICT devices are available, thereby limiting innovative approaches towards content delivery.

Conclusions

Conclusively, ICT/AI resources for teaching chemistry except for desktop computers and laptops are not available. The level of ICT/AI and AI utilization of available tools is low among chemistry teachers in content delivery. This shows a relationship between availability and utilization which was not statistically significant. Also, there is lack of utilization of ICT/AI resources for chemistry content delivery among teachers, except in two areas; result computation and updating of lesson notes via the internet and a significant relationship was established between the availability and utilization of ICT tools among chemistry teachers in Kano Municipal.

Recommendations

AI/ICT resources should be made available to all schools, most importantly colleges of education and universities where teachers are trained, getting use of ICT/AI resources, while under training can help boost their confidence and competency, which, on the other hand, will make utilization even easier.

Responsible bodies such as Kano State Ministry of Education, Education Boards, and Schools Authority should ensure that teachers have easy access to ICT tools.

The lack of Utilization of ICT resources in content delivery among teachers was mostly due to their mindset; in this study, they claimed to have the competency, but still lack of utilization was discovered. This shows that they need motivation, pressure and proper orientation to curtail their mindset, have confidence, and to know that ICT resources are not created specifically for computer subjects only.

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